

Investigating the Darkside of doing Postgraduate
Research: *An Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis
of Algerian Doctoral Students' Demotivation in the UK*

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“How can I be substantial without casting a shadow? I must have a dark side too if I am to be whole; and by becoming conscious of my shadow I remember once more that I am a human being like any other” (Carl Jung, 1933, p. 40).

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Declaration

The research presented in this thesis was carried out by the undersigned. No part of the research has been submitted in support of an application for another degree or qualification at this or another university.

The number of words is 88,566

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20 November 2024

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This piece of work started as a simple idea on demotivation, but it grew into a very interesting investigation into the intricacies of the phenomenon of the dark side through many novel avenues. It has taken significant time, effort, overthinking, many cups of coffee, and ironically, demotivation. Delving into the dark side was indeed fascinating, nevertheless, this thesis would never have come to completion without the help I received.

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Abstract

This thesis combines psychological and sociological perspectives to interrogate and understand the phenomenon of demotivation of Algerian postgraduates in UK universities. Driven by a noticeable absence in the scientific debate into the phenomenon at this level, this research aims to unveil the multiple factors leading to doctoral demotivation, its mechanisms and symptomology, and extend its understanding through seminal sociological dimensions of alienation, and disenchantment. Due to stress, insomnia, high levels of depression, attrition rates, and past instances of suicide among PhD students, studying demotivation becomes important for addressing and preventing such issues. Therefore, to address and highlight such danger zones prior to the irreversible threshold such as attrition and suicide, an Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis approach was utilised to capture the essence of demotivation through the use of multiple in-depth interview sessions (60 to 120 minutes) with eight participants. Results reveal that External Challenges and Life Events, Supervisor-Related Issues, and Personal and Emotional Factors were the main triggers to the dark side of motivation. Moreover, the study reveals different symptoms of demotivation categorised under feelings and thought processes. The former include Dissipation of Enthusiasm, Isolation, Avoidance, and Cultural Dislocation, Negative Self-Perception and Imposter Syndrome, Overwhelming Emotions and Mental Health Challenges, Guilt, Regret and Fear of Failure and Uncertainty. The latter include Critical Voice and NATs, Work Avoidance and Detachment, Worth and Task Value, Suicidal Thoughts and Ideation, Seeking Solutions and Reconciliation. Finally, the sociological dimensions of Alienation and Disenchantment were found to contribute greatly to the demotivation of UK Algerian postgraduates from Disenchantment being the highest to alienation being second. Results indicate that the UK Algerian postgraduates face demotivation at an alarming rate which leads to further suicidal thoughts and attrition thinking. This calls for drastic measures to create a more positive and inclusive environment that prevents students to fall into demotivation and potentially falling into much more severe danger zones.

Keywords: Demotivation, PhD students, Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis, Sociological Dimensions, Mental Health, Algerian Students, UK Universities.

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List of Abbreviations

PhD: Doctor of Philosophy

FLL: Foreign Language Learning

IS: International Students

DS: Doctoral Students

IDS: International Doctoral Students

HESA: Higher Education Statistics Agency

SDT: Self-Determination Theory

IPA: Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis

GETs: Group Experiential Themes

PETs: Personal Experiential Themes

NATs: Negative Automated Thoughts

Chapter I. Setting the Scene: Introduction

1. Establishing the Context

The central argument of this thesis is that the processes of demotivation have gone insufficiently recognised in higher education and that to understand them, we need to utilise concepts from both psychology and sociology. This neglect may arise from cultures of optimism, reputational protection, and the taboo they introduce among PhD students, exposing harm and suffering. One might also argue that there may be an impact of colonialism that controls our gaze away from the dark side. Over 100,000 doctoral students are enrolled in UK universities (HESA, 2021). As such, the doctorate holds a major social and economic position around the world as doctoral candidates generate new ideas and contribute to knowledge advancement (Neumann and Tan, 2011; Frick et al., 2016). Enrolling for a PhD implies accepting a challenge as the doctoral journey is a process of transformation and development (Barnacle, 2005). Moreover, the doctorate offers a multitude of advantages during the research process and after its completion. Examples of the former include a sense of freedom in terms of knowledge pursuit (Frick et al., 2016). Such liberty in research allows candidates to experience the joys of independence, exploration, and discovery (Petre and Rugg, 2010). The latter includes job prospect opportunities as being the ‘highest award’; the doctorate boosts the curriculum vitae and hence offers better job placement in academia or other spheres of work.

However, knowledge production is a complex process. Various authors such as Danby and Lee (2012), and Cuschieri (2021) pinpointed that becoming an expert in the chosen field has to go through different stages; in other words, the process is not a linear one. Additionally, the doctoral level is characterised by a significant attrition rate (ranging from 40-50% depending on the academic discipline). Combined with issues faced while conducting research such as research process and supervision issues (Frick and Pyhältö, 2020), different stressors (Cornwall et al., 2019), and health-related issues (Hyun et al., 2006; Kernan et al., 2011; Levecque et al., 2017). Thus, the chances of students losing their will to carry on their projects increase considerably. Consequently, scholars in higher education were concerned about issues of motivation (Bair and Haworth, 2004; Lovitts, 2001, 2008; Sverdlik and Hall, 2019). With regard to such concerns, this study investigates all blocking forces responsible for doctoral students’ disengagement with their respective research and ultimately withdraw from the program. Put simply, it investigates the other side of the PhD which may be described as ‘dark side’.

2. Statement of the Problem

PhD success does not rely solely on intellectual abilities but also includes a focal construct called motivation. Lovitts (2008, p.313) describes it as “*a key factor that mediates between what a person can do and what a person will do*”. In other words, high academic achievements are anticipated when motivation is included as it boosts individuals to do more than what is necessary out of pure interest or other incentives. Interestingly, Brailsford (2010) explores the initial motivations for starting a history doctorate. Findings reveal that the chances of getting more satisfactory outcomes are relatively high when a commitment to the research project is accompanied by a strong desire to achieve academic success by completing their theses appears to act as a forceful motive for completion. This means that two key ingredients are necessary to achieve the goal of a PhD: the academic and the motivational aspects. As one respondent in Lovitts’ interview (2008) reports “*if you don’t love it and really want it, it won’t get done*” (p. 315). This entails that the doctoral degree requires more than intellectual abilities as these latter might get weakened in long-term projects and motivation is one way to preserve and sustain energy throughout the entire journey. Overall, motivation does not only permit higher quality achievements but also represents the difference between degree completion and non-completion (Lovitts, 2008; Brailsford, 2010; Litalien et al., 2015).

However, due to the nature of the doctoral experience as being an emotional roller coaster (Cuschieri, 2021), many students find the experience extremely challenging to endure. Hawlery (2003, p.24) defines the experience as “*subjectively painful.... that underlie most students’ decision to quit*”; which entails possible hindrances in the process of transforming and drive to potential attrition. Prior research has explored diverse doctoral experiences including isolation (Ali and Kohun, 2006; Janta et al., 2014), socialisation (McCray and Joseph-Richard, 2020), reasons for completion (Devos et al., 2017; McCray and Joseph-Richard, 2020), motivators to pursue PhD (Brailsford, 2010; Wiegerová, 2016; Templeton, 2016), persistence and engagement (Holmes et al., 2016) drop out intentions (Litalien and Guay, 2015), positive and negative experiences of the doctoral journey (Frick and Pyhältö, 2020) doctoral attrition (Maher et al., 2020; Hunt, 2020) and resilience of doctoral completers (McCray and Joseph-Richard, 2020). Most of these studies pinpoint the numerous challenges encountered and negative experiences likely responsible for either the evolvment or the termination of doctoral studies. This implies that the students might lose their motivation to study and withdraw anytime. Nevertheless, studies focused either on motivation which is the initial step or attrition which is the point of no return. Almost no research has ever focused on the phase during research before attrition, where saving/remotivation is still possible. Subsequently, the following study aims to explore the demotivating experiences faced by doctoral students responsible for their unproductivity and potential program withdrawal.

Moreover, the turmoil faced by doctoral students appears to be more pronounced within the social sciences in general and international students in particular. In fact, unlike natural science students who work collectively and collaboratively in laboratories, social science students are isolated from most contact with others due to the individualistic nature of their research and unstructured schedule (Janta et al., 2014). Consequently, they are more prone to social isolation, intellectual isolation, and loneliness (Hockey, 1994; Ali and Kohun, 2006; Janta et al., 2014). These latter negatively impact the students' wellbeing and psychological health (Nutov and Hazzan, 2011; Janta et al., 2014). As for international students, they are more concerned and exposed to these obstacles for several reasons. Defined as a relatively vulnerable population (Sherry et al., 2010), these students face additional obstacles when adjusting to an unfamiliar environment. For instance, a high degree of isolation (Owie, 1982) due to lack of integration and lack of communication (Hockey, 1994; Walsh, 2010). Other difficulties include language barriers, cultural barriers such as insensitivity and expectation (Choy et al., 2015; Kidman et al., 2017), new academic environment, stereotypes, separation from family and support (Winchester-Seeto et al., 2014) which makes settling in a new country extremely hard (Brown and Holloway, 2008a; Janta et al., 2014).

Additionally, there are some differences between Algerian and British culture. Algeria, on the one hand, has a more of a collectivist culture (Berrezoug, 2021) which is a social pattern that stresses the importance of the group rather than individual idiosyncrasies and sees things from a collective perspective (Triandis, 1995; Hofstede, 2001, 2011; Cohen, Wu and Miller, 2016). Britain, on the other hand, has a more individualistic culture which prioritises the individual's personal goals, aspirations and mindset (Triandis, 1995; Hofstede, 2001, 2011) over the collective. When Algerians relocate to British communities, it might increase the risk of demotivational threats while studying. As Algerians are secluded from their community members (family, friends, society), they do not have a space where to vent, share, disseminate and cope with demotivation. It is important to note that neither Algeria nor Britain is fully monolithic/monocultural and both possess qualities of individualism and collectivism. This will be further discussed in the literature review.

Algerians being detached from their home environment, factors such as homesickness, sleeplessness, fear, discrimination, and depression prevail (Brown and Holloway, 2008a). Consequently, the psychological distress and wellbeing of international students are intensified due to their particular case. Therefore, given the fact that a considerable number of studies majorly report negative outcomes from doctoral students' experience, it would appear only logical to think that PhD students are more exposed to the hidden facet or dark side of motivation known as demotivation.

Demotivation is a state that arises when individuals are faced with an obstacle that flips their motivation, either for a fleeting moment or a prolonged period (Bush and Peters, 2020; Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2021). Though the concept was originally used in FLL, it could also account for the behaviours of doctoral students pursuing their degrees. Demotivation is known as the negative counterpart of motivation (Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2021); it nullifies all the positive thoughts, behaviours and attributes causing students to feel unable to accomplish their objectives. In FLL context, demotivation is considered as the sole responsible for foreign language failure (Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2011, 2021). Most factors extracted to this date revolve around the *teacher, inadequate school facilities, reduced self-confidence, negative attitude towards the L2, compulsory nature of L2 study, interference of another foreign language being studied, negative attitude towards L2 community, attitude of group members and course book* (Dörnyei, 1998). However, the present research was unable to locate any study on factors that demotivate students at the doctoral level in general and international social science students in specific. The following study indeed focuses on the dark side of doctoral experience which would appear as negative. Nevertheless, the sole purpose of this study is not to criticise or question the credibility of the doctorate but rather to detect what could hamper students' academic engagement and ultimately the doctoral completion process. Thus, to minimize attrition and boost chances of success and completion rates, this study seeks to unveil these obstacles and dark experiences as lived and perceived by international doctoral students in the UK. In other words, the contribution lies in detecting the demotivating factors and extracting the essence of the experience by IPA which is a thorough investigation of individuals' lifeworlds (Smith et al., 2022). The reason for relying on IPA is justified by the experiential nature of the topic and its suitability for experiences that lack depth and require a fresh perspective (Eatough and Smith, 2017). This is further explored in chapter five.

As mentioned, a major problem with the existing literature on demotivation is its incompleteness with regard to the doctoral level. Indeed, drawing from the most cited reasons for attrition combined with the negative experiences reported by doctoral students, it would be safe to argue that PhD students are highly exposed to demotivational danger. Thus, one of the sole purposes of this thesis is the detection and extraction of the factors that doctoral students perceive as demotivating through understanding the experiences lived by international doctoral students. Most of the past investigations have focused on the positive experiences or motives to pursue a PhD (Brailsford, 2010; Templeton, 2016); neglecting to locate the possible hampering forces/experiences to motivation, especially doctoral students. It has been demonstrated that deleting demotivators is more beneficial to students than actual motivation/motivators (Christophel and Gorham, 1995).

Therefore, extracting the obstacles of academic engagement is of significant importance to the thriving of doctoral students. Moreover, among the studies that focused on demotivation, the totality was conducted on educational levels from undergraduates to lower levels with little regard for doctoral students despite their degree and status. Therefore, this investigation aims to fill the gap of demotivational studies within a new set of participants; namely, doctoral students. Furthermore, the type of international PhD participants utilised is particularly unique in its kind; they are Algerian majors in their respective universities who have been granted a competitive scholarship to carry on their PhD in the UK. They were selected through a national contest that is very selective. Thus, the generated responses come from a new set of participants who have been poorly documented in the literature.

Another novelty introduced in this thesis is extending the limited/narrow scope of demotivation by incorporating sociological theories of alienation and disenchantment. The latter represents one of the study's subsequent contributions to the scientific debate on demotivation. The present study draws upon some of the sociological concepts of Marx and Weber to broaden the current knowledge of demotivation that remained for three decades restrained to psychology. For example, the alienation dimensions advanced by Seeman (1959) known as *powerlessness*, *meaninglessness*, *normlessness*, *isolation*, and *self-estrangement* are relatable to demotivation. The state of demotivation could be defined in terms of these dimensions which all describe a state of deprivation, separateness, and disconnection. A separation of students from their motivation, causing them to feel disconnected from their environment or study goals. Therefore, demotivation is sociologically defined as a state of disempowerment resulting from facing insurmountable forces, a disconnection of students from their learning objectives due to relatively overwhelming oppressing obstacles of which the students may be partially aware.

Interestingly, the level of inquiry matches greatly with the phenomena of demotivation and sociological theorising. First, because the nature of a doctoral degree is relatively isolating; it separates students from their families, friends and even from taking quality time for themselves (Case, 2007; Janta et al., 2014). The feeling of isolation has been identified as one of the reasons behind doctoral students' attrition (Ali and Kohun, 2006). Because isolation puts students in a state of 'convict' who is imprisoned in an 'iron cage' (Weber, 1978; Abramowski, 1982). Consequently, it decreases students' mental toughness and persistence. Therefore, students being under such a separating condition lose their motivation to study and, hence, get demotivated and decide to leave the program. In other words, the feeling of isolation could be considered as a highly demotivating factor. The problem of isolation is more present among the international students as they are pursuing their higher

education in a foreign country in which they face multiple shocks (Brown and Holloway, 2008; Winchester-Seeto et al., 2014). Thus, the present study bridges different disciplines in terms of how demotivation and its symptoms are lived psychologically and socially.

To reiterate, there has been not sufficient research that examines the young phenomenon of demotivation at the international doctoral level; its factors and symptoms from the perspective of adult students. It would be quite interesting to know what might impede students' goal achievement, how they perceive such obstacles and whether these hindrances are challenging but surmountable or insurmountable enough to withdraw from the program. One way of generating data through fresh perspective and first-hand accounts of experiences is through what is known as IPA which disseminates the lived experience as perceived and felt by its participants and provides interpretation while recounting it (Heidegger, 1962, van Manen, 2007, 2023). Finally, in conducting this study, ethical considerations are paramount. The researcher manages ethical considerations by adhering to guidelines such as UWS and BPS. Participants were debriefed, informed and consented to take part in the study. Additionally, they were provided with various supports such as access to relevant websites and the researcher's direct support to address any concerns or emotional distress arising from the study.

3. Aims of the Current Study

In an attempt to solve the problems advanced in the literature, the study focuses on three paramount aims:

- To explore the Algerian postgraduates' dark experiences within UK higher education settings.
- To identify demotivating/demeaning factors of international PhD students' academic engagement.
- To expand the understanding of demotivation through the sociological lenses of alienation and disenchantment.

4. Objectives

The objectives or actions taken in order to achieve the aforementioned aims are as follows:

- Collect participants' experiences through IPA; in which the lived experiences are expressed freely in as much details as they want.
- Construct a new body of knowledge of demotivation at the doctoral level through generated data.
- Synthesise the generated data through a multidisciplinary approach.

5. Scope

Limits to the research are noted from the start. I do not, for example, examine domestic postgraduate students' demotivating factors. The research is narrowed down exclusively to international students; namely, UK Algerian postgraduates. The reason for such choice is because international students' case is more delicate and often described as a vulnerable population (Desa et al., 2012), and that the literature on international students is still scarce and almost non-existent on Algerian students. Moreover, I am interested in students who are still in the process of drafting their thesis; consequently, completers and non-completers are not included in this study. One reason for doing so is that those who succeeded and those who withdrew might give factors by recalling their memories. As considerable time has passed by the answers might be on the benefit of hindsight. Therefore, possible other demotives might have been missed and extracted if the questions were addressed while conducting the PhD. Finally, the research is centred on students in social sciences as they appear more impacted in their studies.

6. Purpose

Due to the isolating nature of PhD, the sociological elements mentioned above might be at their strongest at the doctoral level; which could be magnified within international students due to settling in a new country facing many changes that can result in a shock (e.g., cultural shock, Brown and Holloway, 2008b). Besides, students in doctoral degrees are more exposed to physical, psychological, and sociological distress. Evidence points to the overwhelming pressure PhD students face such as stress, insomnia, and depression (Hyun et al., 2006; Kernan et al., 2011). Therefore, they are likely more prone to demotivation. The sole purpose of this study is to investigate the factors that demotivate full-time PhD students as these latter debilitate their academic outcome and threaten both their wellbeing and their thesis completion. Moreover, it determines which of the sociological factors elaborated might demotivate doctoral students frequently. All serve the aim of unveiling the dark side as lived by international doctoral students. Demotivation from an ethical perspective could be questioned as to whether it is necessary to uncover such harm to increase wellbeing. This is important as it will help in understanding where international doctoral students struggle. Finally, this research aims to provide policy implications to raise awareness of the dark side and have systems in place to diminish it and provide help in predicting drop-out and attrition. These aim to reduce demotivation at the doctoral level, promoting mental health awareness and providing recommendations for institutions.

7. Research Questions

Based on the gaps identified, the following questions are formulated for generating a new bank of knowledge:

***RQ I.** What demotivating factors are experienced by Algerian PhD research students studying at UK universities?*

***RQ II.** How do UK Algerian postgraduates experience demotivation?*

***RQ III.** Are there any sociological dimensions that might contribute to students' demotivation?*

Summary

This chapter is a small outline of what the research aims to achieve. It narrated and explained the context within which the study is situated along with what is lacking in the present literature on the dark side in general and demotivation in specific. It also mentioned the importance of conducting such a project and justified the need for such an endeavour. However, as previously mentioned, the purpose is not to dispute the doctorate by bringing its dark side into light, but rather to raise awareness of such side and enhance the success rate of doctoral students. It is important to note that most valuable lessons are acquired through hardships by making sense of the experience lived (Style, 2010). This evidence represents one of the key motivations behind this research project.

Chapter II. The PhD Journey

Introduction

While a substantial number of doctoral students enjoy their PhD journey, finding it thrilling and positive (Wisker, 2008), some others are highly exposed to isolation and loneliness during their research and therefore more prone to demotivation problems as they face multiple issues related to their psychological, physiological, and sociological wellbeing (Hyun et al., 2006; Wellington and Sikes, 2007; Cornwall et al., 2019). These latter impact negatively on their ongoing motivation and thriving of their respective thesis. Indeed, Hughes (2011, p.621) states “*this period of an academic career [doctoral studies] can be experienced in strongly negative ways, in terms of loneliness, isolation and anxiety about direction and completion*”. Thus, this chapter demonstrates the impact of doing a doctorate on students’ lives and wellbeing in general. It is an opening gate that allows a better understanding as to why PhD students are indeed exposed to demotivation danger more than any other level. It is important to note that these issues are not imported before the commencement of the degree, but rather experienced when starting the research process (Lovitts, 2001; Sverdlik and Hall, 2019).

1. The PhD Award

The doctorate is widely regarded as the pinnacle of education. Referred to as a ‘rite de passage’, it is seen as a crowning achievement by a substantial number of students seeking to fully develop their academic identity (Miller and Brimicombe, 2004; Milroy, 2019). The journey includes various stations that demand students to be flexible, resilient, and consistent (Batchelor and Di Napoli, 2006; Cuschieri, 2021). Students enrolling at such levels are generally the most competent and achieving individuals (Ali and Kohun, 2007; Jairam and Kahl, 2012). Enrolling for a PhD programme is a serious commitment, and students must be aware of the changes that come along with such a journey; in this sense, PhD becomes a priority, and one is willing to make some personal sacrifices to succeed (Gardner and Holley, 2011; Spaulding and Rockinson-Szapkiw, 2012; Cuschieri, 2021). These hardships yield benefits in the end as they facilitate employment for an academic career and add serious weight to people’s curriculum vitae (Petre and Rugg, 2010). Degree completion in both UK and US usually takes 3 to 5 years for full-time students and about 6 to 10 years for part-time students; with UK students completing in much less time than US (Cuschieri, 2021). The interest in Higher Education in the UK has witnessed an exponential increase throughout the years. The number of postgraduate students has grown from 125.890 to 305.025 between 2000/01 and 2018/19 (HESA, 2020). Students’ enrolment numbers for a doctorate rose by 4% between 2014/2018 from 98.555 to 101.885 (73.890 to 77.965 for full-time students). Additionally, the completion rate at the

postgraduate research level also witnessed an increase in number from 21.685 to 29.330 over a nine-year; from 2009/10 to 2018/19 (HESA, 2020). Nevertheless, the number of qualifications for such level decreased the very next year to 28.475 students (HESA, 2021); thus, demonstrating that sometimes students tend to take time to finish or leave their degree before its completion. Doctoral students (especially full-time) in this phase experience a set of challenges that might impede their progress. This chapter explores the challenges and unpleasant experiences they face, especially with regard to psychological and sociological factors. It is worth mentioning that these experiences pertain to completers and non-completers (Lovitts, 2001; Devos et al., 2017; McCray and Joseph-Richard, 2020).

2. Overview of Doctoral Studies

A traditional doctorate, being a more advanced level, is significantly different from an undergraduate in terms of research depth, contribution, and prestige. Such pressuring responsibilities constitute some of the reasons behind the severe psychological and sociological toll that doctoral students experience (Cornwall et al., 2019; Mulligan, 2021). In investigating doctoral experiences through qualitative surveys on 152 full-time first-year students, Cornwall et al. (2019) identified 9 stressors/challenges namely: Time pressure, uncertainty of doctoral processes, sense of belonging in scholarly community, social isolation, financial impact of study, anticipation of future workload associated with PhD, doubt regarding abilities/strengths, work/life balance, engagement, and effectiveness of supervision. These themes have been extracted recurrently over the years by many scholars (Kohun and Ali, 2005; Hyun et al., 2006; Wellington and Sikes, 2007; Kernan et al., 2011; McCray and Joseph-Richard, 2020). Thus, the constant pressures faced by doctoral students still subsist and might alter their flow of learning.

However, not every stressor could be considered demotivating as people react differently in identical situations (Dweck, 1999, 2006). Consequently, stressors could serve as positive stimuli for some individuals (Pekrun et al., 2002; Pappa et al., 2020). Additionally, people embarking on doctoral journeys are well aware that challenges are expected. Furthermore, in Cornwall et al. (2019) study, the effect of such stressors was not conducted in detail to identify its impact on doctoral students. Stress depends on the intensity of other factors such as motivation, social support and so on. Thus, opportunities for doctoral students to narrate their stories should be allowed to examine in-depth what stressors could cause and how students respond/react to them.

Moreover, the doctorate is known to be a relatively isolating journey. A seminal quantitative study conducted by Kohun and Ali (2005) analysed the effect of isolation on doctoral students. Questionnaires containing 10 Likert-scale questions were distributed to 53 doctoral students. Using

Chi-Square, the findings show that isolation feelings among doctoral students are a contributing factor in attrition. Therefore, the feeling of isolation caused by a lack of socialisation and integration is a serious issue for doctoral completion. Moreover, the feeling of isolation is more pronounced among international students seeking further education abroad. Using the Dean Alienation Scale on 29 male and 24 female students studying in the US, Owie (1982) found higher degrees of social alienation/isolation in international students compared to domestic students. Other difficulties include language barriers, cultural barriers such as cultural insensitivity and expectation (Choy et al., 2015; Kidman et al., 2017), new academic environment, stereotypes, separation from family and support (Winchester-Seeto et al., 2014). All of which make settling in a new country extremely hard (Brown and Holloway, 2008b; Janta et al., 2014). As a result of such detachment from one's home, issues such as homesickness, sleeplessness, fear, discrimination, and depression prevail (Brown and Holloway, 2008a; Janta et al., 2014). These reasons make international students more prone to the dangers of demotivation and attrition as they are relatively vulnerable compared to the domestic population. Subsequently, this demonstrates that isolation is a big issue that could easily lead to demotivation as it can drive to attrition.

At the doctoral level, an unchanging dropout percentage of 40-50% has been noticed across the UK and USA in two decades (Golde, 2005; Lovitts, 2005; Litalien and Guay, 2015; Sverdluk and Hall, 2019). Leaving the program entails that the interest has been lost due to different reasons; which imply demotivation; a decrease in the engagement due to encountered obstacles/forces (Dörnyei, 2001). Therefore, several students are likely exposed to demotivation as it is a station that precedes departing. Moreover, the frequency of such occurrences at PhD level is high since it is defined as an intense, demanding, and emotional 'roller coaster' (Morrison-Saunders et al., 2010; Cuschieri, 2021). Thus, elaborating on the possible obstacles that weaken their resolve to study is crucial. Especially, social sciences students as they appear to be more impacted according to the literature (Lave and Wenger, 1991; Chiang, 2003). As a result, the possibility of getting demotivated at this stage of education is relatively high considering isolation and attrition problems. However, it is important to note that even with these multiple challenges, the number of doctorates awarded yearly in the UK has an average annual growth of 4% from 2014 to 2018 (HESA, 2020). To sum up, the subsection reviewed some of the issues doctoral students face during their PhD journey. The most recurrent factor highlighted by the literature is isolation problems as it leads to attrition. Combined with the fluctuating nature of the PhD, the likelihood of encountering demotivation at this stage is therefore high.

It is important to notice that PhD students are generally high achievers who have prior academic experiences. In other words, students enrolling for a PhD are usually very competent people capable of withstanding the pressures of the program (Lovitts, 2001). However, despite that, attrition

remains unchanged (Ali and Kohun, 2006; Sverdlik and Hall, 2019). This means that those who drop out are among the best and brightest (Ali and Kohun, 2006). The case is true for Algerian students who were granted with fully funded scholarship. These students were selected according to their grades and chosen through a national contest to determine the destination of the scholarship (UK, Jordan, or Tunisia). Subsequently, as international students studying social sciences appear to be relatively less performant than students in natural sciences (according to HESA and literature), more investigations should be monitored regarding the subject matter.

3. Isolation and its Consequences: Natural Sciences vs Social Sciences

The doctoral experience can be described as an emotional and multi-faceted passage to becoming a scholar (Janta et al., 2014). Prior investigations reported the PhD as a relatively isolating journey (Hockey, 1994; Wellington and Sikes, 2007). The latter is relatively true for humanities and social sciences PhD where research is conducted individually and therefore more prone to isolation and loneliness problems (Janta et al., 2014; Mulligan, 2021). This solitariness is extremely pressuring and less prominent within natural sciences where the nature of its work is more team-based; hence, social isolation is less of a problem (Hockey, 1994; Chiang, 2003; Janta et al., 2014; Maher et al., 2020). Unfortunately, the consequences of such isolation and lack of external input impede the progress of social science students unlike the support found within natural sciences (Lovitts, 2001; Sinclair, 2004). Chiang's (2003) investigation provides more details on such differences by comparing the perceptions of doctoral students in education and chemistry across several UK departments. The study reveals that social science students are more considered as learners rather than actual members of a research group as they work on different assignments requested by their supervisors. Chemistry students, on the other hand, are in regular contact with professionals "*due the emphasis of team work, close interaction and a sense of collegiality, the overall atmosphere in the department appears to be casual, friendly and lively*" (Chiang, 2003, p. 20). For these reasons, natural science doctoral students are less likely to drop out because of their teamwork and collaborative environment.

Subsequently, social science doctoral students are more likely to be affected by demotivation than any other discipline as a supportive/engaging social atmosphere lacks in comparison to natural science (Chiang, 2003; Sinclair, 2004). The social atmosphere is also known in the foundational work of Lave and Wenger (1991) as 'Legitimate Peripheral Participation' where students acquire the mastery of knowledge and skills through full participation in the sociocultural community of practice. It allows full interaction of newcomers with professionals, hence making learning more engaging as it occurs on a daily basis with students learning from professionals. Social science students' subject matter is society itself or certain aspects of it such as language, culture, their reliance on social

interaction and support is necessary rather than complementary. All of these may contribute to students' disengagement from their studies and ultimately impede their academic progress leading to potential attrition.

Because social science doctoral research is isolating in nature and pertains solely to the researcher's topic, the process is therefore conducted alone at one's desk or home, allocating substantial time to research. The costs of such demands are therefore found in difficulties in maintaining relationships and participating in social activities (Wellington and Sikes, 2007; Case, 2007). In a qualitative survey of 29 British doctoral students, Wellington and Sikes (2007) found that a doctoral program's obligation alters relationships with family members and friends; sometimes causing a strain or even a breakdown. The students were unable to communicate with family/friends as they were unfamiliar with the research context. Subsequently, they develop a feeling of isolation not only from undergraduates, but also from their families and friends making them more prone to stress, anxiety, and depression. Lack of contact with families/friends decreases doctoral students' resilience, and motivation hence increasing attrition risks (Devos et al., 2017; McCray and Joseph-Richard, 2020).

The social side is an important component to thesis completion. Using narrative inquiry approach, McCray and Joseph-Richard (2020) investigated the reasons that make PhD students more resilient to successfully complete their programmes. Stories/narratives were collected from 11 successful completers (6 British, 5 African) ranging from 20 to 60 years. Findings from interviews reveal their success was not solely thanks to them or thanks to a distinguished supervisor. The main reason helping them to build confidence, remain resilient throughout their journey and finish the thesis was thanks to their families, social network, institutional context, the university services and how these were available for them as they provided academic and emotional support. For example, family provided support for completers in reminding them of what they could achieve; friends were also people outside academia that helped them through talks that sustained completers' studies and colleagues offered emotional support as well by sharing their previous experiences with completers helped them to build resilience and remain confident. As for the university's emotional and mental health support, it offered completers opportunities to meet over coffee and discuss every aspect of their lives along with informal gatherings to permit stress release of doctoral pressure. The researchers concluded that resilience protection works with the interrelation of four factors namely; *personal factors* the capable but vulnerable PhD student; *the environmental factors* being the family and the completer's community and networks; *professional factors* incorporating the supervisory relationship; and lastly *institutional factors* which includes university support.

Therefore, asserting one more time the necessity of the external/social component to doctoral completion. Nevertheless, the study might have had different results if the study included the cultural

component of students to explain the resilience of students. Moreover, time-pressure is different between part-time students and full-time students which might yield different results if the research focused on such differences. Lastly, the study only focused on those who have successfully finished, other interesting results might be gained if the research focused on students who are still going through the research process. All of these are contributions that the present study is going to cover which are investigating Algerian PhD students sojourning in the UK who are fully devoted to their PhD.

It is important to note that even successful students experience lots of hardships/challenges including being overwhelmed by intellectual demands, lack of self-confidence and self-doubt, uncertainty about the research, personal relationships, and life events hardships such as divorce, illness, financial problems and job loss (McCray and Joseph-Richard, 2020). Therefore, it demonstrates that both completers and non-completers experience relatively similar challenges that might have demotivated them and potentially drove them to withdraw from the program. However, what helped completers to cope with the challenges was the social/emotional support provided as displayed above regardless of nationalities or age.

Therefore, at this stage, as doctoral students already possess the qualities to deal with the PhD (Lovitts, 2001), what lacks most in their lives is the ability to balance their lives and get encouraged and motivated through social contact. Students isolate themselves to fulfil the demands of the program; nevertheless, they are still in need of social contact to talk about their daily lives and even share and debate about their academic work. The sense of isolation is a recurrent factor in attrition (Ali and Kohun, 2006; Maher et al., 2020). Such isolation and lack of belongingness impact heavily on the mental health of students.

4. Mental Health

Galderisi et al. (2015) define mental health as:

...a dynamic state of internal equilibrium which enables individuals to use their abilities in harmony with universal values of society. Basic cognitive and social skills; ability to recognize, express and modulate one's own emotions, as well as empathize with others; flexibility and ability to cope with adverse life events and function in social roles; and harmonious relationship between body and mind represent important components of mental health which contribute, to varying degrees, to the state of internal equilibrium (pp.231-232).

Therefore, mental health does not necessarily mean being happy but being able to deal and cope with the expected or unexpected changes that might befall individuals leading to the rupture of the equilibrium. Being mentally healthy entails internal equilibrium, homogeneity, and harmony. Thus, mental health usually deals with the internal/intrinsic processes of the individual. Put simply, being mentally healthy is having no mental issues or diseases (Manwell et al., 2015). 'Life event' in the present study refers to conducting a PhD; which can easily impact students' equilibrium and create

internal division if they are not well-equipped. To permit a better understanding of what might hinder mental health, some issues are explicated below.

4.1. Mental Health Issues: Stress, Anxiety and Depression

Mental health issues are a marked deterioration of a person's psychological well-functioning (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). Its impact on motivation depends on the degree of the issue experienced. The following section presents some of the most experienced mental issues faced at the doctoral level.

Stress is defined as a change in the organism's state that disturbs the normal condition of an individual or homeostasis. The homeostasis is compromised because the organism perceives the stimulus as overwhelming; causing them to feel strain (Goodnite, 2014; Arafa et al., 2021). As demonstrated earlier in Cornwall et al. (2019) study, entering the world of pure research generates different stressors which, according to the definition, disturb the homeostasis of doctoral students. Research has shown that the effects of stress on students' lives include exhaustion or burnout, cynicism, and inefficacy (Allen et al., 2021).

Unlike stress, anxiety is more an apprehension or anticipation of future danger. It is "*the product of a multicomplex response system, involving affective, behavioral, physiological, and cognitive components*" (Weems and Silverman, 2013, p.514). Moreover, anxiety is different from actual fear of concrete danger in that anxiety is more reflective of an endangerment that has not appeared yet. Symptoms of general anxiety include increased heart rate, rapid breathing, restlessness, trouble concentrating, and difficulty falling asleep (*ibid*). Examples of anxiety within the doctoral population include doubt regarding abilities/strengths, being overwhelmed by intellectual demands, and uncertainty about the research (Cornwall et al., 2019; McCray and Joseph-Richard, 2020). The symptoms of anxiety are also found within the studied population as shall be presented in the next section.

Finally, depression is a mental health issue utilised to describe a complex pattern of deviation in feeling, cognition, and behaviour (Beck and Alford, 2009). It could be defined in terms of the following aspects:

1. A specific alteration in mood: sadness, loneliness, apathy.
2. A negative self-concept associated with self-reproaches and self-blame.
3. Regressive and self-punitive wishes: desires to escape, hide, or die.

4. Vegetative changes: anorexia, insomnia, loss of libido.
5. Change in activity level: retardation or agitation.

(Beck and Alford, 2009, p. 8)

These symptoms as mentioned in Galderisi et al. (2015) definition disrupt students' equilibrium. Depressive disorder significantly reduces quality of life (Otte et al., 2016). Moreover, depressive disorder was found to be one of the major causes of disability worldwide between 1990 and 2017 (GBD, 2019, Liu et al., 2024). Therefore, having one of these mental issues impacts the life quality of individuals and ultimately their academic life.

4.2. Mental Health of PhD Students

As briefly demonstrated in the previous sections, PhD students face many issues as they embark on their respective doctoral studies, which generate mental health issues that affect doctoral quality and progress (Hughes, 2011; Levecque et al., 2017). Not only do doctoral students experience psychological manifestations of tension such as headaches, high levels of stress, depression, and anxiety, but also health-related problems including upper-respiratory infection, sleeping difficulties, increased severity of somatic symptoms which are indicative of fatigue and weakness (Hyun et al, 2006; Kernan et al, 2011; Onwuegbuzie et al., 2014; Cornwall et al., 2019; Pizuńska et al, 2020; Mulligan, 2021). It is important to state that when compared to the general population, PhD students display significantly more alarming psychiatric symptoms than any other educated population (Levecque et al., 2017). The latter, combined with the isolation problem, serves as evidence as to why doctoral students might be more prone to demotivation/dark side.

Moreover, negative thinking and emotion were lately found among doctoral students. Using a questionnaire and an interview, Hughes (2011) investigates whether doctoral studies are associated with pleasure. The results indicate that displeasure was the most significant affective component found when conducting a PhD. As pleasure is linked to a state of equilibrium (Foucault, 2012; Solms, 2019), it is hardly found in doctoral students because they have to adapt to academic adjustments, stress, anxiety, and depression (Janta et al., 2014; Cornwall et al., 2019). Moreover, Hughes' (2011) findings reveal that pleasure should be treated with caution as it is an unsafe feeling that presages a downfall and is sometimes considered even a reckless daring in doctoral studies. Thus, pleasure is a double-edged emotion that should be treated with caution. Consequently, Hughes' (2011) study pinpoints that pleasure is a short-term emotion that can easily be overshadowed by the daily pressures of doctoral studies.

Interestingly, this state is similar to disenchantment where the pleasure or the magic is lost due to an unforeseen/rude awakening (Smith, 1987), which in this case, is the doctoral pressure. Thus,

demonstrating that doctoral studies' pressures can be highly disenchanting. Since the frequent variables encountered are negative (stress, anxiety, and loneliness); displeasure appears only axiomatic in such a state. Moreover, in the definition of intrinsic motivation, elements such as fun, discovery or pleasure are to be found (Deci and Ryan, 2017). As the most recurring factor extracted in Hughes (2011) study is displeasure; it entails the darker side of motivation; namely demotivation. Therefore, the chances of losing academic engagement at such a level are considerably high given the challenges encountered.

Another concern regarding doctoral students is vulnerability-related issues. Generating responses from 3121 full-time graduate students of different degrees, areas and ages, Hyun et al (2006) found that graduate students are particularly vulnerable to pressures related to conducting research and teaching, publishing, and finding employment. The study also identified multiple factors that depict certain mental exhaustion/fatigue due to the nature of doctoral studies. Nearly half of the students reported stress-related problems that significantly affect their emotional wellbeing and/or academic performance. Additionally, 40% of respondents reported 'feeling exhausted' and 46% reported feeling 'overwhelmed' *frequently* or *all the time*. Thus, demonstrating the wellbeing issues which in turn generate vulnerability responsible for either low academic outcomes or dropout. Because vulnerable students are individuals whose resolve has been weakened; consequently, they are not fully operational and cannot display their potential. All these health concerns highlight the necessity of a stable mental and physical health to boost academic results as the two are facets of the same coin; in other words, they cannot be dissociated.

Similarly, Kernan et al. (2011) through a quantitative study found that graduates (n= 1355) reported a negative perceived academic impact related to psychological concerns such as stress, depression, anxiety, and relationship problems. Additionally, students suffered mostly from upper respiratory infections (cold/flu/sore throat), stress, interpersonal concerns (family/friends) and sleep difficulties. Students who experienced such health concerns and felt a negative impact on their studies reported learning disability and attention deficit disorder to be the greatest negative factors that threatened their studies. Subsequently, as their homeostasis is compromised, students seem unable to fully focus and perform academically.

Correspondingly, Levecque et al. (2017) investigated the mental health of 3659 Belgian doctoral students across a multitude of disciplines (humanities, biomedical, social and applied sciences). Findings show that 51 % of participants report psychological distress with 32% of PhD students at risk of having or developing a common psychiatric disorder; especially depression. Moreover, the most predominant feelings are being under constant strain, overall unhappiness, and depression, sleeping problems due to worries, inability to overcome difficulties and not being able to

enjoy daily activities. Thus, aligning with Hyun et al. (2006), Kernan et al. (2011) and Hughes (2011) findings that demonstrate the constraints faced while conducting a PhD which is magnified within this group contrary to the general population (Levecque et al. 2017).

Overall, these methodologically varied studies among so many others have shown how psychologically, healthily, and socially unbalanced doctoral students are. The PhD journey seems to take a great toll on students' wellbeing and positive attitude, as they are more reluctant to participate in social events and have difficulties connecting with their entourage. Furthermore, symptoms such as depression and anxiety aggravate psychological distress, and reduce motivation (also known as motivational dysfunction) and academic performance (Kernan et al., 2011; Simmen-Janevska et al., 2012). For these reasons, they are more prone to losing their engagement as their wellbeing is not optimal. Besides, a demotivated student is not someone disinterested in the learning process but rather discouraged due to some encountered internal factors (anxiety, depression) and external factors (lack of social contact). However, these quantitative studies did not delve into details in relation to how these issues are faced, perceived, and dealt with by doctoral students. Opportunities to narrate stories through students' lenses were not given and this constitutes one of the delimitations found in these reviewed studies.

The mental health of postgraduate students in general and doctoral students in particular seems to be alarming. Each mental health issue experienced can disrupt the internal homogeneity of students and prevent them from unleashing their full potential; causing a loss or dysfunction of motivation. The previous sections have offered an overview of the varied internal/psychological impact that doctoral studies generate which are displayed externally (social isolation, academic isolation and so on). Such concerns, as previously mentioned, in turn disrupt one focal element in students' path to success known as motivation.

5. Motivation and its importance at Doctoral Level

The term *motivated* is used to differentiate successful learners from unsuccessful ones (Dörnyei, 2001). In other words, all the positive and efficient behaviours students display in the learning process and their potential success are under the term of motivated. In contrast, students with little engagement and poor results are often described as unmotivated or demotivated, depending on the situation (Chambers, 1993). While the reasons behind each student's success might vary, motivation is the umbrella term that covers the major explanation of such attribution to success.

Despite the varieties of motivational frameworks advanced by scholars; such as Maslow (1954), Bandura (1986) Locke and Latham (1990) or Dörnyei (2000), who based their interpretation on different standpoints. Yet, most of them do agree on a universal definition that encompasses both

direction and *magnitude* of an action (Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2021). Consequently, motivation is mainly the reason that explains:

6. *The choice of a particular action*; or simply the reason behind such choice or why.
7. *The persistence with it*; in other words, the amount of time dedicated to the action and how long the individual are willing to sustain from such activity.
8. *Effort expended to it*; pursuing difficult goal might call for a higher degree of efforts.

(Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2021, p.4)

Similarly, at the doctoral level, motivation has been characterised as a key construct separating PhD completers and non-completers (Bair and Haworth, 2004; Lovitts, 2001, 2008; Kyvik and Olsen, 2014; Litalien and Guay, 2015). Motivation provides the reasoning behind the driving force but also permits persistence in the face of unwanted/unexpected complications. Both in questionnaires and interviews, PhD students have reported that the presence or absence of motivation is the reason behind their persistence or attrition (*ibid*).

Kyvik and Olsen (2014) investigated Norwegian doctoral training and found that completion rates increased due to extrinsic motivation requiring a PhD for any permanent academic position and as a pathway for successful researchers. Likewise, Lindsay (2015) found through semi-structured interviews that personal motivation was a key enabler or hindrance to timely thesis completion; with some participants outperforming academically competent students due to their scheduled objectives (goal setting). Thus, motivation is a variable that plays an important role in thesis completion and making the journey more enchanting. Nevertheless, it is important to note that the intensity of motivation is severely undermined when psychological well-being is diminished. An example of a motivational theory has been presented below and how devastating the effect of depression impacts the driving force.

5.1. Self-efficacy

Self-efficacy is a theory developed by Bandura (1977) and refers to people's assessments of their ability to complete various activities. Perceived competence is a potent motivator since it influences the activities pursued, as well as the level of desire to achieve the intended task, the amount of work put in, and the tenacity/persistence shown (Bandura, 1978). People with poor self-efficacy regard tough activities as personal menaces and focus on their own personal flaws and difficulties rather than how to do the work effectively.

Different researchers have contended that students' view of their capacity to prevail with regard to accomplishing the necessities of a degree program can clarify contrasts in students'

achievement across all educational levels (Litalien and Guay, 2015; Nilsen, 2009). Specifically, Litalien and Guay (2015) find that PhD students' trust in their scholastic capacities is an indicator of completers and non-completers. It is accommodating when doctoral students comprehend and have confidence in their writing skills and research abilities, which lessens the recurrence and length of episodic self-doubting or questioning (Lindsay, 2015). Numerous PhD students report encountering a specific degree of vulnerability about their abilities; at the point when this self-question is tireless, students may wind up self-sabotaging and procrastinating or not endeavouring undertakings inspired by a paranoid fear of disappointment and failure (Wao and Onwuegbuzie, 2011). Multiple studies have reported PhD students feeling incompetent or self-doubting their abilities (Onwuegbuzie et al., 2014; McCray and Joseph-Richards, 2020). This, according to Bandura (1982), makes people more prone to stress and vulnerability leading to depression and ultimately losing their motivation.

Summary

The rite de passage of PhD, as demonstrated in this chapter, is filled with both positive and negative experiences. The transition from student to novice researcher is perceived differently according to individualistic variables (such as experience or intelligence). The chapter fulfilled its main aim by showing that the dark side in general and demotivation in particular exists at the doctoral level as intensely as others found at other levels, if not more. The particularity of the PhD is that its high value in the hierarchy of education engenders some side effects proper to its merits (such as psychological and social).

III. Surfacing the Shadow World: Examining the Literature

Introduction

Demotivation impedes academic progress not only to undergraduates, secondary and primary school students but also to doctoral students (Cantu, 2016). Besides the psychological aspect, demotivation is also heavily influenced by societal factors, and since the educational setting is social (Lave and Wenger, 1991), limiting the scope of this study to the psychological might overlook a significantly large portion of what is already an under-investigated area, that is, demotivation at the doctoral level. After overviewing the impact of doing a PhD at psychological, societal and physiological levels, the present chapter is a literature review with three sections. The first section is devoted to demotivation; its definition, importance, threat and previous investigations. The second section delves into the other challenges that international students face in addition to the doctoral demands. Finally, section three studies demotivation through the sociological lenses of alienation and disenchantment. Therefore, this study has a multidisciplinary dimension set to prove that demotivation exists at a doctoral level and that the phenomenon can be explained through the alternative sociological perspective used. For a comprehensive discussion of the methodology and literature review process, please see Appendix 1

1. Demotivation

Demotivation has been conceptualized as any force that reduces a student's energy to learn or as the absence of a force that stimulates a student to learn (Zhang, 2007). It is a negative phenomenon that impedes successful learning, and achievements and turns the most engaging and committed student into a non-functional element (Chambers, 1993). It is worth noting that most demotivation studies are mainly related to ESL/EFL at universities to lower levels (Gorham and Christophel, 1992; Chambers, 1993; Sakai and Kikuchi, 2009; Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2011) as this particular field of study was characterized by language failure (Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2021) which spurred the need to investigate the reasons behind students' difficulties in learning a second/foreign language. However, despite the significant amount of literature on the subject, very little empirical research has focused on the problem at the doctoral level; leaving the demotivation literature incomplete. The central argument in this thesis is that not enough attention has been paid to the negative impacts that demotivation could cause in the postgraduate route. This study, therefore, intends to extend the literature on demotivation by relocating it to the doctoral context.

1.1. Defining and Situating Demotivation

Demotivation, even though representing a danger to students' academic thriving, is a relatively new concept compared to motivation (Dörnyei, 2001). Previous research (Brailsford, 2010; Wiegerová, 2016; Templeton, 2016; Lustyantie and Aprilia, 2021) have mainly focused on how to motivate students. However, because motivation fluctuates through time (Dörnyei and Ottó, 1988), there are situations where this fluctuation is descending. Indeed, motivated students experience at least once in their academic life a decrease in motivation or demotivation (Gorham and Christophel, 1992; Dörnyei, 1998). This phase is particularly threatening to students as it drives them to 'potential motivational pitfalls and danger zones' that could prevent them from successful learning (Dörnyei, 2001). Simply put, students influenced by demotivation are trapped in a state that restrains their potential by driving them to live unpleasant experiences leading to potential failure.

In this vein, Dörnyei and Ushioda (2021) define demotivation as the decrease and neutralization of positive behaviours and intentions due to negative processes. In other words, the ongoing engagement is decreased due to encountered factors that result in the impediment of the positive attributes leading to successful learning. Therefore, if motives empower and positively affect engagement with learning and goal achievement, demotivation does the opposite by restraining positive behaviours and making students lose their will to study. This definition is valid as it talks about processes or factors that could include both internal damaging processes such as lack of self-confidence (Sakai and Kikuchi, 2009) and external damaging processes such as the teacher and the learning process (Chambers, 1993; Dörnyei, 1998). These negative processes 'pull the learner down' (Kikuchi, 2015, p.4) rendering the most effective student into an alienated one.

Demotivation is therefore a state that happens after being motivated (Dörnyei, 2001; Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2011, 2021). That is, originally there was a motivational basis. In this sense, demotivation should not be considered as the opposite of motivation, but as an aspect of it since it is related to motivation theory (Hamada, 2011). Moreover, demotivation should not be confused with amotivation. The former is a temporary state of motivation deterioration, which entails that the restrained motivation is not beyond repair and that demotivated students could be remotivated if the negative factors were omitted (Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2011). Whereas the latter refers to the absence of motivation not due to obstacles encountered but because of experiencing feelings of incompetence and helplessness and that amotivated students perceive their lack of motivation as being beyond their control (Vallerand, 2000; Deci and Ryan, 2017). Simply put, amotivated students, as opposed to demotivated students, have originally no motivational basis.

2. Characteristics/Symptoms of Demotivated Students

Students under the influence of demotivation tend to be less engaged. However, it is worth noting that demotivated students are not 'less capable'. They are as capable as highly motivated students but due to their current condition, they cannot be as performant as their motivated peers. Similarly, Chambers (1993) conducted a survey on 191 year-nine pupils enrolled in eight classes from four UK schools in Leeds. The classes were identified as having demotivated elements by their teachers. He asserts that demotivated students are the most challenging task because they have all the required capacities but are reluctant to participate and display their disengagement to their teachers. Following this thought, demotivated students are not escaping their teachers but seeking their help as they do not want to be ignored. Moreover, Chambers (1993, p.16) concludes that these pupils labelled as demotivated are not looking to be ignored or described as bad students because despite what they seem like, they are still demanding encouragement. Therefore, demotivated students are not completely self-destructing when being in that phase but rather seek additional attention from their teachers to be remotivated. This aligns perfectly with Dörnyei and Ushioda (2011) claiming that demotivation does not mean the annulment of all the positive attributes, but instead, they are in a state of motivation restriction due to some negative forces. In this sense, motivation just needs to be triggered to work again.

Additionally, Chambers' investigation showed that demotivated students have significantly *low self-esteem* and need to be positively reinforced about the things they can do. The results demonstrate that demotivated students are a special case that demands a careful approach from teachers that could either help them overcome the situation or worsen their state. Subsequently, drawing from Chambers' (1993) claim on experiencing demotivation, combined with the delicate situation doctoral students experience when facing challenges such as stress, depression, anxiety, feeling incompetent and so on (McCray and Joseph-Richards, 2020), the possibilities of facing such impediment at the doctoral level are relatively high. However, no similar study at the international doctoral level has been conducted to check whether they display similar symptoms; accordingly, one of the present study's contributions is shedding light on the demotivated symptoms (internal and external) displayed by international doctoral students. Moreover, Chambers' (1993) investigation concerns 9-year-olds who are still not mature like doctoral students who are full-grown independent students. Adults are more equipped to handle negative situations than children as they have more control and regulation over their emotions (Puente-Martínez et al., 2021). Therefore, their reaction differs from that of children who are at the beginning of their life experiences. Lastly, as the symptoms reviewed in previous studies of demotivation appear to be relatively few, the following subpart are feelings and thought processes that could potentially be categorised under demotivational symptoms.

2.1. Feelings

The feelings that accompany demotivated doctoral students might vary depending on individuals. However, a particular focus is made on these four categories namely, Self-deprecation, Imposter syndrome, Guilt and Regret, Uncertainty and Fear of Failure.

2.1.1. Self-Deprecation

Self-deprecation reflects an inner struggle within individuals where they constantly put themselves down. It is known as negative self-inner talk that stems mostly from a lack of self-esteem, inferiority, and negative self-regard (Speer, 2019). Such self-downgrading phenomena lead individuals to utter negative sentences such as “I wish I could have more respect for myself”, “I certainly feel useless at times” and/or “At times I think I am no good at all” (Owens et al., 2006, p.183). Interestingly, in the PhD context, due to the fact that the latter is an emotional roller coaster (Cuschieri, 2021), not experiencing such feelings is highly unlikely. Thus, self-deprecation as a demotivational symptom appears relatively cogent and plausible as they share similitude in pulling the learner down (Kikuchi, 2015, p.4).

2.1.2. Imposter Syndrome

Imposter syndrome is a phenomenon where individuals do not feel deserving of their actual place or status and they attribute their success to external factors such as luck or coincidence (Langford and Clance, 1993; Di Pierro, 2007; Sverdlik et al., 2020). People with such feelings tend to always attach their success to anything besides their efforts and are constantly worried about being discovered, as they think of themselves as ‘frauds’. This phenomenon is common within the academic field (Langford and Clance, 1993) and especially potent at the doctoral level where students suffer mostly from mental health-related issues. Indeed, Di Pierro (2007, p.370) highlights, “at the heart of doctoral students’ struggling lie serious concerns that challenge the notions of certainty that they are indeed worthy of embarking upon doctoral study”. PhD students are constantly accompanied by feelings of inadequacy regarding their capability to undergo the task. Research on imposter syndrome at the doctoral level found that imposter syndrome leads doctoral students to question the legitimacy of their positions as well as a constant fear of being exposed (Bothello and Roulet, 2019; Henning et al., 1998; Parkman, 2016; Villwock et al., 2016; Gadsby, 2022).

Imposter syndrome seems to negate the confidence of individuals despite their efforts and achievements. It is a force that constantly hits doctoral students during their journey, weakening their resolve and ultimately leading to mental health-related issues (Sverdlik et al., 2020). Therefore, having the feeling of an imposter as a result of a decrease in motivation or demotivation appears to be a logical turn of events.

2.1.3. Guilt and Regret

Guilt is a negative emotion that is associated with misconduct or wrongful actions (Sullivan, 2014). Such a phenomenon occurs after assessing a situation that has been judged as being transgressional and that the person should have done things differently and thus engage in the form of retribution (Tracy and Robins, 2004). Guilt is a self-conscious emotion that manifests itself as a need for punishment (Freud, 1930/2002). It could be regarded as a potential demotivating symptom as it happens after having motivated/engaged attributes dissolved such as diligence, productivity and ethical conduct (requirements for international PhD student code of conduct).

Often accompanying guilt, regret represents feelings of remorse and shame towards a situation that was not entirely positive or productive and could have been undertaken differently (Connolly and Zeelenberg, 2002; Pieters and Zeelenberg, 2007). Research in this area has shown that regret is linked to poor judgment or decision-making, decision avoidance, risk-taking and health-related issues (Pieters and Zeelenberg, 2007; Västfjäll et al., 2011). Similarly, demotivation is known as the negative force that shuts down all positive attributes (Kikuchi, 2015). After having the motivation flipped, individuals will experience a decrease in their productive habits necessary to goal achievements (Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2021; Locke and Latham, 1990, 2006). Consequently, by observing a clear decline in productivity; as an undesirable outcome, individuals can find themselves trapped in an inner voice of pervasive guilt and regret, as they reflect on missed opportunities or unfulfilled potential.

2.1.4. Uncertainty and Fear of Failure

Uncertainty represents a state of the unknown where the individual possesses little or no information about the situation which triggers insecurities about future outcomes (Carleton, 2016; Morriss et al., 2022). Similarly, when demotivation occurs, it deprives individuals of their confidence and trust in their abilities and planning, which could cause feelings of insecurity and uncertainty. Subsequently, having uncertainty as a potential demotivating characterises is highly probable due to the decreased motivational qualities.

Fear of failure is a constant feeling that individuals experience in general and PhD students in particular. It is a “persistent and irrational anxiety about failing to measure up to the standards and goals set by oneself or others” (American Psychological Association 2007, p. 369). Thus, fear of failure is an overwhelming sensation whereby individuals imagine worst-case scenarios. Previous studies have found that fear of failure impacts motivation and therefore goal achievements (Atkinson, 1964; McGregor and Elliot, 2005; Wright et al., 2009). Thus, fear of failure as a component of

demotivation is highly plausible as it weakens the motivation of students. Especially because the PhD context is filled with fear and anxiety about the direction of the project (Hughes, 2011).

2.2. Thought Processes

Even though demotivation is predominantly a feeling, it is not uncommon for demotivated students to be filled with thought processes during that period. Major instances include Negative Automated Thoughts, and Suicidal Thoughts.

2.2.1. Negative Automated Thoughts (NATs)

Having negative thoughts during troubled periods is a natural occurrence. Because of the low mood and inability to reach one's goal, people are often filled with invasive negative thoughts. In Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT), this phenomenon is known as Negative Automated Thoughts (NATs) which are uncontrollable thinking patterns or thought processes that emerge during a psychological issue (Stott et al., 2010; Neenan, 2018). Due to the fact that these thoughts are predominantly negative, they are extremely hard to eradicate (Beck, 1967). Examples of NATs include thoughts such as "I am going to fail" (Fenn and Byrne, 2013, p. 579). Similarly, demotivated students are people who have lost their positive attributes, thoughts and behaviours and have arrived at a phase of total negativity. Key elements of demotivated students are a lack of self-confidence or self-esteem (Chambers, 1993). The latter perfectly matches the NATs of individuals, nevertheless despite their intricate and axiomatic relationship, the link between demotivation and NATs in scholarly articles is meagre. Subsequently, the present study aims to provide further evidence of the relationship by illuminating the symptoms of demotivation.

2.2.2. Suicidal Thoughts

A potential outcome of demotivation as a thought process is the risk of suicide or suicidal thoughts. Suicide is the act of self-inflicting injury with the intent to kill one's self (Rosenberg et al., 1988, Nock, 2014). According to Durkheim (1897/1951) and Merton (1968) suicide as a deviant behaviour occurs as a result of abrupt societal changes and societal pressures. In the context of HE, HESA data identified 319 students who died by suicide between the academic year ending 2017 and the academic year ending 2020 (Office for National Statistics, 2022). Despite the severity of the phenomenon, merged with the high possibility of such occurrence at a doctoral level, very few attempts have been made.

Hazell et al. (2022) use a qualitative cross-sectional survey design spread across all UK doctoral colleges. Among 3,352 DRs, 1,263 (41.64%) reported living with constant suicidal thoughts and ideation, highlighting the gravity and mental health state of doctoral students during their PhD

journey. Results from qualitative survey include answers from DRs such as ‘I have had 7 suicide attempts over the past 9 years, including 4 during my PhD’, ‘Unfortunately suicidal ideation is a symptom I am very familiar with. My PhD crushes me sometimes and sucks all the happiness I had out of me’ and ‘I think the main reason for feeling suicidal and that you want to give up is the fact that you're doing your best to prove you are very smart and capable and you end up being put down and criticised very harshly I truly believe that a PhD degree can kill you’ (Hazell et al., 2021, p.761-763). The data provided serve as compelling evidence as to why doctoral students have higher psychological distress than any other type. Suicide is not a short-term occurrence, rather it is an inner battle that lasts for a significant amount of time (Courtet, 2016). Demotivation is a potential risk factor leading to suicidal attempts. Due to the fact that the latter dampens the motivation and happiness of its individual, a severe case could potentially lead to consider such measures. The case is particularly true for individuals reaching states of hopelessness and helplessness after demotivation (Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2011). Therefore, detecting phases that precede the irreversible threshold of suicide is of humanitarian importance and demotivation could be the phase that indicates what Kikuchi (2015) terms as danger zones. The present study thus investigates whether the phenomenon of demotivation could potentially lead to suicide.

3. Demotivation in Doctoral Lifeworlds

Previous studies on demotivation have disregarded the doctoral level; therefore, a substantial empirical void worthy of investigation is present. The following studies are more pronounced as they logically infer demotivation. The common themes found are self-distraction, loneliness, feelings of isolation, and psychological illness as possible internal demotivators. As regards the external demotives, they include *the supervisor, lack of support, structure and resources, personal issues* and *research-related problems*.

It is important to note that this study’s primary focus is not on gender. However, the research recognises that gender can influence the direction, nature and intensity of doctoral demotivation. Previous studies reflected on gender challenges in doctoral studies such as issues of work-life balance, pregnancy, announcing a child to supervisors, and gender issues (Kurtz-Costes et al., 2006; Onwuegbuzie et al., 2014; Schmidt and Umans, 2012; Handforth, 2022; Urban et al., 2025). Nevertheless, the aim of this study is to investigate and identify overreaching demotivating factors that are applicable across participants irrespective of gender. I further note the issue of gender in the limitation section and raise it as an area for future research. I believe that on their journeys the sample experienced factors that were common and accept there is also likely to be a nuance of gender.

Using interviews, Onwuegbuzie et al. (2014) investigated the life experiences of 8 doctoral women (2 single, 5 married and 1 divorced). Findings were classified into three meta-themes: *adjustment*, *encouragement* and *discouragement*. Adjustment refers to the necessary accommodation regarding their lives when transitioning from student to researcher. Such adjustment concerns time management, interaction, belief and lifestyle. Encouragement comprises intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. The former concerns factors emanating from within individuals, such as pursuing a PhD for its own sake. The latter emerging from outside of the individual refers to support from friends and family (spouses for married women). Discouragement was divided into internal and external. Internal discouragement included *self-distraction* and *loneliness*; thus validating once again the dangers of isolation as mentioned earlier (Ali and Kohun, 2006; Janta et al., 2014). External discouraging obstacles were the lack of a support system such as university-grade friends and family's lack of understanding. Concerning the difference between married and single women, married women were more inclined to external motivators because of their families/husbands who offer support. For single women, an inclination towards internal forces such as faith in god was noticed.

The very first doctoral study on demotivation was conducted recently by Cantu (2016). She aimed to identify which instructor behaviours doctoral computer science and information science students found demotivating and to what extent their perceptions of these demotivating instructor behaviours influenced their information-seeking behaviours in a face-to-face classroom. Mixed-methods approach included demographic and student-perceived demotivating instructor behaviour surveys along with semi-structured interviews and follow-up questions. Results indicate that instructor demotivating behaviours not only impact negatively on student information seeking behaviours, but also their impact lasts. When experiencing negative behaviours from instructors, participants hold on to the negative feeling. Subsequently, because of such traumatic experiences, participants abstained from being completely at ease in the classroom. Therefore, the feeling of demotivation was not preconceived, but it emerged through the negative experience. Finally, the expectations held by students influence the level of demotivation they feel in a face-to-face classroom.

The research offered a primary foundation for doctoral demotivation. Nevertheless, the study has focused on computer science doctoral students who study in a classroom setting. Therefore, researchers in social sciences are not concerned with this study. Because research in such disciplines is conducted individually and has no fixed schedule (Janta et al., 2014).

Drawing a cross-country research, Frick and Pyhältö (2020) investigate the positive and negative experiences of the doctoral journey at Finish and South African universities. Participants were asked to recall two key turning points of their doctoral journey. Both negative and positive results were classified under six aspects of doctoral experience including *experiences of doctoral research*,

structures and resources, scholarly community, supervision, development as a scholar, and personal issues.

The negative experiences included a perceived lack of supervisory support such as insufficient supervision, lack of encouragement, and lack of interest and support (mostly from South Africans). Finnish respondents expressed their negative perception towards structure and resources; particularly, the insecure financial situation and high bureaucracy of doctoral programs. Similarly, South African respondents reported funding issues and a lack of institutional support. Respondents also reported difficulties in time management in terms of balancing academic studies and other duties (work, personal). Furthermore, personal issues such as family-related, psychological, and physical illness, lack of motivation and feelings of isolation were among the negative experiences faced by respondents. However, the research has asked very limited questions. It gives ideas of what participants are reporting about their doctoral experience, but they do it vague fashion.

Over the years, the most recurrent factors in doctoral experience are extrinsic such as institutional or personal (Devos et al., 2017; van Rooij et al., 2019; Hardman, 2020). Although international doctoral students' demotivation literature is scarce, research on PhD completion or attrition is useful in drawing possible external factors.

3.1. Supervisor

One of the most important and influential factors for doctoral students' progress and development is the supervisor (Hockey, 1996; Golde and Dore, 2001; Heath, 2002; McAlpine and Norton, 2006; Ives and Rowley, 2005; Mainhard et al, 2009; Cheon et al, 2009; Halse, 2011; Platow, 2012; Devos et al, 2017; Hardman, 2020). Notably, Lovitts (2001, p.139) states that the supervisor *“influences how the student comes to understand the discipline and the roles and responsibilities of academic professionals, their socialization as a teacher and a researcher, the selection of dissertation topic, the quality of the dissertation, and subsequent job placement”*. Thus, indicating the role of the supervisor not only as the gatekeeper of knowledge but also helps supervisees to transition from students to professional researchers by teaching them the necessary research skillsets and providing support for future occupational state.

Moreover, it is the traits that the supervisor possesses that lead students to succeed in the doctoral journey. First, due to the emotional and cognitive aspects of the PhD, supervisors must hold the necessary skills (social, technical, academic) that allow them to deal with the non-linearity of the doctoral research (Sambrook, Stewart and Roberts, 2008). Key elements supervisors must also hold are summarized in the work of Wisker (2008, p. 40):

to supervise...to read you work thoroughly and in advance...to be available when needed...to be friendly open and supportive...to be constructively critical...to have a

good knowledge of the research area...to structure the supervision, and ongoing relationship...to know how to ask open questions, how to draw out ideas and problems, and how to elicit information even if the student finds communication difficult.

Thus, the supervisor's role is complex and multifaceted. It represents a significant responsibility as they have the lives of doctoral students depending on them to succeed in the virgin route of the PhD. Thus, Wisker's (2008) passage adds a layer of strength to the importance of the supervisory team in influencing the success or failure of PhD students. This is also supported by the work of Zhao et al. (2007) and van Rooij et al. (2019) on how a good quality relationship leads to progress, goal achievement and thus PhD success. Thus, the supervisor is a crucial factor that cannot be ignored and represents one contributor to PhD success.

Additionally, using IPA, Hardman (2020) found out that one of the reasons behind timely doctoral completion for international students was having a knowledgeable and enthusiastic supervisor about the topic who is also supportive and motivating to their students. Similarly, van Rooij et al. (2019) collected surveys from 839 PhD students on factors affecting PhD success demonstrated the relevance of the supervisor-supervisee relationships as having a detrimental impact on satisfaction and attention to pursue; demonstrating their positive influence and motivating effect. Lastly, based on a qualitative analysis of 29 interviews, Devos et al. (2015) identified how doctoral supervisors provide structure, involvement, and autonomy support to their doctoral students. Demonstrating through various methodological approaches the role model of supervisors in promoting future researchers and facilitating supervisees' development through fostering a positive and informative environment. Subsequently, supervisors in these examples act as a booster for motivation.

However, the literature also indicates that the supervisor can act sometimes in the opposite direction leading to disengagement and attrition. Using regression analysis on the results obtained from 839 doctoral students, van Rooij et al. (2019) found that two supervision characteristics lead students to withdraw from their doctoral program namely: academic support and high expectations. Participants who perceived less academic support from their supervisors and had high expectations more frequently considered departing. Moreover, having negative advising relationships was also found to lead to attrition (Golde, 2005; Bair and Haworth, 2004; Barnes and Austin, 2009). Echoing that, Maher et al. (2020) recently approved such findings by interviewing 18 biomedical doctoral students who withdrew from their programs. More than half of the participants reported that problematic advising relationships were their main reason to depart from their studies; whereas for others, it was the last straw that pushed them to quit.

Thus, indicating that the supervisor can either act as a motivator or a demotivator that can even push students to cancel their academic efforts. Finally, the supervisors' impact is more significant to

international students who are away from their homes (Janta et al., 2014) and supervisors represent in a way a member of their abroad ‘family’ (Walsh, 2010). Subsequently, if the dimension from which the supervisor acts is negative, it incrementally gets exacerbated for international students due to their precarious situation.

3.2. Family

It has been proven that having a family member in academia influences future academic path careers (Templeton, 2016). If the family understands the value of academia, their attitude and support play a huge impact on doctoral students’ motivation, resilience and success (Breitenbach et al, 2019; McCray and Joseph-Richards, 2020). As pinpointed by Onieal (2010. p. 4) “*Bring on your family as a key component of your staff because it is the family that finishes the dissertation*”. Meaning that the family provides help until the goal is reached as it supplies emotional/academic support that increases resilience, reduces stress and boosts academic progress (Volkert et al., 2018; McCray and Joseph-Richards, 2020).

Using a descriptive survey of 835 doctoral students, Volkert et al. (2018) investigate how environmental/external stressors predict students’ intention to leave their doctoral studies. Findings indicated that support issues and program stressors are strong indicators of intention to leave. Specifically, results from support issues revealed that the intention to leave increases when family support decreases; thus showing the prominent role of the family in eliminating or creating stressors in students’ path which impact their motivation and persistence. Moreover, findings related to family support is critical for success had the largest effect size; indicating the role of the family in the academic persistence and continuance of doctoral students. Consequently, the family is a strong influencer that can either facilitate or hinder doctoral completion. Having family issues not only adds stress but also raises the risks of attrition as their supportive environment is reduced (Volkert et al., 2018).

Moreover, Breitenbach et al. (2019) investigated what the term family includes and how students explain family influences on doctoral success through qualitative online surveys of 133 doctoral students. An important finding indicates that family does not only include blood relatives but also includes friends and co-workers. Therefore, enlarging the understanding of family signification and inclusion. Further findings explicate family influences through themes including *time, family support, positive experience, pride from family, negative feedback, more stress, cost and lack of understanding*. The family support that was most significant to doctoral students across all age groups is encouragement, supportive attitude and understanding. These latter come when families have experienced similar academic routes and provide their children/spouses with understanding and most

importantly the gift of time to dedicate to the thesis process. However, the lack of support was mirrored in families' misunderstanding of time commitment regarding the thesis' obligation and the value of a doctoral degree. The negative perception of families caused various impacts on the relationships such as divorce for married students. Thus, highlighting how family influence can contribute to students' encouragement/motivation to display greater efforts or decrease their engagement by not being supportive of what their relatives/spouses/friends are pursuing and ultimately cause students' disengagement/demotivation. As they have a clear impact on students' thesis progress, for instance, if encouragement and positive reinforcement are provided, motivation only increases as the work is valued and rewarded by the most important environmental factor for students. However, if what is undertaken by students is not approved by their families, elements such as misunderstanding, criticism and blame are to be apparent, which generates demotivation. Subsequently, family is a strong influencing societal factor that cannot be ignored.

3.4. Peers

In any instance of learning, students have with them individuals pursuing the same academic program called peers. These peers accompany students as they are going through the same experience. One of the advantages of having peers is that they could be considered as 'learning partners' (Flores-Scott and Nerad, 2012, p.74). They are regarded as "*important agents of community, learning, and development at this level of graduate work*" (Flores-Scott and Nerad, 2012, p.75). Using Vygotsky's (1978) terms, peers act as mediators or More Knowledgeable Other (MKO) where they offer support and assist students with their experience, knowledge and skills and help them transcend the Zone of Proximal development (ZPD); which is an unknown area for students. This kind of collaborative learning was also highlighted in Lave and Wenger's (1991) notion of Communities of practice where novice students work within the same learning environment as professionals and acquire knowledge through Legitimate Peripheral Participation (LPP). Therefore, the importance of peers is of fundamental importance to students' development, learning and achievement.

Former studies have demonstrated the importance of peer learning at the undergraduate level (Lave and Wenger, 1991; Boud, 2001; Boud and Lee, 2005) and even at the postgraduate level (Devenish et al., 2009; Devos et al., 2017). Nevertheless, little is known about peer learning for international postgraduate students. One reason for that is because postgraduate students have already completed their undergraduate degrees; thus, they do not require support to belong to the university community as they already belong to one (Carver and Cuffe, 2012). However, this does not concern international students who started their postgraduate education abroad. International students face issues such as difficulties in adapting to the learning environment (Campbell, 2012). Moreover, their coping

mechanism to the new learning environment is reduced due to acculturation problems; homesickness, language problems, isolation, and loneliness (Campbell, 2015). For these reasons, international students are more prone to get demotivated, lose their academic engagement in the learning process, and ultimately affect positive achievement (Liu et al., 2024). Up until recently, Evans (2015) used action research method to investigate how peer learning could support international postgraduate students' journey and enhance their learning experience. Results demonstrate that students have learned from their peers in terms of how to improve their organisational skills, study skills, reaction to feedback, time management and academic writing. Consequently, peer learning is helpful for international postgraduate students as this kind of learning is more horizontal and offers chances for mutual learning and sharing a sense of belonging through mutual experiences (Boud and Lee, 2005). As pinpointed by Weidman et al. (2001, p.62) "*the cohort influences the learning process, opens support mechanisms, and enriches the experience socially and emotionally*". Therefore, the support offered is not only academic but also includes emotional and social support as international students' sense of loneliness is more exacerbated and need to feel a sense of belonging.

The state of not being able to belong to an academic community has been described as a state of alienation (Strayhorn, 2012, 2018) which greatly influences doctoral students' progress. Alienation is the act of losing connection to oneself and others which results in negative feelings such as loneliness, uncontrollability and hopelessness (Zhu et al., 2021). Therefore, the concept raised by Strayhorn is valid as a sense of belonging is one of the fundamental needs in human nature (Maslow, 1954). Therefore, a lack of sense of belonging makes students feel unimportant, unrecognized and most importantly alienated/strangers from their community. Moreover, alienation, in this context, is greatly predictive of poor mental health problems and Post-Traumatic stress (Sprang and Silman, 2013), which are highly found in doctoral students. Subsequently, the academic community is of great help to students as they provide a multitude of support (professional, personal and emotional).

Nevertheless, Golde (2000, p. 222) highlights "*the absence of social integration can have a negative effect on the quality of the students' experience, such absence is not a precipitator of attrition*". Confirmed lately, Maher et al. (2020) demonstrated that peers were not a reason to withdraw from the doctoral program; however, they played an influential role when observing their peers' behaviours. Simply put, peers can have a positive influence on doctoral progression as they can have a negative influence that is not a predictor of attrition. However, studies at the doctoral level have not fully explored whether peers can lead to disengagement/demotivation as previous research has only investigated the positive effect of peers (Breitenbach et al., 2019; Maher et al., 2020, McCray and Joseph-Richards, 2020).

3.5. Covid-19 Pandemic

The Covid pandemic represents one of the most unexpected and destabilising factors in humanity. People's lives have been disrupted leading to a complete entry into a new world of uncertainty (Burns, 2023). In the academic context, it also introduced new adjustments such as online/remote teaching and learning and limited access to university campuses. While some have adapted to the situation, students in higher education have had challenges with the current situation leading to mental health-related challenges, decreased motivation, and heightened isolation (Korkmaz and Toraman, 2020; Donohue et al., 2021; Sverdlik et al., 2023). Using an online survey of 4454 doctoral students across 249 Russian universities, Abdul-Rahaman (2023) found that Covid had a negative consequence for both international and domestic students' learning experience, satisfaction with supervision, dissertation experience, and doctoral program satisfaction. Furthermore, the results indicated that international students were more exposed to higher levels of stress, burnout, frustration, dissatisfaction, and dropout due to bad experiences arising from non-suitable learning environments, poor supervision that affects student grooming, and late dissertation defences. This highlights how international students are impacted by Covid more than any other domestic students.

Similarly, Sverdlik et al. (2023) unveiled challenges doctoral students faced during Covid outbreak. Using a questionnaire on 708 doctoral students, results found most impediments to be: inability to see family/friends, being home-bound, blurring of work/family time, isolation, and inability to access campus. These results demonstrate the importance of having regular networking, workplace and social gatherings to permit the full thriving of the thesis. By students having been deprived of their everyday life, they lose their focus and motivation to complete their thesis. This was confirmed by Korkmatz and Toraman (2020) and Donohue et al. (2021) on how PhD students lost their motivation, focus and energy during Covid. Donohue et al. (2021) also found through 235 participants how Covid impacted PhD students from various sectors mainly: Research design (delayed fieldwork, change design, availability of participants), access to resources (spaces, resources, peers), workload (job demands), mental health (stress, lack of focus, motivation, energy and procrastination) and finances. From the studies reported, there is an indication of how Covid can be a dampening force leading to demotivation. As students lose their focus, energy and motivation, which are elements of motivated behaviour (Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2021), the axiomatic or logical inference would consider Covid to be demotivating. However, due to the lack of studies on the specific topic, there is a lack of literature relating Covid to demotivation. Therefore, the present study aims to assess whether Covid has a demotivating effect on the journeys of UK Algerian postgraduates.

In sum, although the reason for starting a PhD is predominantly a personal choice, different elements enter the equation while undertaking the research. This section revealed that there are

significant stations faced during the journey. While there are joys of doing research in terms of exploration, excitement, discovery and contribution to knowledge; there exist a substantial number of factors that impact the doctoral route namely the psychological, physiological, social and many more. Combined with the attrition rate at this level and due to the fact that a PhD is ‘an emotional roller coaster’ (Cuschieri, 2021) that contains displeasure (Hughes, 2011) the possibility of getting demotivated at this level is therefore extremely high. Therefore, this chapter serves as a foundational block to introduce and prove the existence of the demotivation phenomenon at the doctoral level as almost no studies have been conducted at such level. Moreover, the phenomenon of demotivation is further exacerbated for international postgraduate students as they are completely secluded from their homes and have to deal with supplementary issues other than doctoral demands.

4. International Students’ Transition

In addition to the doctoral challenges mentioned above, international students are more impacted as they are a relatively vulnerable population (Desa et al., 2012). The following section reviews the additional obstacles international students face in higher education that could potentially be added as demotives towards success.

4.1. Cultural Challenges

Cultural challenges designate factors encountered by international students during their sojourn in the host country. These challenges can, in some cases, shake their belief systems or cultural identity. Before enumerating the challenges, a definition is provided.

Culture is an umbrella term that includes bodies of knowledge, sets of beliefs, morals, norms, traditions, customs, laws and perceptions (Scott, 2014; Taylor, 2010). Culture includes both tangible elements such as clothes and food and non-tangible elements such as beliefs and customs (Little, 2023). An interesting aspect of culture is that it is learned and transmitted as Scott (2016, p.260) highlights “culture is all that in human society which is socially rather than biologically transmitted”. Therefore, much like genes that are transmitted biologically, culture is a trait that is transmitted through the social aspect. International students navigate different cultural shifts when relocating to a different context (Forbes-Mewett and Nyland, 2008). The latter coincides with the Algerian students who have to culturally adapt by integrating the new cultural norms while maintaining their cultural heritage or identity.

As raised in the introductory chapter, the move from a more collectivist culture to a more individualist culture can be challenging. Culture cannot be simplified into a dyadic division as it concerns complex human lives (Vignoles, 2018). In other words, such generalisations cannot apply

to the whole UK or Algeria. In line with such argument, previous research has shown significant cultural differences within countries such as the USA being more individualistic than the UK despite the fact that both of them are individualistically oriented (Hofstede et al. 2010; Kitayama et al. 2009). Aside from national degree differences, studies have shown individualistic-collectivist within the same country. For example, using an index of collectivism, Vandello and Cohen (1999) find that regions within the USA such as the Deep South had the highest collectivism score whereas regions such as the Mountain West and Great Plains had the highest individualism score. Additionally, such differentiation in cultural perception was observed within different cultural groups and social classes. For instance, Grossmann and Varnum (2011) found that people from the upper and middle classes in America and Russia are more inclined to individualism than the working class. Subsequently, it is safe to argue that overgeneralisation is not applicable to social realities and a more hybrid and fluid culture is noticed in countries rather than a rigid dichotomy. Finally, people differ in how they react while transitioning into a new cultural context. While some students might succumb to isolation, alienation and homesickness due to the blatant difference of the place, others might successfully adapt and develop individualistic tendencies necessary for cultural adaptation leading to the emergence of a hybrid individualistic-collectivist new identity, in other words, a more fluid cultural identity.

Negotiating cultural differences can act as a motivating or demotivating experience. Changing a cultural setting is like changing a whole new world. The intensity of such stress is moderated by whether there are similarities between international students' culture and the host's (Cox, 1989). It also differs according to personal features, the extent to which the culture has been exposed, educational background and competencies, gender, age, language, race and psychological and spiritual assets, along with the host culture's political and social attitudes to international students (Desa et al., 2012). Therefore, if the change is too radical, international students experience what is known as 'acculturative stress' (Cox, 1989).

Acculturative stress is a phenomenon that impacts international students on multiple levels. Desa et al (2012) define it as:

A marked deterioration of the general health status of an individual; it encompasses physiological, psychological, and social aspects that are explicitly linked to the acculturation process. It is also marked by physical and psychological changes due to the adaptation required in diet, climate, housing, interactional styles, norms and values to a new culture (p.364)

Therefore, international students try to adapt to the various changes when entering a new country with a different culture. Titrek et al. (2016) used semi-structured interviews to account for the challenges faced by international students in Turkey. Results revealed the following challenges: *communication*

problems, housing, the environment, cultural problems, health problems, as well as social issues such as *separation from families, friends and romantic partners, fear of failure, academic transfer, and academic challenges*. Participants reported that cultural change was the most significant challenge they faced. Examples of cultural problems include food, greetings, wearing, holidays, and religious activities. Consequently, the participants living in a culture that is relatively different to theirs ultimately experience acculturative stress. The latter impact on their physiological, psychological and mental health as reported; leading them to feel estranged, alienated and not comprehended. Therefore, cultural change when too radical could be considered as very demotivating as it alienates international students (Seeman, 1959; Royce, 2015). However, cultural problems as being demotivating at the postgraduate level in relation to the present study population remain an unanswered question.

Nevertheless, there are instances where cultural change is not a hindrance to the learning process. Contrary to Titrek et al. (2016), Sherry et al. (2010) provide an alternative result of cultural adjustment. In interviewing international students of Toledo, the cultural adaptation issue was not found to be of major concern. Participants reported because the host culture and theirs' are not very different, or due to personal factors such as having already visited the country before; therefore making the process of acclimation to a new culture less difficult. Therefore, as stipulated above, the intensity of cultural shock depends on the degree of difference the cultures encompass. The more different, the more international students are prone to acculturative stress (Cox, 1989; Desa et al., 2012), which in turn hinders all the necessary components to successful learning.

However, studies on culture at the international level, and postgraduates most importantly, have not sought to investigate whether such challenges might lead to demotivation at the doctoral level. People encounter myriads of obstacles that act as interfering forces (Higgins, 2006); the question is whether these international students perceive these obstacles as surmountable or insurmountable obstacles (Marguc et al., 2010). The former refers to interfering forces with the goal without necessarily blocking the progress, whereas the latter refers to obstacles that completely block development and progress (Marguc et al., 2010). Subsequently, the present research aims to investigate whether the most apparent challenges according to the literature could be regarded as demotivating.

4.2. Effect of Culture

Given that the difficulties with the culture are more likely to be at their highest in the initial stage of the sojourn, one cannot help but have conflicting ideas about that particular period of time previously associated with excitement and positive feelings. Brown and Holloway (2008) study happens to address this very point by investigating how international postgraduate students adjust

themselves at a UK university using ethnographic study. The findings opposed major studies that reported feelings of excitement and euphoria in the initial stages of sojourning such as Brown's (1980) acculturation model or Adler's (1975) model of transitional experience. It revealed that major feelings were common symptoms related to cultural shock. Although there were feelings of enthusiasm with regard to starting a new life in a new setting, these were overshadowed by states of anxiety, depression, loneliness and stress. As health must accompany students to boost their learning development (Kernan et al., 2011), having poor emotional health only hinders international students' opportunities to focus on their goals. However, this study has not investigated whether these obstacles experienced are strong enough to demotivate international students. The following thesis aims to fill this gap by looking at whether the unique challenges faced by international students are strong enough to demotivate international students and to what extent some challenges are insurmountable (Marguc et al., 2010).

4.3. Psychological Wellbeing: The Impact of Doctoral Studies and International Situation

Psychological wellbeing is one of the very fundamental human needs to have a healthy learning experience. In motivational theories, psychological wellbeing is the intrinsic part of human motivation that drives success (Deci and Ryan, 2017). Nevertheless, psychological wellbeing is highly impacted by several factors when entering the world of pure research as reported by the literature (Hyun et al., 2006; Kernan et al., 2011; Levecque et al., 2017; Sverdlik et al., 2018, 2020). The nature of PhD as being a 'solitary affair' (Cotterall, 2013, p.180) impacts all doctoral students on their progress and sometimes causes even attrition (Kohun and Ali, 2005), with a greater impact on social science postgraduate students due to their individualistic nature of the program (Chiang, 2003).

Elements reported by the literature weakening the psychological wellbeing or mental health of doctoral students include workload demands, isolation, feelings of inadequacy, and issues related to personal and professional relationships (Lovitts, 2001; Walsh, 2010; Acker and Haque, 2015; Löfström and Pyhältö, 2015). Experiencing such issues lead doctoral students to undergo stress (Devos et al., 2017), anxiety (Hyun et al., 2006; El-Ghoroury et al., 2012), displeasure (Hughes, 2011) guilt (Brooks, 2015; Gutierrez et al., 2020), and procrastination (Kearns et al., 2008). These are all potential obstacles/hindrances to students' progress and enjoyment within the doctoral research process. However, despite the extensive literature on doctoral challenges, there has been nearly no dedicated study of doctoral students' demotivation that this research is aware of.

As mentioned, the effect of doctoral hardships is exacerbated within international students. In addition to the impact generated by the demands of the degree, international students must cope with extra issues such as adjusting to a new environment which already triggers negative emotions such as acculturation, loneliness, stress, homesickness, alienation and estrangement (Schram and Lauver,

1988; Owie, 1982; Brown and Holloway, 2008; Desa et al., 2012; Janta et al., 2014). For instance, during a study of 219 international graduate students from 12 different universities across Japan, Pallos et al. (2005) showed that 53% of participants suffered from emotional disturbance. The latter concerns four factors that accounted for 51% of the variance in distress including “anxiety and insomnia” (29%), “social dysfunction” (11% such as social isolation), “symptoms of depression” (6%), and “feelings of incompetence” (5%). The findings are valid given the fact that international students face considerable changes when moving abroad and have to adjust to regain equilibrium.

4.4. Lack of Support Systems (Lack of belongingness)

Other challenging aspects associated with being an international student in UK universities include the lack of support systems or at least the lack of familiar support systems such as the ones offered by family and religious organisations back in the sojourner’s home country as well as struggling with feeling included in the local community (Sherry et al., 2010; Desa et al., 2012; Titrek et al., 2016). Studies reported the incapacity of most international students to make friends in the host country due to cultural differences or religious differences. For instance, Sherry et al. (2010) indicated that a significant number of international students tend to make friends only with other international students from the same country or culture. Participants reported having difficulties forming friendships with Americans due to perceived unfriendliness. Others reported issues in creating such relations due to the dissimilarity of their respective cultures. Using qualitative questionnaires, Novera (2004) investigated the adjustment of Indonesian postgraduate students studying in an Australian university. Participants stated that having a lack of contextual topics such as football and alcohol culture were their main problems. The latter is due to the fact that Indonesians’ culture and religion prohibit the use of alcohol. Subsequently, they found themselves living in a world totally stranger to them, making them feel living in an alienated world and culture. Consequently, they are under more pressure than domestic students as their belonging needs are not fully achieved (Maslow, 1954; Strayhorn, 2018); driving them to feel alienated.

Lack of sense of belongingness in the academic community was also an issue faced by international students. Sherry et al. (2010) reported from participants that the reasons for such disconnection from the university were mainly due to the mutual intelligibility of international and domestic students, racial discrimination, feeling unaccepted and cultural issues such as food in the dorm. In this sense, lack of belongings happens to be a strong obstacle blocking international students from enjoying their unique experiences. Similarly, Moh et al. (2021) reported a lack of interest of domestic students towards international students’; which causes a disappointment of international students. Nevertheless, most of Moh et al. (2021) include Asian participants; therefore, such results

are only applicable to similar populations. Moreover, the findings are related to undergraduate and graduate university students from various disciplines.

5. Sociology of Demotivation

The scope of demotivation has always been limited to FLL (Chambers, 1993; Oxford, 1998; Sakai and Kikuchi, 2009). Consequently, the phenomenon lacks breadth and depth. One way to solve such limitations is by borrowing knowledge from other disciplines. Thus, this section will broaden/enlarge the understanding of demotivation by relating it to sociological theories of alienation and disenchantment also called ‘application spotting’ (Alvesson and Sandberg, 2013, p.11). The phenomenon shares something in common which is the loss/deprivation of an essence that is relative to individuals’ identities (Marx, 1844, Seeman, 1959; Weber 1946; Chambers, 1993). This section will be devoted to sociological concepts and how they resemble and account for the psychological concept of demotivation with critics and how doctoral students in general and international students in specific are indeed exposed to such phenomena more than any other level.

5.1. Alienation

Originating from Karl Marx’s (1818-1883) claims against the capitalist system threats to the individual, he theorized the nature of the labour market as being an alienating process to the worker, in other words, such occurrence is inevitable. Jaeggi (2014, p.1) defines alienation as “*a relation of relationlessness... [It] is a failure to apprehend, and a halting of, the movement of appropriation*”. This means that alienated individuals find themselves lost and unable to reclaim what is theirs. The latter gives a sense of powerlessness, estrangement and detachment from oneself and society, leading them to live a life that is not theirs. In an alienated world, they behave ‘artificially’ and ‘non-authentically’ and are acting based on other’s desires. Similarly, demotivated students present a ‘halt’ in their motivated behaviour due to critical events (Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2021). The latter drives them to feel powerless regardless of their competencies as presented by Chambers (1993) and consequently ‘pulling the learner down’ (Kikuchi, 2015, p.4). Subsequently, symptoms of alienated people are found within demotivated ones.

Alienation is a negative phase where individuals’ state is opposite to normal and feel dehumanized, powerless and more importantly estranged. Alienated people feel indifferent and go through an internal division, they experience a lot of deprivation such as power and freedom and are unable to socialise with others as the world surrounding them feels alien or strange to them (Jaeggi, 2014). Similarly, demotivated individuals lose their motivation (Kikuchi, 2015) which is an ‘essential’ component to a successful doctoral degree (Lovitts, 2001, 2008; Brailsford et al., 2010). Therefore,

losing such a focal component in one's academic life drives students to feel powerless, as reported by clear definitions and symptoms of demotivated students (Chambers, 1993; Dörnyei, 1998, 2001).

5.1.1. Dimensions of Alienation

Sociologist Melvin Seeman (1959) opted for a socio-psychological approach to alienation. Based on the works of Marx, Weber and Durkheim, he presented five dimensions of alienation. It is worth noting that these states may also account for demotivated behaviours as the symptoms behind alienation accords with demotivated ones (Chambers, 1993; Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2021).

Powerlessness: Taken mainly from Marx's claims about the capitalist domination over its workers. Powerlessness denotes workers having no power over the things they produce. Given the fact that they work for someone else's business, workers are compelled to do whatever higher authorities say. As a result of the lack of power, a lack of freedom emerges as "*the worker exists to satisfy the need of existing values for valorization*" (Marx et al, 1990, p. 799). Though this term is purely sociological, it is greatly relatable to the notion of demotivation in the educational setting. As demotivated students are those who lost their power/motivation to pursue their objectives; therefore demotivation could be regarded as a state of powerlessness and incapability due to inescapable factors. Méndez and Tun (2017) pinpointed through interviews and emotional agendas that demotivated students at university feel a myriad of negative emotions and powerlessness was among them. However, studies have never been conducted at a doctoral level or in relation to the present research sample.

Meaninglessness: The worker unable to relate himself to the product, a sense of purposelessness emerges. However, because workers are obliged to work for survival, they are forced to undertake the task regardless of existing alienation. They became mere instruments or cogs in bigger machines. In this sense, meaning offers purpose to do what is necessary. If the meaning is lost, it stops the person from moving forward. Similarly, the latter is basically what demotivation accounts for; a halt of the responsible moving forces due to perceived purposelessness in unrewarded efforts such as getting low/bad marks (Sakai and Kikuchi, 2009; Mirza et al., 2016) or meaninglessness of the item learned (Kim, 2015). Additionally, it is relatable to the sample used in the present thesis; the Algerian students studying in UK Universities are part of a program that is going to determine their career choices, all of which may see them going through the motions meaninglessly in order to secure a job or maintain their position of perceived privilege over their Algerian-still counterparts. However, to check the validity of such a claim must be investigated.

Isolation: due to the failure of establishing working relationships, workers feel separated or isolated from their co-workers. In other words, in the workplace, workers feel estranged from the working community. Experiencing such a feeling leads them to see and "*assign low reward value to goals or*

beliefs that are typically highly valued in the given society" (Seeman, 1959, p. 789). Similarly, in the academic community, integration is a vital component for academic thriving and its absence (also known as lack of belongingness) was one of the reasons behind students' doctoral attrition (Kohun and Ali, 2005). Moreover, It has been proven that isolation from family, friends and academic community leads to alienation (Case, 2007; Strayhorn, 2012, 2018). Therefore, lack of belongingness could be a strong demotivating factor. Similarly, as international students settle in another country, difficulties in acclimating are reported by the literature and isolation due to lack of friends in the host country was a major theme in many studies (Novera, 2004; Brown, 2008; Sherry et al., 2010). However, a clear study that demonstrates isolation as a demotivating factor in relation to the present study sample has not yet been conducted. Even though studies have demonstrated the exacerbated state of international students (Sherry et al., 2010; Desa et al., 2012; Titrek et al., 2016), little is known about whether this dimension could actually pull learners down and block their advancement.

Self-estrangement: self-estrangement implies feelings of change and unrecognizing. It can be seen as a failure of self-realisation (Seeman, 1975, p.104). In a way, it entails a deficiency in personal identity. Brennan and Auslander (1979, p.16) describe that any individual "*in this mode is theoretically expected to be unable to be genuine self in participation with others*". Interestingly, the quote refers to the sample type advocated in the present study; as international students are experiencing a new cultural environment, they face difficulties in acclimating to the new setting. International students in this sense are self-alienated or self-estranged since they cannot behave like they used to do; 'loneliness of the inner self' (Andersson, 1986, p.685) or "a feeling of estrangement from one's own personality" emerges (Gaev, 1976, p.9). Self-estrangement in international students has been reported in seminal works of Owie (1982) Schram and Lauver (1988), and lately in Sherry et al. (2010), Desa et al. (2012), Titrek et al. (2016) due to cultural, linguistic, and social issues. However, despite the existence of alienation and its component within international students, very little is known about whether such factors could actually demotivate international students in their postgraduate research process.

Normlessness: Derived from Emile Durkheim's work on 'anomie', it concerns mainly the social side of alienation. Seeman (1959, p. 787) identifies it as "*a situation in which the social norms regulating individual conduct have broken down or are no longer effective as rules for behaviour*". Meaning that the regulations/norms that were once approved were lost; leaving individuals to live in a world stranger to them. When assimilated into the educational context, normlessness denotes a state where students are not feeling normal anymore. Normality in education means being operational and engaging in work, it entails motivation. Whereas, when the normality is compromised, negative attributes such as disengagement are to occur within the students' journey. Examples of normlessness

in demotivation include students being disengaged and perturbing others in the learning process as presented in Chambers' (1993) investigation. Finally, normlessness is noticeable in international students as previous studies have already reported a high level of alienation (Owie, 1982; Klomegah, 2006). Because they are in a new setting, their regulations are no longer identifiable in such a context; causing them to act irregularly to the domestic population. However, such a state was never found as a potential demotivator in relation to adult students; therefore, the present study entails to unveil whether such symptoms are present within the adopted research population.

5.1.2. Alienation, Demotivation and PhD: an Intertwined Relation

Alienation, though an old concept, still subsists in the technological era. Geyer (2001) claims that alienation has evolved with the advancement of the world. Moreover, some scholars such as Case (2007) and Asare et al. (2017) have used such terms in higher education to explicate and give alternative perspective for students' experience at such a level, providing an insight that most students at this level experience alienation due to some factors.

Under alienation, every human essence such as power, freedom, leisure and autonomy is all deprived because of capitalism (Royce, 2015; Hall, 2018). Marx (1990) describes capitalist work as a 'torment' of a 'forced activity' imposed by a need to earn a living. Moreover, capitalist work 'mortifies' both the body and the mind of the worker (Royce, 2015). Parallel to such claims, previous research has demonstrated the effects of PhD on doctoral students' physical health such as sore throat and insomnia (Hyun et al., 2006; Kernan et al., 2011) social issues such as lack of contact and lack of support from families and friends (Volkert et al., 2018; Breitenbach et al., 2019) and psychological concerns such as anxiety, stress and depression (Janta et al., 2014; Cornwall et al., 2019). Therefore, as the doctorate monopolises the lifetime and health of the students to some extent, subsequently, the PhD could be regarded as an alienating process as they cause similar effects on individuals.

Moreover, Marx et al (1990, p. 517) said that the worker "*falls under the sway of his product*" and the capitalist system "*transform his lifetime into working time*" and even "*drag his wife and child [family] beneath the wheel of juggernaut of capital*". In other words, not only does capitalism alienate the worker from his products and monopolise all of his lifetime, but also it drags the family of the worker into the same domination and exploitation system. Similar to such a claim, doctoral research has shown that the nature of the level is isolating (McAlpine and Norton, 2006; Case, 2007; Nutov and Hazzan, 2011; Janta et al., 2014). Because the 'product' in this case 'PhD' absorbs a considerable amount of time and monopolises all thoughts, it separates doctoral students from all forms of socializing and sometimes even causes the rupture of such relations (Wellington and Sikes, 2007). This feeling of alienation demeans the ongoing forces of doctoral students.

5.1.3. Alienation and Engagement

Alienation was used to offer an alternative perspective regarding higher students' experience and their engagement. Using semi-structured interviews, Case (2007) asks 36 chemical engineering students to open up about their learning experiences. The aim was to identify the categories representing the various relationships that students potentially engaged in, and evidence of alienation or engagement in these various relationships. Case (2007) identifies six relationships where alienation might occur: to one's studies; to the broader university life; to home; to the career; to one's classmates; and the lecturer. The first result, some students found it extremely hard to maintain the demands of the program, leading them to disengage regardless of the consequences. Expressing disengagement, one participant responds, "*The thing is, learning chem[ical] eng[ineering] is not fun, it really isn't like, it's tons and tons of maths, and all you have to do is work, and it takes over your whole life*" (Case, 2007, p. 123). Thus proving the point expressed earlier about time absorption and absence of leisure and fun. If undergraduates experience such kind of obstacles, doctoral students might undergo even harder situations given the status of the degree, word count, quality of analysis and scale of demands. Moreover, alienation impacts even the students' way of thinking. Students think that everything except studies is not worthy and considered as a waste of time, "*when you do anything else apart from studying, actually you are wasting time*" (Case, 2007, p.124). Meaning that alienation not only monopolises their time but also deprives them of doing extra-activities which is incorrect as wellbeing must be taken care of to maximize learning outcomes (Kernan et al., 2011). Moreover, one respondent states "Enjoy...*I forgot how to spell that word*" (*ibid*), proving that the work they do deprives them to have extra activities that generate fun and pleasure that promote better wellbeing. Such results corroborate with Hughes (2011) who identifies displeasure to be the major feeling within doctoral studies thus showing that doctoral students are also alienated because of their work and deprives them of having some quality time which could lead to disengaging from the research process.

As the work monopolises students' lives, it leads them to live a life of alienation and deprivation (such as social life and freedom). The dominant experience of being a student in this context is one of denial, devoid of passion and enjoyment, and in some instances leading to a complete disengagement (Mann, 2001; Case, 2007; Asare et al, 2017). Similarly, in a recent study, Asare et al. (2017) report that students show signs of alienation when they do not pay attention in learning activities and talk about things that are out of the learning context thus showing totally disengaged behaviours.

6. Disenchantment

Disenchantment also refers to a state that concerns transition. However, the latter concerns a change that impacts a much larger population as it deals with global assumptions such as worldview.

Disenchantment is characterised by a shift from a pre-modern view of the world, also known as enchanted, to a modern view of the world that is disenchanted (Royce, 2015). Therefore, if enchantment of the world means being under a world characterised by a “desirable spell” or living under a magical world (Smith, 1987, p.39); disenchantment, conversely, demystifies and unveils such magic. In the transition from pre-modernity to the modernity era, the world is subject to “lose their magical significance” and therefore becomes disenchanted (Weber, 1978, p.506).

The reason for abolishing magical entities from the world is due to intellectualization or intellectual objectivity. As Weber (1946, p. 151) points “*The fate of our times is characterized by rationalization and intellectualization and, above all, by the disenchantment of the world*”.

The choice of the term is because Weber sees disenchantment as negative and alienating. First, since it changes individuals’ worldviews, it deprives them of sense and purpose. Moreover, because intellectualisation renders all thinking scientifically based and where science replaces religion, values and ideas which are unproved scientifically due to their highly subjective nature are not recognised (Abramowski, 1982). Since their previous worldviews have been rejected, individuals feel alienated as their perspectives have been crushed or ‘collapsed’ (Smith, 1987). Resulting in individuals struggling in a world that is stranger to them as disenchantment progressively abolishes everything that once had significance for them. Moreover, due to the multifaceted explanations provided by sciences regarding the different interpretations of worldviews under intellectualisation, each interpretation rivals the other leaving the individual to “*feel himself subject to the struggle between multiple sets of values*” (Royce, 2015, p. 120). Thus, a disenchanted world leaves the person alienated, lost, pressured, struggling, and voided from sense and purpose. In the academic world, disenchantment resulted from a lack of advocacy, support and agency, and contempt towards academia. The experience was also a huge contributor to attrition thinking in graduate students (Shanachilubwa, 2023). Therefore, disenchantment in academia represents a potent force that declines students’ aspirations to achieve their goals. The explanations provided coincide with the present research in two ways. First, international students as being alienated have been established. Second, to demotivation as their significance share similarities; which is the loss of magic or in educational terms motivation.

6.1. Disenchantment and Demotivation: a ‘De-magification’ Relationship

Disenchantment makes people emotionally reluctant in the face of such change. As Smith (1987, p. 39) points out, “*Disenchantment appears to be a particularly traumatic instance of unlearning*”. In other words, disenchantment is an undesirable and scary experience that individuals are forced to incorporate. Moreover, she (1987) further states that the emotional impact of new information is not the sole responsible for such reaction, but rather the old information being replaced

by new ones. Disenchantment is one of the reasons behind students' opposition to learning or demotivation in learning as she (1987, p. 39) asserts “ *Failure to learn in many cases may not reflect a low IQ as often as it may simply reflect resistance to the discomfort and dis-ease the displacement and replacement of fantasies occasion* ”. Similarly, demotivated students posit similar characteristics as even the smartest individual could be demotivated for a reason that aligns with Smith's claim. In multiple studies such as Sakai and Kikuchi (2009), factors such as *boring course content* could be taken as disenchanting as interesting course content is motivating and enchanting. Another consequence that emerged from disenchantment is the ‘iron cage’. Weber was interested in the effect of such modernity and the ‘inner effect’ on personality (Hennis, 1988; Schroeder, 1991). As a result, the iron cage theory was formulated. It “*encapsulates the idea that modern people are trapped in a rationalistic, bureaucratized organisation prison that deprives them of freedom and creativity*” (Woods, 2009, p. 120). Meaning that disenchantment imprisons and deprives people of their freedom as well as their ability to be creative (Giddens and Sutton, 2021; Royce, 2015). However, the phrase ‘iron cage’ is not taken in its literal sense; rather, it denotes a forced part of thinking integrated into the personality of the individual. The ‘iron’ which is the characteristic part of modernity is forged by people living in the modern world (Mazlish, 1971; Woods, 2009) which is according to Woods (2009) and Royce (2015) much more sinister and jeopardizing. Interestingly, such a description is intimately linked to demotivation. Since the latter is described as the negative force that neutralizes the ongoing motivation (Dörnyei, 2001b), there is a sense of figurative restriction or imprisonment of academic engagement. Thus demotivation, from a sociological perspective, could be regarded as the ‘iron cage’ of motivation.

Finally, disenchantment causes other negative outcomes such as a decrease in productivity, deteriorates the health and wellbeing of individuals and generates dissatisfaction (Furnham and Treglown, 2017). All of these are linked to symptoms/consequences of demotivation as they are less engaged and committed (Chambers, 1993; Asare et al., 2017). Hence, disenchantment could be regarded as a demeaning factor to academic engagement. Nevertheless, despite the danger disenchantment might impact students' academic engagement, no study has looked specifically at whether disenchantment is related or could lead to actual demotivation.

7. Theoretical synergy

The study utilises psychological and sociological concepts to embrace the internal and external life worlds impacting the doctoral student's life. Demotivation, alienation, and disenchantment have a common point which is lack of interest. Demotivated people are not interested in the attainment of objectives relative to their duties and responsibilities. This is because they do not have the

psychological force that allows them to act and make decisions to get what seems to interest them as members of society. The psychological force that pushes individuals to make efforts to reach the goals they set in their lives can be lost because of many factors such as alienation and disenchantment. Alienated people are not interested in what their group does because they feel that they do not belong to the group (Case, 2007). In other words, alienation describes an absence of willingness to participate in the construction process in a society, either physical or mental. In education, alienated learners do not participate and take part in the learning situation because they feel that they are alienated or isolated by their classes (Asare et al., 2017). Alienation, therefore, can be a great source of demotivation. As regards disenchantment, it describes a feeling of disappointment or dissatisfaction. In teaching and learning when students become disenchanted in their teachers, they are no longer interested in what is being taught by the teachers. This may demotivate them and make them disinterested in learning.

8. Knowledge Gap

Most investigations on demotivation were conducted on second/foreign language learning in classroom settings. The studies included academic levels ranging from elementary school to university within different contexts such as the Western context (UK, USA, and EU) to the Asian context (Chinese, Japanese). The interest in demotivation studies was triggered by the continuous second/foreign language learning failure (Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2011). Moreover, drawing on Gardner et al. (2004) research, a pattern of gradual demotivation is observed as the resourcefulness behind learning a language vanishes and becomes more challenging along with a constant increasing cognitive, linguistic, and curricular demands and social pressures that take place. Similarly, as the doctorate is a much higher degree intellectually (Hockey, 1994; Hawlery, 2003) that isolates socially (Janta et al., 2014) and due to the fact that PhD has been described as an intense, demanding, and emotional ‘roller coaster’ (Morrison-Saunders et al., 2010; Cuschieri, 2021); therefore, despite these evidenced claims, little attention has been paid to the negative impact demotivation can do in the postgraduate route. The chances of getting demotivated at this level are significant as they have more responsibilities in crafting original research that contributes to the existing knowledge. Additionally, demotivation could be more experienced by international students who are facing more issues in relation to their identities, language, socialisation, and culture (Sherry et al., 2010; Desa et al., 2012; Titrek et al., 2016). Nevertheless, despite evidence reported by the literature regarding challenges faced at the doctoral level, few attempts have focused on the phenomenon rigorously. For these multiple reasons, investigations around the phenomenon at such level deserve more attention and scrutiny. One way to generate meticulous and first-hand data on the undocumented experiential

feature is through IPA which aims to gather rich and first-person accounts of a specific experience (Smith and Nizza, 2021).

To reiterate, there are fundamentally two issues concerning demotivation literature. First, existing knowledge only concerns the learning of a foreign language, thus leaving other important areas completely overlooked. Secondly, resource availability of the phenomenon in relation to PhD students is relatively inexistent despite their alarming cases (attrition, low motivation, depression, anxiety, and stress) that suggest urgency. Moreover, the state of doctoral students is more alarming and observable among the social sciences students (Chiang, 2003; Mc Alpine and Norton, 2006) who work in an isolated way than natural sciences and especially international students who face other challenges such as language, culture difficulties in making friends and so on (Sherry et al., 2010; Desa et al., 2012; Titrek et al., 2016). Consequently, demotivation studies have left important gaps within the doctoral context. Therefore, the current thesis contribution will address the aforementioned niches by investigating the factors that demotivate international postgraduate students in social sciences and learn about how they perceive and process such state as it is one of the various reasons leading to the abandonment of efforts and interest in studies and potentially failing to attrition

9. Discussion

Research on demotivation is the first step to do in order to know how to counter it. Motivation has been demonstrated as one of the key determinants of doctoral completion (Lovitts, 2008; Onwuegbuzie et al., 2014; Sverdlik and Hall, 2019; McCray and Joseph-Richard, 2020). Therefore, any factor that threatens motivation ultimately jeopardizes the progress of doctoral studies. Indeed, past studies have found that one reason behind doctoral students' attrition is a lack of motivation (Lovitts, 2001; Walsh, 2010) and the lack of thereof influences achievement as well as persistence in doctoral education (Brown and Watson, 2010; Hegarty, 2011). Thus, such dangers should not be left unsolved and reasons behind impediments to academic engagement should be monitored; especially at the doctoral level where different challenging stations are met during the PhD route such as displeasure (Hughes, 2011) stress, anxiety and depression (Hyun et al., 2006; Kernan et al., 2011; Cornwall et al., 2019), lack of support from university, families and friend (Onwuegbuzie et al., 2014) and other factors related to difficulties in research processes (Frick and Pyhältö, 2020). However, almost no research has delved into whether these obstacles pull the learners' motivation down or not. Subsequently, the present research aims to answer all the questions around whether students perceive such challenges as strong enough to negate all their positive attributes or not.

Another reason behind studying demotivation is that its absence is more beneficial than the presence of motivation. Christophel and Gorham (1995) discovered that the absence of negative teacher

behaviours increased the motivation of students better than when there was a presence of positive teacher behaviours. Having a supportive supervisor increases the motivation and confidence of doctoral students (Lovitts, 2001; Overall et al., 2011; Mason, 2012); whereas having a less supportive and problematic relationship with a supervisor hinders progress and leads to potential attrition (van Rooij et al., 2019; Maher et al., 2020). However, what most doctoral studies have focused on was mostly on attrition, which is the actual departure from studies, not demotivation which is just a temporal phase experienced while pursuing the program. Consequently, detecting obstacles prior to attrition to allow a better experience for doctoral students is of major importance to increase their chances of success. Finally, another reason why demotivation should be conducted in doctoral studies is that according to Nakata (2006), demotivation if not repaired develops into amotivation, then learned helplessness; which refers to students having and shaping only negative and destructive beliefs. Thus, raising awareness of demotivation is of great importance, especially at the doctoral level where practically no literature on the subject exists.

Summary

The chapter has emphasised the reasons why doctoral students are more prone to alienation-related concepts and demotivation danger than any other level. It started by highlighting a significant gap in the current research on demotivation in social science doctoral students and international students. After that, the second section delves into myriads of other obstacles international students face. Finally, the third section linked the psychological phenomenon and the sociological components/theories of alienation and disenchantment by pointing at shared commonalities and symptoms.

Chapter IV. Conceptual Framework

Introduction

The present thesis, besides social theory, is grounded on the psychological theory of Self-Determination Theory (1985, 2017) to identify and classify several factors encountered by doctoral students throughout their journey. This chapter starts with an overview of the theoretical framework adopted along with justification in regard to such a choice. It is noteworthy that the usage of the theory under the present study is novelistic and unique in its way. As the thesis seeks to unveil the potential danger zones leading to total disengagement, it mainly investigates the dark side and not the driving forces. Finally, at the heart of SDT's intrinsic and extrinsic division, obstacle theory (Marguc et al., 2010) is discussed and integrated to further SDT's cause for the purpose of the research. Thus, creating a reversed-scaled SDT theory suited for the current study.

1. Self Determination Theory: A Brief Presentation

Originating from the work of Deci and Ryan (1985), SDT is a theory of motivation and personality that attempts to explain human behaviours to attain optimal functioning. The theory examines how biological, social, and cultural conditions contribute to the development or undermining of human thriving. These factors affect human psychological growth, engagement, and wellness (Deci and Ryan, 2017). Self-determination theory builds its theory and informs its classroom applications using standard empirical techniques. The theory, which has been forty years within the making, assumes that all students, regardless of their age, gender, socioeconomic status, nationality, or cultural background, possess inherent growth tendencies (e.g., intrinsic motivation, curiosity, psychological needs) that give a psychological feature foundation for their high-quality room engagement and positive faculty functioning (Reeve, 2012).

Self-determination theory represents one of the most successful theories in the educational field (Deci and Ryan, 2009, 2020). Furthermore, recent studies have demonstrated its prevalence and utility in regard to its assumptions in even higher forms of education such as the PhD context (Litalien et al., 2015; Beck, 2016). In other words, regardless of the educational level, SDT still accounts for the reasons behind students' success and failure in their doctoral studies.

A basic assumption in SDT theory is that people constantly evolve and inherently move towards psychological growth and therefore towards learning, mastery, and connection with others (Ryan and Deci, 2020). However, these human qualities are not automatically triggered and thus require some conditions to be completely activated. The three psychological needs that are considered

fundamentally responsible for human development are autonomy, competence, and relatedness (Deci and Ryan, 2017). According to both Ryan (2009) and Ryan and Deci (2020) only when these three needs are fulfilled and maintained will people feel more vivacity, self-motivation, and enhanced wellbeing. Contrariwise, the impediment of such elementary needs potentially leads to damaged self-motivation and weakened wellbeing or ill-being.

2. Basic Psychological Human Needs Theory: Autonomy, Competence and Relatedness

A critical tenet of SDT is that optimal functioning and growth are triggered when three psychological needs are fulfilled (Deci and Ryan, 2000; Sheldon and Filak, 2008). These “universal needs” are autonomy, competence, and relatedness (Deci and Ryan, 2000). Definitions and explanations are provided below along with the importance of having such needs at the doctoral level and what happens when they are compromised. In other words, as each of the needs promotes certain capacities and growth, once one/all of them is/are not promoted, it only impacts the individual growth in a negative way; leading to damaging effects as shall be discussed below. Finally, as PhD students are a unique population transitioning to the echelon of novice researchers, SDT was deemed most appropriate. SDT is particularly relevant because at the doctoral level, more autonomy, dependence, and self-efficacy are required from students and so the theory is particularly relevant at the doctoral level.

Autonomy refers to having the liberty to take proprietorship over one’s actions (Ryan and Deci, 2020; Deci and Ryan, 2017). Such psychological freedom and sense of decision-making are reinforced by experiences of internal relevance (value and interest) and undermined by external forms of control such as rewards or punishment (Ryan and Deci, 2020; Kumar and Kaur, 2019). Autonomy in doctoral research was found to be a focal element in students’ continuance of their programs, better satisfaction, and higher sense of competence (Mason, 2012; Overall et al., 2011). Mason (2012) researched the roles of psychological needs and student satisfaction on students’ motivation in doctoral programs. A total of 125 students responded to a survey on how autonomous, competent, satisfied and motivated they were. Results showed a positive correlation between motivation to continue and psychological needs. Moreover, autonomy and relatedness were related to satisfaction. Students having a sense of freedom demonstrate more motivation than those who do not have a sense of autonomy (Mason, 2012). As they hold more control over the tasks they value, they take more responsibility towards learning; thus, more enthusiasm is present in autonomous students (for a review see, Dickinson, 1995).

Competence denotes feelings of self-efficacy and mastering challenging tasks to further growth and development (Ryan and Deci, 2020; Deci and Ryan, 2017). Such need encompasses beliefs of success and the need to prove one's capacities (Deci and Ryan, 2000; Kumar and Kaul, 2019). Competence has been positively associated with the dissertation writing process (Faghihi et al., 1999) and better productivity (Hollingsworth and Fassinger, 2002). Lately, it has also been reported that stronger forms of motivation were held by doctoral students with a higher sense of competence (Mason, 2012). This appears to be axiomatic given the fact that any kind of motivation must yield competence; otherwise, people might likely feel helpless and amotivated.

Relatedness involves a sense of belongingness and connection (Ryan and Deci, 2020; Strayhorn, 2018). Because humans are inherently social beings, they require meaningful interaction, care, mutual respect and understanding (Ryan and Deci, 2020; Kumar and Kaur, 2019). Within the doctoral context, this might signal the sense of belongingness of students in relation to their academic community or their relationships with supervisors. Indeed, previous research has shown the prominence of having good relationships with supervisors that go beyond academic purposes (Lovitts, 2001; Overall et al., 2011). Students with more sense of relatedness with their supervisors are indeed more motivated (Mason, 2012), more productive (Paglis et al., 2006), progress better (Faghini et al., 1999) and less prone to attrition thinking (Bair and Haworth, 2004). The case is particularly more pronounced among international students seeking their place in the academic community and research world. The reason why it is more challenging for international students is the fact that they are double outsiders; they are new to the PhD and also the fact that they are from a different culture and educational system. Thus, in a way, they have to work more to integrate, adapt and more importantly, to succeed.

As previously mentioned, thwarting such basic needs leads to damaging both motivation and wellness (Ryan and Deci, 2020). In the doctoral context, the frustration of such needs is responsible for students' attrition. As demonstrated in a recent phenomenological study, Burns and Gillespie (2018) found that changes in feelings of autonomy and relatedness mostly drove PhD students to withdraw from their respective programs. The alteration in basic needs was most prevalent when participants moved from coursework to the dissertation stage. For Example, lack of autonomy for some was comprised in topic decisions and dissertation execution; while for others, too much freedom with little or almost no guidance or assistance negatively impacted their sense of autonomy; questioning their abilities and thus creating frustration and feelings of unsureness. As for the lack of relatedness, it was mostly due to a change of supervisor after establishing a foundational relationship.

Subsequently, demonstrating the prevalence of psychological needs to successful goal achievements and SDT's credibility in accounting for human behaviours in general and doctoral success in particular.

3. Reasons for Adopting SDT as one of Theoretical Frameworks

The adoption of SDT as a framework or a blueprint for the thesis was not made haphazardly, different reasons drove the choice of the theory. Mainly, it serves the aims of the research in the following ways:

- SDT identifies principles that might directly influence successful social practice by investigating how developmental proclivities and social environments combine to favour or hinder various types of human motivation and wellbeing across domains (Deci and Ryan, 2017). Therefore, the theory offers perspectives of gaining various contextual insights along with factors that can either facilitate or hinder the success of the intended goals; in this case, doctoral success.
- SDT defines the self predominantly in a phenomenological manner (Deci and Ryan, 2017); which aligns perfectly with the research method adopted in the present research. As one of its aims concerns the abroad experiences of international doctoral students. It will mainly involve a phenomenological study that is devoted to the study of individuals' experiences (Smith et al., 2022). Therefore, a phenomenological approach along with SDT as a theoretical lens serves appropriately the purpose of the thesis.
- SDT focuses on the experiences that underpin autonomous acts, such as volition and self-endorsement, rather than people's self-concepts, identities, or self-evaluations and assessments. Acting with a feeling of autonomy, on the other hand, necessitates integration, as full-volition experiences are marked by a lack of inner conflict and voluntary participation (Deci and Ryan, 2017). The description fits the PhD participants of the present study who are supposed to be autonomous learners transitioning from novice researchers to scholars (Hawlery, 2003).
- SDT merges perfectly with the literature content; in other words, most of the literature reviewed corroborates with SDT theory. For example, the lack of sense of belongingness reviewed falls under the relatedness concept of SDT. Reasons for pursuing a PhD, factors of attrition or even experiential features of international students fall into the dyadic paradigm of intrinsic and extrinsic factors.
- The Theory is concerned with how behaviour is organised as a consequence of conscious or unconscious causes or motives. These motives and justifications, which usually take the shape of wants, anxieties, reflective values, and aspirations, are sometimes obvious and sometimes rejected or

guarded. Therefore, the theory explicates the why of behaviours along with consideration of the relevant psychological concepts relevant to the present thesis.

- SDT research thus critically examines variables that promote vitality, motivation, social integration, and well-being, as well as those that lead to depletion, fragmentation, antisocial behaviour, and unhappiness, both inherent to individual development and within social contexts. Correspondingly, as the present research is interested in the dark side, it focuses on the possible experiences, events, or factors responsible for doctoral students' depletion of their inner or external motive for program completion.

- Among all the theories constructed on motivation, SDT is among the few that can integrate all of the theoretical frameworks in its paradigm. For instance, a type of achievement goal theory called the mastery approach is within the intrinsic motivation as it shares a lot of similarities such as the motive behind learning which is generally for its own sake or a thirst for knowledge. Also, proponents of such an approach are decision-makers and independents, and therefore, are autonomous learners. Performance-based approach lies within the external paradigm as it stresses more on the concrete and beneficial outcomes or motives. They both attach their success or failure to external attributives such as marks, teachers, parents, and peers.

- Deci and Ryan (2017) also highlighted that the factors that influence human thriving can alternatively contribute to depletion, fragmentation antisocial behaviours and unhappiness. In this sense, a miscalculation of such variables or a misuse of them could lead to demotivation (loss of motivation, unhappiness) and possibly alienation (antisocial behaviours). In fact, by considering relevant past literature, it could be advanced that hypothetically speaking, people with more internal incentives would be better copers in the face of demotivation and alienation as these kinds of obstacles call for a high sense of responsibility and determination.

4. Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation: The Dyadic Division

As mentioned, one of the most accomplished paradigms in motivational studies is the dyadic division known as intrinsic/extrinsic motivation. Dörnyei (1998, p.121), an imminent psycholinguist specialised in second/foreign language motivation, denotes “*one of the most general and well-known distinctions in motivation theories is that of intrinsic versus extrinsic motivation*”. Thus, the theory is well-recognised in the social science domain and its division is not unknown to scholars and aspired researchers. The following subsection dives into the taxonomy of motivation and its subtypes.

Students are motivated to learn for various reasons such as studying to get a good mark, to be praised by either teacher or parents, to be acknowledged, to appear intelligent, to get a reward, to master a language or even for intellectual reasons such as to sharpen or boost knowledge. All these academically existing reasons and so many others fall under the dyadic paradigm of self-determination theory that is intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. It is worth noting, however, that SDT does not include only positive reasons of motivation, but also possible negative reasons for students' loss of motivation or demotivation (Deci and Ryan, 2000, 2017).

Figure 1: Self Determination Theory (adapted from Cook and Artino, 2016, p.1010).

4.1. Intrinsic Inclination

Ryan and Deci (2000, p.55) define intrinsic motivation as “*doing something because it is inherently interesting or enjoyable*”. Meaning that the action taken toward a certain goal is due to the internal value attributed to it. Examples are learning for fun, curiosity, inner satisfaction, and personal development. Such spontaneous tendencies “*seek out novelty and challenges, to extend and exercise one’s capacity, to explore, and to learn*” (Ryan and Deci, 2000, p.70). In other words, the behaviour taken is independent from any physiological reward and activated only when the target actions sustain people’s curiosity such as challenges or learning new things. SDT research confirmed that satisfaction associated with competence and autonomy is what makes intrinsic motivation mostly enjoyable (Ryan and Moller, 2017; Deci and Ryan, 2017; Ryan and Deci, 2020). Opportunities to test one’s knowledge

and capacities and take full charge of one's actions along with feeling capable and free are the major contentment in intrinsic motivation.

As such, intrinsic forms of incentive were found to have numerous advantages. Studies have shown that intrinsic motivation fosters the ability to cope with unpredictable situations or challenging tasks; that is to say, adaptive strategies (Deci and Ryan, 2017). It has also been found to be an essential determinant in academic achievement (Froiland and Worrell, 2016). Moreover, intrinsic motivation is considered to be the dominant factor in pursuing a PhD (Lindholm, 2004, Templeton, 2016) and one of the reasons behind timely thesis completion (Lindsay, 2015). Additionally, internally motivated people display higher academic performance, more enjoyment of learning and overall experience grander psychological wellbeing (Goodman et al., 2011; Deci and Ryan, 2017). Thus, approving Deci and Ryan's (2000) claim on the superiority of internal motivation in providing advanced levels of commitment; suggesting higher levels of problem-solving, creativity and potential elevated outcomes. Finally, internal tendencies are more developed within adults as they take initiatives, are more independent and possess the internal drive to learn as they age (Lee and Pang, 2014). Subsequently, according to the literature, higher forms of learning and success in doctoral studies are associated with internal motivation where students are mainly grown individuals.

Besides the educational level, intrinsic motivation was subject to investigation from a neuroscientific perspective. The use of neuroscience to examine intrinsic motivational processes has been adopted up until recently (Ryan and Di Domenico, 2016; Di Domenico and Ryan, 2017). Intrinsic motivation is found to activate the rewards area of the brain; more specifically the neurotransmitter or messenger substance known as dopamine (Baik, 2013; Betsy, 2017; Di Domenico and Ryan, 2017; Freed, 2022). Dopamine is a neurotransmitter that helps in managing the brain's reward and pleasure centres along with motivational and emotional reactions (Baik, 2013; Betsy, 2017); it is particularly known as 'the happy hormone' (Medical University of Vienna, 2016). Indeed, neuroimaging studies pinpointed that students who are internally motivated are subverted by neural areas related to dopaminergic systems (for a review, see Di Domenico and Ryan, 2017). Dopamine is also responsible for feelings of concentration, alertness, and enthusiasm (Pietrangelo, 2019). Thus, explaining why internal motivation was found more beneficial to students; particularly to doctoral students who frequently experience a great deal of stress, anxiety, and depression in their journey (Kernan et al., 2011; Levecque et al., 2017).

According to the literature, internal motivation not only produces external beneficial results but also releases chemical substances that act as both rewards and counteragents against mental health

issues such as anxiety, depression, and somatic disorders. Nevertheless, the limited literature on doctoral motivation focused on the helping factors; leaving potential barriers to demotivation almost undiscovered. Thus, the present study is involved with what kind of internal barriers are met within the PhD route and which are complex and difficult to drive to the dark side.

4.2. External Inclination

Extrinsic motivation is defined as “*doing something because it leads to a separable outcome*” (Deci and Ryan, 2000, p.55). Here the value attributed is directed to something gained which has concrete or physiological properties such as money, praising or simply avoiding punishment. Under such type, driving forces and rewards for commitments are ‘extrinsic to the activity’ (Ryan and Moller, 2017) and therefore actions are carried out for all that is not related to inherent pleasure (Ryan and Deci, 2020). The reason for the existence of extrinsic motivation is discussed by Deci and Ryan (2017) arguing:

Yet socialized life is not all fun and games. As group animals, we engage in many behaviors that may not be intrinsically motivated, including chores, work, duties, rituals, and exercising self-restraint. We often adopt such practices because socializing agents expect, promote, laud, or even compel them. (p.179)

Simply put, the action is not necessarily intrinsically interesting; however, it is deemed useful as it procures instrumental outcomes. For instance, getting a doctorate to secure a well-paid job. As demonstrated in Lovitts’ (2001) research, she identified seven types of motivation contributing to thesis completion, one of which boosted students to finish their dissertation in the limited time frame was the increased earned income in future employment. Another extrinsic incentive in the doctoral context is family. In an auto-ethnography, Templeton (2016) found that one of the reasons to enrol for a PhD was having a family that has academia as a lifestyle. Thus, external driving forces are somewhat different and detached from the individual; nevertheless, they drive to the same outcome and serve as a means to an end.

Unlike intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation is a relatively differentiated concept. Indeed, extrinsic motivation has its mini theory to account for different variants of external motives called Organismic Integration Theory. The latter divides the external type of motivation into four levels/stages: *external regulation*, *interjected regulation*, *identified regulation* and *integrated regulation*. Self-determination theory is the sole theory providing such classification of extrinsic variables in order to better explain the contingencies of motivation (Deci and Ryan, 2017; Reeve, 2012). OIT asserts that pupils are naturally and voluntarily motivated to internalise parts of their social environment and to incorporate some of these beliefs and behaviours as learned motivation (Reeve,

2012). Internalization may be thought of as a spectrum, ranging from most regulated (least autonomous) to maximum autonomous and highly integrated at the opposite end (Ryan and Connell, 1989; Ryan and Deci, 2000; Ryan and Moller, 2017).

5. Critics Towards SDT

- Primal criticism is the paradigm is way too simplistic to describe human behaviours that are complex and unpredictable beings.

- The distinction between extrinsic and intrinsic motivation makes sense. This distinction, on the other hand, should not be viewed as an "either-or" choice. To summarise, an individual can be intrinsically motivated in one domain of knowledge, such as psychiatry, and extrinsically motivated in another domain of knowledge, such as astronomy. It assumes that one individual must possess one type whereas the two could be found in one individual; the same could be applied to demotivation.

- The model was not extensively applied either qualitatively or in the doctoral context. The empirical history of SDT dates back 40 years ago; however, in this field, limited endeavours conducting qualitative research were traced and only recently it has been adopted to the postgraduate level (Templeton, 2016; Kumar and Kaur, 2019). The present thesis represents one of the very few studies conducted at the doctoral level using such organismic theory.

- No scale inside the dyadic paradigm was ever produced; as individuals act differently to similar situations or events (Dweck, 1999), students will perceive the obstacle according to their personal constructs, background, and intelligence. Therefore, a new theory shall be presented and integrated inside the dualistic forms of motivation to further its complexity; creating new dimensions inside of it to classify further identified barriers.

6. Obstacle Theory

The reason for integrating another theory inside a well-established theory that is SDT is the fact that it lacks scale in terms of motivating/demotivating forces. In the context of this research, a multitude of obstacles are met and reviewed in previous studies. However, there is a paucity among which of the myriad of obstacles doctoral students meet are high in their level of surmountability/difficulty that it might impair people's cognitive and emotional wellbeing, hinder all progress, and ultimately feel disengaged and demotivated. The remainder of this chapter talks about the different types of obstacles according to Marguc et al. (2010) and how they serve the study in terms of the dark side and scalability of potential barriers.

People frequently encounter difficulties or impediments when developing knowledge. Obstacles are everything that obstructs, hinders, or impedes a single human in everyday life, and they

come and go, creating barriers for those who meet them. Learning barriers are fundamentally a phenomenon that manifests itself in many forms of behaviour. The presence of some barriers will generally reveal itself in elements of motoric, cognitive, and emotional behaviour long into the process and learning objectives are attained (Marguc et al., 2010).

Rather than assuming that all obstacles should have the same effects, Marguc et al. (2010) propose to differentiate between two types of obstacles. *Surmountable obstacles* are considered to slow progress or achievement of a goal but do not obstruct progress or accomplishment fully and *insurmountable obstacles* halt completely the development of task completion. The former is inhibiting factors that cause minor setbacks whereas the latter are obstructing factors that completely disprove goal achievement. The present study uses the theory to identify which of the possible obstructing forces are insurmountable enough to drive to a total halt of engagement, in other words, demotivation.

Figure 2: Obstacle Theory by Marguc et al. (2010).

The perception of a barrier as surmountable or insurmountable can affect not only the actual trajectory of an activity or goal pursuit, but also the emotional, motivational, and cognitive processes that accompany these trajectories (for a review, see Marguc et al., 2010). The capacity to overcome a challenge is in the mind of the beholder; as individuals react differently to similar situations (Dweck, 1999). Consequently, the present thesis aims to ask for individualistic responses from participants regarding their potential insurmountable factors leading to demotivation. The unique contribution of this study lies within its difference from the phenomenon of attrition. The present study holds the premise that demotivation is a state/phase prior to attrition. Additionally, the phenomenon of demotivation could be solved while students are still enrolled in the doctoral program whereas attrition denotes a total cancellation of studies. However, if not dealt with, demotivation might worsen and lead to the decision to withdraw from studies; thus, making the importance of the present study more significant than ever.

6.1. The Merged Theoretical Frameworks

Figure 3: Reversed Scaled SDT.

With this new framework, factors generated go through two sets of classifications: type of obstacle and difficulty of the latter. The first will be used through SDT lenses to determine whether the hindering factors emerge from within or outside of the individual. In other words, whether the obstacles faced by international doctoral students are physical or nonphysical; extrinsic or intrinsic. The second level weighs the dangerousness of the identified factor by establishing whether it challenges the individual’s goals (thesis completion) or stops progress completely. Depending on individuals’ perceptions, the framework serves as a toolbox to allow better clarity in terms of potential danger zones of the postgraduate route. Therefore, the new model distinguishes clearly between negative but stimulating events and completely blocking events. Not only is the lifeworld of

participants detailed and labelled, but also through their narrative of experiential barriers regarding the dark side phenomena will be classified accordingly.

Summary

The chapter presented a novelistic way of interpreting self-determination theory along with reasons underlying the choice of the theory. The present study utilised the theory in a relatively under-documented area; that is to say, doctoral level. After defining relevant concepts to the study, the thesis goes on by identifying some of its limitations. One major limitation concerns a lack of scale inside the well-known division called intrinsic/extrinsic motivators. After that, Obstacle theory was presented and integrated inside the organismic theory in order to best serve the purpose of the present study; it helps to identify and classify complete blockers of PhD progression to mild blockers according to international doctoral students' perceptions.

Chapter V. Finding the Answers: Research Methodology

Introduction

The current research problem raised needs a specific research plan. Therefore, this chapter justifies the research design and methodological rationale for addressing my research questions. Before tackling the gathering data instrument utilised along with the type of participants, this chapter starts with the ontological and epistemological considerations regarding how truth is perceived and attained. After clarifying such perceptions of reality, the paradigm adopted will be presented and justified, which gives rise to the data-gathering tool selected. It is worth mentioning that all these considerations serve the purpose of answering the research questions advanced. Inevitably, concluding that demotivation in doctoral studies is poorly investigated despite their state and importance in the echelon of the academic community has ultimately led me to embark on this particular research study.

1. Ontological and Epistemological Underpinnings

Grix (2001) defines ontology as “*the image of social reality upon which a theory is based*”. It concerns “*the claims and assumptions that are made about the nature of social reality*” (p. 26). In short, it is about what we believe constitutes social reality. The ontological stance advocated in this research is a constructionist one, which states that “*social phenomena and their meanings are continually being accomplished by social actors. It implies that social phenomena and categories are not only produced through social interaction but that they are in a constant state of revision*” (Bryman, 2016, p.29). Meaning that the phenomenon and its signification cannot be separated from its social actors, in other words, the reality cannot be decontextualized. It is an interactive process that occurs between the researcher and the participants of the research since they are both responsible for the knowledge construction as this latter is self-defined.

After setting up the ontological lens, this would automatically give rise to the epistemological choice adopted. Epistemology concerns the practical side of knowledge. Thomas (2017, p.123) defines epistemology as “*the study of our knowledge of the world. How do we know about the world that we have defined ontologically*”. Put simply, epistemology is a roadmap or strategy adopted to gain the knowledge assumed. It focuses on the ‘knowledge-gathering process’ (Grix, 2001, 2018). As the ontological standpoint I am adopting views reality as socially constructed, the practical application of such an approach is the interpretive epistemological stance which “*predicated upon the view that a strategy is required that respects the differences between people and the objects of natural sciences and therefore require the social scientist to grasp the subjective meaning of social action*” (Bryman,

2012, p.30). The characteristic of such a subjective approach is that it views the world as a much more personally based and humanly crafted kind of knowledge (Cohen et al., 2017). Here, the particularity of such an epistemological approach lies in the fact that the researcher and the object of the study are interlinked and connected so that the actual truth is constructed as the investigation takes place (Guba and Lincoln, 1994).

2. Rejection of the Positivist Approach

As I am adopting a focused lens that emphasises more on in-depth analysis of words rather than enumeration or frequency, and on individuals as entities rather than numbers; inevitably, this present study rejects the positivist approach as it does not serve the purpose of this research. Moreover, considering the research questions along with the current gap in the field, adopting an approach based on positivism and the application of quantitative methods would not suit the purpose of this study. Ontologically speaking, positivism would require me to believe in a pre-existing objective reality that would push me to use an objective epistemology without giving much importance to the social side of the phenomenon as perceived by its individuals; which contrasts one of the aims of the present research targeting PhD experiences as lived by its population. Thus, to gather rich, in-depth accounts of reality, the constructivist approach appears to be the most fitting choice for exploring and filling the current niche of demotivation at the international doctoral level.

Furthermore, the positivist approach in the educational context has been widely criticised (Cohen et al., 2017). The positivist approach, by nature, focuses more on the measurement of a particular phenomenon through quantifiable measures rather than trying to understand the uniqueness of individuals' experiences and stories. Thus, such a mechanistic approach to reality in the social world not only undermines the validity of the truth collected; as it lacks its necessary component, but also excludes notions of freedom, choice, individuality, and moral responsibility (Cohen et al., 2017) rendering the world more like a machine rather than treating it as a living organism and dehumanizes it. As pinpointed by Guba and Lincoln (1994, p. 106) "*human behavior, unlike that of physical objects, cannot be understood without reference to the meanings and purposes attached by human actors to their activities*". Meaning that, the phenomenon cannot be detached from its social aspect, otherwise, the meaning will be lost. The latter speaks relatively of the educational context as it is predominantly a social activity and research on such contexts involves human components to unravel the true signification of the phenomenon.

Moreover, Max Weber rejected positivism in sociological studies and asserted that the "*ultimate unit of social analysis remained the concrete acting person*" (Coser, 1971, p.218). Furthermore, Weber (1958) added:

Interpretive sociology considers the individual and his action as the basic unit, as its 'atom', - if the disputable comparison for once may be permitted. In this approach, the individual is also the upper limit and the sole carrier of meaningful conduct ... In general, for sociology, such concepts as 'state', 'association', 'feudalism' and the like designate certain categories of human interaction. Hence it is the task of sociology to reduce these concepts to 'understandable' action, that is, without exception, to the actions of participating individual men (p.55).

Therefore, the social scientist's main interest lies in unravelling the realities and qualities as ascribed by human actors. The human aspect is not one part in observing or discovering the truth but is the sole agent in sociological events since it mainly concerns the social actors and how they see, perceive, and make sense of the subject in question. These arguments among others constitute some of the reasons regarding the rejection of the positivist approach in the educational context in general and the present topic in particular.

Finally, since my main focus is unravelling some truths as perceived by its individuals, it focuses less on establishing a single, objective and generalisable reality but more on transferrable ones. This adopted approach, unlike the positivist one, does not strip consideration of context and unique experiences of individuals. It includes both meaning and its purpose as it is viewed by its social constituents. Some of the generalisability problems are that although they are mathematically accurate, they have no applicability in the individual case (Guba and Lincoln, 1994). The issue is that social science is different from natural science as it studies human beings and their actions. These characteristics, unlike natural phenomena, are unpredictable and idiosyncratic behaviour. As Dweck (2006) pinpointed people act differently in similar situations, people are unique and interpret events happening to them depending on a set of personal, cultural, and contextual criteria. The goal behind such an approach is not to create an overall numerical truth but rather to understand and interpret the phenomenon as it is consciously lived by its population in its naturalistic context without constraints or limitations. Such reasoning paves a clear way for qualitative measures as it perfectly aligns with the goal of this research of exploring and gaining a deep understating form its participants in its social context.

3. Research Paradigm

Selecting a philosophical stance triggers a succession of other subtypes of research. The step prior to tackling the methodological underpinnings is called a paradigm. It is an established academic approach; a framework that encompasses the methodologies and modes of thinking and working within a particular scientific field (Kuhn, 1970). In more simplistic terms, it is a worldview of a given phenomenon; an 'accepted model or pattern' (Kuhn, 1962, p. 23). The purpose of paradigms is to inform and guide the research project using a set of principles. Logically, advocating the constructionist's view of knowledge gives rise to a specific paradigm. The latter is known as the

interpretive paradigm (Cohen et al., 2017) also known as the ‘understanding paradigm’ (Lather, 2004). The interpretive paradigm comprises the constructionist ontology and interpretivist epistemology. This approach was often attributed to the sociologist Weber and his concept of ‘verstehen’ (Weber, 1949; Tucker, 1965) which means “*understanding something in context*” (Holloway, 1997, p.2).

Therefore, the interpretive paradigm is mainly using qualitative aspects of research; which focuses on “*a small number of naturally occurring cases in detail*” (Hammersley, 2012, p.12). In other words, the number of participants is quite small unlike quantitative measures; however, the detailed investigation allowed by the qualitative approach would enable the researcher to provide what is known as a “thick description” (Geertz, 1973). Simply put, an exhaustive account of the phenomenon under study as voiced by the participants themselves. Unlike quantitative paradigms that seek the gathering of facts in numerical data, qualitative data emphasises establishing realities that are context-specific (Njie and Asimiran, 2014, Ngozwana, 2018). It uses more verbal modes of inquiry that are less structured based on detailed subjective experiences which aim at relatability (Denzin et al., 2011) rather than statistical generalisable results. Because I am interested in an in-depth demotivation study due to its lack of empirical literature on doctoral studies, I have decided to adopt a qualitative approach that focuses more on delving into details and exploring how the phenomenon is viewed, constructed, and faced by doctoral students. Allowing them to voice and express their version of reality the way they see it in their own words and in as much details as they want. This qualitative approach may promote human rights of freedom of expression more so than purely quantitative/statistical might. Thus, subjectivity is fully embraced in the present research as social research bias or subjectivity is almost impossible to avoid. Subjectivity “*recognizes knowledge as value laden. Unaffected and universal knowledge of an external reality is not possible beyond individual reflections and interpretations*” (Levers, 2013, p.3). Simply put, subjectivity allows one to access the full scope of reality as it is perceived by its primary experienced population. Indeed, Schwartz-Shea and Yanow (2012, p.98) declare “*to presume that humans cannot be aware of their “biases” is to reject human consciousness the possibility of self-awareness and reflexivity and human capacity for learning*”. In other words, subjectivity, in some cases, is not a hindrance to understanding but may be a necessity to fully extract the meaning of a phenomenon.

This paradigm provides a solid framework for my current study, which aims to voice the personal experiences of my participants, the processes they engage in, and their reflections, with an ontology of multiple, socially constructed realities, an epistemology based on an interactive link between researcher and participants, explicit values and clear goals, and a primarily qualitative methodology (Bloomberg and Volpe, 2018).

4. Qualitative Methodology

Due to the heavily under-researched area of demotivation at the doctoral level, the qualitative methodology is the most suitable approach to tackle such a problem. Qualitative research is usually adopted because a problem needs to be explored (Creswell and Poth, 2016). Because demotivation is a complex and uncharted variable in relation to doctoral studies and the study population, a detailed understanding of the issue is needed and one way to do so is by conducting qualitative research. The latter is appropriate because it gathers rich data and allows an in-depth investigation that could yield extensive data on a topic that is currently scarce in the literature.

Van Maanen (1979) defines qualitative research as “*an umbrella term to cover an array of interpretive techniques that can describe, decode, translate, and otherwise come to terms with the meaning, not the frequency, of certain more or less naturally occurring phenomena in the social world*” (p. 520). A more recent definition is offered by Denzin and Lincoln (2011) stating:

Qualitative research is a situated activity that locates the observer in the world. Qualitative research consists of a set of interpretive, material practices that make the world visible. These practices transform the world. They turn the world into a series of representations, including field notes, interviews, conversations, photographs, recordings, and memos to the self. At this level, qualitative research involves an interpretive, naturalistic approach to the world. This means that qualitative researchers study things in their natural setting, attempting to make sense of, or interpret, phenomena in terms of the meanings people bring to them (p.43)

Simply put, qualitative research is the study of how people interpret their experiences, construct their worlds, make sense of those experiences, and express them through their verbal descriptions. By placing more emphasis on the meaning-making processes carried out by research participants rather than their products. Qualitative research takes a typical research approach that does not attempt to predict what might happen to the research future but instead tries to understand the nature of a context, what it means for participants to be in this context, what their life looks like, what the world looks like in this context (Merriam and Tisdell, 2015; Cohen et al., 2017). Thus, collecting people’s interpretation in their natural habitat. All of these are consistent with the goal of my research to explore the PhD experiences of Algerian postgraduate students in the UK from their perspective and their own subjective experiences.

Since the phenomenological research technique is specifically developed to assist researchers in understanding participants' unique and shared experiences, it was determined that this approach was the best fit for answering the research problem within this research (Padilla-Díaz, 2015).

4.1. Phenomenology

Phenomenology is a method that embodies qualitative measures and Husserl's (1970) school of philosophy in the twentieth century (Merriam and Tisdell, 2015). The emphasis in phenomenology is

on the lived experience itself and how the latter is transformed into consciousness (Burch, 1990; Merriam and Tisdell, 2015 van Manen, 2017). van Manen (2014, p.28) explicates: “*Phenomenology is the way of access to the world as we experience it prereflectively. Prereflective experience is the ordinary experience that we live in and that we live through for most, if not all, of our day-to-day existence*”. Thus, phenomenology is the scientific study of people's conscious experiences of their daily lives; in other words, their “*everyday life and social action*” (Schram, 2003, p.71) are brought to light and studied meticulously. All of which aligns with a primary definition of phenomenology offered by Heidegger (1962, p.51) which entails “*to bring something to the light of the day, to put in light*”. In other words, the phenomenon is concealed and hardly accessible by classical means that requires an in-depth methodology that sheds light on it and the most appropriate way of doing so is by conducting phenomenology. As the present study investigates the dark side of doing postgraduate research, it aims to enlighten a side of inquiry poorly investigated; especially in terms of demotivation within an underrepresented sample of the international population; in other words, Algerian postgraduates in the UK.

Phenomenology was adopted in this study because it permits to approach the phenomenon “... *from a fresh perspective, as if viewed for the first time, through the eyes of the participants who have direct, immediate experience with it*” (Hays and Singh, 2011, p.50). This strategy helped achieve the aim of gathering detailed, first-hand information about the participants' experiences, while also recognizing their contributions as experts. However, the phenomenologist must interview only the participants who have lived the experience of interest (van Manen, 2017). Consider the loss of a loved one for instance. Participants who have experienced sorrow or grief would be interviewed by phenomenologists about their awareness of their grief, how their sadness connects with their lifeworld, and what universal features can be identified about grief (Hays and Singh, 2011). Therefore, meticulous detection and selection of relevant participants must take place before tackling the interview process which will be discussed further in its own section.

Phenomenology is not elaborated for objectivist modes of operating; it rather keeps a very open mindset on how things might happen with a focal emphasis on the narratives of lived experiences of participants. As clearly presented by van Manen (1997):

From a phenomenological point of view, we are less interested in the factual status of particular instances: whether something happened, how often it tends to happen, or how the occurrence of an experience is related to the prevalence of other conditions or events. For example, phenomenology does not ask “how do these children learn this particular material?” but it asks, “What is the nature or essence of the experience of learning (so that I now better understand what this particular learning experience is like for these children)?” (p.10)

Thus, phenomenology essentially allows the researcher to dive in-depth and explore areas that quantitative measures cannot. The ‘essence’ (Husserl, 1970) of any lived experience is a rich unrestricted investigation allowing the exploration of the multiple layers within the same phenomenon. In other words, in socially bound elements of inquiry, phenomenology aims at providing the correct way of investigation.

When addressing qualitative techniques, two consequences of the phenomenological perspective are frequently misunderstood. The first implication is that it is crucial to understand what individuals go through and how they interpret their surroundings. The focus of the phenomenological investigation is on this subject; that is to say, lived experiences. The second point to consider is one of the method. Only by actually experiencing the phenomena for ourselves can we truly understand what another person is going through. As a result, participant observation and in-depth interviews become increasingly important (Patton, 2015). As an international Algerian PhD student myself studying at the same study level as my participants who are also international Algerian PhD students; I am highly sensitive and understanding of the context my participants are in and what might be appropriate for them to be asked or not. Thus, making me the best candidate for carrying out this research. Overall, in both scenarios, the phenomenological findings are successful when “*the essence or nature of an experience has been adequately described in language if the description reawakens or shows us the lived quality and significance of the experience in a fuller and deeper manner*” (van Manen, 1997, p.10).

The areas of emphasis in phenomenological studies include emotions (grief, anger, jealousy, love, betrayal etc), a culture, an organisation, or a program (Hays and Singh, 2011; Patton, 2015; Merriam and Tisdell, 2015). A PhD is a program established to prepare students to become researchers; which has been reported to be an emotional roller coaster (Cushieri, 2021). As such, the phenomenological approach was deemed the most appropriate to investigate and depict the essence of the lived experiences of international PhD students regarding their doctoral experience abroad. Finally, the usefulness of phenomenology is twofold; not only does it permit the participants to open up about their experience freely, but also the resulting experience is valuable for therapists, teachers, health personnel and policymakers (Creswell and Poth, 2016).

4.2. Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis

IPA is a relatively new and quickly expanding method of qualitative research. First articulated in the UK in the 1990s by Smith’s (1996) seminal work; its origins and best-known applications are in psychology, but it is rapidly being adopted by people working in related fields in the human, social, and health sciences (Smith et al., 2022; Eatough and Smith, 2017) as previously reviewed. IPA is one

of several phenomenological methods, all of which differ in various ways in terms of theoretical emphasis and methodological commitments, but all agree on the need for an experience viewpoint for the field (Eatough and Smith, 2017).

IPA is a qualitative research technique dedicated to investigating how people make meaning/sense of important life events. It is mainly “*concerned with the detailed examination of personal lived experiences*” (Eatough and Smith, 2017, p.1). IPA is phenomenological in the sense that it seeks to understand experience on its own terms (Smith et al., 2009); in other terms, it investigates the phenomenon as lived by its participants. This particular study follows the approach of philosopher Edmund Husserl, who notably advised phenomenologists to "go back to the things themselves" rather than seeking to categorise experience into predetermined or too abstract categories. IPA was developed as a unique research methodology in response to dissatisfaction with the overemphasis placed on quantitative approaches in psychological research (Smith, 1996).

IPA is concerned with a thorough analysis of details, first offering a clear in-depth description of each instance and then looking for patterns of convergence and divergence across cases (Eatough and Smith, 2017; Smith et al., 2009). The use of IPA as a methodology is highly beneficial for investigating issues that are complicated, confusing, and emotionally laden (Smith and Osborn, 2015). As previously reviewed in the background and literature chapter, the PhD in itself is a very complex and challenging endeavour. Additionally, previous literature has noted a significant psychological distress and dropout rate in doctoral students compared to other levels (Levecque et al., 2017; Kernan et al., 2011; Lovitts, 2001). Furthermore, the hardships are sometimes intensified among social science students in general and international students in specific (Chiang, 2003; Sherry et al., 2010). Thus, adopting IPA appears as a suitable choice to investigate clearly such a complex subject as it aims to meticulously voice the participants’ stories and make sense of their narratives. The latter is one of the basic human rights attributed to participants when undertaking research as they should be treated with care, respect and consideration, vocalise their lifeworlds and report it as faithfully as possible (BPS, 2021; BERA, 2018).

5. Population of Interest

The population this study is interested in are the Algerian postgraduates in the UK. These participants have benefited from a fully funded scholarship after majoring in their respective Algerian universities in social sciences. They were selected through a contest arranged by the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research. The first cohort in the UK started the academic year of 2014/15. The total number of Algerian PhD students who are granted a fully funded scholarship across UK Universities is five hundred (from 2014 to 2018). The rationale behind such a choice is to

contribute to the international literature by adding the Algerian population to it as it appears pretty scarce in comparison to Asian, Australian or American (HESA, 2021). Thus, tackling the novelistic topic through an unprecedented study population through IPA might emerge new insights valuable for policy implementation and knowledge contribution.

5.1. Deriving a Sample Population

The sample size in IPA studies is relatively small in numbers (Smith et al., 2009; Smith and Osborn, 2015; Eatough and Smith, 2017). As the focus is on the ‘micro-level’ of people’s accounts (Smith and Osburn, 2015, p. 42), the emphasis is primarily stressed on quality, rather than quantity. IPA treats each case individually and meticulously before moving to the next. As Smith et al. (2022, p.46) assert “*the issue is quality, not quantity, and given the complexity of most human phenomena, IPA studies usually benefit from a concentrated focus on a small number of cases*”. Therefore, IPA research does not consider that a higher number necessarily means better or more correct. The dedication to describing the richness and unpredictability of human experience while also illustrating what similar experiences across participants can generate a conflict, although a positive one, that stimulates innovative thinking about how to preserve both perspectives (Eatough and Smith, 2017). Thus, a rich IPA study depends on the researcher’s abilities and engagement with the investigation and the sample chosen to take part in the inquiry.

The sampling strategy adopted is purposive as it permits to optimise the chances of getting the best and most suitable participants who are willing to participate and competent in their storytelling. As the sample size is relatively small, the study has to possess participants who are the gatekeepers of information-rich and insightful perspectives of the phenomena to allow its illumination (Smith et al., 2009; Rapley, 2014; Patton, 2015). The purposive sampling method “*also called judgment sampling, is the deliberate choice of a participant due to the qualities the participant possesses. It is a nonrandom technique that does not need underlying theories or a set number of participants.*” (Etikan et al., 2016, p.2). Data gathering is crucial for research, and in qualitative studies, a careful selection of respondents is detrimental to research richness and contribution. Etikan et al. (2016, p.2) further add that the selection criteria involve “*identification and selection of individuals or groups of individuals that are proficient and well-informed with a phenomenon of interest*”. Contrary to random sampling which incorporates different criteria such as age and culture but might not generate sufficient and rich answers, purposive sampling filtrates unnecessary criteria and puts an emphasis on potential participants knowledgeable about the phenomenon of interest. The selected participants can be described as a theoretical sample, one chosen as they typify the characteristics sought/judged relevant to this study.

Participants were accessed via a personal selection of people known to have faced demotivation through personal chats online and face-to-face. They were colleagues with whom I started networking after we met in Canterbury, upon normal chats, some were interested in the topic and offered to participate. Moreover, an email was sent to the representative of Algerian postgraduates in the UK (APS-UK) who shared the email with the community as well as the Algerian embassy in the UK to further the distribution/diffusion of the participant recruitment (Appendix 4). Finally, snowball sampling was utilised when a participant (Amel) left the interview due to health-related issues and offered a replacement (Zineb). Snowball sampling permits researchers to identify informants that would then direct them to potential participants, also known as ‘chain-referral method’ (Cohen et al., 2017). Concerning the consent towards the study, the participants were sent both the interview schedule and the consent form before the commencement of the study. Finally, no impact on the sample was noticed as the study, due to its topic, specifically targets people who have faced and lived such experiences (information-rich, gatekeepers). Thus, the selection criteria are justified by the nature of the phenomenon of enquiry and hence serve its purpose.

However, it is noteworthy that purposive sampling is not without its areas of contestation. First, the sampling purposefully chosen can highly be subject to researcher bias (Cohen et al., 2017). Especially when compared to random sampling that counters such biases. Nevertheless, the subjective component of purposive sampling is only inconvenient when the latter is not reinforced with purpose and clear elaboration (Rai and Thapa, 2015). As the present research utilises IPA as its main methodology, it embraces its philosophical and theoretical assumptions. Smith et al. (2009) highlight that researchers conducting IPA should recruit a homogenous sample who are in a way experts in their experiential endeavours and are enabled to explicitly articulate and reflect their lifeworld and experience of the phenomenon. Thus, the biased nature of the sampling procedure is justified by the particularity needed in the study participants allowing for the elicitation of data needed to answer the research questions.

Another area of contestation reported in relation to purposive sampling is the question of representativeness (Rai and Thapa, 2015). The subjective quality of unit selection can become difficult to defend in terms of generalisability. Nonetheless, as this research is qualitative, the aim is not to generate generalisable data, but rather what is termed as ‘theoretical transferability’ (Smith et al., 2009, p. 51). By generating a thorough, unconcealed and contextual examination of the participant’s individual experience, the reader relates the IPA inquiry to their personal and professional experience and the previous data reported in the literature (Smith et al., 2022). Therefore, the purpose of the present research is to generate a study sufficiently transferrable/relatable to similar contexts. Similarly,

Maxwell (1992, p.290) talks about psychological/mental resonance or ‘internal generalisability’ as a type of generalisation as the obtained findings are valid/resonating with the community facing such experiential features.

Thus, the number advocated and utilised in this research is around ten participants. However, to maximize the chances of having a fairly homogenous and appropriate group of individuals for the study, some criteria are taken into consideration to identify those who would meet the criteria to participate. All recruited participants must find the research questions meaningful and subsequently be ‘a gatekeeper’ of the collected knowledge (Smith et al., 2009). Here are the characteristics following:

- Participants must have at least been enrolled for one year in their respective doctoral programs. This criterion is to ensure that the participants have accumulated a wide range of experience to reflect upon and share.
- Participants should have experienced some obstacles and stopping moments that would have hampered their engagement and progression to thesis completion. This criterion was established to ensure that the participants incorporated would have lived the phenomenon of interest (Smith et al., 2009; Roulston, 2010; van Manen, 2014; Padilla-Díaz, 2015). This criterion can be fulfilled due to the nature of the PhD as elaborated in the literature, and the current exceptional side effects of the pandemic.
- Participants must be interested in participating and willing to share their detailed stories and experiences in relation to every expected and unexpected negative instance that befell them during their doctoral route. This was to ensure the students that they had a strong desire to take part in the research project. This shall be fulfilled by making a preselection in the recruitment by filtering and including only the participants who present a genuine interest and a desire to participate.

6. Data Collection Method

The most frequent method adopted under IPA is the semi-structured interview (Smith et al., 2022; Padilla-Díaz, 2015); which the present study utilises. Defined as a “*conversation with a purpose*” (Smith et al., 2009, p. 57), the phenomenological interview aims to:

...generate detailed and in-depth descriptions of human experiences. Thus, questions that generate detailed information concerning these experiences as well as the participant’s responses to the phenomenon of investigation are crucial. Since researchers want to understand the participants’ feelings, perceptions and understandings, open questions are particularly useful in providing a format for interviewees to answer in their own words (p.16).

Thus, to elicit participants’ stories, anecdotes and experiences, open-ended questions are the most appropriate types of questions. The reasons for adopting semi-structured interviews are threefold; first,

it promotes the idiographic element aimed in this study. Idiography is the focus on the particular and commitment to a thorough detailed analysis of the text (Shinebourne, 2011; Smith et al., 2009). Second, the semi-structured interview not only permits to tackle the most relevant questions of the present study but also allows them to speak freely and dive into interesting and unexpected areas narrated by the participants (Smith et al., 2022). Finally, the semi-structured interview offers a scaffold for the researcher as opposed to an unstructured interview; which gives more confidence and order to the researcher during the interview.

The interview duration is set to last between one hour to two; depending on how much the participants share and reflect upon their experience. After introducing the topic and starting with simple questions to set the scene and make the participants feel comfortable, they were allowed to take their time exploring instances of their experiences, how they felt during the experience, perceived it and interpreted it. The interviewer talk range in phenomenological interviews is usually kept to a minimum, prompts are only used when necessary to avoid getting out of topic. Concerning the location, participants are given the opportunity to choose a suitable place where they can share their insights freely without interruptions or restraints. However, due to COVID-19 restrictions, all interviews were conducted online to ensure participants' safety and accessibility. Online interviews offer a range of advantages such as broader participation, accessibility of the participant's desired time and low to no expenses for travel and hotel booking (Lobe et al., 2022). Evidently, before the interview process, the participants will be given the interview schedule and will be allocated 7 days to think over it. As regards how the interview schedule was utilised, sections one and two were covered in the first-round interview. Section three was addressed in the second-round interview. Finally, section four was discussed in the third-round interview. The only exception is Liza who could not unpack many deep questions simultaneously, therefore, five-round interviews were taken to explore each section and subsection accordingly.

During the interview, the interviewer acts as a student of the interviewee. The interviewer gains as much insight as possible from the interviewee through meticulous questioning and prompts without interrupting the participant (Roulston, 2010). Personal accounts generated are different from one another and follow-up questions are asked when entering new areas or asking for further elaboration; thus, the end product is a rich and very unique complete picture of participants' accounts (Pringle et al., 2011). All interviews are recorded to prevent disrupting the interviewee's flow of the story and more importantly to give attention and show respect for the participants. Meanwhile, notes and observation are noted as the participants narrate and these latter were used in the analysis. The transcription is left post-interview.

Concerning potential issues raised from the interview such as power and emotion. In acknowledgement of the ‘power asymmetry’ (Edwards and Holland, 2013, p. 78) existing and documented between the interviewer and interviewees, as being the initiator of the topic and frame of the conversation direction (Kvale, 1996), I sought to generate a comfortable atmosphere and create an amicable relationship from the beginning with my participants. The creation of such an atmosphere is less complicated to ensure due to my similar nature with my participants as a PhD student.

7. Data Analysis

Smith et al. (2009, 2022) present a variety of data analysis steps that were utilised flexibly to assist the process. The evolving analysis entailed shifting from an individual focus to a more common understanding, as well as from a descriptive level to a more interpretive one. It is noteworthy that the analysis was a cyclical rather than a linear process. In order to comprehend part-whole connections, it was also treated with the hermeneutic circle in mind where the researcher makes sense of the participants trying to make sense of their lifeworld (double hermeneutics). The stages and procedures are presented below (adapted from Smith et al., 2009, 2022):

Table 1: IPA Analytical Stages/Processes

Stages	Procedure
1. Reading and Re-reading	The investigation began with a thorough analysis of one transcript. While reading it, I listened to the audio recording to ensure I understood everything that was said. Moreover, to aid the comprehension of the interview, recollections of the interview and initial remarks were written down.
2. Exploratory Commenting	This step entailed taking preliminary notes in order to investigate the topic on a more in-depth level. It entailed recording seemingly important things and attempting to convey their meaning. The exploratory remarks were broken down into three categories: <i>descriptive remarks</i> : focusing on content and identifying the items of interest. <i>Linguistic remark</i> : a reflection on the use of language in a given context. Asking questions of the facts and working towards a better conceptual grasp of what it means to have these worries in this situation are examples of <i>conceptual remarks</i> .

3. Developing Emergent Themes	The goal of this stage was to concentrate on little sections of text in order to remember what had been learnt through exploratory commenting (descriptive, linguistic and conceptual). To capture and express understanding, concise sentences (emerging themes) were produced.
4. Searching for Connections Across Themes	The analysis gained structure at this point. The principles of abstraction (similar themes brought together), subsumption (emerging topic becomes subordinate theme or Personal Experiential Themes), numeration (frequency in which theme is supported signals importance), and function were used to bring emergent themes together by discovering common linkages between them (what function it serves).
5. Moving to the Next Case	After finishing with the detailed individual case, the study starts over with a new case using the same procedures as demonstrated in 1-4.
6. Looking for Patterns Across Cases	This step entailed looking for links between instances. Individual emerging and subordinate themes were relabelled and rearranged as a result of this process. Subordinate topics that did not appear in at least half of the transcripts were eliminated. The group's subordinate themes or PETs were grouped together, resulting in a number of superordinate themes also known as Group Experiential Themes, each having a number of related subordinate themes/Personal Experiential Themes.

N.B: This table includes both old and new appellation of the analysis developed themes (Subordinate Theme/Personal Experiential Theme). However, the present study will advocate the use of the new terms in Smith et al. (2022) second edition.

As discussed in the table, data were analysed thematically and followed IPA measures. It is a process of rigorous analysis of the transcripts through various steps, then highlighting different commonalities across the emerged themes. The process is ideographically undertaken wherein one participant is dealt with at a time. Moreover, when moving to the next case, no prior knowledge or themes of the first case examined must influence the second case. It differs from thematic analysis as the latter is more detail-oriented and focuses more on the detailed life experiences of the individuals and their uniqueness. Data were transcribed and analysed manually, as Smith et al. (2022) recommended that novice researchers should deal with the data themselves in order to familiarise themselves with the IPA data analytical process. It is important to highlight that Covid did initially impact the data gathering stage by impeding access to face-to-face, however, it was solved when the

research used online interviews which procured better accessibility, a range of participants across the UK and maintained their safety. Finally, a detailed timeline is provided in Appendix 6.

7.1. Rationales for Adopting Separates Group Experiential Themes

GETs represent themes that emerge after comparing and contrasting the personal experiential themes. The convergences and divergences of participants' data represent what a GET is; a compilation of different or agreed views or perceptions under a meta-theme (Smith et al., 2022). However, the pioneers of IPA did not impose researchers to follow the analytical stages as a prescription and reported that the procedures are just guidelines (*Ibid*). Therefore, they offer certain flexibility in terms of analysis and the processes to take. The present study followed all six stages with one addition, which is a different GET for each research question. The rationale for undertaking such a procedure is further elaborated below, using core methodological work as support.

The decision as to why each research question is assigned a different GET is rooted within IPA's principles. According to Smith et al. (2009, 2022), IPA is a methodology that stresses the importance of providing meticulous and nuanced comprehension of the studied phenomena/experience. By using separate GETs for each research question, the study has more chances to get a better understanding and capture the specific themes pertaining to each research question when they emerge. Thus, through this process, a detailed account of the phenomenon under investigation is provided; thereby fulfilling the requirement of thoroughness and idiography.

Moreover, this approach is also in accordance with the seminal work of Braun and Clarke (2006). They argue that thematic analysis is a flexible approach that adapts to the researcher's needs and context. As the present research seeks more clarity in the lifeworld of participants, the adoption of separate GETs is a suitable approach that only makes sense. By doing so, not only primacy on experience is ensured, but also the subtilities and intricacies of the demotivating experiences are portrayed through the participants' detailed/idiographic lenses.

Furthermore, separate GETs can enhance the organisation and the presentation of findings. Using a structured approach when dealing with huge amounts of data would only facilitate clarity and overall understanding of the findings while maintaining complexity (Nowell et al., 2017; King, 2004). Thus, having an organised chapter with GETs that deal with each research question separately permits a clearer understanding of the phenomenon and allows readers to capture the essence of demotivation as experienced by its participants.

In summary, the rationale for opting separate GETs for each research question is justified and supported by the border literature in IPA methodology and thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Smith et al., 2009, 2022; Nowell et al., 2017). This approach used flexibility for the sake of getting a

more focused and nuanced research data. Thus, allowing a deeper comprehension into the intricate and multilayered phenomenon of demotivation.

8. Quality in Qualitative Research

An effective qualitative study promotes “*understand[ing] a situation that would otherwise be enigmatic or confusing*” (Eisner, 1991, p.58). However, to construct good research that generates understanding, qualitative research undergoes procedures to check its validity. The question was raised by Lincoln and Guba (1985, p.290) “*how can an inquirer persuade his or her audiences that the research findings of an inquiry are worth paying attention to*”. According to Patton (2015), validity and reliability are two characteristics that each qualitative researcher should consider while planning a study, assessing data, and judging the study's quality. While such terms are predominantly used within quantitative methodology, qualitative methodologies generally utilise terms such as credibility and trustworthiness. Throughout time, different guidelines have been produced to ensure the quality of qualitative study (such as Elliot et al., 1999; Yardley, 2000, 2017; Tracy, 2010).

However, as the present research is using IPA, consequently it puts more emphasis on validity guidelines proposed by Smith (2011). IPA, as displayed by Smith et al. (2009) advocates criteria from Yardley's (2000, 2017), which are *sensitivity to the context, commitment and rigour, transparency and coherence, and impact and importance*.

The first dimension is *sensitivity to the context*. One of the most significant advantages of qualitative research is the ability to investigate and hypothesise contextual influences (Yardley, 2017). The motivation for utilising IPA is sometimes based on a perceived requirement for context sensitivity through intimate interaction with the idiographic and the particular (Smith et al., 2009). As shown in multiple studies such as Smith and Osburn (2015) on experiencing pain (IPA), Hellman (2016) on sexual assault survivors (hermeneutics), Smith et al. (2017) on psychological challenges of living with ileostomy, or Smith and Shaw (2017) on living with Parkinson disease. Thus, IPA is perfectly fitted with such dimension to validity as its primary focus is on sensitive topics from which its participants are selected purposefully. Subsequently, as this study itself is concerned with the dark side of doctoral research; which is a relatively delicate topic, it requires an appropriate approach and IPA as a methodology has sensitivity in its underpinnings.

Sensitivity to context is also established by familiarising myself with the context of the study and the literature. Being an international PhD student in social sciences myself who investigates the experiences of the doctoral journey, it permits me to have an insider look and relate to the experiences of participants. Moreover, my understanding of the PhD experience was broadened by reviewing and immersing myself in the literature on the topic. Furthermore, sensitivity is demonstrated by

establishing a good rapport with my research participants. This is achieved by showing empathy, putting them in a comfortable situation by fostering a positive atmosphere that would encourage them to open up, telling them there are no right or wrong answers, breaking the hierarchy and giving them a sense of power by telling them that they are the experts, and my concern is to hear attentively and learn as much as possible from their unique experience.

Commitment and rigour are the second dimension in Yardley's (2000, 2017) principles of validity. Similarly, with IPA underpinnings, it is expected that dedication will be demonstrated in the level of attention paid to the participant throughout data collection and the care with which each case is analysed (Smith et al., 2022). To perform an in-depth IPA interview successfully, the researcher must make a significant personal effort and investment in assuring the subject's comfort and paying close attention to what the participant is saying. Thus, the principle of Yardley (2000, 2017) aligns with the procedures undertaken to generate a good IPA study. Furthermore, rigour, according to Smith et al. (2009) and Tracy (2010), is demonstrated through selecting a relevant sample appropriate for the research. Because the research participants were selected purposefully, the aim of such selection was to optimise the chances of getting an appropriate and qualified sample to elicit their experiences as explicitly and eloquently as possible.

Other areas where commitment and rigour are displayed include the quality of the interview and the completeness of the analysis undertaken. The in-depth interview employed in the present study requires serious engagement and thorough attention to storytelling for a prolonged period of time. Moreover, according to Smith (2011), the analysis should be detailed and interpretive, highlighting the predominance of each topic and displaying excerpts from a variety of participants. Subsequently, the homogeneity of the research participants combined with a thorough and exhaustive interviewing validates the level of rigour and commitment required for a work of quality.

Another feature of successful research, according to Yardly (2000), is *transparency and coherence*. I hope that the reader will be able to identify a good match between the research topic and the technique chosen as a result of the talks in this methodology chapter. I've also attempted to be as honest as possible about the methods, including details on how the interview was put up, how the participants were chosen, how the interviews were done, and how the data was analysed. Moreover, in the results section, I will be presenting transcript excerpts to allow the reader to think about my interpretations and examine possible alternatives.

Finally, the most important criterion for evaluating any piece of research is, according to Yardley (2000), *impact and importance*. It is insufficient to produce a sensitive, comprehensive, and convincing analysis if the researcher's ideas have no impact on other people's views or behaviours. However, there are many different types of usefulness and the ultimate worth of a piece of research

can only be determined by considering the analyses' aims, the applications it was designed for, and the community to whom the results were judged relevant (Yardley, 2000). Similarly, Tracy (2010) highlights that a sense of importance and impact begins by selecting a valuable topic. I would argue that investigating the dark/negative side of the doctoral path is an extremely important topic considering the amount of late literature highlighting the different kinds of hardships (health, educational, psychological and social). Moreover, combined with the percentage of attrition and the fact that doctoral attrition has been described as the most well-kept secret (Lovitts, 2001). Any research established to make the journey less disenchanting and more bearable is worth conducting. The present study aims at enriching our understanding of PhD topic through the dark side utilizing a novelistic method of inquiry. Finally, it is hoped that the obtained results will serve policymakers to receive such a report on how international students might perceive the PhD in the long-term.

9. Ethical Consideration

The study followed the British Psychological Society's Code of Human Research Ethics (BPS, 2021) which is advocated by Smith et al. (2009) when deciding to use IPA. During the design and execution of the study, it was critical to ensure that the research process was backed by a respectful and trustworthy approach, with special attention devoted to permission, confidentiality, and the reduction of the risk of harm. It is noteworthy that the ethical elements considered below align with UWS ethical guidelines (2020) for human participation. These elements are *autonomy veracity and informed consent, privacy and confidentiality, justice and inclusiveness, and benefit and harm*. Although BPS (2021) guidelines and UWS ethical guidelines (2020) differ in the appellation, the meaning behind each code is the same and centres on respect for human dignity.

Through the use of a participant information sheet, all of the participants had the required competence to provide consent to participate, and they were completely and accurately informed about all elements of the research (Appendix 2). Before consenting to participate, the participants were given time to digest and process the material. Before each interview, written consent was collected, and participants were required to affirm that they had read the participant information sheet, understood that their participation was voluntary and that their replies would be anonymous. Before consenting to participate, they were also given the option to ask more questions. Although written agreement was gained once, maintaining continuous consent was a continuous procedure that required staying alert to the participants' verbal and nonverbal behaviour. Additionally, participants were told that they might withdraw at any moment without reason, and this was emphasised before each interview.

Concerning personal Information, participants' potential identifiers were replaced using nicknames. "*Psychologists value the dignity and worth of all persons, with sensitivity to the dynamics*

of perceived authority or influence over persons and peoples and with particular regard to people's rights" (Code of Ethics and Conduct, 2018, p.5). Thus, in addition to the anonymity of the name, the researcher made sure that the participants felt validated and respected during the interview. To make certain that people's rights are maintained and safeguarded, participants' intellectual property and data ownership rights must be honoured in all kinds of media. Throughout the research process, researchers will actively give these rights to participants (BPS, 2021). In compliance with GDPR (UK Research and Innovation, 2020), all the participants' data were securely stored on the encrypted UWS researcher's laptop, which is only accessible through the researcher's unique banner number and password.

Lastly, an important element highlighted in BPS guidelines is maximising benefits and minimising harm. Psychologists must be aware of the possible consequences of their interactions with participants, such as the risk of unintentionally inflicting discomfort or instilling self-doubt. Even though researchers try to minimise it, there is usually a power differential between researchers and participants. As a result, sensitivity is needed, and prudence is always required. In combination with the preceding section of this Code of Human Research Ethics, researchers may need to weigh the costs to the individual participant against the possible societal benefits (BPS, 2021).

Interview questions were cautiously asked and were handled with care in order not to upset the participants. They were debriefed on the particularity of the questions in the interview schedule "*I will be asking you deep questions, I am sorry for the inconvenience*" and hence should participants feel distress or discomfort, a signpost to relevant agencies was added in the consent form. In cases where participants became distressed (such as Liza), the recording was stopped, and breaks were introduced, as well as reminding participants that they could withdraw at any time if they felt overwhelmed. The latter coincides with ethical guidelines policies on minimising harm and maximising benefits from BPS (2021), BERA (2024) and UWS ethical guidelines on how to deal with the potentiality of harm rising within the research. The researcher stresses that it is within his ethical responsibilities to foster a safe and positive environment and adjust accordingly should an ethical issue arise.

However, I believe to the best of my knowledge that this interview procedure will not or at the very least will not stimulate or emerge any trauma that would risk hurting the participants. By exteriorising negative instances of life helps participants to better reflect and see the issue much more clearly as they have concretised it through words. In other words, qualitative interviews have therapeutic values (Rossetto, 2014); The QRI setting provides a forum for exchanging tales, similar to clinical interviews, which can yield rich information for researchers and fulfil a therapeutic meaning-making role for participants (Gale, 1992), because it promotes emotional catharsis and can

improve people's moods (Kottler, 1991). Self-awareness may be increased by sharing knowledge, stories, and experiences (Hutchinson et al., 1994). Through exteriorising their stories, participants would comprehend their situation significantly better (MacKinnon et al., 2015), find purpose (Hutchinson et al., 1994) and even alter their thought processes routine for a better future outcome (Pennebaker, 2021). Therefore, qualitative interviews have therapeutic value as they promote emotional catharsis (Kottler, 1991), self-reflection (Hutchinson et al., 1994), narrative reconstruction and emotional release (Gale, 1992), emotional healing and psychological insight (Pennebaker, 2021), empowerment (Hutchinson et al., 1994), and meaning-making (Smith et al., 2022). These elements are recognised by psychological therapies such as Person-Centred Therapy (Rogers, 1951), Dialectical Behavioural Therapy (DBT) (Linehan, 1980) and Trauma-Focused Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (TF-CBT) (Cohen, 1990).

Moreover, the process of knowledge production is collaborative. Indeed, both the researcher and the participants co-construct the knowledge during the interview process. Moreover, such an application is not a result of simply extracting but active dialogue between the two parties. This corroborates with BPS' (2021) principle of showing respect for the autonomy and dignity of the person. This entails respecting the input of the participants and making sure that their voices and perspectives are authentically represented. Additionally, the co-construction of knowledge during qualitative interviews was highlighted by Smith et al. (2022) where knowledge is not existent in the outside world but rather involves the active participation of both the researcher and the participants to bring the phenomenon to the light of the day (Heidegger, 1962). Simply put, interviews construct reality (Smith et al., 2009).

Ethical considerations are of paramount importance given the sensitive nature of the research topic investigated. Having elaborated on the therapeutic and helping value of exteriorising one's demotivational experience, it is also important to notice that humans are unpredictable as people act differently in identical situations (Dweck, 2006), and the reaction might differ not only because of their personalities but also depending on the severity of the lived phenomenon and how it impacted their lives. The case was particularly true for Liza, who had severe demotivation and depression, and measures were taken to minimize and eliminate any harm. The experience was a teachable moment in how to handle difficult or unexpected situations arising from interviews. Subsequently, knowledge of therapeutic and risk aspects is provided to protect participants' emotional state and maintain the ethical handling of the research. It emphasises the importance that researchers should be alert and ready to handle the emotional issues of participants especially when covering emotionally sensitive materials (dark side) and hence invasive.

In hindsight, I now realise that although the participants gave their fully-informed consent on the nature of the questions during the interview (interview schedule and in participant information sheet), it might have been better had I outlined to them in more detail that there was a possibility of them feeling some discomfort during the interview and that might have an impact on the way they felt. Whilst details of the interview procedure and its content were fully and transparently outlined in the interview schedule and participant information sheet, the research could have used a much more explicit delineation of some potential emotional labour. Thus, I have acknowledged the therapeutic value to it, but I need also to acknowledge that there might be unintended negative consequences that are unavoidable in the encounters researched.

10. Research Positionality

Positionality is an important concept in research that needs to be addressed; it permits to state where researchers stand in relation to their research. As Hall (1990, p.18) pinpoints, “*There’s no enunciation without positionality. You have to position yourself somewhere in order to say anything at all*”. It is fair to anticipate that the researcher's opinions, political positions, and cultural background (gender, race, class, socioeconomic level, religion, and educational background) will be key elements that influence the research process. In this case, it is important to indicate where the researcher stands (Bourke, 2014; Merriam and Tisdell, 2015; Creswell and Poth, 2016). The researcher is considered as the data instrument in qualitative research in general and phenomenological study in particular (Bourke, 2014; Hopkins et al., 2017).

As I am adopting an approach that is purely interpretative, my positionality is one of an insider and subjective researcher because I believe that in qualitative research, it is rather naïve to expect being an outsider from the researched phenomenon. As Bourke (2014, p.3) stated “*To achieve a pure objectivism is a naïve quest, and we can never truly divorce ourselves of subjectivity*”. Moreover, as this study is heavily influenced by hermeneutics, Heidegger (1962) proposed that researchers' prior knowledge and preconceptions aid their understanding of the phenomena under investigation. According to him, an individual and the world co-constitute each other, which means that our viewpoints are formed by the world we live in, but we also influence and alter those perspectives. ‘Being-in-the-world’ was Heidegger's term for this reciprocal and inseparable interaction between humans and the world, with the hyphens indicating the oneness of subjects and objects rather than their separation (Hopkins et al., 2016).

Because Heidegger's philosophy argues that a person and the world are inextricably linked, a person must make sense of the world as they live within it rather than as something apart from it. As a result, Heidegger rejects Husserl's notion that we may bracket off our presuppositions and prior

experiences in order to have a more objective perspective of reality. According to him, a researcher's subjectivity is not an undesirable condition that has to be avoided and monitored to do more reliable study (Glesne, 2016). Preconceptions, on the other hand, are viewed as assets that researchers may utilise to get a better understanding. Thus, instead of removing the researcher's subjectivity, reflexivity, the recording, tracking, questioning, and sharing of how we form and are shaped by the research process should be used to manage it (Glesne, 2016; Hopkins et al., 2016).

I am a male, heterosexual, Kabyle person (from Algeria, North Africa), raised in a middle-class family in a city called Draa Ben Khedda. Algeria predominantly speaks Arabic, and it is the official language taught in schools and used in administrative spheres (in addition to French). My Kabylia/Berber upbringing makes me learn the Kabyle language as a mother tongue first before learning Arabic in elementary school. The first foreign language I have learnt after that was the French language (mainly due to the legacy of the French invasion). Thus, making me a multilingual speaker of more than five languages (German in Secondary school and Japanese in University for fun). Concerning the religious side, most Algerians are Muslims (Islam as a religion means a submission to God; in Arabic known as Allah). Arriving at university, I conducted my very first academic piece of research entitled "Investigating the Factors that Demotivate EFL Students: *The Case of Master I Students at MMUTO, Department of English*". I got a scholarship to conduct a PhD in the UK after winning a national contest held by the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research. Before starting the PhD program, all laureates were taken to Canterbury Christ Church University for a pre-session program aimed to prepare us for the PhD in the UK. After that, I started my PhD journey at the University of the West of Scotland.

The reason for me being an insider is that I have a relatively similar background as my research participants and was granted the same international opportunity. This particularity of sharing the same characteristics as my participants permits me to get access to their stories more freely as there is no power hierarchy or feeling of incomprehensiveness of the experience put on the participants (as may put an outsider). Such particularity creates an atmosphere of trust and easement where participants feel relatively confident and are not judged because they are sharing stories with a colleague who has the same doctorate as theirs. Such options offered by my positionality might not offer the same experiential accounts and ultimately the same results that an outsider might collect. Lastly, my interpretation is influenced by subjectivity as an insider and permits me to picture the lived experience more appropriately than other candidates. Thus, my subjectivity is used for the sake of bettering the research rather than constraining it; as those who have gone through the events, they investigate and have more authority and credibility to advance knowledge claims about a specific issue than those

who have just read or pondered about such experiences; hence a subjective account of research can assist the inquiry (Allen, 2017).

However, due to the nature of the topic, it is important to acknowledge the emotional toll and mental health challenges during the research process. The researcher is not immune to potential emotional experiences during the data collection phase (Hochschild, 1983; Hubbard et al., 2001; Dickson-Swift et al., 2007). Similarly, during the present research, the fieldwork was filled with emotionally distressing elements which could be termed as ‘emotional labour’ (Hochschild, 1983). During the fieldwork, some participants recounted distressing and alarming life events that impacted the emotional state of the researcher. For example, Liza during the field speculated not only on her depression and attrition because of demotivation, but also considered much more worst-case scenario thinking patterns such as suicidal thoughts and ideation. Another example is dealing with a parent’s death, which was the case of Vegeta. One year prior to the fieldwork, Vegeta expressed losing his father due to Covid-19. The latter also represents an emotionally rooted experience that leads to sadness and upset. These elements portray the emotionally rooted experiences that might impact the researcher. Due to the fact that emotions are inescapable (Hubbard et al., 2001), acknowledging them is not inherently a shortcoming but helps to extract the true essence of the phenomenological core of the emotional experience that is demotivation. Finally, acknowledging these elements are important factors that contribute to the researcher’s integrity, transparency and trustworthiness (Yardley, 2000; 2017). Subsequently, offering a reflective account of the research process along with positionality permits the research to have its own context and contribution.

11. Participants’ Demographics

The following table offers information in regard to the present research study’s participants. The table includes elements such as age, gender, region, research area, interview rounds, length, and the transcription process. As clearly shown in the table below, a clear diversity in gender, UK university type and research area is noticed. The latter fills one of the most important cores of IPA which is uniqueness (Smith et al., 2022). By having a diversified research group, the research is assured to have unique experiences and perspectives which will aid in enriching the phenomenon of demotivation.

Table 2: Participants Information Sheet

Participants' Nicknames	Age (years)	Gender	UK Host University	Area of Research	Interview Round Numbers	Interview Length	Interview Transcript (words/pages)
1. Stallion	28	Male	Russel Group University	Writing Studies	3 Rounds (finished)	1-2 hours (60 to 120 minutes) per round.	63 pages/ 27254 words.
2. John	28	Male	Post 1992 University	Education	3 Rounds (finished)	1-2 hours (60 to 120 minutes) per round.	84 pages/40575 words.
3. Amel	28	Female	Post 1992 University	Social Sciences	1 Round (won't participate any further)	1-2 hours (60 to 120 minutes) per round.	-----
4. Zineb	28	Female	Post 1992 University	Adoption Studies	3 Rounds (finished)	1-2 hours (60 to 120 minutes) per round.	88 pages/ 42023 words
5. Manel	28	Female	Russel Group University / Red Brick University	Language Studies	3 Rounds (finished)	1-2 hours (60 to 120 minutes) per round.	78 pages /38192 words
6. Vegeta	28	Male	Russel Group University / Red Brick University	Literacy and Socialisation Studies	3 Rounds (finished)	1-2 hours (60 to 120 minutes) per round.	94 pages/ 52618words
7. Leila	28	Female	Post 1992 University	ESP	3 Rounds (finished)	1-2 hours (60 to 120 minutes) per round.	82 pages/ 46362 words
8. Liza	28	Female	Russel Group University / Red Brick University	Child Development Studies	5 Rounds (finished)	1-2 hours (60 to 120 minutes) per round.	89 pages /46456 words
9. Oreo	29	Female	Post 1992 University	Literary Studies	3 Rounds (Finished)	1-2 hours (60 to 120 minutes) per round.	62 pages/ 28657 words
10. Nervious	28	Male	Russel Group University /Red Brick University	Discourse Analysis	1 Round Forfeit (multiple reminders sent from August to October)	1-2 hours (60 to 120 minutes) per round.	-----

As displayed, the research initially started with ten participants. However, after the first interview session, two participants withdrew due to different reasons. Amel has a visual disability and upon finishing the first-round interview, she realised how demanding the interview is in terms of length, volume and type of questions. Therefore, she decided to withdraw from participation which was within her full rights as a participant. Concerning Nervious, his participation was withdrawn due

to unresponsiveness despite multiple attempts of communication and reminders via social media. Therefore, the totality of the participants fully engaging with the present study was eight. This underscores the level of requisite depth and commitment required for participants during IPA interviews. Finally, all participants were in their second year of the PhD except Oreo who was in her fourth year.

Summary

The chapter outlined every step the present research is undertaking; starting from a general understanding of reality (ontology, epistemology), to the methodology and methods adopted (IPA and semi-structured interview). The IPA was deemed appropriate as it seeks a thorough investigation of people's lived experiences and brings to light phenomena relatively uncovered; the dark side of postgraduate study is an interesting topic and worthy of being brought into focus to ameliorate the experience for domestic students in general and international students in particular. Finally, sampling, analysis, reliability, ethical consideration, and positionality were addressed sequentially to permit the reader to see how the project came into existence.

Chapter VI. Navigating the Peregrination: Demotivating Factors in the Journey of Algerian Postgraduate Students in the UK

Introduction:

This chapter presents the demotivating factors experienced by UK Algerian postgraduates. This IPA research is rooted in the principles of phenomenology, hermeneutics and idiography (Smith et al., 2022; Smith and Nizza, 2022). Through an in-depth analysis of the participants' experiences which comprises six stages/levels that are Reading and Re-reading, Exploratory Comments, Developing Emergent Themes, Searching for Connections Across Themes, Moving to the Next Case, and Looking for Patterns across cases, three major GETs have emerged from the collective interviews which are the following: *External Challenges and Life Events*, *Supervisor-Related Issues*, and *Personal and Emotional Factors*; all of which will be elaborated thoroughly in this chapter. The chapter is therefore divided into these three aforementioned categories. The academic world is a place for advancing knowledge and bringing enlightenment to diverse subjects. Nevertheless, it has a dark side that deserves to be unveiled as well. The aim is to provide a nuanced understanding of the ill-documented phenomena at an international doctoral level.

The table below enumerates the PETs of each participant regarding the phenomenon of demotivation. In other words, each of the respondent's personal experiences and narratives regarding demotivation is presented. Moreover, it justifies logically how these themes contribute to the development of wider themes that are known as GETs. Finally, the tabular data offers a rationale for each presented classification.

Table 3: Group Experiential Themes Related to Demotivating Factors.

Group Experiential Themes	Personal Experiential Themes
<p>GET 1: External Challenges and Life Events</p> <p><i>GET 1 captures the external challenges and life events outside the participants' control. The GET includes events such as the Covid break and its subsequent effect, isolation from family and personal life events such as divorce.</i></p>	<p>John: Covid, isolated from family and community. Zineb: Being away from family/homesickness, Divorce/failed relationship. Manel: Covid. Vegeta: Father's Passing Away Due to Covid, Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic. Oreo: The Pandemic, International Challenge. Leila: Pandemic Effect, Personal, International.</p>
<p>GET 2: Supervisor-Related Issues</p> <p><i>GET 2 focuses on the issues related to supervisors. It narrates how issues related to the latter flip the motivation to its dark counterpart. Supervisor's issues include departure, feedback and overall duties.</i></p>	<p>Stallion: Supervisor's Feedback. John: Supervisor unexpected departure. Manel: Supervisors' feedback. Liza: Supervisor Related issues Oreo: Supervisor's Sudden Departure, Supervisory meetings and Feedback. Leila: Change of Topic due to Supervisor's Retirement, Change of the Research, Pressures, Uncertainty and Expectations.</p>
<p>GET 3: Personal and Emotional Factors</p> <p><i>GET 3 encompasses personal and emotional factors. The elements discussed are mainly intrinsic factors leading to demotivation such as self-demotivation, imposter syndrome and lack of interest.</i></p>	<p>Stallion: Unproductivity, Self-demotivation. John: Re-finding motivation. Manel: Imposter Syndrome, Invading Thoughts, Fear of being Deceived, Mood Swings, Emotional State. Vegeta: Lack of interest, Time Remaining, Finding Motivation. Liza: Being behind schedule. Oreo: Feeling overwhelmed, Imposter syndrome, Lack of Understanding and judgment by Others.</p>

I. GET 1: External Challenges and Life Events

GET 1 encompasses *the External Challenges and Life Events* that lie beyond the participants' control. It includes factors such as the pandemic, isolation from support systems and personal life circumstances. These are mostly unexpected experiences that destabilise students' motivation and

their PhD thesis' ongoing progress. Such themes are prevalent across participants; however, the specific event and experience may differ as they have unique experiences. The shared nature of these themes highlights the convergences of external factors which influence the participants' motivation and academic progress during their postgraduate studies.

Table 4: Personal Experiential Themes Relating to Group Experiential Theme 1

Personal Experiential Themes	John	Zineb	Manel	Vegeta	Leila	Liza	Oreo
Impact of the Covid-19 Pandemic	✓		✓	✓	✓		✓
Isolation from Family and Community	✓	✓	✓	✓			
Personal Factors (Breakup, Divorce, International)		✓			✓	✓	✓

1. Impact of the Covid-19 Pandemic

The COVID-19 pandemic is undoubtedly one of the most unexpected factors that demotivated UK Algerian postgraduates' journey. Covid caused several disruptions and damages both at a personal and academic level. Moreover, due to travel restrictions during that period, many international students were separated from their families and were unable to see them. Finally, a major disruption and critical life event is the loss of relatives due to the pandemic. The latter could be observed in the following: "...challenges started with COVID, I'm not an indoor person, I'm very sociable, then all of a sudden I needed to study and do everything at home without being in touch with anyone, this was really horrible and because of that I lost my motivation" (John, line 26-29, page 10).

John appears to have started to face demotivation when the pandemic took place leaving him secluded from society and his educational environment; which consists of a very important component for him to be/stay motivated. Such a break led him to face a myriad of challenges: "I was stressed about what was going to happen to my family, I couldn't focus on my studies because of all that anxiety...I still feel a bit demotivated, I wasn't productive during COVID" (line 12-13, page 23). Due to the constant stress, John develops a health-related problem:

...because of all that, I developed an auto-immune disease...I've been struggling with my concentration...there are times where I feel so weak that I can't even wake up in the morning...Why am I not motivated? Why can't I concentrate? Why don't I want to study? (line 10-21, page 12)

John offers a glimpse of the challenges that international doctoral students face during the pandemic. The passages also show how such a factor impacted heavily on his motivation and health thus compromising his thesis thriving. In the first passage, John opens up on how the pandemic took his focus away from studies to constantly worrying about his family's wellbeing. The latter stripped away

his motivation to undertake his main task which is the PhD. Due to the emotional burden resulting from the constant stress, John develops an autoimmune disease which he stresses "...high TSH, I had a hormonal problem" (line 12, page 78). Even though the stress reduced, he still reports feeling demotivated, which highlights its lingering effect. The second passage elaborates more on the TSH issue and its subsequent effect on John's study routine such as waking up in the morning and being motivated. The latter caused John to question himself which is also known as an existential crisis "why am I not motivated?". Thus, John during this phase reflects a period of inner conflict and self-doubt which could be translated into demotivation.

The extracts above highlight the interconnectedness of several factors such as stress, anxiety, health, and motivation and how these interact and impact each other. The experiences lived by John underscore the complexity of demotivation and how different factors contribute to its development. John's generated stress and anxiety rendered him unable to focus on his work and be productive, which further developed in him an auto-immune disease.

Similarly, Manel mentioned that COVID-19 has demotivated her for multiple reasons primarily fear "you're always afraid of something happening...your focus is directed to a totally different thing than studies...sometimes when events happen in your country, just feel tied up, you cannot write anything, you cannot focus because your mind is filled of bad thing" (Manel, line 12-16, p. 31). Due to the continuous pressure, Manel envisages worst-case scenarios which only worsen her situation "What if something happens to me or my loved ones when I'm just here doing a PhD, is a PhD going to do anything to me if something happens to my beloved ones" (Manel, line 18-23, p. 36). The extracts reflect the impact of external factors on Manel's motivation during the pandemic. First, she expresses how her fear and anxiety about her family and country paralyses her from undertaking her PhD. Consequently, this fear causes a mental block preventing Manel from fully concentrating on her work and hence making it difficult to be productive. Manel's lifeworld highlights how external factors can hinder motivation. Equally, the second passage reveals the distress Manel experiences when she envisages potential death within her family. The latter causes her to question the utility and value of the PhD as the latter would not bring her family back to life if they ever were to die. Thus, due to fear and uncertainty of that period and what the pandemic could potentially do to her loved ones, Manel's motivation decreased significantly which led to a lack of focus and productivity.

Correspondingly, Vegeta expresses his experience of COVID-19 stating "COVID blocked me entirely" (line 41, page 29), demonstrating the disengaging/debilitating effect of the pandemic. Another reason to his demotivation is his father's death due to COVID and his inability to fly to

Algeria due to restrictions “I had a seven-month interruption...The impact...was demotivating...it was even more demotivating...due to my inability...dealing with the passing of my father and me not being able to go home” (Vegeta, line 20-25, page 9).

The death of a loved one is an extremely difficult process, Vegeta reports he took a seven-month interruption from his studies just for him to attend his father’s funeral and grieve. However, he was unable to leave UK soil due to the travel restrictions at that time. Unfortunately, the toll on Vegeta's mental health was significant as he could not be surrounded by his family to process the critical event. Additionally, not having established any social connection in the UK made him alienated and isolated “I didn’t have any form of social structure so when the impact of that was bad on my mental health” (Vegeta, line 32-33, page 9), leading him to feel more demotivated as he could not share or vent his feelings.

However, he posited some interesting facts and rather ‘out-of-the-box’ thinking that made him unique compared to others in his approach/reasoning:

I was forced to study and write from home as I used to exclusively work at the university. I felt betrayed by the university...I felt I had to perform in this stressful, weird, and isolated situation. The initial value I had in pursuing a PhD was shattered by the fact that the pandemic rendered my interest null. The value of the PhD was in the university's infrastructure, community, physical interaction, access to facilities, and geographic relocation, participating in a university as a student was what gave value to my entire idea, and when those things were removed, my motivation was lost. (Vegeta, line 34-13, page 31-32)

Vegeta states being ‘forced’ to perform at home away from the university which indicates his disapproval of the situation. He reports feeling betrayed and not reassured about the situation, as international students being away from home can be stressful especially as they have no establishment roots such as domestic students. Vegeta reports that he had to perform under a “stressful, weird, and isolated situation” which was not his initial idea of the PhD abroad. Ultimately, Vegeta finds himself losing the value attached to the PhD due to the pandemic which is a clear indication of the loss of motivation or demotivation.

Moreover, Vegeta used an interesting analogy to express how he felt scammed by the university during the pandemic. The analogy was ordering a full car only to receive the wheels which constitute a small part of the whole (such as the doors, engine, seat and so on). He believed that the value of his full-time PhD was linked to physical access to facilities, libraries, and communities of researchers, and felt that his motivation was lost when those things were taken away. This is apparent in both these passages: “If you remove those things, my motivation and perception of value are gone, and I no longer have interest in pursuing academia as I did not have the access I anticipated based on my full

PhD engagement” (Vegeta, line 22-38, page 32). Vegeta expresses how his demotivation is filled by a sense of disenchantment and betrayal. To describe his initial feelings of demotivation, Vegeta remarkably relates his situation to ordering a car and receiving only the wheels hence calling it a ‘scam’. It seems that Vegeta attaches a great value to the physical facilities offered by the university, which he describes as the sole reason behind his relocation. As he saw no return of value on the paid money and yet still had to perform to the universities’ standards under such pressure, Vegeta ended up disenchanted, demotivated and deprived his value of the PhD “rendering the experience valueless causing me to lose motivation until I returned home...I got completely disenchanted with the prospect of finishing a PhD” (Vegeta, line 41-11, page 32-33). Therefore, Vegeta’s motivation was purely extrinsic. Interestingly, using the term ‘deprived’ perfectly fits the image of demotivation as it is a state of deprivation leading to unproductivity and decreased value (Kikuchi, 2015). Finally, Vegeta uses the term ‘disenchantment’ highlighting his deception for not accessing the facilities and how this leads to demotivation. As his enchantment, or in this case motivation, was based on visiting the university resources and fully immersing himself in the research world, not having met the latter triggers his disenchantment and demotivation. Thus, the passage provided by Vegeta connects two different terminologies from psychology and sociology which are demotivation and disenchantment. The triggering factor was the magic (having facilities) disappearing which acts as a demotivating force, especially for international doctoral students who travelled thousands of miles to access better research centres.

Similarly, Oreo questions the value of the PhD due to COVID stating:

...it felt that the world has stopped, and I was asking myself “what's the point of doing this? of going on?” We don't even know what's going to happen in a year or two, maybe six months, in a month, it was very stressful period, we didn't know where the world was going back then, really it was very demotivating. (line 23-27, page 13)

COVID-19 has transitioned the world to a period of uncertainty and worry, which impacted doctoral students such as Oreo. The latter leads to existential questions about the purpose of pursuing academic or professional goals in such a time of upheaval. This questioning was highlighted in Oreo's account of feeling overwhelmed by the unknown future and asking herself “what's the point of doing this?”. This kind of questioning marks a demotivating period which was also highlighted “it was really demotivating”. Therefore, periods of extreme uncertainty and worry prevent students from achieving their goals as their priorities have shifted, leading to demotivation not only in life in general but also in studies as well.

Lastly, Leila’s vision about the pandemic and how that led to demotivation is presented. She stresses that the impact was more emotional which severed her motivation from working “If I weren’t

that affected emotionally, I could've done better" (Leila, line 19-26, page 23). Leila highlights the impact of the pandemic on her emotional state and academic progress. She reports that she was still productive during the pandemic, however, she strongly believes that her productivity would have been optimal if she had not been impacted by her emotional side. Because her equilibrium was compromised from an emotional perspective, Leila was not able to derive her full potential. Thus, her passage reveals the importance of emotional stability in undertaking academic tasks.

The passage above highlights how demotivation impacted people differently from stopping completely to just decreasing progress. Although her experience of demotivation does not contradict others, she expressed how the pandemic affected her emotionally leading to an indirect hit on her academic performance. Thus, IPA offers a chance for others to express their unique perspectives of the same phenomenon and how individuals who are from the same cultural background act in a different manner towards it (Dweck, 1999).

The impact of Covid on human lives in general and students in specific has been massively documented. An impressive number of studies demonstrated the negative instances that accompanied the pandemic (Donohue et al., 2021; Burns, 2023; Abdul-Rahaman, 2023; Sverdlik, Hall and Vallerand, 2023; Korkmaz and Toraman, 2022). The pandemic has had detrimental impacts on the wellbeing of participants and led to decreased performance and negative overall experience. Similarly, this echoes Abdul-Rahaman (2023) in his large-scale study of 4454 doctoral students across 249 Russian universities found that international students were the most impacted by the pandemic in comparison to domestic students due to their delicate situation of being away from their homes. His results demonstrate the negative consequences of Covid on learning experience, satisfaction with supervision, dissertation experience, and doctoral program satisfaction. Furthermore, the results indicated that international students were more exposed to higher levels of stress, burnout, frustration, dissatisfaction, and dropout due to bad experiences arising from non-suitable learning environments, poor supervision that affects student grooming, and late dissertation defences. The present study validates these results from another methodological perspective, highlighting how Covid has destabilised international doctoral students' wellbeing and thesis thriving.

Moreover, present results on the inability of participants to see their families, working from home, forced isolation, and not accessing the school facilities corroborate recent work of Sverdlik, Hall and Vallerand (2023). The study employed a questionnaire on 708 international doctoral students across various disciplines and found results that agree with the present research on demotivation. Similarly, it agrees partially with the fact that females were more stressed and emotionally impacted than males.

In the present study, Leila reports the impact of the pandemic to be more emotional than academic highlighting the psychological and emotional toll of the pandemic on females compared to males. However, the slight difference is that one male participant (John) has what seems to be an emotional response to the pandemic which could be due to the hormonal situation. Another important uniqueness emerging from this IPA study is Vegeta's reflection and interpretation of the phenomenon such as loss of value, feeling scammed, betrayed and demotivated. Finally, the results also corroborate with Donohue et al. (2020) on how Covid-19 lead to a decrease in motivation, focus, and energy. Using online interviews with 235 participants, the results found that PhD students lost their motivation, focus and energy due to Covid-19. Similarly, most participants noticed a decline in motivated behaviours notably John "why am I not motivated", "I cannot focus" Manel "your focus is just directed to a totally different thing than work, than studies" and Oreo "it was very demotivating". Therefore, it is safe to assume that the pandemic has had a demotivating effect on UK Algerian postgraduates leading to a state of self-doubt, sickness, loss of value, betrayal, emotional impact and existential crisis. The same results obtained through different approaches pinpoint the severity of such occurrence as a reality dislocation phenomenon, however, the present study offered students the chance to voice their concerns significantly more as IPA provides such an advantage (Smith et al., 2022). Taken altogether, Covid represents a demotivating force that impeded an important number of IDS.

2. Geographical and Cultural Distance/Isolation from Family and Community

PET 2 pertains to demotivation due to Geographical and Cultural Distance or Isolation from Family and Community. Algerians while being away from their home country experience homesickness and isolation. The distance from their families and communities negatively impacts their mental health and motivation to pursue their academic goals and ultimately timely PhD completion.

Both John and Zineb mention the importance of having support systems beside them to deal with everyday issues in general and doctoral in particular. Starting with John:

...being far from family is another challenge, loneliness is a very big challenge, spending the lockdown alone didn't help, not having someone to share your problems with is a challenge, you don't want to call your parents and tell them about the problems you have when you're far, that affected my PhD experience. (John, line 11-16, page 11)

John describes one of the foundations of having a support system which is sharing. By having that element deprived, he finds himself isolated and unheard, impossible to convey his feelings and share his negative experiences to benefit from the exhalation of having someone listen to him. Zineb, in her case, expresses a deep sense of missing her family which ultimately impacted her mood. She illustrates

with an example of how missing familial opportunities such as birthdays demotivates her: “today is my niece’s birthday, and I’m missing that...I really want to go back to see my family, even if for a week or two” (Zineb, line 8-14, page 33). Moreover, she highlights the need for a parent to cope with the PhD:

When feeling that this process of PhD is too overwhelming, sometimes as any child or any person growing up, I need my mom, there are things that can't be replaced, having someone comforting you, the mother is the best source of comfort; especially on demotivated periods. (Zineb, 17-20, page 33)

Zineb’s case illustrates the double-edged nature of studies abroad. On the one hand, students academically develop their abilities and acquire a diploma at a UK institution which is highly regarded in Algeria. On the other hand, however, they need to undertake the full experience/process alone, away from their support system and therefore have to sacrifice attending important familial events such as birthdays. Finally, Zineb highlights the necessity of having the presence of her mother during hard times such as demotivation, and regressing herself to a 'child' in need of their mother.

From Manel’s perspective, demotivation under this category is leaving family behind as she occupies a big place as an elder sister, driving her to question the value of doing her PhD in the first place: “*is it worth it? Is it worth all this suffering all these tears?*” because I cry a lot when I leave I always say to myself “*maybe I’m just wasting my time*”, “*maybe I’ve taken the wrong decision*” (Manel, line 2-7, page 29). She further has the highest level of questioning at that moment stating: “*what if I just give up everything and just have a normal life like ordinary people do?*” I always question my decision, I always ask myself, “*Is it worth spending all this time away from my family? And because of something like because of a degree?!*”. (Manel, line 10-14, page 29). Manel underscores the heavy and painful process she undergoes when leaving for the UK. Upon her departure, she is filled with tears, doubts and questioning her decision “is it worth it?”. Manel questions the worthiness of the PhD calling the situation of being away as from her family ‘suffering’, highlighting the intense pain she feels during this transition. Despite the PhD being the highest academic achievement, it becomes almost inconsequential “because of a degree?!” when compared to losing the support system of everyday life which is her family. This pinpoints the demotivating state and existential questioning that Manel experiences.

The following stories highlighted important aspects of everyday life that lead to demotivation. John, Zineb and Manel although have different experiences at different times and locations, they share similarities in how critical families are to their motivation and wellbeing. They report that such support is needed in times of crisis and being isolated from that leads to total demotivation, decreased mood and wellbeing, doubt and existential crisis. The importance of family members besides students has

been keenly observed throughout the years. The present study's results offer support to the previous works of Templeton (2016), Breitenbach et al. (2019) and McCray and Joseph-Richards (2020) on how family support contributes to doctoral students' motivation, resilience and success.

The decrease in family support or presence in this case is a huge demotivator. The latter corroborates with studies of Volkert et al. (2018) where the intention to leave the doctoral program is associated with a lack of support from family. In a similar vein, the present participants lost their motivation and intention to undertake the doctorate as they noticed their support system missing.

For example, Manel questioning the value of the PhD "is it worth it...all this suffering...for a degree" could be understood as her having an inner battle where she leans toward attrition as being away from her family is not in her favour. John by having no support around as well puts him in a horrible state wherein his motivation is severely reduced. Finally, Zineb highlights how immensely she needs her mother by her side during times of demotivation, regressing to a childlike state longing for a mother as a source of support. Subsequently, it is safe to assume that the deprivation of family or family absence is a huge contributor to demotivation.

3. Personal Life Events

Personal life events such as divorce or failed relationships can also contribute to demotivation. The case is particularly true for Zineb and Leila who have lived rather unpleasant/traumatic experiences that deviated their motivation to the dark side.

Starting with Zineb who lived an experience that changed her perception. In her case, she lived an abusive and dysfunctional relationship that led to a divorce. She expresses "I had a year's interruption because the first year I came with my ex-husband and I had so many problems, so I decided to stand for myself and carry on my life alone" (line 22-26, page 8). This kind of experience delayed her progress for a year and was unable to perform under such a traumatic event. She also reports that the post-divorce period was also hard to cope with as the thought of a failed relationship was recurrent in her mind "my life-changing experience blocked really my progress because going through hardship and a failed relationship is something that's hard to handle" (31-33, page 26). The consequence was to terminate the relationship that was in her words 'abusive', start over, immerse herself in her academic studies, and enjoy even vicissitudes of research:

I kicked him out, it went to physical abuse, and we had problems, screaming all the time, I was so ashamed next to the neighbours. I decided to eradicate him from my life. So after it, my PhD is my healing process, I really enjoy everything about it, even the most non-enjoyable parts of it. (Zineb, line 12-15, page 9)

The divorce is clearly a demotivating event for Zineb that had its impact lingering even after the split. She endured the thought of a ‘failed relationship’ and noticed a huge block in productivity. She also narrates that divorce as a thought was hard to eradicate which could also be regarded as discouraging. However, what seems to be different is her agency in regard to the event. Zineb seems to have taken a new leaf where she regains control over her life by casting away the negativity and enjoying the process of research, both positives and negatives. This result strengthens the claim about the family’s importance to academic success such as Breitenbach et al. (2019) and Volkert et al. (2018). Similarly, Zineb by having no support from her husband went into a period of extreme trauma and demotivation. The result also validates the claim made by Frick and Pyhältö’s (2020) on how family-related problems were negatively experienced by doctoral students. However, the present result differs in terms of the nature and the surmountability of the factor (Marguc et al., 2010). Indeed, previous research did not report divorce as a demotivating factor despite the axiomatic nature of the event. Moreover, the participants in Onwuegbuzie et al. (2014) comprised of divorced participants, but it was not stated that the divorce happened during the academic experience. Subsequently, the present study offers a newly found demotivating factor for international doctoral students.

Concerning Leila, she attaches a great value to her personal life, and the potential disruption of the latter affects every other side/area of her life as she highlights:

Personal problems did affect me because personal life matters, if I go through an emotional, personal problem with my family, [or] person that I love, that affects me because that threatens my life and the stability of my personal life, which matters for me more than the stability of my academic life to be frank. (line 17-21, page 24)

Leila highlights the order of importance/priority in her life stating that her personal life precedes her academic life and the fact of having a problem in her life threatens the stability of her wellbeing in general. Interestingly, using the term ‘stability’ denotes how Leila’s equilibrium depends on how well her life turns. Stability highlights a sense of static flow and positive energy, much like motivation (Dörnyei, 2011). Therefore, when Leila experiences a breakup, it ultimately affects her engagement with her doctoral studies: “(I) experienced a breakup, you won’t be in the mental state of being creative and sitting on a laptop and writing. So it’s the human side of me, the social side of me, absolutely affect academics side of me” (Leila, 19-21, page 30) or “It affected my progress, I was no more thinking about PhD, I was more thinking about that issue” (Leila, 29-30, page 30). From these extracts, Leila underscores the demotivating effect of failed relationships and personal problems. For her, having personal problems occupies all her thoughts and deviates her from performing any kind of academic activity. Subsequently, as her productivity which is a focal component of a motivated person (Dörnyei, 2011) becomes compromised, demotivation prevails. Moreover, she pinpoints that she

cannot think of the PhD in these circumstances and thus highlights the blocking effect of demotivation on human minds.

It is also noteworthy to mention that the placement of some themes is interchangeable, for example, Vegeta experiencing a loss could also be placed under personal, and the same could be applied to John TSH's disease.

Interestingly, some factors that have emerged can be termed as international demotivators. Leila, Oreo, and Liza have their involvements. Starting with Leila on the instability and risks of the journey, especially in case of failure: "your stay here is related to your academic progress, so it's kind of unstable, if you don't make progress, you're deported at any point, and your future is somehow ruined, that's the only feeling that makes me feel bad about being [an]international" (Leila, line 12-17, page 32). This highlights the international demotivating factor of feeling a sense of instability and insecurity in the host country. Leila claims that their stay in the UK is completely contingent on their academic progress and failing to do so puts them at risk of deportation. What is more, Leila mentions that going back to Algeria would ruin her future and would require starting over from scratch. This pinpoints the risky situation Algerians are constantly faced with. The instability of the future, combined with the instability of the situation puts Algerians under a tremendous amount of stress, pressure and thereby only exacerbating their demotivation. Therefore, the passage reflects a sense of demotivation and existential crisis stemming from a fear in case of failure. This factor constitutes a new set of data to be added to the literature. Previous studies have documented many factors faced by international students such as language, culture, and stereotype (Sherry et al., 2010; Desa et al., 2012; Titrek et al., 2016). Nevertheless, a fear of deportation as a demotivating factor for legal students on UK soil has not been extensively reported by the literature.

Oreo's input, on the other hand, concerns a less existential, conditional momentum and a more detail-oriented event. Particularly how she is perceived by UK citizens "living with other people is difficult because they don't really understand the challenge of doing the PhD as an international student, it's overwhelming" (line 23-25, page 15). She further gives reason as to why this is demotivating, particularly lack of understanding: "...they're not really aware because they're not in the field themselves, they're not doing PhD, so they are not going through the same experience. they don't really understand what I'm going through, so they don't really help" (line 28-31, page 15). She adds:

People can be inconsiderate of the challenges faced by international students, I've had flatmates imply that my sponsorship made my experience easier. This induced self-doubt and was demotivating. Doing a PhD as a sponsored student can be stressful and challenging, and hearing such comments can be demotivating. (line 22-32, page 16)

Oreo highlights the lack of understanding from UK citizens and how it leads to demotivation. She mentions instances of assumptions by friends as her being 'sponsored' and how this is supposed to facilitate her life. Because they do not share the same cultural or academic background, they seem to take her case for granted and perceive her as 'spoiled' or 'lucky'. Such a lack of empathy and understanding induces self-doubt and demotivation. The barrier created by this perception puts Oreo in isolation which only furthers her demotivation. The lack of understanding between international and domestic people corroborate with previous studies such as Sherry et al. (2010); Desa et al. (2012); Titrek et al. (2016). Moreover, participants in this case felt alienated which consolidates Strayhorn's (2012, 2019) claim that the lack of belongingness leads to alienation. Being from a different culture and background makes people less intelligible and understanding. UK people, by not having to undergo a PhD in the UK for a limited timeframe cannot comprehend the situation Algerians are put in. Leila stresses the cruciality of succeeding in this endeavour as their lives are at stake, highlighting their distress and predicament despite having a fully-funded scholarship. It is for such reasons that internationals tend to make more connections with people from their culture rather than another. Because the lack of similitude and understanding might lead to a feeling of demotivation which is one of the findings of this research. This might also have to do with the fact of moving to a less collectivist culture where Algerian postgraduates have the need to be around a society that shares similar norms and values in order to feel understood and supported.

One major international demotivating factor faced by Liza in her PhD journey was the unequal treatment based on national origin:

I noticed that students coming from Westernized countries are more valued; even if they're not sponsored, I know that I'm sponsored as an international student and I'm paying three times their tuition fees, but I'm not as valued as they are, I'm not given as much attention as they are because I'm coming from a non-westernized country. (Liza, line 4-9, page 33)

Issues of bias against non-Western students in academia are clearly highlighted. The latter is a great contributor to demotivation and feelings of not being valued or respected as a researcher. Liza claims that despite her paying thrice the amount of tuition fees in comparison to domestic students, she is clearly treated in a different manner because of her being an Algerian student (non-Westernized country). Due to such treatment, Liza finds herself demotivated as she is not valued despite being a laureate back in Algeria.

Liza also experienced discrimination based on her religious beliefs. She felt that her supervisor treated her differently after she started wearing the hijab "Whenever we have a meeting and I'm wearing hijab, I feel like she doesn't even want to listen to me or even look at me in the camera" (Liza, line

20-23, page 34). Another instance was a woman shouting at her outside “*you scared my daughter!*” (Liza, line 14, page 35). Afterwards, Liza reported shock due to the woman using very racial language “she said very ugly words describing me as fully covered and really I was surprised”. Ultimately after a succession of negative experiences, Liza concludes “discrimination exists and full stop” (Liza, Line 16-19, page 35). Finally, Liza raises concerns about safety in the UK, the case was particularly true for her being the only girl in the accommodation and having a traumatic event where the landlord kicked her “the landlord kicks me out and said he has already agreed to give the room to another tenant” (Liza, line 19-20, page 37). These challenges of living in an unfamiliar environment can lead to stress, anxiety, and demotivation.

As a result of the accumulated stress and demotivation, Liza develops health concerns “because of all that stress, I had vasovagal syncope my brain decides to shut out” (Liza, line 23-24, page 37). Upon probing, Liza admits to fainting regularly as a symptom of the disease: “I had vasovagal syncope and arrhythmia as well and I fainted so many times out of sudden, I feel like I'm so energetic and life is good, life is pink and I'm doing everything good and suddenly I just faint I just don't remember what happens” (Liza, line 26-29, page 36). Therefore, just as John, Liza's health deteriorated due to demotivation that stems from international demotivating experiences. Previous studies such as Shery et al. (2010), Desa et al. (2012) and Titrek et al. (2016) have reported additional challenges and struggles that international students face, however, the case of Liza and John appears rather unique in comparison to these studies. The uniqueness resides in developing health concerns at a doctoral level, which appears much more plausible given the psychological distress (Levecque et al., 2017; Hyun et al., 2006). Thus, the present results corroborate with previous studies but also offer crucial elements denoting the severity of international doctoral students due to demotivation.

Moreover, the experiences lived by Liza highlight the unparalleled additional challenges international students face. Unequal treatment from a supervisor, discrimination based on her religious beliefs, and difficulties finding accommodation constitute blatant examples of how challenged they are compared to domestic students. The experiences she faces echoed perfectly with previous studies such as Titrek et al.(2016) and how internationals are challenged. What is unique about Liza's experience is the level of her study (doctoral). Moreover, as there are blatant differences between her host country and country of origin, she experiences what is called acculturative stress:

A marked deterioration of the general health status of an individual; it encompasses physiological, psychological, and social aspects that are explicitly linked to the acculturation process. It is also marked by physical and psychological changes due to the adaptation required in diet, climate, housing, interactional styles, norms and values to a new culture. (Desa et al., 2012, p.364)

The passage reflects Liza’s state adequately as she developed vasovagal syncope and arrhythmia because of demotivation. Due to the unfair treatment and multiple challenges she experienced as an international student in housing such as being the only female and being kicked out, cultural differences and discrimination, she found her physical and mental health deteriorating, leading to the development of a disease that might only add further complexity of her case. Moreover, her lack of inclusion within the scientific or societal community highlights a strong sense of alienation (Strayhorn, 2012, 2019). Subsequently, the present study not only confirms previous endeavours but also adds a layer of originality regarding the severity of international students’ experiences, particularly the demotivating ones.

In summary, GET 1 has enumerated and discussed factors that pertain to External Challenges and Life Events. The section reviewed factors such as Covid, distance and personal life events and how these elements lead to demotivation. Participants shared their stories in detail and seemed to have reflected on the phenomenon upon questioning. Moreover, the section also gave justice to participants who diverged from others in some respects, thus, applying one of the key fundamentals in IPA known as idiography.

II. GET2: Supervisor-Related Issues

GET 2 highlights the importance of academic supervisors in shaping UK Algerian postgraduates’ experiences. The data analysis shows that such a factor is extremely demotivating. For a better illustration, a table has been provided to facilitate understanding:

Table 5: Personal Experiential Themes Relating to Group Experiential Theme 2

Personal Experiential Theme	Stallion	John	Zineb	Manel	Vegeta	Leila	Liza	Oreo
Supervisor-Related Issues	✓	✓		✓		✓	✓	✓

As demonstrated, six participants out of eight highlighted supervisory-related issues as being demotivating. Despite their differences and uniqueness, 75% of the participants narrated stories of such factors as being disengaging, pinpointing the influence of the supervisor on the doctoral journey.

1. Supervisor-Related Challenges

The nature of the student-supervisor relationship determines the academic trajectory to either its success or failure. The results in the present research demonstrate that factors such as the supervisor's departure constitute a huge demotivator in doctoral students' journey. Additionally, the feedback can play a significant role. For example, if the feedback is overly critical or non-constructive,

this will only negate motivation to its dark side (demotivation). Similarly, results reported the supervisor's lack of interest, engagement, communication (or communicative competence), responsiveness, support and guidance as significant demotivating factors.

1.2. Supervisor's Departure

Three participants shared a common demotivating experience related to the supervisor's unexpected departure or change. John, Oreo, and Leila's accounts on the experience are provided. First John states "...one of my supervisors needed to leave for some reasons" (John, 29-30, page 10) the supervisor's departure causes him to feel unstable as he values the latter "...I love stability and then all of a sudden you hear that your supervisor needs to leave...we don't know how things will be, so I was a bit afraid of the unknown" (John, line 4-9, page 12). John describes a demotivating instance related to a supervisor's departure due to personal reasons. This triggered feelings of uncertainty and fear of the unknown as he attributes great value to stability. With his supervisor's departure, his equilibrium and stability have been shaken, paving the way for demotivation to overcome as he does not know how his PhD is going to be with a newly appointed supervisor. From the passages, it seems that John attached an important value to his supervisor, which constitutes part of his motivation to succeed in his doctoral studies. Moreover, the narrative also denotes a fear of abandonment wherein John is left in the dark without the supervisor being the light in the doctoral journey, and fears what might be ahead. Therefore, it highlights the crucial importance of having stable relationships necessary for equilibrium, motivation and academic success.

Similarly, Oreo expresses feelings of demotivation with the sudden departure of her supervisor who represented her main source of support and expertise "...when my supervisor was made redundant...it was really hard, demotivating, maybe the most demotivating factor that happened to me during my journey. I was considering withdrawing" (Oreo, line 1-4, page 26). For Oreo, losing such an important asset was unexpected and so sudden as "...he was the main supervisor and he had the most expertise in the field, so he was the one who did most of the work and he was very supportive..." (Oreo, line 10-12, page 13).

Oreo recalls the demotivating experience of her supervisor's unexpected departure. The lifeworld was, according to her, the most demotivating instance she lived during her whole doctoral journey. Due to that, Oreo was considering withdrawing from the program, thus highlighting the importance of a strong supervisory academic relationship and how such deprivation decreases motivation and commitment to studies. The experience clearly illustrates the great attachment Oreo has to her supervisor and how his departure compromised her equilibrium, reaching points of attrition thinking.

Moreover, Oreo explains why such an issue is demotivating and alarming. She narrates that her supervisor was very knowledgeable and most importantly supportive, indicating how motivating her advisor is to her and her thesis's progress. The emotional loss of losing her supportive supervisor generated feelings of uncertainty concerning her stay at her current institution and whether to join him at his newly established university. Oreo eventually decided to remain at her institution, however, she acknowledges that such a decision was difficult and that she felt demotivated for a considerable amount of time. Therefore, given the optimal and positive relationship with her supervisor, being severely demotivated for a considerable amount of time only seems plausible.

Leila shared her version of supervisory departure and how the latter led to significant changes in her personal, emotional, and psychological state. Leila's supervisor's departure was mainly due to retirement and not redundancy or personal issues as she stresses:

...because my supervisor retired and had new supervisory team, we came up with new ideas, new vision to my study. I had to adapt to their vision and then with time constraints and the contract constraints and my personal experiences that have been through emotional, psychological experiences I've been through, I think four depressions up to now from the start of the PhD. (Leila, line 11-15, page 22)

Leila's account highlights the complexity and interconnectedness of her challenges. She emphasises how adapting to new supervisors and their visions impacted her motivation and progress. Moreover, she reports that the change was made in her mid-3-year of PhD, which is problematic and challenging as at that period, students should enter the final stages (written stage) and the change at that point of time is highly concerning and stressful. Coupled with her contractual obligation of being funded by the Algerian government and having to finish on time otherwise, she might lose job prospects back in Algeria, Leila finds herself struggling with a succession of negative instances due to demotivation. The latter leads to several episodes of depression highlighting the significant impact and the role of the supervisory team not only in academic progress but also the overall wellbeing of international doctoral students. Thus, any supervisory change, minor or major, disrupt significantly the equilibrium of doctoral students and hence their completion time.

The role of the supervisor has been documented extensively as being either a factor in success or failure (Hockey, 1996; Golde and Dore, 2001; Heath, 2002; McApline and Norton, 2006; Ives and Rowley, 2005; Mainhard et al, 2009; Cheon et al, 2009; Halse, 2011; Platow, 2012; Devos et al, 2017; Hardman, 2020). The supervisor's role is critical for doctoral student's personal and professional development. As Lovitts (2001, p.139) states the supervisor "*influences how the student comes to understand the discipline and the roles and responsibilities of academic professionals, their socialization as a teacher and a researcher, the selection of dissertation topic, the quality of the*

dissertation, and subsequent job placement". Therefore, the supervisor has a multitasking position and influences greatly the direction of the doctoral students in various domains such as understanding the area, the academic world and its demands, the quality work of the written report and many more.

Similarly, for John and Oreo mostly, their supervisor represented the epitome of knowledge and facilitated the transition to the academic world. In this case, the supervisor serves as an MKO (More Knowledgeable Other, Vygotsky, 1987) and through their expertise and support offers certainty and relief to these students who are *Tabula rasa* (blank slate) in the scholarly world. By losing such a crucial factor or their light, students remained in the dark and were incapable in processing the situation on their own, leading to feelings of abandonment and demotivation. This demonstrates how important supervisors are in opening the gate for doctoral students and become aspiring/novice researchers.

Previous research has identified reasons leading to the departure of students from the PhD program (Golde, 2005; Bair and Harworth, 2004; Barnes and Austin, 2009). However, the supervisor's unexpected departure as a demotivating factor for international doctoral students emerges as being highly undocumented. Therefore, the current study on the topic of supervisor increased the originality of the present work. As students were highly motivated by their supervisors who offered guidance, stability and positive feedback, the event of losing such an important factor in their doctoral journey only led to experiencing the dark side of motivation which further developed into the intention to withdraw from the program, representing a new avenue of knowledge. Future endeavours are recommended to deeply engage with this potential challenge to international students' wellbeing, notably on factors such as academic continuity, emotional support, institutional resources, and intention to withdraw.

1.3. Supervisor's Feedback

The supervisor's feedback is a double-edged sword. In this research, participants reported instances where the feedback is demotivating and sometimes even traumatising. Starting with Stallion on his visual feedback as a demotivating force:

When I finish the creative work...send it to my supervisor and she returns the work loaded with comments and annotations. That I don't like, it keeps me up at night actually...When I work hard on a critical chapter, and I feel good about it, she returns it to me loaded with comments, loaded with sections that need to be edited, yes then I feel very demotivated. (Stallion, line 21-26, page 10)

Stallion depicts an interesting facet of the written feedback that is visual. According to him, he feels extremely demotivated after performing at his best for a piece of academic work and then the supervisor returns it filled with comments and annotations. He also reports another instance where he

gets demotivated when the piece of work he submits is returned 'red'. The outcome of receiving such feedback prevents him from sleeping, highlighting the severity of the factor on his sleeping schedule and mental health wellbeing. Because Stallion was satisfied after putting effort into the work, and by receiving such a response, the logical answer would be demotivation and even disenchantment. This means that his expectations clashed with reality leading to feel disheartened (Weber, 1948).

This result also corroborates with previous works of Hyun et al. (2006) and Kernan et al. (2011) on how doctoral studies engendered stress leading to sleeplessness and insomnia. Furthermore, as the experience seems to be recurrent, the brain is creating a similar pattern wherein demotivation, stress and anxiety are activated whenever feedback is received. Thus, the feedback activates the demotivation mode that is associated with the amygdala responsible for such emotions, creating a negative loop.

Additionally, Manel offers her perception of feedback on how traumatising and overwhelming as she highlights "when my supervisor(s) send me their comments on the piece of work I've done, I avoid reading them before I go to sleep so that I won't spoil my sleep for that night, I just leave it to spoil my next day" (Manel, line 17-20, page 24). Manel prefers to keep the feedback unread until the next morning to avoid ruining her night. The situation appears different yet similar with Stallion as the outcome is how feedback impacts sleep schedule.

Moreover, Manel denounces how the event leads to a severe emotional reaction. In an instance, she highlights how her first exposure to feedback led to a chain reaction of negative emotions such as overwhelm and intention to withdraw: "...when I received for the first-time comments from my supervisors about my written piece of work, there was a lot of comments. I felt overwhelmed, and "*I cannot do this anymore*", I remember crying..."*I cannot do this! this is too much for me*" (Manel, line 14-18, page 36). The passage denotes the demotivating effect of feedback in her doctoral journey. Manel stresses that the event was so overwhelming that she could not retain her composure and had an emotional meltdown (crying), reaching points of attrition thinking. Thus, the emotional reaction indicates how the feedback impacts students' motivation and wellbeing. Additionally, considering withdrawing is also another indication of the severity of the demotivating event.

Furthermore, Manel perceives the feedback received as being insurmountable (Marguc et al., 2010) leading to feelings of incompetence or self-doubt. The latter is apparent in instances such as "*I cannot do this! this is too much for me*". The overwhelming sensation of feeling unfit or incompetent to achieve the necessary level leads her to consider withdrawing from the program despite being a

laureate in Algeria. Therefore, the perception of criticism seems to have a strong impact on the students' ability causing them to consider leaving the program they were motivated to do initially.

Similarly, Oreo shares patterns of emotional reaction when receiving feedback as she elaborates "...when I receive a feedback where I have to just do a little bit more editing than I expected to, it just feels overwhelming" (Oreo, line 29-31, page 13). Oreo describes a sensation of stress emerging from the apprehension of supervisory meetings, she also reports that if anything exceeds her expectations even by a little, it overwhelms and demotivates her. Thus, Oreo describes the stress and overwhelming sensation from supervisory meetings and the outcome that comes from it.

Finally, Liza illustrates that her lived experience with the supervisory team did not meet her expectations, leading to feelings of disenchantment "...I thought they'll be so motivating, they'll hear my voice, read what I write, provide me with constructive feedback, care about my topic or my project, I think I was too ambitious about that" (Liza, line 31-34, page 8). Moreover, when asked about the reality she highlights "It was 360 degrees different" (Liza, line 2, page 9). The passages reveal a total opposition/dissonance between her expectations and reality. Liza expected to be motivated and engaged, heard, provided with constructive feedback and most importantly that her supervisors would show interest and care about her topic. The latter were, according to her, way too ambitious which denotes that the reality was not as expected. Additionally, she reveals that the reality was 360 degrees different, highlighting that her actual experience was not even remotely close to her aspirations. The experiences of Liza, Oreo, and Stallion echo the work of Weber (1948) on disenchantment wherein the expectation is clashed with the actual reality. Liza aspired and held certain images about her supervisory team which constituted her motivation/magic. Oreo has a limited and strict amount of feedback expected. Stallion has high hopes for a draft he works diligently on. However, upon colliding with reality they found a huge difference which led their world to crumble and "lose its magical significance" (Weber, 1978, p.506), thereby triggering demotivation.

Additionally, Liza declares receiving contradictory and non-informative feedback which demotivates her as it makes her feel neglected:

...the first time was after sending the first chapter to my supervisor, she emailed me and said everything is OK, and go ahead. After two months, she sent "*you need to rewrite the whole chapter, what is that?*" I say, OK, she didn't read it, and she was just telling me everything's OK so that she won't have that burden of correcting me or providing feedback. So that was a disappointment and demotivating moment for me. (Liza, line 7-14, page 20)

Liza illustrates a moment where the supervisor neglected to provide constructive feedback. She recounts an incident when after submission, the supervisor gave her the green light about a certain

piece of work. After a significant time (two months), she retracted her first feedback highlighting that the work needed major revisions, suggesting to Liza that she did not study the piece in the first place. This not only wasted two months of her doctoral journey but also made Liza extremely neglected, disappointed, and most importantly demotivated. Additionally, as she iterates the phrase “the first time was” pinpoints that such instances of receiving non-informative feedback are frequent, which might hint at potential negative long-term effects on her mental health. Finally, the feedback to rewrite the work provided by the supervisor “what is that?” might have shaken Liza’s self-confidence about her abilities, as the tone appears more shocking and guiltig her rather than being constructive. Subsequently, this data demonstrates the prevalence of supervisors and their feedback mediating the doctoral students’ journey as well as their motivational orientation and timely completion.

Interestingly, Liza’s supervisory experience in this section contradicts the foundational work of Wisker (2008) on the key responsibilities of the supervisor. Factors such as ‘to be friendly, open and supportive’ were not found as Liza reports “I thought they’ll be so motivating, they’ll hear my voice”, highlighting her demotivation of not being heard and supported. Moreover, the element of providing constructive feedback (Wisker, 2008, p.40) was lacking as Liza indicates the opposite on multiple occasions (examples above). Therefore, as the supervisor does not offer the necessary and needed attributes and support for students’ motivation and success, the reaction of a letdown or demotivation in this case is a cogent/axiomatic human reaction.

Such recurrent events lead Liza to dismiss the importance of her supervisor. According to her, the feedback is impeding her advancement to thesis completion: “...because previously I felt what was hindering my progress were my supervisor’s comments because she didn’t inform anything in the feedback she was providing” (Liza, line 31-33, page 14). Despite the undisputed importance of the supervisor in previous literature (Hockey, 1996; Golde and Dore, 2001; Heath, 2002; Devos et al, 2017; Hardman, 2020), Liza arrived at a stage where she does not feel the need for a supervisor anymore. The reason is not out of egotism but because she keeps receiving only non-informative feedback and neglection which only harms her self-confidence and motivation to pursue her goal. This presents a new avenue of how impactful the supervisor’s feedback can be. However, what seems interesting is the fact of that her not thinking of attrition, unlike Manel, but rather not needing the supervisory support anymore. This might indicate that Liza still has inner strength to finish the PhD rather than attrition.

In this subsection, participants reported instances of how simple feedback can generate stress and other severe reactions. A common theme among participants is the perception of the supervisor’s

comment and how the latter leads to further impacts. For example, Stallion feels blocked and insomniac after receiving heavily and red annotated hard work. Similarly, Manel procrastinates the reading of comments to avoid spoiling her night acknowledging the emotional impact of feedback. She further adds how the volume of comments overwhelmed her and made her cry. Liza, feeling crushed after receiving initial insurance that her work is fine and after some time receiving the total opposite, coupled with her frustration of how feedback lacks information and direction led her to feel neglected and rebel against her supervisor to the point of not needing them. Lastly, Oreo feels overwhelmed by the amount of editing she needs to do after receiving feedback. Subsequently, the following findings highlight how extensive or unclear feedback leads to demotivation, stress, insomnia and even attrition.

These findings also offer support to Van Rooij et al. (2019) and Maher et al.(2020) concerning how lack of academic support from supervisors leads to attrition. Using regression analysis on results obtained from 839 doctoral students, Van Rooij et al. (2019) found out two aspects of the supervisor drive students to withdraw from the program: lack of academic support and high expectations. Participants who perceived less constructive and supportive feedback more frequently considered withdrawing. Moreover, Maher et al. (2020) reported that problematic relationships with supervisors were the main reason to quit or the last straw to do so. Similar to these, participants in the present study all reported problematic relationships and feedback which led to demotivation and stress. Additionally, some of the participants considered withdrawing due to the overwhelming situation highlighting the alarming stage of the UK Algerian postgraduates. Finally, the present study was able to locate that demotivation is indeed a phase preceding attrition which constitutes a significant contribution, Future studies should channel more interventions and studies to try and resuscitate students' motivation before the irreversible outcome (attrition or suicide).

GET 2 has highlighted supervisory-related issues. The participants narrated their unique experiences regarding the importance of the supervisor and how it affected their motivation and wellbeing. The uniqueness of each story highlights the core principles of IPA known as idiography (Smith et al., 2022). The results shared during the analysis include supervisors' departure, feedback (red, full, non-informative and non-constructive), and behaviour (lack of support, feedback, interest, and treatment). Due to such events, participants felt a significant decline in their engagement towards their respective studies. Moreover, the demotivation stemming from the supervisor made them feel stuck, incapable and incapacitated, unworthy, not smart, and even to consider withdrawing; therefore, highlighting how untreated demotivation is a preceding phase to depression and attrition. The

emerging data suggests creating a better and more supportive environment characterised by a guiding, encouraging and positive supervisory approach.

III. GET 3: Personal and Emotional Factors

GET 3 discusses Personal and Emotional Factors leading to demotivation. This section will review Motivation-Related Factors, Imposter Syndrome and Self-Doubt, and how these factors impede both motivation and ongoing PhD progress. For a better illustration, a table has been provided.

Table 6: Personal Experiential Themes Relating to Group Experiential Theme 3

GET	PETs	Stallion	John	Manel	Vegeta	Liza	Oreo
Personal and Emotional		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Motivation-Related Factors	✓	✓		✓	✓	
	Imposter Syndrome and Self-Doubt			✓			✓

1. Motivation-Related Factors

Motivation-Related Factors encompass inner/internal struggles that lead to demotivation. The results include self-demotivation, loss of motivation, and finding and maintaining motivation. Such results demonstrate the importance of motivation to counter demotivation and how the absence of demotivation is crucial in goal achievement (Christophel and Gorham, 1995).

First, Stallion identifies unproductivity and self-demotivation as his main sources of demotivation. He highlights that lack of progress and productivity lead to negative emotions contributing to demotivation "...unproductivity and the absence of progress, when I'm not progressing as a researcher, as a writer, I don't like that and it's very negative. That's probably the agents that lead to demotivation" (line 27-29, page 9). Stallion attaches significant importance to his progress and productivity. He reports that when he is faced with absence the latter, it generates negative feelings such as demotivation. Stallion does not like being stuck in an unproductive situation/phase. Stallion's dissatisfaction with his current stagnant situation appears to downgrade his mood and motivation. Subsequently, his positivity and motivation are dependent on being productive and the deprivation of such lead to demotivation.

Stallion highlights that productivity is essential to his happiness and motivation and provides sense to his life: "I work 6,7,8 hours a day, and when I worked those hours and produce something, a substantial piece of work, it makes me feel happy, it makes me feel motivated to wake up the next morning and work again" (line, 3-5, page 10). Stallion finds meaning and purpose in his life through

work and progress. His daily worktime duration reveals that he is a creature of habit, and his happiness is contingent with the fact of being productive. Therefore Stallion appears intrinsically motivated (Deci and Ryan, 2016). He describes a day as being successful only if he produces quality work, which constitutes his daily goal (Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2021; Locke and Latham, 1990, 2006) and needs to be achieved in order to sustain motivation to work the next day. However, if these criteria/conditions are not met, Stallion loses purpose in his life and becomes unhappy and demotivated. Therefore, Stallion's experience offers insights into how an international doctoral student's experience is shaped on a daily basis and how unmet goals not only demotivate but also lead to meaninglessness and purposelessness (Seeman, 1959).

Moreover, when Stallion does not meet his productivity goals, he experiences negative emotions and becomes the tool for his own downfall, in other words, he self-demotivates: "I start thinking about this and saying, 'why have I not produced anything today?'" Like somehow, in a sense, I demotivate myself. So productivity is essential in my life, productivity makes me happy, it motivates me" (line, 6-9, page 10). Stallion falls into a state of self-doubt and questions his unproductivity. Self-doubt in this instance echoes the work of Chambers (1993) highlighting how demotivated students lack confidence in their abilities. Nevertheless, the data offers deeper insights into the psyche of Stallion during his demotivational state and therefore introduces an original contribution. His passage reflects a sense of frustration and disappointment when not reaching his goals as these latter offer purpose and motivation to his life. Indeed, Stallion highlights that productivity is not a preferred state or an optional criterion but rather an 'essential' part of his life, highlighting its cruciality in fulfilling his existence. Just as water and food represent the essential elements for survival, Stallion seems to have regarded productivity as an element similar to those in importance. The latter could be justified due to his nature as an international student and that his stay and success depend on his progress and timely PhD completion. Subsequently, Stallion directs into the necessity of productivity not as a higher need in hierarchy, but more as a basic, detrimental and nutritional need for his existence (Maslow, 1954).

Second, John's experience emphasises the cyclical nature and difficulty of overcoming demotivation. He explains that he lost motivation only once, but it led to a "nightmare" that affected his mental health "I lost my motivation, I lost it only once, and now I'm just crawling" (line 27-28, page 12). The latter highlights an interesting and unexpected facet which is the absence of remotivation. Demotivation is a state that should not last permanently and with time regulation, motivation can be restored (Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2011). However, John's case appears to be different as he is unable to return to his prior/initial state of motivation, offering thus a new facet of motivational

direction not to a remotivated state but rather to a loop of negativity and demotivation. The state is illustrated in his adoption of terms such as “nightmare” and “crawling”, highlighting the severity of the impact, difficulty in coping and overcoming, and its long-lasting effect. Furthermore, his state further develops into depression as a result of cyclical demotivation. Subsequently, John represents a case offering new sets of data on demotivational factors and their nature that remained heavily undocumented.

Furthermore, Vegeta’s main concern is finding the motivation to study. He pinpoints the importance of finding purpose and passion in research. Vegeta notes that his main struggle is regaining the incentive and interest in his study, and such absence was his primary demotivating source “The main challenge for me now is finding the motivation to study again, and that's the biggest challenge ever; finding the motivation to study, to work and concentrate” (line 22-23, page 13). Vegeta's experience illustrates how one's intrinsic motivation and passion for research can drive his motivation and prevent demotivation as he states, “I think the one that's blocking me the most is the interest part; motivation part” (Vegeta, line 30, page 29). From Vegeta’s declarations, it seems that another factor emerging in this study is the absence of motivation is demotivating which in a sense parallels and complements Christophel and Gorham (1995) who found that the absence of negative teacher behaviour is more motivating than having positive teacher behaviours. Similarly, Vegeta’s experience underlines that the absence of intrinsic motivation is in itself demotivating therefore offering a new contribution to the phenomenon.

Additionally, Vegeta highlights the importance of intrinsic motivation in finishing the PhD. This corroborates with seminal works of Deci and Ryan (2017) on how intrinsic motivation is essential to adapt to unexpected situations which corresponds perfectly with the PhD journey as it is more of a roller coaster (Cuschieri, 2021). Furthermore, because a PhD is the peak of academic achievements, it requires engagement, hard work and aptitude to take challenges; all of which accord with intrinsic motivation. Moreover, intrinsic motivation is a detrimental factor to academic achievements and timely PhD completion (Froiland and Worrell, 2016; Lindsay, 2015). Thus, Vegeta’s argument for the necessity of internal motivation for PhD success is highly founded in the literature and thus represents a cogent argument in the literary debate.

Finally, Liza’s experience highlights the importance of time management in maintaining motivation. She notes that feeling behind schedule and missing deadlines can significantly demotivate her as she states: “If you hear that you’re quite a bit behind and everyone has passed the upgrade and even in your department, you’re the only one, literally this is demotivating” (line 3-5, page 18).

Additionally, she notes that exceeding the expected deadline and requesting an extension significantly contributed to her demotivation "...a second time was missing the time for the upgrade, and I had to ask for an extension that was a demotivating factor for me because I keep reminding myself that I was a valedictorian student, I wasn't the one I am now" (line 14-18, page 20). Liza admits how missing important PhD milestones lead to demotivation. During her PhD, Liza reports a demotivating event upon missing her upgrade. Both her situation and condition worsened as she reluctantly requested an extension which landed a substantial blow to her credibility and status. As a 'valedictorian' student, Liza seems to hold the title in high esteem. However, during the interview, Liza admits to her not being the same academic that she was, highlighting a significant shift in her identity. The latter coincides with Seeman's (1959) self-estrangement where individuals are unable to recognise themselves or self-realisation failure (Seeman, 1979, p.16). Liza, upon her demotivating experience, fails to realise who she is and faces troubles in identity (Brennan and Auslander, 1979). Thus, in this case, Liza is demotivated from the events and as a result finds herself struggling with alienation issues.

It can be safely assumed that her regression is due to demotivation. Her current condition perfectly reflects the standard definition of demotivation. Dörnyei and Ushioda (2021) define demotivation as the decrease or neutralisation of positive behaviours. Similarly, Liza who is a valedictorian student at a prestigious university seems to have her positive attributes neutralised due to encountered life events. As a result, the demotivation lived by Liza pulls her down and damages her aspirations and goals (Kikuchi, 2015). Subsequently, drawing from the present data, coupled with previous corroborated literature, demotivation could be regarded as a negative phase responsible for transitioning or shifting the most motivated and intelligent individuals into a regressed form unable to achieve the originally set goals.

This section has disseminated the motivation-related factors responsible for demotivation. Although the outcome is the same, the triggering elements vary across participants. While Stallion and Liza for example emphasise the necessity of having progress and good time management to promote a fulfilling life that fuels and sustains motivation, others like John highlight how true drive once lost cannot be always restored, thus perpetuating an endless loop of demotivation. Finally, Vegeta's experience reports the cruciality of having intrinsic motivation in a project and how the absence and loss of passion and interest only fuel demotivation.

2. Imposter Syndrome and Self-Doubt

In this subsection, two emerging demotivating factors from the data will be discussed notably imposter syndrome and self-doubt. Both Manel and Oreo have experienced such internal demotivators

leading to decreased mental health wellbeing. To begin with, Manel experiences mixed feelings and waves of intrusive thoughts that lead to imposter syndrome and self-doubt. This drives her to question her abilities and whether she belongs to the world of academia:

Everyone is smarter, everyone is better, and you're just afraid of even saying anything to not sound stupid in front of everybody else...just feel like 'no, this is not for me, I'm not good enough,' 'my presence here just a fluke,' 'I've just been here because I've been lucky.' and this makes me doubt my decision. (Manel, line 19-22, page 28-29)

Despite being a laureate, Manel during her journey seems to have grappled with instances of imposter syndrome and self-doubt. This is reflected when noting that 'everyone is smarter' and 'better', by excluding herself, we can assume that she is not within the described population. Moreover, she seems to be constantly on her guard and 'afraid' avoiding any utterances otherwise she might appear as 'stupid'. Furthermore, she attributes her actual presence within the academic community to pure 'luck' and feels that she does not belong there ultimately doubting her own decisions.

Next, Oreo highlights how she struggles with imposter syndrome as the latter is kept within herself stating "with the imposter syndrome, it's really stressful, it's really overwhelming because I keep that in myself" (Oreo, line 38-40, page 17). Oreo reports how feelings of imposter generate stress and overwhelm, leading to feelings of demotivation. Additionally, keeping such feelings imprisoned within one's self only worsens the situation, which can be illustrated as a sense of isolation and internalisation. By not expressing such feelings to colleagues or professionals, Oreo finds herself with recurrent feelings of inadequacy and thoughts of imposter unable to break free from them. The reason as why Oreo does not seem to share might be attributed to shame or embarrassment.

Finally, clear-cut evidence of Oreo's imposter phenomenon is questioning her abilities. She went through thought processes of self-interrogation and wondering whether she possessed the necessary toolkits to success "sometimes I just feel that I am not equipped to deal with this or not cut out for this kind of career" (line 32, page 12-13). This demonstrates that she goes through phases of self-doubt and feelings of imposter towards her abilities as a researcher and questioning if she chooses the appropriate path. This kind of reflective thinking adds a layer of richness to the phenomenon of demotivation as previous research dealt with children who cannot reflect deeply on their lifeworld (Chambers, 1993).

PhD students are faced with numerous mental health-related challenges (Levecque et al., 2017; Hyun et al., 2006; Cornwall et al., 2019; Mulligan et al., 2021). Imposter syndrome is one of the mental health challenges that despite being highly common is still scarce within the literature. This phenomenon is a condition where people who achieve goals and succeed in getting important positions

ascribe their attainment to pure luck or fluke rather than hard work and academic prowess (Bothello and Roulet, 2019). Imposter syndrome induces fear of being exposed as a charlatan or a con and that they are not as intelligent as the rest of the people holding the position (Leonhardt, 2017). Echoing with that, both Manel and Oreo expressed similar feelings of inadequacy and the fact that ‘everyone is smart’, ‘better’, ‘I’m not good enough’, ‘my presence here just a fluke’, ‘I’ve just been here because I’ve been lucky’ or ‘I am not cut for this career’ illustrate perfectly the imposter syndrome as explicated by Bothello and Roulet (2019) and Leonhardt (2017). The feelings of the imposter in this case served as a negative instance fuelling demotivation. Previous literature has documented the phenomenon, however, very scarce literature linked the phenomenon to induce demotivation highlighting a significant contribution to the current demotivation debate. Therefore, the present IPA study offers new insights into the phenomenon by enriching its demotives through both internal and external factors.

Overall, these experiences highlighted the internal factors that lead to demotivation. Participants in this category reported instances of self-doubt and imposter syndrome responsible for the decline in motivation and its transformation. The particularity of these factors is that they are concealed and could not be detected without the respondents vocalising them. The latter posits some dangers to these people as not exteriorising such factors might lead to a perpetual negative loop that only harms the individual in the long-term. Consequently, supervisors, wellbeing services, and institutions should encourage students to voice their concerns at an early stage of their PhD before developing into more severe and irreversible states.

GET 3 sheds light on the personal and emotional factors that lead to demotivation among Algerian UK postgraduate students pursuing a PhD. The themes related to this GET were Motivation-related aspects, imposter syndrome and self-doubt. By examining the experiences of demotivation through the participant’s lenses, a better understanding of the intricate and multi-layered phenomenon is obtained. The particularity of this section resides in its type of factors, specifically intrinsic. Indeed most factors that emerged in this section are from an internal side, highlighting how fluctuating their self-image and confidence wavers during the PhD journey. More importantly, these emerged from laureates, highlighting the existence of such inner battles even within the mostly intellectual community. Subsequently, providing adequate support and continuing *suivie* is of detrimental importance to the completion of the project as the most important part of the PhD thesis is the researcher’s wellbeing and state.

Summary

To conclude, this chapter addressed the demotivating factors of UK Algerian postgraduate experience in their PhD journey. The analysis of the participants' PETs led to the identification of three main themes or GETs. These themes were External Challenges and Life Events, Supervisor-Related Issues, and Personal and Emotional Factors. These factors demonstrated how strong-willed and dedicated aspiring researchers can fall into the influence of demotivation by having issues with the supervisor or isolation from family. It is important to acknowledge and raise awareness of such predicaments as this research demonstrated how demotivation can severely impact not only PhD progress, but also their mental health wellbeing leading to anxiety, stress, existential questioning, and depression. It is imperative that for the sake of future international students, these elements should be studied thoroughly in order to offer the best possible solution to effectively reduce negativity and re-engage students into their research. Potent strategies to counter demotivation include offering specialized support services, improving supervisor-student communication, and promoting mental health and well-being initiatives.

Chapter VII. Inner World of Demotivation

Introduction

The present chapter outlines the feelings and thought processes experienced by UK Algerian postgraduates. The umbrella term ‘inner world’ has been utilised as it designates internalised feelings and cognitive patterns, both conscious and unconscious (Rogers, 1951; Beck et al., 1979). Therefore, this chapter is divided into two main sections with subsequent subdivisions. This part of the thesis offers an extensive and exhaustive analytical presentation, interpretation and discussion of the phenomenon of demotivation that remains heavily understudied for a significant period of time. The aim is not only to contribute to the scientific debate on demotivation but also to highlight specificities pertaining to Algerian doctoral students while navigating their journey. The objective behind this phenomenological enquiry is to gain insights that would inform and improve future pedagogical approaches, policy making, and research on overall postgraduate studies.

Classifying the Participants

Before exploring the symptomology of demotivation as felt by the participants, a classification system has been developed and provided. This ‘Demotivation Spectrum’ provides a clearer picture and situates each participant’s level of severity of the lived phenomenon/demotivation from mild to extreme.

Figure 4: Participants’ Demotivational Spectrum: Degrees of Demotivation in UK Algerian Postgraduates.

As displayed, Liza has the most severe symptoms of demotivation reaching points of attrition thinking and suicide contemplation. As such reactions denote a sense of urgency, she was placed near the red colour. At the other end of the spectrum, Stallion with the least severe reaction, displays symptoms of avoidance and isolation. Although Stallion’s reactions are substantially milder, it does not necessarily imply a lack of demotivation but raises possibilities of denial or avoidance in facing or acknowledging such experiences. Thus, this framework offers a thorough comprehension of the diverse levels of demotivation that remained largely uncharted until now. After delineating this spectrum, this chapter moves into the first part of the analysis and discussion labelled as *feelings*.

1. Feelings

This section presents and discusses the IPA findings in relation to the feelings associated with demotivation. As per the introduction, the inner world chapter is divided into two sections to facilitate the understanding of the symptomology of demotivation. Upon analysis, the GETs associated with feelings are sixfold. These are illustrated below through a table offering further illumination by showcasing the different PETs that contribute to its formation along with an elaboration.

Table 7: Feelings Associated with Demotivation

GETs of Feelings	Personal Experiential Themes
<p>GET 1. The Dissipation of Enthusiasm: An Exploration of Diminished Motivation and Energy</p> <p><i>GET 1 is related to participants having their motivation lost or dissipated. Participants under this category lost the drive that was once their reason to undertake the PhD in the first place.</i></p>	<p>Stallion: Exhausted battery, losing interest in the work. Manel: Lack of motivation and drive. Vegeta: Lack of drive, debilitation. Oreo: Exhaustiveness and burnout, distraction and avoiding academic activities.</p>
<p>GET 2. Alone in the Crowd: The Multifaceted Experiences of Social Isolation, Avoidance, and Cultural Dislocation</p> <p><i>GET 2 highlights symptoms of demotivation related to isolating one's self due to the heavy toll experienced. It encompasses feelings of emptiness, worthlessness, isolation and distraction.</i></p>	<p>Stallion: Avoid meeting people/socialize less. John: Emptiness, feeling of worthlessness, Isolation, and emptiness. Zineb: Alienation and cultural shock. Liza: Isolation and avoidance of social interaction.</p>
<p>GET 3. Mirror of Doubt: Unravelling Negative Self-Perception and Imposter Syndrome</p> <p><i>GET 3 highlights instances that attack someone's self-image. Demotivated students in this case/category display and report feelings of self-hatred, low self-esteem, self-doubt, feelings of inadequacy and imposter syndrome.</i></p>	<p>John: Self-hatred and low self-esteem, Self-doubt and imposter syndrome, Overthinking, and self-doubt. Zineb: Self-doubt and guilt. Manel: Feeling of inadequacy. Vegeta: Imposter syndrome. Liza: Self-doubt and imposter syndrome. Oreo: Imposter syndrome.</p>

<p>GET 4. Tidal Waves of Emotion: Navigating Overwhelming Emotions</p> <p><i>GET 4 emphasises the mental health toll demotivated students experience. As demotivation decreases their ability to fully function, elements declining their mental health prevail such as exhaustiveness, feelings of drowning, overwhelm, and panic attacks.</i></p>	<p>Zineb: Feeling drowning in the ocean. Manel: Stress overwhelmed and panicked, Negative impact on mental health, including panic attacks and nightmares, sleep disruption and exhaustions. Leila: Overwhelming burden leading to boredom.</p>
<p>GET 5. Unshackling Self: The Intricate Dance of Autonomy, Guilt, and Regret</p> <p><i>GET 5 highlights feelings of guilt and regret as a symptom of demotivation. The interplay between these two factors prevents students from assessing their situation and acting in their best interest. Consequently, their overall wellbeing and thesis progression are compromised.</i></p>	<p>John: Cycle of regret and self-blame, regret for not being productive, Periodic resonance. Zineb: Overwhelmed by the price of being autonomous and away from home (homesickness), Being/feeling trapped in a negative ‘bubble;’ Self-doubt and guilt. Manel: Stress, guilt, overwhelmed and panicked. Vegeta: Regret and guilt. Leila: Sense of guilt. Oreo: Feelings of guilt.</p>
<p>GET 6. Shadows of Insecurity: The Shared Experience of Fear and Uncertainty</p> <p><i>GET 6 encompasses feelings of drastic emotional change, worry, self-doubt, uncertainty and fear of failure in the PhD due to demotivation.</i></p>	<p>John: Emotional change, transition/shift from being active, happy, and satisfied to being passive and unsatisfied. Leila: Worry and uncertainty. Oreo: Fear of failure.</p>

1.1. The Dissipation of Enthusiasm: An Exploration of Diminished Motivation and Energy

GET 1 highlights demotivated symptoms characterised by declined motivated behaviours and energy levels. These are reported through the participant’s own voices to illustrate the shift.

First, Stallion expresses how he experiences a demotivating day, describing it as strenuous “...it’s a tiring day when I’m demotivated, my day tires me, I lose focus, energy, I tend to sleep a lot during the day of demotivation” (Stallion, line 5-6, page 18). Stallion reports feeling drained and empty of energy when he is demotivated. He also highlights how he loses his focus to undertake his PhD and is subject to sleeping a lot, which demonstrates the debilitating impact of demotivation. Moreover, Stallion uses different metaphors to describe his state. During the interview, he often describes himself as an ‘empty

battery' which captures how demotivation drains his energy levels. He further adds that due to such a low level, he cannot fully function which is pinpointed in the following "I have no energy...no wish to work, no wish to produce, I'm just very, very exhausted and spent like a battery, like an old, tired battery" (Stallion, line 3-5, page 17) or "I'm practically an exhausted battery when demotivated" (Stallion, line 22, page 16). These passages provide a hint into how Stallion changes from a motivated and energetic individual to a completely tired version of himself looking to sleep and avoid work. It highlights the depleting effect of demotivation on energy reservoirs. This imagery, provided by Stallion, demonstrates the utility and suitability of IPA in collecting deeper experiential features of the ill-documented phenomenon that is demotivation.

Stallion's provided imagery encapsulates perfectly the overall phenomenon/definition of demotivation. As the latter is known to switch off motivated behaviours (Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2021). However, an interesting addition is the fact that Stallion reports that demotivation not only deprives him of his motivation but also constantly drains his energy, focus and productivity. Thus, what Stallion offers is a relatively new understanding of demotivation. Rather than switching the positive qualities into their negative counterparts, demotivation continuously drains Stallion from his motivation and other positive attributes such as productivity and energy. From the interpretation, the latter is not a mere switch to the dark side, but rather a perpetual depletion of the positive reservoirs. Such deep and detailed description is a testimony regarding the dangers of demotivation not only at doctoral level but in life in general. Doctoral students need a healthy mental state to fully operate within the doctoral field (Kernan et al., 2011) and leaving demotivation unsolved and unchecked appears to cause a decline in mental health leading to exhaustion and burnout which indicate an earlier sign of depression.

In addition to losing the energy to undertake the work or 'energy depletion'. Stallion finds himself losing interest in his aspiration (the PhD). Raising such a case is important as he was the most motivated and dedicated interviewee. He highlights "I lose interest in my work...I don't like it because I'm aware of it. I'm aware that I'm experiencing it, and it's terrible" (Stallion, line 22-25, page 16). The passage demonstrates how Stallion becomes disinterested in his work, echoing the description of Kikuchi (2015) on the pulling down force of demotivation. Stallion who has the dedication and management skills for his PhD, finds himself losing the sparkle that ignited his desire to obtain it. The latter also coincides with Chambers (1993) on how demotivated students become disengaged or in this case, disinterested. Finally, Stallion's case worsens as he seems to be fully aware of his disinterest which according to him is a "terrible" feeling. Stallion provides multi-layered experiential features of demotivation that were not fully documented in past studies. While Kikuchi (2015, p.4) describes

demotivation as a force that 'pulls the learner down', there was no recollection of learners being lucid and fully aware to experience the pain of demotivation, hence adding variables in the magnitude of the demotivation's equation. The latter hence constitutes a new addition to the experience that is demotivation obtained through IPA.

Finally, Stallion seems to avoid his PhD duties during demotivation. He stresses "I tend to stay away from my work, I don't switch on my computer...I don't think about the work. I feel drained, devoid of energy, empty of words. For a writer, which is terrible to grow tired of words" (Stallion, line 34-37, page 19). What Stallion confesses is a side of himself that is an estranged version that he was unaware of existing. Despite having a regular schedule of waking up early, heading to the office, and producing a piece of work, Stallion in the demotivated phase, finds himself avoiding starting his computer, feeling exhausted and depleted. This level of avoidance that stems from demotivation is similar to feelings of repulsiveness. Additionally, he further states that he loses his inspiration to produce words which according to him is a terrible experience to live as a creative writer.

Overall, Stallion's experience represents and illustrates the impact of demotivation; which deviates a student from being motivated, focused and productive to a disinterested, depleted and unproductive pupil. The retreat from his research reaching points of physical avoidance highlights the harmful impact of demotivation on PhD students' lives. This corroborates with the works of Chambers (1993) and Dörnyei and Ushioda (2011, 2021) on the fact that demotivation blocks the positive attributes and stops students from displaying their highest levels of performance. Subsequently, this experience stresses the need to elaborate effective strategies to counteract demotivation while it is still in its preliminary stages as it leads to total negative attributes that only obstruct PhD achievement.

Similar to Stallion, Manel's demotivation is characterised by diminished energy and motivation. However, in addition to work avoidance, she experiences a change of heart or loss of value in the initial goal as she stresses "it's like not wanting to work and feeling that what I am doing isn't suitable for me. It's like feeling that you've no urge or will to carry on what you've been doing and not seeing any use in doing the thing that you're demotivated about" (Manel, line 25-28, page 47). Demotivation seems to have deprived Manel of her initial attributed value and renders her completely disinterested in the PhD. Her response opposes her initial aspiration to undertake the doctorate. Not only Manel lost the will to undertake the regular research sessions 'not wanting to work' but also seems to have lost the core of what drove her in the first place 'not seeing any use'. The latter illuminates how demotivation hindrance to students' progress. Therefore, demotivation deprived both the energy to undertake the endeavour and the initial value attached.

Furthermore, Manel offers an exhaustive response denoting the powerful effect of demotivation on her desire to work and how the latter gets suppressed. As she describes:

You don't feel the urge to switch on your laptop and start writing. You do anything except what you're supposed to, there's no reason, no encouragement, no will to carry on. It's waking up and not wanting to do anything PhD-related, just distracting yourself with things like watching TV, eating, or going out. (Manel, line 1–9, page 49)

The experience raised in this passage coincides with Stallion's on how demotivation depletes his energy level. However, Manel adds one aspect of demotivational symptoms which is a distraction. Indeed, she depicts having struggles with demotivation and battles for purpose. She describes a sense of disinterest and reluctance to undertake her PhD studies, despite having a moral duty towards it. Although such endeavour was her whole motivation to relocate to the UK, she finds herself battling to reignite and find the purpose she lost due to demotivation. This data supports and corroborates Seeman's (1959) meaninglessness and purposelessness dimensions, where workers do not find any meaning and purpose behind the product of their labour. Similarly, Manel, under the influence of demotivation, lost purpose towards undertaking her PhD. Consequently, this leads to a behavioural shift. This underlines any activity besides her PhD such as 'watching TV', 'eating' and 'going out' which perfectly describes distraction. Thus, demotivation is a state that brings all the important activities to a halt, it also directs all the attention to activities other than studies. This reinforces the notion that demotivation is a critical issue that must be addressed to promote academic engagement and progress among postgraduate students.

Vegeta highlights a sense of debilitation during demotivation. He expresses being submerged with a multitude of negative feelings that impede his motivation "...my feelings during demotivation are generally a whole bunch of negative feelings; mainly lack of drive, by drive I mean the will to execute, not to think...I would call it executive dysfunction" (Vegeta, line 26-29, page 46). He further adds "I feel completely debilitated, so I lack the will to act upon my knowledge, that's how I would describe my demotivation" (Vegeta, line 32-33, page 46). Vegeta makes a distinction between intellectual prowess and execution. In this case, the issue he highlights is not a lack of knowledge, criticality or a higher level of thinking, but rather a distinct lack of action. He appears unable or incapacitated to take action or lacks 'the will to execute' upon his knowledge, which demonstrates the debilitating effect of demotivation.

This process of being unable to execute actions despite knowledge has been termed by Vegeta as 'executive dysfunction' underlining the paralysing effect of demotivation. Previous studies such as Chambers (1993) and Dörnyei and Ushioda (2011, 2021) have highlighted a few elements of

demotivated students, such as a lack of confidence and self-esteem. However, there were no instances of extensive narratives that permit a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon due to the methodology employed and the participants involved, unlike the present study. Executive Dysfunction as a symptom of demotivation has not yet been documented, thus such new terminology contributes to demotivation literature by offering more information and details into how this phenomenon operates and what the symptoms that its victims display. Subsequently, this shows how dedicated and intelligent laureates get swallowed by the dark side of motivation, rendering them unable to even use their knowledge to achieve their goals, which again demonstrates the severity of the phenomenon that was taken lightly in this context for years. Therefore, more attention and strategies to remotivate IDS should be undertaken as this only leads to negative outcomes if not treated.

Lastly, Oreo highlights feelings of exhaustiveness and burnout and narrates a full cycle of demotivational experience:

when I'm demotivated, I feel like I don't want to get out of bed... it's really stressful because I feel guilty about not being productive, about being demotivated, but at the same time I can't help being demotivated, so I don't feel like doing anything at all, especially academia and I think I flee demotivation by doing other things like watching series, cleaning, baking, cooking, folding laundry...(Oreo, 18-24, page 20)

Similar to Vegeta, Oreo narrates the paralysing effect of demotivation. However, the magnitude of the toll seemed stronger as she could not get out of bed to undertake her daily tasks. This demonstrates the profound impact demotivation instils in people's lives that extends beyond academic projects. Moreover, due to inactivity and lack of achievement of small goals, Oreo finds herself feeling guilty about being unproductive. The latter also indicates an internal struggle she faces when being demotivated. Nonetheless, she stresses that she cannot help herself when being demotivated as it seems to have paralysed and incapacitated her, which resembles a comatose state where the only activity remaining is brain activity. Finally, to fill the gap and the moral voice that compels her to undertake her PhD duties, Oreo pinpoints acts of evasion and distraction schemes to fill her thoughts and silence her inner voice of guilt. Examples are housework such as cleaning, cooking, and watching TV which echoes Manel and Stallion's avoidance and distraction altogether. This underscores how prolonged academic pressures can lead to demotivation which in turn seems to nullify all the necessary efforts and diligence necessary to PhD completion. The escapism as a symptom adds logic to the characteristics of demotivated students as these students fall into the danger zones of motivation (Dörnyei, 2011), yet the literature on such debate remains heavily undocumented. Thus, the present IPA study considerably illuminates the phenomenon that remained in the dark.

This subsection explored the symptoms of demotivation related to the dissipation of enthusiasm. The demotivated symptoms included elements such as lack of drive, disinterest in the work, disconnection from PhD, loss of value (purposelessness), executive dysfunction, physical exhaustion and evasion strategies. The results show that demotivation is a danger zone that prevents students not only from achieving their goals but also from undertaking their daily activities.

1.2. Alone in the Crowd: The Multifaceted Experiences of Social Isolation, Avoidance, and Cultural Dislocation

This section disseminates characteristics of demotivation related to lack of socialisation, emptiness, alienation and self-imposed isolation.

Stallion's demotivational symptoms exhibit forms of social isolation and avoidance. The whole theme in this category revolved around this excerpt "I avoid meeting people, I socialise less" (Stallion, line 22, page 16). The latter denotes withdrawal from social activities and might be indicative of shielding himself and his emotional state or saving and conserving what is left of his exhausted battery. The coping mechanism resulting from feeling demotivated can potentially lead to feelings of loneliness and isolation which only exacerbate the current state thereby exemplifying how individuals act in a demotivated state.

Similarly yet differently, John expresses feelings of isolation paired with worthlessness and emptiness. This is observed and reported in multiple instances such as "that feeling just kills you, then at the end there was just emptiness" (John, line 7-8, page 22). During demotivation, John describes feeling empty because of his lack of productivity and negative self-image. John considers his life to be fulfilling and meaningful only if the day is filled with productivity; a trait of motivated students (Dörnyei, 1998; Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2021). In this vein, demotivation and unproductivity parallel motivation and productivity. As John loses his motivation and will to produce, he finds himself unable to pursue and accomplish his daily goals, the resulting emptiness becomes a logical consequence of demotivation.

Moreover, he reports how emptiness as a feeling makes his life harder "I was feeling empty, even now sometimes I go through these phases from time to time...it was a hard period of my life, it wasn't an easy one" (John, line 7-9, page 22). John acknowledges that demotivation as a period was of great challenge to him as feelings of emptiness were not pleasant and helpful. Additionally, the occurrence of such feelings seems to be repetitive and not a one-time occurrence "from time to time", indicating the frequency and regularity of the feeling. Demotivation is a threat not only to academic progress but also to wellbeing as it leads to feelings of emptiness and helplessness. The latter aligns with Kikuchi

(2015) on how demotivation is a negative force that pulls the learner down. However, there were no instances where participants shared their stories with such a level of detail. Additionally, demotivation and emptiness were not found in doctoral studies, highlighting another substantial contribution to the field. Therefore, the latter shows how demotivation is a threat to doctoral students and therefore needs more attention in the future.

Zineb's experience adds an intercultural aspect to the GET, highlighting a sense of alienation and cultural shock. This was first apparent during her relocation "when I'm demotivated, I don't want to do anything...I noticed that during my first five months here in the UK, it was like the first contact with the culture the society, and the feeling homesick, cultural shocks like a whole lot of things". (Zineb, line 22-28, page 44). In addition to feeling disconnected from the PhD duties, which indicates a demotivational symptom of unproductivity and converging with other participants, Zineb links her experience to cultural shock, disorientation and homesickness. Her feeling of demotivation seems to have made her aware of how lonely she is and how far she is from her home country. Additionally, the cultural differences also magnify the feelings of alienation and thus lead to seclusion and isolation. Such cultural differences might also relate to the nature of relocating to a less collectivist country. Zineb who lived a significant portion of her life in Algeria seems to have faced different challenges that relate to her host country such as homesickness (missing family, friends and societal gatherings) and cultural shock (finding blatant differences in norms which represent the core of someone's shaped identity. The latter was also highlighted in her disenchanting experience).

An interesting imagery provided by Zineb in this account is her isolation holding her in a bubble. Indeed, Zineb describes a sense of isolation that makes her feel that she is 'trapped in a bubble' (Zineb, line 5-8, page 46). This imagery provides an understanding that when Zineb is demotivated, she is in a way, imprisoned in a bubble of isolation, unable to connect with others; leading to a sense of alienation. This metaphor 'trapped in a bubble' provides a new understanding of how demotivation isolates PhD students. The 'bubble' not only dismissed her positive attitudes and actions towards goal completion but also confined her from contact with society. Thus, demotivation not only has the ability to incapacitate students from reaching their goals (Dörnyei, 1994) but also seems to hinder the chances for interaction, which could benefit her.

Similarly, Liza's experiences underscored the aspect of self-imposed isolation and avoidance of social interaction when demotivated as she pinpoints: "I don't want to talk to any person, I keep the struggle inside of me and I don't want to share with anyone, I don't want to put any burden or create any problems to any other person, that's why I want to stay in my own bubble" (Liza, line 15-26, page

41). Interestingly, Liza used the same imagery Zineb did, which is being inside a ‘bubble’. Liza’s responses might suggest plain isolation that resembles Stallion’s or Zineb’s. However, the reason behind such isolation is unique, highlighting the idiographic element captured through IPA (Smith et al., 2022). Her self-imposed isolation is mainly due to avoid burdening anyone with her issues. Additionally, Liza reports that telling her parents or husband will only result in more worries, which is why she abstains. Therefore, she chooses to remain isolated in her own ‘bubble’. During periods of demotivation, Liza prioritises staying alone and secludes herself from the rest of the world. Therefore, such a passage might conclude that Liza prefers to stay in her ‘iron cage of demotivation’. The cage is not indicative of thought processes that are imprisoning her, but rather her being the one imprisoning herself willingly. Although the keyword is inspired by Weber (1948), the difference is in terms of physicality, subsequently offering new nuances to be added to the phenomenon.

Furthermore, Liza’s degree of self-imposed isolation reaches the point of refusing to attend social events. She declares “I would opt for 'no' whenever I get invited to an event. I prefer to be isolated, staying alone at home, not talking, not watching, not doing any activity. I don't even want to see people moving around because it triggers me a lot” (Liza, line 14-18, page 47). Liza’s sense of isolation extends beyond mere conventional terms as she reports declining any type of socialisation as a result of demotivation. In the extract, she reports secluding herself from any contact with the outside world by rejecting invitations to social events as she prefers to remain isolated. Additionally, she seems to avoid any normal daily tasks such as ‘talking’, ‘watching’ or any type of ‘activity’, highlighting the dangerousness of demotivation in her personality. The latter might heighten her sense of demotivation as being distracted keeps the mind from processing the negative thoughts. Finally, Liza states that the simple fact of seeing people moving around triggers her which highlights a sensitive or short-tempered mood. These experiences offer new insights into the phenomenon of demotivation as what Liza is exhibiting is related to what is known as social anxiety disorder and avoidant personality traits. The phenomenon is closely related to isolation from Seeman’s (1959) alienating dimensions, and previous studies on how international students are isolated such as (Titrek et al., 2016). Liza, in this context, seems to be isolated from the world of academia and society as a result of demotivation, bringing confirmation to one of the subsequent hypotheses in the literature. However, an imminent originality resides in the fact that after the isolation, Liza tends not to find solutions, rather she voluntarily isolates herself in a cage (Weber, 1948) which could be either a coping mechanism or a self-sabotaging technique as a result of self-defeatism of demotivation.

This subsection highlighted originality pertaining to the social aspect of demotivated PhD students. The results reviewed include decreased socialisation, cultural dislocation, alienation, worthlessness

and self-imposed isolation. While some participants such as Stallion and Liza withdraw from social participation and confine themselves, others like John confront their feelings leading to worthlessness and emptiness. The variations of the lived phenomenon highlight the idiographic nature of the participants (Smith et al., 2022).

1.3. Mirror of Doubt: Unravelling Negative Self-Perception and Imposter Syndrome

Demotivation deprives individuals of their optimal selves. As a result, individuals showcase instances of decreased self-image and imposter syndrome. The following subsection delineates how demotivation turns motivated and positive individuals into vessels of negativity and self-doubt.

To begin with, John expresses feelings of self-hatred and low self-esteem when demotivated. Interestingly, his self-hatred reaches the point of avoiding seeing himself in the mirror: "...I hated myself, I couldn't even see myself in front of a mirror, I wasn't proud of myself, I didn't like the fact that I wasn't productive, I wasn't studying as hard as I was studying before, then I had that feeling of regret, like 'why am I not studying?'" (John, line 3-6, page 22). This excerpt provides the complex inner battles demotivated students go through and how the latter leads to exacerbated negative feelings/states. John feels self-hatred and regret as he was not productive. However, what is noteworthy is the fact that John could not bear to see his reflection in the mirror, highlighting the gravity of his demotivation. John pinpoints his disgust towards the product he looks into (the product of demotivation) which aligns with what Seeman (1959) terms as self-estrangement, denoting feelings of unrecognising. Thus, John's data corroborates with Seeman's socio-psychological dimensions of alienation. Nevertheless, the difference lies in the degree and the severity of change reaching levels of repulsiveness. Moreover, John questions the sudden change in his work ethic, diligence and productivity as they decreased in a significant manner. The excerpt is a clear indication of how demotivation leads to a sense of negative self-perception (self-hatred and low self-esteem) rendering students into vessels of doubt in their forte.

This data adds a layer of strength to the previously established study of demotivation by Chambers (1993) on how demotivated students lack self-confidence and self-esteem. In this context, John displays tendencies of low self-esteem emerging from his demotivation, However, John provides a new avenue by indicating how demotivation leads him to feel hatred towards himself. The act of having such negative perceptions and negative inner voice is known as self-deprecation (Speer, 2019). John, within this scope, belittles himself and diminishes his achievement through harsh inner comments portraying hatred and disgust. These thoughts that emerge from John's responses align also with Owen et al. (2006). Similitudes between them are noticed in comments such as "I hate myself"

(John) and “I am no good at all” (Owen et al., 2006, p.61). Self-deprecation is usually associated with anxiety and depression (Owen et al., 2006), elements which are already expressed and narrated by the participant. As demotivation is a state particularly resembling these two mental health conditions, it stands to reason that individuals experiencing demotivation may also exhibit self-deprecating tendencies as these emerged during the interviews. Because participants feel incapacitated or unable to perform at their best, this leads to self-deprecating feelings just as John displayed on his self-image. Subsequently, this study not only corroborates with past scholarly endeavours but also provides more detail into the phenomenon, thus enriching its scope.

Self-doubt and imposter syndrome were also highly reported symptoms of demotivation. In this part, participants were submerged with feelings of inadequacy and whether they were deserving of their PhD status. The latter are present within John’s, Liza’s, and Oreó’s narratives. Moreover, Vegeta contributed to the subpart by revealing his feelings of imposter, thereby reinforcing the prevalence of the overall theme.

John reflects on his struggle with self-doubt and imposter syndrome during demotivation. The feelings of emptiness resulting from demotivation led him to question the entirety of his capabilities as a laureate: “there was a time where I used to feel really empty like I can't do anything, I don't wanna do anything, I'm not good at anything, maybe I don't deserve this PhD, why am I doing it?...it was really a hard period of my life, it wasn't an easy one” (John, line 10-14, page 22). The symptoms reported in this passage are a lack of inadequacy and feelings of imposter. John clearly articulates what is known as a lack of adequacy and feelings of imposter. As John does not feel at the required level, he questions his presence and whether he is truly deserving of the PhD. The latter is observable in the sentence "maybe I don't deserve this PhD", highlighting the disarming effect of demotivation on his confidence that was built on past achievements. Moreover, John reports having struggled with the period, calling it "hard period of my life" which suggests the insurmountability (Marguc et al., 2010) and devastating effect of the latter which could have lasted for a considerable period of time. Additionally, coupled with his emptiness, incapacity and unwillingness to act, it seems logical to conclude that demotivation is a truly dangerous state that flips all the positive attributes to its dark counterpart, aligning thus with the seminal works of Dörnyei (1994).

Similarly, Liza and Oreó provide their lifeworld of imposter and inadequacy during demotivation. Starting with Liza who constantly questions her adequacy in regard to her abilities and suitability of the topic highlighting “probably I'm not at the required level, probably my topic is not at the required level, it doesn't meet the PhD criteria” (Liza, line 12-14, page 42). Despite being a valedictorian

student at a top-ranked UK university, Liza reports often struggling with such feelings when demotivated. The latter showcases the immense pulling down force that is demotivation. Second, Oreo voiced similar concerns about her abilities and feeling undeserving of such status “I feel like I'm not doing good enough, maybe I'm never going to meet my deadline, and that I'm somehow careless, that I probably don't deserve to be here to do what I'm doing” (Oreo, line 31-33, page 20). Oreo and Liza provide an inner insights into how imposter syndrome and feeling of inadequacy infiltrate them when being demotivated. The passages also demonstrate that despite their past achievement as laureates securing a fully funded scholarship in the UK, demotivation successfully demystifies the latter which represents the building blocks or basis of their confidence and motivation, rendering them empty vessels lost during the journey.

Moving to Vegeta, who similarly identified feelings of self-doubt and imposter syndrome further exemplifying the theme. He narrates how he feels like an imposter or a fraud, stating that he does not feel like the right person to do the job requested:

...feeling of questioning one's adequacy to perform the task at hand... don't feel like the right person for the job...you feel like a fraud, and that is a major feeling when it comes to demotivation...to PhD, I feel like 'OK, hold on, I'm not academic enough, nor was I ever this academic enough to carry out or to pretend that I have anything, any business doing what I'm doing'. (Vegeta, line 9-18, page 49)

This quote clearly describes cases of imposter syndrome and feelings of inadequacy. Vegeta while expressing his feelings of inadequacy and unfitness to the educational context used important terms such as ‘imposter’, ‘fraud’, ‘pretend’ or ‘right person’ which are keywords perfectly representing a person suffering from such feelings. The latter aligns with the experiences described by Liza and Oreo, therefore strengthening and demonstrating the importance of such feelings that come with demotivation.

Manel also expresses feelings of inadequacy as a symptom of demotivation. She feels that she does not have the required level, and the work is no longer suitable for her “it's like not wanting to work and feeling that what I am doing isn't suitable for me” (Manel, line 25-26, page 47). The latter suggests a lack of confidence in her ability to perform the task she initially was motivated to undertake. Thus, indicating the impact of demotivation in transforming not only motivated behaviours but also the personal positive attributes of highly skilled people such as self-confidence.

Zineb's self-doubt mainly stems from academic struggles being a source of suffering for her family, driving her to feel guilty and selfish. This was highlighted in the passage “is it worth it?...noticeable how your family are suffering from this distance, I felt guilty because you are fulfilling your life, you're like quite selfish to have the opportunity and come here and try to study” (Zineb, line 12-16,

page 40). Zineb's unique experience delves into proprieties of self-doubt, selfishness, and guilt. She attributes her opportunity as being a source of misery to her family due to the distance. The latter drives Zineb to question whether she made the right decision embarking on the PhD.

The data presented in this section offers support to the pioneering study of Chambers (1993) on how demotivated students are disengaged, lacking confidence and esteem in their capabilities. This has clearly been displayed by all the participants under this category. The latter also corroborates with Di Pierro (2007, p.370) on imposter syndrome highlighting "at the heart of doctoral students' struggling lie serious concerns that challenge the notions of certainty that they are indeed worthy of embarking upon doctoral study". Despite their previous achievements and status as laureates, participants during their doctoral studies had serious concerns about whether their competencies were enough to succeed. The lack of adequacy and trust in their capabilities makes them feel like they are 'frauds'; which was also reported by Vegeta and described by the rest of the participants. This corroborates how feelings of inadequacy and imposter stripe doctoral students from their confidence and weaken their resolve (Di Pierro, 2007; Sverdlik et al., 2020). However, one major difference is the fact that imposter syndrome is not the trigger of demotivation, but its subsequent symptom, which constitutes a notable contribution to the phenomenon and a newly added description of demotivated behaviours of international doctoral students.

Overall, demotivation drives PhD students to question their competence and suitability for academic endeavours, which contributes to creating a negative loop or a cyclical pattern that deteriorates motivation and confidence.

1.4. Tidal Waves of Emotion: Navigating Overwhelming Emotions

As demotivation strips away the positive attitude and meaning behind the efforts displayed, students experience a lack of enthusiasm, isolation, doubt and imposter syndrome. These exert a significant toll on PhD students leading to states of overwhelm and mental health issues. Thus, highlighting the detrimental impact of demotivation on PhD students' mental health.

The prevalence of exhaustion and fatigue is observable in the narratives of Stallion and Oreo. Descriptions such as 'feeling tired,' 'losing energy,' 'exhausted battery,' 'exhaustiveness,' and 'burnout' are evidence for the issues they are trying to explain. Although it was presented in the previous theme, the latter deserves acknowledgement in this subsection. It is important to note that the themes border with each other due to their fluidity.

Overwhelming and stress are reported by Zineb, Manel, and Leila. Starting with Zineb feeling overwhelmed by the price of being autonomous and feeling homesick:

I'm quite that person who is really attached to her family. So, coming here was my first experience traveling and being away from my family, that was quite a lot to handle because I felt alone, you've to stand on your own try to deal with your life without the support of anyone around you, that autonomy is the first I noticed. (Zineb, line 10-14, page 45)

Zineb's narrative offers a deeply personal exploration of her overwhelm stemming from autonomy. Precisely, due to the fact that she is relocating alone without her support system (family), she expresses how that generated feelings of having to handle everything alone, which overwhelmed her. Her passage represents a clear indication of how international-related factors add layers of difficulties to the experience of IDS. As she is away from her family which constitutes her main source of support, she is faced with additional complications beyond doctoral studies. This includes her having to make her own decisions and take charge of her own life. The latter seems to generate emotional distress and overwhelm as she cannot fully operate without the help of her family to lighten her burden. Subsequently, Zineb offers a rather unique state of overwhelm generated from the price of being autonomous.

The data generated from Zineb corroborates perfectly with previous literature such as Adler (1975) and Brown and Holloway (2008). For example, Brown and Holloway (2008) ethnographic study shows that international postgraduate students were feeling homesick and as a result mourned about having no one besides them to provide support. Having a support system is one of the factors that lead PhD students to complete their thesis. Because family provides support needed from both an academic and emotional side which in turn strengthens resilience and motivation (Volkert et al., 2018; McCray and Joseph-Richards, 2020). Using a descriptive survey of 835 doctoral students, Volkert et al. (2018) found that the doctoral students' intention to withdraw increases as the family support decreases. Moreover, McCray and Joseph-Richard (2020) study reveals that family is an important resilient component in the doctoral students' journey. Thus, highlighting the importance of such support systems to accomplish PhD endeavours. Subsequently, the present study data strengthens previous studies and updates the literature with the cultural aspect of the Algerian context.

Allowing to reach new depths in the understanding of demotivation, Zineb offers imagery depicting how the experience feels. The latter is a state of drowning in the ocean as she states, "when you are demotivated, you are like drowning in the ocean" (Zineb, line 26, page 46). Zineb describes demotivation as a state where she cannot stop herself from being pulled down into the ocean. The essence of demotivation in this passage highlights a state of powerlessness and overwhelm. Her state during demotivation is thus a state of a critical event resembling a near-death experience. The latter justifies the reasons as to why she could not perform at her best for her PhD studies.

The drowning represents a real-life negative critical event or state of being constantly being pulled down and unable to breathe which in a way parallels demotivation. It perfectly corroborates with Kikuchi's (2015, p.4) definition as "demotivation concerns of negative process that pulls learners down". Demotivation, in this context, like drowning drags the learners down from their safe and positive environment to a negative and dangerous (or deadly in this metaphor) state. This in turn compromises all the positive attributes such as resilience and productivity. Because there is a lack of oxygen and even vision underwater, individuals find themselves incapacitated to change their direction and keep sinking. This is also exacerbated as Zineb did not have her support system by her side to save her from drowning or in this case remotivate her. Interestingly, the passage also highlights a rather sociological dimension known as powerlessness (Seeman, 1959), where an alienated worker has no control over his product or life (Royce, 2015; Spracklen et al, 2016) or in this case no power to pull herself up from the drowning situation. This image is a contribution to understanding not only the world of PhD students in the dark side but also offers new additions and richness to the phenomenon of demotivation. Subsequently, IPA appears appropriate as a choice of methodology as it aided in looking deeper into the phenomenon to its core and unveiled facets that remained hidden. In summary, the passage highlights the detrimental impact of demotivation on an individual's functioning. Using unique and highly representative analogies such as drowning in the ocean, states of overwhelm and powerlessness highlight the severity of the event. The latter calls for more support systems which can be represented as "lifeguards" to help students resurface and remotivate in times of need or demotivation.

As regards Manel, she struggles with feelings of stress, panic and other mental-related issues. These overwhelming mental health issues arise when the equilibrium is compromised. Consequently, Manel suffers from forgetfulness as a symptom of demotivation "Sometimes I totally forget where I've stopped reading or where I've stopped writing anything like a document" (Manel, line 3-4, page 50). This compromises her academic productivity and advancement. Moreover, she displays avoidance tendencies which reflects a tendency to neglect responsibility "Sometimes I go weeks without, I don't even check my emails when I'm demotivated" (Manel, line 4-5, page 50). When feeling demotivated, Manel seems to disregard checking her emails which are important components in communicating with supervisors and establishing meetings and progress reports. Thus, demonstrating how demotivation leads to avoiding tasks that are paramount to goal achievement.

Additionally, forgetfulness and avoidance as symptoms only intensify her stress and panic. The latter only creates a perpetual loop of demotivation highlighting "This causes me to be more demotivated when I see that I've wasted a lot of time without doing anything and then this is another

demotivating factor for me because it just makes you stressed and panicked” (Manel, line 6-8, page 50). The latter demonstrates how demotivation acts as an interminable circle that only aggravates the already negative states.

However, the detrimental effects of demotivation on Manel's life do not stop at mere stress. During the interview, she reveals an experience that takes demotivation to another level of severity which is sleep nightmares and panic attacks episode:

I have nightmares, and panic attacks, and I just wake up. So, I cannot sleep unless I'm really exhausted because when I sleep, and I'm not really exhausted...I'm feeling guilty, I cannot sleep because my sleep is always interrupted by panic attacks and nightmares relating to the fact that I'm late and I'm behind with my studies. (Manel, line 4-18, page 51)

Manel describes an overwhelming mental health situation that occurs as a result of her demotivation. She reports being subject to sleep nightmares that prevent her from restoring her energy levels (RAM sleep). Moreover, she highlights that she can only sleep when she is exhausted. However, as soon as she sleeps, she is immediately woken up due to the nightmares and panic attacks as a result of her being behind her studies. Demotivation, in this case, impacted Manel at a deeper psychological level reaching her subconscious. Thus, this experience serves as a demonstration of how demotivation not only disrupts mental health but also the overall homeostasis of the individuals such as sleep quality.

Previous research has already established how PhD students' mental health and sleep schedules get disrupted (Hyun et al., 2006; Kernan et al., 2011). Therefore, this research corroborates with previous studies by bringing forth data from a different methodological approach. However, the difference lies within the trigger and the nature of the factors. In this study, the nature of sleep issues emerges as a component of a demotivated person after having their motivation dissipated. Moreover, the results refer to sleeping difficulties and not insomnia and sleep nightmares; highlighting another difference that constitutes a unique contribution to the scientific debate. Additionally, previous studies have not successfully provided any insights relating demotivation to nightmares and panic attacks, which constitute yet another original addition to the phenomenon. Subsequently, demotivation seems to compromise the homeostasis of PhD students transitioning them from engaged and diligent students to avoidant and deviant students suffering from mental health issues such as nightmares and panic attacks.

Contrary to Manel, Leila's experience presents a less severe yet still important aspect of demotivation. The overwhelming sensation stemming from PhD demotivation leads her to boredom as she repeatedly reported such feeling stating it plainly “boredom as well” (Leila, line 22, page 38) and “I feel bored” (Line 24, page 38). Leila exposes that the seriousness of the PhD is one source of

demotivation “it's always related to the fact that PhD is too serious, and I just get enough, I get bored, being stuck to my laptop, keep on doing things the same way” (Leila, 27-29, page 38). The passage reflects PhD as being a serious endeavour that stripes away the fun from Leila and derives it to feelings of boredom as it necessitates doing things regularly such as sitting at a desk and working on a laptop, which in a way resembles the isolation mentioned by Liza in earlier themes “only talking to my laptop”. The boredom result as an effect echoes Case’s (2007) study on how chemical engineering students lose the element of joy due to the vicissitudes of research. Despite that the study predominantly focused on alienation, the latter shares commonalities with the phenomenon of demotivation.

Upon elaboration, Leila used an Arabic phrase to encapsulate her feelings denoting dissatisfaction and boredom. She states that PhD is “شغل ثقيلة على القلب” (Leila, 30-32, page 38), which translates to “feels like a burden; doing something out of heart”. She further expresses this burden when she says, “it's just a burden, an extra burden” (Leila, 34-35, page 38). As a reaction, Leila seems to distance herself from PhD seriousness as an escape to recharge “...I do feel the need to escape...all the boredom, all of that... I do go out, I do spend the entire day in bed, I plan a trip, I do different things that help me escape this serious mode” (13-16, page 47). Therefore, as a coping strategy, Leila takes breaks from academic studies by planning outings and social gatherings to escape the monotony and seriousness of the PhD that generates boredom. Interestingly, she seems like the only participant who differs from others as she constantly tries to find solutions to her predicament, highlighting the uniqueness of her lifeworld (Smith et al., 2022).

Interest is an important factor in internal motivation (Deci and Ryan, 2016). Losing the interest entails that the efforts towards the goal diminish greatly. In this context, Leila’s demotivation is manifested through feelings of boredom due to the seriousness of the PhD. The latter appears as a logical outcome that stems from losing enthusiasm for an activity. However, boredom as an outcome of demotivation still remains undocumented, especially at an international doctoral level. Thus, the present study offers support to Chambers (1993) on demotivated behaviours by highlighting symptoms other than a lack of self-doubt and self-esteem.

In summary, this part has highlighted the emotional toll and mental health complications UK Algerian postgraduates face upon demotivation. Elements described are overwhelming sensations, powerlessness, stress, anxiety, nightmares, panic attacks and boredom. These symptoms pinpoint how severe the mental state of international students gets when demotivated. These underscore the need for more efficient strategies to tackle the urgent state of international PhD students.

1.5. Unshackling Self: The Intricate Dance of Autonomy, Guilt, and Regret

This GET is associated with feelings of guilt and regret stemming from demotivation. The participants elaborate on how being unproductive in times of demotivation leads to feelings of guilt and regret. The latter is further exacerbated due to the self-isolating nature of the PhD and the fact that PhD progress depends entirely on students' autonomy and self-learning. Thus, by demotivation destabilising the productive habits of PhD students, a cyclical phase of negative feelings emerges.

To begin with, John's feelings during demotivation illustrate a cycle of regret and self-blame. During that phase, John frequently feels remorse as he is not being productive in his PhD which compromises his timely completion. He expresses "I didn't like the fact that I wasn't productive, I wasn't working, or studying as hard as I was studying before...why am I not studying?" (John, line 4-6, page 22). John unlike other participants, such as Stallion and Oreo, does not seem to avoid his feelings but rather openly faces them, which only exacerbates his demotivation. In the passage, he displays feelings of guilt towards not being productive. The sense of guilt is further developed into regret as he is aware of the wasted time and potential. Additionally, the feeling is heightened as he is aware of the extent of his hard work and diligence before demotivation. By comparing himself to his previous motivated version, he finds himself filled with remorse and guilt only worsening the situation. Moreover, what is interesting to notice is the recurring pattern of this emotion (or periodic resonance), stating, "even now sometimes I go through these phases from time to time" (John, line 8-9, page 22). Thus, acknowledging the persistent nature of demotivation which only damages the self-image and overall motivation.

The importance of productivity and goal achievement is highlighted in John's narratives. As a PhD student, he attaches significant importance to daily production and progression towards completion. This can be perceived as a self-imposed pressure to succeed. The latter if not fulfilled triggers feelings of disenchantment and demotivation which is clearly expressed in the following "Whenever I wasn't productive then I would think 'Oh my God, I haven't done anything, I should have done more'" (John, line 27-28, page 27). The passage meticulously describes a demotivated person when not achieving set goals. John upon not achieving his desired productivity and study protocol finds himself dragged into the cycle of blame and regret which was clear during his passage "I haven't done anything" and "I should've done more". Thus, indicating the negative cycle of regret and blame that occurs with demotivation.

Guilt and remorse were also highlighted in Manel's experience. She reflects on the periods of unproductivity, wasted time, and comparison with others, triggering such feelings "Feeling guilty is

just looking at the time you wasted doing other stuff...comes this feeling of guilt when you see that I've lost one week I did nothing...not progressed enough" (Manel, line 9, page 50). In periods of demotivation, Manel seems to be incapacitated to undertake her daily academic/research duties. After reflecting on the wasted period, she feels an immense *tristesse* and regret as she could have made progress during that time. Demotivation incapacitates the behaviours needed for productivity and progression, nevertheless, it does not seem to numb the feelings students experience as they see themselves in the negative zone.

Similarly, Leila pinpoints the universal presence of guilt when demotivated as she states, "We all have this sense of guilt when being demotivated" (Leila, line 4, page 49). The passage highlights the human function of feeling bad after not taking advantage during a situation and progress. She further elaborates:

you feel guilty of being demotivated somehow you feel "*I'm not doing enough*", "*I should be working more*", "*if it was different, I would be doing better*", "*what's going wrong?*" "*why is this happening to me?*" "*how can I fix that?*" "*how can I get it done as soon as possible?*" (Leila, line 6-8, page 49)

Thus, similar to John and Manel, Leila undergoes feelings and mixed thoughts of remorse and guilt. Leila not only goes through a period of guilt but also a cycle of questioning towards her wasted time and productivity. Thus, demotivation not only decreases the self-esteem and confidence of students (Chambers, 1993) but also triggers additional negative feelings such as guilt and remorse, highlighting the complex nature of the phenomenon. Nevertheless, a notable difference and uniqueness of Leila is that she does not stay in the middle of the transitional phase but goes and asks questions that might raise potential answers such as "how can I fix that?". This indicates despite the devastating nature of demotivation, Leila remains focused and tries to find adequate coping strategies to get remotivated. The latter indicates and demonstrates the uniqueness and idiographic aspect that can only be collected through IPA measures.

Furthermore, Vegeta adds a layer to the theme by stating that there is a lapse between demotivation, guilt and regret. He highlights that the latter comes only after long-term periods of demotivation as self-realisation of the wasted time as he states:

Regret comes after some time has passed without me actually doing anything. It doesn't come initially, but after a while of being demotivated, you feel like, "Well, if I wasn't demotivated for the last month, I would have advanced so much." It's regret and guilt that come later, after a relatively long period of demotivation. (Vegeta, line 20-24, page 49)

Vegeta offers similar concerns on how demotivation leads to feelings of guilt and regret. However, it seems that for Vegeta, the period between demotivation and guilt realisation is significantly longer. It

is only after that the negative period lasts long enough and his productivity is compromised within a month that his feelings of guilt and regret manifest. Thus, although the experience remains the same, the period of impact or symptoms is notably longer, highlighting how people experience the same phenomenon differently (Smith et al., 2022).

Nevertheless, Vegeta highlights an internal conflict that represents his lifeworld's uniqueness. The additional component magnifying his negative feelings is the fact of realising that he is wasting the Algerian government's money for nought, which raises an ethical dilemma and guilt him at a significantly higher level:

What is an ethical dilemma within my heart when I feel like I'm just sitting around and not making the most of a scholarship that other people are paying for, so you feel guilty for not performing adequately, while also benefiting from it. So I'd rather not do the PhD than take the money and just fail, so that's another element and it's mostly translated into guilt. (Vegeta, line, 3-8, page 61)

Vegeta, as a fully-funded student in the UK, finds himself guilt over using the government's funds without making the most of it, which is acquiring the PhD. Due to such feelings of involved third parties, his feelings of guilt are worsened as he appears not to be the only one concerned in the story/equation. This guilt leads him to stay at home and not doing the PhD rather than use the money and not meet the required outcome. In this instance, Vegeta's guilt acts as a positive factor trying to remotivate him so as to give sense to all the money he has received. The ethical dilemma provided resonates deeply with the essence of demotivation. Thus, the particularity of Vegeta resides in his unique feelings during the troubled period. Vegeta, despite sharing commonalities with others, reflected at deeper a level and provided with a core of demotivation that has remained in the dark.

Next is Oreo who feels guilty of being demotivated, unproductive, and unable to do anything academically related. As she states, "I feel guilty about not being productive, about being demotivated...I don't feel like doing anything at all, especially academia" (Oreo, line 18-24, page 20). Her words serve as compelling evidence of the profound guilt experienced during demotivation. It also pinpoints that despite the lived guilt, she cannot seem to do anything to change her current condition, thus demonstrating the debilitating effect of demotivation. Demotivation, thus incapacitates individual beyond their academic duties, highlighting the severity of the phenomenon in daily life in general and academic in specific. The latter is more alarming for international students as the sole purpose of their relocation to the UK is for study purposes.

Guilt is an inner feeling that occurs as a reaction to stimuli. Generally, this reactional phenomenon occurs upon making actions that are wrongful or are regarded as transgressional (Tracy and Robins, 2004; Sullivan, 2014). Because individuals did not act properly or in accordance with the conventions

agreed upon, they found that they should have done actions during that period and should have engaged in a form of retribution to clean their consciousness and fair the trade. Similarly, in the present study, the activation of guilt is due to the participants not being productive and wasting their time and the government's money.

Demotivation deprives participants of displaying the necessary behaviours towards goal completion such as productivity and autonomous learning. As participants feel that they should have worked during the demotivation phase, after noticing the wasted time and transgression towards their academic duties (international students upon receiving their visas are compelled to work for 35 hours per week in their PhD as full-timers). Having seen the wrongful act and ethical misconduct, they are filled with guilt and regret which are feelings that usually accompany each other (Tilghman-Osborne et al., 2010; Brewer, 2016). Regret represents feelings of remorse and shame towards a chosen situation that is not the most appropriate one and that another alternative could have been better (Connolly and Zeelenberg, 2002). The latter was also observed within the participants' narrative such as *"if it was different, I would be doing better"* (Leila). Research in this area has shown that regret is linked to bad decision-making, decision-avoidance, risk taking and health-related issues (Zeelenberg and Pieters, 2007; Västfjäll et al., 2011). These reported studies corroborate with the present data as most participants felt guilt, regret and displayed these tendencies that appear to be self-destructive towards health and academic achievements such as avoidance, bad decision-making and health-related issues. Subsequently, guilt and regret as reactional phenomena appear to be symptoms of demotivation as the displayed tendencies by the participants align with definitions of these negative emotions. Thus, the present IPA study reported and discussed new elements that bring more understanding to the phenomenon of demotivation.

1.6. Shadows of Insecurity: The Shared Experience of Fear and Uncertainty

GET 6 exposes the profound emotional experiences of uncertainty and fear of failure as a symptom of demotivation. As participants lost almost all of their positive attributes necessary for success, individuals find themselves insecure about their futures.

John's uncertainty and fear rose as a reaction to his change due to demotivation. He expresses that he shifts to a new facet of himself that is estranged to him as he pinpoints "it's hard to explain the emotional changes, but it's like, there was a shift from being satisfied of my life, of who I was, to being unsatisfied, a shift from being proud, to being ashamed of who I was" (John, line 33-2, pages 25-26). The statement is a declaration of a transition in John's identity where he does not feel like the version he is proud of himself anymore. Moreover, the difficulty to fully explicate himself highlights

the intensity and the overwhelming emotional challenges he is experiencing. The quote signals a departure from the positive state of being proud and content about one's state to one of dissatisfaction and self-estrangement (Seeman, 1959). Therefore, demotivation causes a negative transitional shift that leaves the individuals estranged and unrecognisable which generates feelings of fear and uncertainty.

Next, Leila narrates that she is riddled with fear about her future and how uncertain her trajectory is if the PhD is not completed, considering even alternative options:

“what if this PhD doesn't work?”, *“what else I can do?”*, *“what are the other options?”*
I was worried about my future, about my studies. So I felt as that my PhD is at stake, and I was searching of alternative options. So in the worst-case scenarios, how can I save “ما يمكن إنقاذه” (Arabic for: what can be saved). (Leila, line 32-36, page 47)

Leila's demotivation is accompanied by a sense of fear and uncertainty about her future. She is constantly filled with negative feelings such as worrying about her studies and her overall future life. The constant worries are highlighted in multiple instances such as *“what if this PhD does not work?”*, which highlights the fear of failure and the potential outcomes it might generate. She also narrates that she felt that her PhD was at stake during demotivation, highlighting the severity and threat demotivation poses to academic thriving. Leila divulge that she was trying to save what can be saved indicating a sense of urgency, thus demonstrating the toll demotivation had on her studies. The case for Algerians is more pronounced as they were promised a job when finishing the PhD and not respecting the clause might make them subject to huge losses such as losing the job prospect in Algeria and having to pay back the money, which constitutes another huge additional pressure on Algerians to either 'finish/publish or perish'.

Lastly, Oreo shares her fear of failure as a subsequent experience of demotivation. Additionally, when prompted she further elaborates: “...now I'm due to submitting in less than two months...if I miss my deadline, it's going to be a big problem because I can't do an extension, so it's a ride or die kind of thing so it's very intense” (Oreo, line 12-16, page 22). Oreo depicts an experience that generated fear of failure and uncertainty during her journey. She expresses a fear in regard to not meeting the deadline she has for her thesis draft submission and how the latter significantly impacts her emotional state. The pressure to meet deadlines might impact producing quality work in both ways (Cornwall et al., 2019). Oreo delves into how many tasks she still has left before submitting including editing the whole work, working and updating the literature. She realises the consequences of her actions if she fails which is the inability to file for an extension and thus possibly fail the grade. Knowing that, Oreo is pressured to complete the PhD otherwise the consequences would be irreversible. However, these

feelings might have the opposite effect where the fear of failure becomes a barrier to progress thus perpetuating the cycle of demotivation.

Uncertainty represents a state of the unknown where the individual possesses little or no information about the situation, triggering insecurities about future outcomes (Carleton, 2016; Morriss et al., 2019). Fear of failure is usually known as “persistent and irrational anxiety about failing to measure up to the standards and goals set by oneself or others” (American Psychological Association 2007, p. 369). Both these definitions perfectly represent the state of the participants under this category. For instance, John’s transition from a recognisable version of himself from active, happy and satisfied to becoming passive and unsatisfied, triggered uncertainty as to whether he is able to achieve his goal of PhD completion. Leila and Oreo, on the other hand, typically displayed fear of failure tendencies where they imagine worst-case scenarios: “*what if this PhD does not work?*” (Leila), “so it's a ride or die kind of thing” (Oreo). Thus, prior studies corroborate current findings and offer reinforcement. However, a slight difference between previous studies and the actual one is the trigger. The present study’s element that sets things in motion is demotivation. While previous studies such as Chambers (1993) offered core entry into the symptomology of demotivation, the latter neither collected nor recounted an extensive and exhaustive experience of the issue. Subsequently, offering new insights and better comprehension of demotivation and how the latter influences individuals during their academic journey. Demotivation deprives participants of their inherent strengths during their respective PhDs. They find themselves with an estranged version of themselves devoid of any attribute that they once defined their identity. Such troubling periods generate uncertainty due to the situation.

2. Thought Processes

This section delineates the cognitive aspects of demotivation. The thought processes that accompany demotivation are generally myriads of negative and unhelpful thinking patterns such as NATs, questioning the value of the task at hand, to more extreme ends such as suicidal thoughts and ideation. However, an interesting positive symptom that emerged was termed *reconciliation* where a participant focused all her thought processes on finding a solution to the maze that is demotivation. For a more comprehensive overview, a table has been below.

Table 8: Thought Processes Associated with Demotivation

GETs of Thought Processes	Personal Experiential Themes
<p>GET 1: The Labyrinth of Negativity: Exploring the Realm Critical Voice and Negative Automated Thoughts (NATs)</p> <p><i>This GET encompasses patterns of negative thinking and self-criticism experienced by the participants during their demotivated state.</i></p>	<p>Stallion: Unhappy thoughts, Critical voice about his work, Having a dark/negative perspective of the world. John: Overthinking, Critical voice. Zineb: Negative thinking merged with her personality, Negative self-talk/critical voice. Manel: Negative thoughts. Liza: Negative thinking patterns/critical voice in times of demotivation, Feeling trapped and isolated in a black bubble.</p>
<p>GET 2: Disconnected Drift: Exploring the Dynamics of Study Avoidance, Detachment and Attrition</p> <p><i>This GET reflects the participants' tendency to neglect academic duty during the demotivated phase.</i></p>	<p>Stallion: Not thinking about work. Vegeta: Arguing against the task at hand. Liza: Thinking of withdrawal. Oreo: Internal dialogue and self-reflection.</p>
<p>GET 3: Questioning Self-Worth and Losing Faith in the PhD: Navigating Doubt and Purpose</p> <p><i>This GET unfolds the demotivating thought processes related to questioning the value of the task at hand and self-worth.</i></p>	<p>Zineb: Questioning the worth of the task undertaken. Liza: Despair and existential crisis, thinking of going back home and live a meaningless jobless life.</p>
<p>GET 4: Reaching the Breaking Point: Suicidal Thoughts and Ideation</p> <p><i>This GET encompasses the distressing experiences of suicidal thoughts and ideation that Liza encounters during demotivated states.</i></p>	<p>Liza: Suicidal thoughts and ideation.</p>
<p>GET 5: Navigating the Maze: Seeking Solutions and Reconciliation</p> <p><i>This GET represents the participant's efforts to seek solutions and reconcile with the experience of demotivation.</i></p>	<p>Leila: Reconcile/acknowledge with the idea of demotivation, Trying to find solutions to minimize its effect.</p>

2.1. The Labyrinth of Negativity: Exploring the Realm of Critical Voice and Negative Automated Thoughts (NATs)

Data reveal that negative thinking and self-criticism are common in demotivated states. Starting with Stallion who expresses being submerged with negative and unhappy thoughts when being demotivated as he states “Oh no happy thoughts. When demotivated, my brain is loaded with negative thoughts” (Stallion, line 4-5, page 20). Moreover, due to his demotivation, his perception of his work gets bleaker or more critical as he highlights “I start thinking negatively about my work because I’m not progressing” (Stallion, line 7-8, page 20). Lastly, Stallion gets disenchanted and portrays a dark/negative perspective of the world: “The world is very, very dark when I am demotivated...when demotivated, I tend to focus on the negativities of my life, I don’t focus on the positives, that’s the essential one, I tend to focus on what’s negative about the world” (Stallion, line 22-25, page 20).

From the passages, Stallion reports a shift in his thinking patterns that are predominantly negative. The negative thoughts entail life in general “oh no happy thoughts”, the PhD “I think negatively about my work”, and the worldview in general “the world is very dark”. Demotivation seems to have transformed Stallion who is the most motivated element into a vessel of negativity and darkness, highlighting its danger. Such change mirrors what Kikuchi (2015) terms as ‘pulling the learner down’, where a positive and diligent element becomes an estranged and darker entity of demotivation. Stallion’s worldview during demotivation becomes bleak which perfectly opposes the motivated state. The shift also corroborates Weber’s (1948) disenchantment where Stallion loses all of his magical or positive attributes leading him to feel disenchanted or in this case demotivated.

John mentions overthinking and experiencing what is known as a critical voice, as he expresses:

it's overthinking, maybe I'm not good enough, maybe I don't deserve this PhD? What am I doing? A PhD student should work more!....These things will just come into my mind, I didn't want to think about them...then of course your mind would take you somewhere else, your brain will take you somewhere else. (John, line 25-32, page 27)

John had a critical inner voice that contributed to negative self-talk during his demotivating period. He talks about how his actual situation led him to overthink and be critical about his capacity to undertake the PhD. The latter triggers feelings such as guilt and regret indicating his focus on productivity and self-worth. Finally, John reports that under demotivation his thoughts take him somewhere else, indicating lack of control over his own thought processes.

John experiences intrusive thoughts and a lack of control over his thought processes when he is demotivated. This loss of control over one's own thoughts can be a source of distress and may contribute to other emotional changes, such as low self-esteem and anxiety (which was already demonstrated in the previous section). Subsequently, demotivation seems to drive to what is known as Negative Automated Thoughts (NATs) which are intrusive and negative thoughts that individuals experience during a psychological problem. It functions as uncontrollable thoughts that pop into the mind and are hard to switch off (Beck, 1967; Stott et al., 2010; Neenan, 2018). Similarly, John experiences a psychological problem (demotivation) and is filled with destructive and negative thoughts (NATs) and feels powerless to change them. Examples are noticeable in John's passage such as "I'm not good enough" and "maybe I don't deserve this PhD?". John's automatic thoughts corrupt his mind and incapacitate him from displaying his full potential, putting a halt to his motivated thoughts and behaviours. Therefore, John's experience corroborates with previous literature and offers a new insight into the phenomenon of demotivation by linking it to NATs.

Zineb described negative thinking merged with her personality and engaging in negative self-talk. She states:

I was having negative thinking, most of it was quite destructive because you can't focus whenever you say "*OK, I need to force myself, I need to study*" but then those negative thoughts start like raining on you, you're trying to handle that, but at the time, I couldn't see anything that could help me. (Zineb, line 25-28, page 47)

Zineb recounts instances of negative thoughts upon demotivation. She stresses that her thoughts were 'destructive', which represents thoughts that are far more dangerous than mere negative thoughts as destructive could imply sabotaging her PhD thriving. In other words, these destructive thoughts hinder her ability to focus and study optimally. Interestingly, Zineb states that despite trying to find a way to cope, uncontrollable 'negative thoughts raining on you'. This metaphor entails that much like the rain that falls relentlessly and uncontrollably, negative thoughts seem to be unavoidable and overwhelming during demotivation, leaving Zineb with no escape from them. The latter represents a powerful metaphor/representation highlighting her mental/emotional hopelessness. Moreover, similar to John, whenever she tries to reason with her thoughts or mind, she finds herself unable to control her intrusive thoughts "I couldn't see anything that could help me", highlighting a lack of control or sense of powerlessness over the situation (Seeman, 1975; Neenan, 2018) merged with lack of coping mechanism to the situation. The sentence also denotes a sense of hopelessness where Zineb perceives a lack of adequate solutions or resources to address the challenge (Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2021).

Such negative thinking according to her is exacerbated due to her type of personality that constantly self-criticises and evaluates herself "I'm always criticizing my work, I feel that it's not valuable

enough, I can do better than this... So I think this type of feelings when you feel that you're not good enough to do that PhD" (Zineb, line 9-15, page 48). This passage not only underscores a critical voice towards one's self or work but also highlights an instance of emotional reasoning where feelings are believed to be facts (Neenan, 2018). This is observable in the last bit "you feel that you're not good enough to do that PhD", pinpointing the multifaced and destructive nature of demotivation on doctoral students' motivation and confidence. Zineb's experiences of demotivation are reflected by NATs as her destructive thoughts are merged with her personality and self-criticism. These internal tormenting voices do not allow her to stay focused and study well. The continuous assessment of oneself and the sense of inadequacy that accompanies it make the control of those emotions very hard. Thus, Zineb pinpoints the necessity of overcoming self-critical tendencies to surmount the PhD curve (Cushieri, 2021).

Similarly, Manel and Liza shared experiences of negative thinking patterns and a critical voice during demotivation, feeling trapped and isolated in a negative bubble. Manel's depiction of negative thinking is merged with self-doubt and existential crisis, as she pinpoints:

...like an umbrella term, I have negative thoughts when I'm demotivated: not wanting to do this, feeling like this isn't for me, maybe I'm just here by chance. I don't deserve this, I'm not strong enough. It starts with "I can't do it," then "I don't want to do it." When there's a lot of work I haven't done, I just give up and say, "I'm not gonna do this, it's too much for me, I can't handle it any longer!" (Manel, line 6-14, page 49)

Manel's passage depicts the different thinking patterns she undergoes under the influence of demotivation. She initially puts the processes under the umbrella term of "negative thoughts", which englobes the various thought processes that come into her mind whole being demotivated. Basically, during demotivation, her mind is full of negative thoughts such as "I don't deserve this" and "I cannot do it" which depicts instances of NATs. However, Manel's case is approaching an alarming state known as an existential crisis. The latter is observable in her quotes such as "it is too much for me, I can't handle it any longer!". It appears that the level of her obstacle in this extract has reached what Marguc et al. (2010) termed as insurmountable, which is beyond what she can handle. Manel who is a motivated and highly achieving individual finds herself on the brink of extreme psychological problems. Thus, highlighting the gravity of demotivation on people's wellbeing.

Liza's demotivational cognitive patterns revolve around negative thinking, denoting the same critical voice mentioned earlier:

...I do have all the negative thoughts, but I do keep encouraging myself to think positively, but whenever I start thinking positively, I recognise that this is quite impossible... there are only the bad scenarios. I want to get out of this black bubble, but I can't find solutions. So that's why I have more options while thinking negatively. (Liza, line 2-7, page 50)

Liza highlights the demotivating thinking patterns that erode her from her studies. First, similarities between herself and other participants such as Manel and Zineb are highlighted in the use of the expression ‘negative thoughts’. However, Liza pinpoints that she has ‘all the negative thoughts’ which constitute the main difference between her and other participants. The latter suggests that Liza has more negative thinking patterns than the rest of the respondents which is logical given the fact that she is the most demotivated case. She stresses that despite her multiple trials to see the positive sides, she realises that doing so is an unachievable task or an insurmountable obstacle (Marguc et al., 2010). She expresses that her main goal is to escape the ‘black bubble’ of demotivation. However, her attempts always seem to fail as she has more options in the dark side which is why she focuses more on them. Thus, highlighting the predominance of negative thinking during demotivation. It also demonstrates that despite having positive thoughts amidst the demotivated period, these get extinguished due to the pulling-down nature of demotivation.

The idea of ‘black bubble’ Liza encapsulates feeling trapped or enclosed in a negative mental space. Such imagery perfectly represents demotivation as the latter in some way imprison the positive attributes and behaviours of its victims. Similar to the psychological concept, the sociological concept of the ‘iron cage’ refers to a situation where individuals are trapped in a negative/loop thinking due to their disenchantment (Weber, 1948, Royce, 2015). In Liza’s case, the black bubble represents an abstract cage or a psychological state where she cannot think positively and is unable to escape the negativity of her thoughts. This original concept could be termed as ‘The Iron Cage of Demotivation’. It is noteworthy that Liza has uttered the phrase ‘black bubble’ more than once upon probing and the examination divulged most of what it encapsulates. However, due to brevity reasons, the present research only reported the most important and overarching result.

In this GET, participants recounted instances of negative automated thinking and critical voice. Key elements reported are negative thinking about one’s self, work and the world, intrusive and destructive thoughts and being trapped in a black bubble of negativity. These perfectly align with definitions of NATs and critical voice as intrusive and negative thoughts that invade the mind with no control over them (Beck, 1967; Stott et al., 2010). The negative thoughts that infiltrate the mind happen during psychological problems (Neenan, 2018).

The manifestation of negative thoughts in the context of demotivation reflects a psychological distress phenomenon. Correspondingly, Weishaar (1996, p.188) stresses that “during psychological distress a person’s thinking becomes more rigid and distorted, judgements become overgeneralized and absolute, and the person’s basic beliefs about the self and the world become fixed”. Participants under

this category perfectly displayed NATs when being demotivated. They reported instances of distorted thinking, emotional reasoning, and fixed mindset tendencies. Their equilibrium or homeostasis is compromised as demotivation flips the natural side into its unnatural or dark one. Subsequently, the present research offers new insights into the intricacies and functionalities of demotivation and how the latter turns the most motivated PhD students into vessels of negativity. By exploring the relationship between demotivation and NATs, a deeper understanding of the psychological mechanisms underlying motivational challenges in academic settings is gained.

The provided figure below represents the dyadic experience of motivation and demotivation and how motivated individuals switch their thought processes after being disengaged. The elements presented below are actual quotes from the participants allowing a more contextually-based illustration:

Figure 5: Negative Automated Thoughts Associated with Demotivation.

As displayed, the upper half represents motivated sentences to sustain motivation during a goal achievement. The bottom half, however, encapsulates the demotivating thought processes that cross IDS' minds while having psychological issues (Neenan, 2018). The sentences utilised in the bottom half of the figure are original quotes adapted from each participant's interviews. The few quotes used serve as a clear demonstration of how NATs operate under demotivation and how information and thoughts are distorted during the dark phase.

2.2. Disconnected Drift: Unravelling the Dynamics of Study Avoidance, Detachment and Attrition

PhD students often engage in avoidance and detachment tendencies during demotivated phases. GET 2 discusses the different thought processes pertaining to avoidance and detachment from work to considering withdrawing from a PhD.

For Vegeta, most of his thought processes under this category are being ‘the devil’s advocate’ as he creates a case against engaging with his PhD duties. As he clearly states:

Mainly all the reasons why I shouldn’t take whatever task I have seriously, my thought process is always the cons. My head plays on repeat every possible con. I brainstorm all the reasons why I shouldn't and elaborate on that mentally just to justify the fact that I am not actually doing it. (Vegeta, line 33-39, page 46)

Vegeta’s main preoccupation during demotivation is sitting on the opposite side of his PhD. In other words, his thought processes in the disengaging phase majorly revolve around brainstorming all the reasons not to take the task at hand. While motivation drives individuals to find the necessary reasons to undertake the action (Bandura, 1986; Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2021), demotivation seems to have the opposite effect. The case is demonstrated with Vegeta’s input. While he should be looking for reasons to finish his thesis, when he is demotivated, his mind shifts to the other side only searching for justification in order not to work, hence playing the devil’s advocate. This shows how demotivation is a negative agent that debilitates the brightest students.

Moreover, Vegeta's analytical skills under demotivation switch to the dark side where he argues against the task at hand:

I'm generally objective in my analysis, but when I'm demotivated, I'm not and I know I'm not but it's more of my favourite...mental training when I'm demotivated, arguing against whatever thing I was meant to do before I got demotivated, giving myself a good case for failing it in a way. (Vegeta, line 8-11, page 50)

Vegeta's narratives reveal a demotivation-related cognitive shift. He reports that in his normal state, he is usually objective in his analysis. However, when he becomes demotivated, his thought processes switch from objectivity to subjectivity. Interestingly, Vegeta reports that not only he is aware of such a switch but also reports favouring the latter. Moreover, he pinpoints that the bias serves as a justification in case of failure. Therefore, from Vegeta's testimony, demotivation not only deviates the moral compass of students but also seems to be fully aware of the shift when it occurs. Subsequently, Vegeta’s case is a clear demonstration of how demotivation turns the most motivated individual into an inactive PhD student using most of their thought processes on the negative sides to justify potential negative/unfavourable outcomes. This result adds a layer of complexity to the demotivation literature (Chambers, 1993) by highlighting how disengaged students become engaged in the dark side.

Conversely, at the end of the spectrum, Liza’s demotivating thoughts focus mainly on attrition. When she is confronted with demotivation, the thinking patterns emerging from her are mostly leaving the doctoral studies as she stresses: “I so many times wanted and decided to drop out, I wanted to withdraw because I felt like whatever I do is not at the level, so I don’t belong to this university, I don’t belong to this PhD, let me say probably I'm not at this level” (Liza, line 5-7, page 42). Additionally, she

stresses that attrition thinking due to demotivation is a daily thought that crosses her mind: “In terms of withdrawal, this is something that I live with daily, it's not really something that comes and goes but since I've been going through lots of demotivating events, this didn't stop me thinking about withdrawing” (Liza, line 21-25, page 47).

In these passages, Liza highlights how her demotivated experiences led her to think about attrition on multiple occasions. The latter demonstrates that demotivation leads to thoughts of attrition. However, her experience is rather unique, instead of having attrition thoughts on a few occasions, she shares that the feeling of attrition has never ceased in her mind. The level of demotivation in her case is so severe that she cannot possibly think of any other solution than attrition. This indicates that when demotivation arrives at a deteriorated stage, the mind loses its ability to regulate and process thoughts.

Having to constantly think about attrition can serve as an additional demotivating instance which might block her from progressing in her PhD. Rather than trying to find coping strategies, Liza's thoughts seem to be automatic, unrelenting and negative leading her to a complete halt in her motivated actions. This might also suggest that after demotivation, Liza might think that attrition is a potential solution to her unavoidable outcome, which is failure. As an IPA researcher, this result is of great importance as it highlights potential danger zones that previous studies on demotivation rarely found. This data is a clear indication that demotivation not only stops PhD students from performing at their best but also drives them to the darkest thoughts such as attrition and discredit the efforts displayed prior to the demotivation phase.

In sum, while Vegeta argues against his work and tries to find justifications for his inactivity, Liza completely rejects every possible solution and focuses solely on withdrawal, illustrating how two individuals from the same Algerian background perceive the phenomenon differently (Dweck, 1999). Vegeta's data corroborates with previous investigations on how disengaged from activities demotivated students become and how the behaviours needed for goal attainment are hindered (Chambers, 1993; Kikuchi, 2015, Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2021). Nevertheless, the present study differs in terms of depth and variety in the thought processes collected which constitute an emergent originality from previous research. The participants in this study offered eloquent and detailed answers that enabled them to extract the phenomenological core of demotivation.

Liza's data also corroborates with previous studies on how a lack of motivation leads to attrition thinking (Lovitts, 2001). Liza, due to her demotivation, is constantly filled with thoughts of quitting her endeavour despite her status of being a laureate. Her experience was filled with negative and painful life events that deprived her desire to fulfil her academic dream. The latter also

corroborates with how Hawlery (2003, p.24) described the PhD experience as “subjectively painful....that underlie most students’ decision to quit”. This accurately reflects Liza’s experience as she only recounts instances of demotivation and disenchantment stemming from her UK journey, which leads her to constantly think about quitting. Despite the fact that this study offers support to the previous scholarly work, there was almost no consideration of demotivation as a potential factor in attrition. This underscores another contribution to the study of demotivation at the international doctoral level.

2.3. Questioning Self-Worth and Losing Faith in the PhD: Navigating Doubt and Purpose

An important cognitive phenomenon observed as a result of demotivation is a series of questioning and reevaluating the self and the task at hand. The latter was pronounced more particularly within Liza and Zineb’s narratives, where due to challenges that impede goal achievement undergo a process of cognitive recalibration.

Starting with Zineb's discourse where she initially reveals a deep sense of self-reflection. Indeed, Zineb was questioning the value of the PhD in comparison to the suffering experienced “is it really worth it? all that suffering, is it worth it?” (Zineb, line 19-23, page 47). This demonstrates a critical moment where she doubts the value of her academic pursuits, primarily because of the emotional distress she has as an outcome of the task. From the quote, Zineb seems to have reached a breaking point where her tolerance for the struggle has been exhausted. In other words, despite having higher value attached to the PhD, facing struggles related to demotivation leads to reconsidering the actual worth of the goal as the latter costs her mental health.

Following the thought, Zineb pinpoints the mental health toll she experiences due to academic pressure “we’re all the time saying oh this PhD! We’re so tired! why are we doing this? like at a certain point, you feel that it's too heavy on you, it did impact your mental state” (Zineb, line 24-26, page 58). This illustrates the great sacrifices such as fatigue, disillusionment, and potential negative emotional consequences that come with the PhD in general and in falling under demotivation in specific. Moreover, she reports that such experience is not a one-time occurrence, but rather a lingering and permanent situation that coexists with the PhD during her doctoral timeline. Subsequently, the intrusive thought of PhD overwhelm is a recurrent and cyclical experience that is perpetuated by demotivation, highlighting once more its severity if left unaddressed. The case is particularly correct with the next respondent narrating desires to withdraw from the program.

Liza discloses how demotivation leads to despair and thoughts of withdrawal/attrition from her academic life. The latter is very concerning considering her status and motivation to pursue higher

education pursuits. She stresses, "when I am demotivated, I fell into despair and I only think about withdrawing and sometimes when I cannot even handle it because I know that I'm not good at anything else, I think about why I still exist" (Liza, line 1-4, page 79). This passage indicates the severity of demotivation driving motivated individuals not only from academic withdrawal but also to existential crisis. The sentence "I think about why I still exist" represents a deep-rooted questioning that Liza experiences upon heightened unaddressed demotivation. Because she attributes a great value to her academic studies which also constitute a great part of her identity, having the latter hindered shakes the very foundation of herself.

SDT defines that people experience intrinsic motivation when they have competence, autonomy, and relatedness (Deci and Ryan, 1980). Whereas, if these needs are unmet, the intrinsic motivation is also lowered. In Zineb's case, the initial enthusiasm and personal value attached to her PhD journey gave way to doubt and emotional distress, as seen in her reflection: 'is it really worth it? all that suffering, is it worth it?' (Zineb, line 19-23, page 47). This devaluation is in line with SDT as perceived incompetence and lack of autonomy lead to a decrease in intrinsic motivation (Deci and Ryan, 2017). Similarly, Liza's attrition thinking and existential questioning can be seen as a significant drop in internal drive due to demotivation 'I think about why I still exist'. In her case, the importance of relatedness is highlighted as rejection by the academic community which made her feel socially isolated. The latter made her less motivated, less productive and more prone to attrition thinking and even questioning her whole existence and purpose. The latter corroborates with the work of Mason (2012) on how students are more motivated when a sense of relatedness with the supervisor is achieved (which is not her case). It also coincides with Paglis et al. (2006) on how relatedness leads to productivity, better progression (Faghini et al., 1999) and most importantly less prone to attrition thinking (Bair and Haworth, 2004). Similarly, having relatedness omitted leads to the opposite results, which are observable within Liza's narrative and behaviours. Thus, SDT is applicable for broad consideration of the demotivational threats of these students and for highlighting the importance of their psychological needs fulfilment for their motivational and psychological states. Nevertheless, the extent to which Liza is questioning her whole existence as a result of demotivation is seldom recounted in the literature, highlighting new avenues for further exploration into how a simple decrease in motivation leads to life-threatening questions.

Moreover, demotivation was so impactful that Liza considered leaving her academic aspiration, even if it meant leading a jobless life. As she stresses:

So let's get rid of all these problems and burden and just satisfy myself with what I have and go back to the country and live the typical life that a jobless person might

have, why would I just face all these problems if they don't want me here?, I feel like my supervisor doesn't want me to belong to the researchers' world. (Liza, line 14-17, page 42)

Liza expresses her frustration with the current situation which does not favour her aspiration, along with a desire to escape the current pressuring academic environment. The existential crisis stemming from her demotivation drives her to think not only about quitting but also about settling for a simpler life, which is a clear decrease/shift in her aspirations. The latter highlights a somewhat defeatist attitude or an escape where she thinks that the trouble experienced is not worth the goal at the end of the journey, even if the job prospect is lost and her professional life might become non-existent. The phenomenological core extracted from Liza's demotivational experience highlights a multitude of interconnected themes. The latter are the following:

2.3.1. Escaping the Burden

Liza starts with a declarative sentence where she wants to “get rid of all these problems and burdens” as a result of her demotivation. This highlights her strong desire to liberate herself from the repetitive and lasting academic challenges/demotivation that became a burden rather than an elevating and rewarding pursuit. Moreover, the use of the word ‘problem’ might indicate the existence of other related issues that were not stated explicitly in the interview.

2.3.2. Settling for a Simpler Life

Liza, upon facing recurrent and lasting demotivating instances decided to “go back to the country and live the typical life that a jobless person might have”. Such a radical shift is not out of pure will but rather is a result of deep exhaustion and frustration. Liza's constant struggles with demotivation and suicidal thoughts lead her to consider going back to Algeria without accomplishing her dreams and living a jobless life as that would be less damaging to her mental health. Such a change of heart could be understood as a defeatist attitude and resignation from PhD goal in exchange for peace of mind.

2.3.3. Perceived Alienation

Liza's feelings of alienation and rejection are evident when she says “why would I just face all these problems if they don't want me here? I feel like my supervisor doesn't want me to belong to the researchers' world”. The feelings of exclusion result in emotional distress and a desire to withdraw as her belongingness is almost non-existent. This coincides with Strayhorn (2012) on how lack of belongingness leads to alienation. The case is particularly true for international students who abandoned their lives and went abroad. In a sense, the academic community represents the surrogate family (Walsh, 2010) they aspired to integrate.

2.3.4. Desire to Withdraw

Lastly, Liza's consideration to withdraw is not only a result of demotivation but also seems like a coping strategy to mitigate her emotional turmoil or to minimise the damages during her PhD journey. The latter highlights some experiences that remained in the dark for a considerable time. Thus, the following study shed led on the tumultuous journey of demotivated students who often face thought processes that sometimes go at the end of the spectrum.

GET 3 highlighted the cognitive processes that international doctoral students undergo when demotivated. Particularly, evaluating the worth of the PhD and the self during troubled periods of demotivation. Participants reported instances of questioning the value of the PhD in comparison to the mental health toll experienced, along with existential crisis. Such experience confirms the alarming state that some IDS undergo and therefore careful precautions and interventions need to be put into practice.

2.4. Reaching the Breaking Point: Suicidal Thoughts and Ideation

The following analysis represents one of the highest forms of severe demotivational symptoms reported in this study. The present GET enters into the deep psychological essence of demotivation experienced by Liza. Her passages offer transparent insights into her inner struggles; particularly on suicidal thoughts, ideation and contemplation. These extreme symptoms are rooted in her perceived disconnection and alienation from the academic community and home society. Liza's narrative provides a snapshot into how a motivated IDS can descend to severe demotivation, leading to considering a non-reversible outcome.

Liza opens an intimate window on the gravity of her suicidal thoughts where she delineates her silent suffering and despair. Such experiences and contemplation to harm one's self appear to be in secrecy as only her husband and a mental health professional are privy to her crisis:

I would be more honest with you, only my husband and the expert from well-being services know about this. I was secretly thinking about it, but one day, she asked me, 'Are you thinking of suicide?' I burst into tears because I had enough. Some might say, 'Really? Suicide over studies?' But for me, if I don't succeed, what would I do?...If my supervisor keeps rejecting my work with vague feedback like 'Would you please clarify that?' or 'This needs substantial changes,' how can I improve? I feel like I don't belong anywhere, not to the world of researchers, nor to any other space. What if I fail my thesis? What if I don't pass my upgrade? I will be excluded from the world of researchers... (Liza, lines 17-26; 1-33, page 42-43)

The passage demystifies Liza's distress around suicidal thoughts. Her narrative clearly indicates her intention to harm herself after her demotivation and foreseeing her inevitable academic failure. Such data corroborates with Hazell et al. (2021) on how PhD students suffer from suicidal thoughts. Using a qualitative cross-sectional survey design, they asked every doctoral college in the UK to spread the

survey to their doctoral students. Among 3,352 DRs, 1,263 (41.64%) reported living with suicidality. Sentences from participants include ‘I have had 7 suicide attempts over the past 9 years, including 4 during my PhD’, ‘Unfortunately suicidal ideation is a symptom I am very familiar with. My PhD crushes me sometimes and sucks all the happiness I had out of me’ and ‘I think the main reason for feeling suicidal and that you want to give up is the fact that you're doing your best to prove you are very smart and capable and you end up being put down and criticised very harshly I truly believe that a PhD degree can kill you’ (Hazell et al., 2021, p.761-763). These sentences perfectly align with Liza’s experience as she feels that life is not worth living because of her potential academic failure. Moreover, the last sentence matches the current predicament Liza is currently experiencing with her supervisor as she is always criticised and harshly commented over her drafts, leading to a feeling of suicidality. However, the difference lies in the trigger of such feelings. Demotivation as a cause of suicide at an international doctoral level was not collected in previous studies and hence represents a new originality and addition to the danger zones of the demotivational experiential feature.

Additionally, despite the fact that in Islam suicide is forbidden and viewed negatively, she seems fully aware of the situation as she reported it. The fact that she fears failure of PhD more than fear of death itself is concerning and indicative of the gravity of the situation as fear of death is a sociological and biological trait instilled in individuals to preserve them from self-harm (Bryant, 2011). The barrier that prevents self-harm seems to be cancelled per her academic predicament. Liza’s academic thriving seems to be an existential necessity where failure is equated with death. Because Liza lost motivation in her aspired community and was excluded, her demotivation led her to feel that there was nothing worth living for, thus engaging in suicidal thoughts and ideation. Therefore, in addition to depression, which is a risk factor for suicide, severe demotivation appears to be a factor as impactful as depression as it leads to total defeatism and reflections on self-harm.

2.4.1. Emotional breakdown during the interview

During the interview, Liza had an emotional breakdown where recounting the experience was so vivid to her that she started crying. Being the researcher, I stopped the interview per her acceptance of the request and scheduled another convenient meeting afterwards thus respecting the ethical consideration of minimising harm and maximizing benefit (BPS, 2021). Moreover, upon stopping the recording, I had an informal chat with her and made her laugh which represents the researcher offering immediate and direct support therefore ensuring ethical considerations. The reaction Liza had upon narrating her demotivating experience was insurmountable even being a past recurrence, this highlights the severity of the lived experience and adds a layer of importance and cruciality of demotivation at an international doctoral level.

Several implications could be inferred such as in relation to academic environment and mental health support services. The former could introduce new strategies to foster a more inclusive environment through training and mentorship programs where students collaborate with senior peers to avoid seclusion. The latter could tailor interventions such as early identification of mental health issues such as demotivation and alienation. Developing better protocols to refer students to adequate and appropriate mental health resources. Mental Health Screenings through screenings and surveys, increasing availability of counselling and offering anonymous online support. The latter is especially true for Algerians who regard talking about such problems as being embarrassing or even taboo. Thus, through the promotion of various strategies, the chances of getting severe demotivation and suicidal thoughts would decrease considerably.

2.5. Navigating the Maze: Seeking Solutions and Reconciliation

Contrary to Liza, Leila's approach seems to cope with demotivation by acknowledging and making sense of it. Indeed, her active acceptance and reconciliation with demotivation is noticed in her words: "I actually acknowledge me being demotivated, so whenever I feel demotivated, I just go with the flow, so I just give myself a say...have a rest...I'm OK with the fact of being demotivated" (Leila, line 19-25, page 42). This passage reflects the importance of meaning-making and acknowledging the naturality of demotivation as a rite de passage in the PhD journey "I do know that it's normal to be demotivated" (Leila, line 26-27, page 47). Leila recognises demotivation as a part of her academic journey. Her unique perception highlights the importance of acknowledging natural occurrences in daily life and goal achievements. Her responses refer to what is termed as meaning-making where people attribute sense to their experience as a part of the learning processes. Subsequently, due to the fact that she takes time to adjust and recalibrate her motivation, Leila's trajectory after the demotivating phase appears to be remotivation (Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2011).

Moreover, she implies the importance of self-care during such periods stating "I just try to forget about everything and to get a life and so that I can recharge my batteries" (Leila, line3-4, page 43). Because demotivation empties her batteries (such as Stallion), Leila takes a step back from her studies and diverts her current situation by focusing on her life in order to refill her inner strength and motivation. Furthermore, she used an Arabic sentence "أنا أتصالح مع الفكرة" which literally means "I reconcile with the idea", denoting a sense of acceptance towards the negative state of demotivation. The PhD is known as a roller coaster (Cuschieri, 2021), meaning that having a hard time in academic pursuit is not uncommon. Leila acknowledging such tribulations permits her to regulate herself and take time off to readjust and allow herself to rest. Instead of reacting emotionally to her demotivation, Leila recognizes the importance of prioritizing her mental health and decides to take some time away

from the current situation. Moreover, Leila adds to the inevitability of demotivation stating, “I mean four years journey, how on Earth you cannot be demotivated?” (Leila, line 8-9, page 46). Thus, reinforcing Cuschieri’s (2021) statement, Leila admits a hard reality that cannot be overturned by stating that demotivation is unavoidable during the course of the PhD program. Her statement normalizes the feeling of demotivation, viewing it as a typical part of her PhD journey. This also corroborates with Dörnyei and Ottó (1998) highlighting the fluctuating nature of motivation and how hard it is to sustain it in long-term goals such as the PhD.

The coping strategy is opposite to Liza for instance who chooses a much more severe and bleaker path after being demotivated. Leila's active acceptance and deliberate self-care strategies highlight her proactive approach to minimising the impact of demotivation and maintaining her well-being throughout her PhD program. Furthermore, Leila’s proactive approach entails minimising the effect of demotivation and finding solutions as soon as possible “So I think about how I can treat or heal the state of demotivated...I tried to reduce the effect and the period of demotivation” (Leila, line 3-5, page 43). Leila during the period of demotivation does not seem to relinquish all her motivated behaviours, rather she tries to find solutions in order to solve and cope with such a state, highlighting her inner desire to withdraw from the actual situation to resume her work. The latter is stated in her words “I try my best to not get too much immersed in the state of demotivation and carelessness so that it's easy to 'reprendre' (French for resume or get back)” (Leila, line 8-11, page 43). In this passage, Leila stresses her need to exit the demotivational mood or cage as quickly as possible to permit an easier resuming of her academic studies. The latter also implies her potential fear of a demotivational impact on her studies if the period lasted longer. Such a potential scenario could be informed or represented by Liza’s case where the demotivation accompanied her for a substantial period. Therefore, Leila’s unique reaction to demotivation highlights the uniqueness of individual experiences of the same phenomenon and how these react differently in the same situations (Dweck, 2006; Smith et al., 2022). Leila’s journey serves as an illuminating case of resilience and adaptability, essential qualities for PhD students in overcoming challenges such as demotivation.

Therefore, much like any other mental issue, demotivation has to be abated in order for the body to start the restoration of its systems. In other words, demotivation disturbs the relaxed state or equilibrium of the individual and the body can only regain its composure once demotivation is suppressed. The present chapter has demonstrated how thoughts can be dangerous leading its victims to consider worst-case scenarios such as attrition and suicide. Demotivation is thus a state that precedes these irreversible states. These findings suggest that demotivation has to be taken seriously at its earlier stages before the latter develops into severe cases as shown in the chapter.

Summary

Overall, this chapter extensively reported and discussed the experience of demotivation at an international doctoral level. More specifically, it focused on the inner world: feelings and thought processes that accompany demotivated doctoral students. Key elements pertaining to feelings include dissipation of enthusiasm; lack of socialisation, emptiness, alienation and avoidance; negative self-perception and imposter syndrome; overwhelming emotions and mental health challenges; autonomy, guilt, and regret and; fear and uncertainty. As regards thought processes, participants' narratives exhibited negative automated thoughts, avoidance, self-deprecation, withdrawal or attrition and suicidal thoughts. The findings discussed demonstrate the cyclical relationship between the two aspects and how one fuels the other. The findings also reveal how individuals react differently to the same event. For example, while some participants reach instances of existential crisis and suicide, others actively search for solutions during the phase, highlighting instances of resilience and coping strategies. The latter provides invaluable knowledge to foster better strategies to reduce the risk of demotivation for future PhD students. Feelings and thought processes represent two facets of the same coin that cannot be separated and need to be dually studied to fully understand and extract the phenomenological core of demotivation.

Chapter VIII. Sociological Dimensions of Demotivation

Introduction

The narratives in previous chapters have explored demotivation from a psychological perspective. However, such insight remains incomplete without considering the broader sociological milieu of their lifeworlds. For this reason, the present chapter expands the horizons of demotivation through the three sociological lenses of alienation and disenchantment which will be presented accordingly. These elements offer a compelling analysis of the UK Algerian postgraduates' experience. This part of the thesis will unfold how these sociological dimensions and their unique intricacies trigger demotivation hence contributing to the enrichment and the deciphering of the latter, reaching what Alvesson and Sandberg (2011) refer to as 'application spotting'. This research exploration not only enriches our understanding of demotivation through its novel approach but also offers an original report to policymakers through students' voices therefore enabling them to devise strategies to foster motivation for international doctoral students and even non-European students.

1. Alienating Experiences of UK Algerian Postgraduates

Prior to addressing the specific factors that triggered alienation for UK Algerian postgraduates, a brief explanation of the phenomenon is offered. The choice was made to use one passage as it resonates among all participants as they have all gone through a period of alienation. Stallion's excerpts provide an acute description of the phenomenon highlighting how the participants reflected on their own experiences, which is a core element in IPA known as hermeneutics (Smith et al., 2022). Stallion describes the phenomenon as follows:

As an international student, I tend to face the same recurrent challenge, it haunts my days and that's alienation...especially when I discovered that people are not interested in my culture, they don't understand my culture, they don't want to understand my culture and I feel that this is a little bit un-inclusive. I feel nostalgic to my country, to my people, to my culture, yes the only challenge I keep experiencing is alienation, although I've been living here for almost four years now. (Stallion, line 7-15, page 11)

Stallion's passage highlights the pervasiveness of the experience describing it as 'recurrent' and 'haunting'. He considers the phenomenon to be a challenge, which is, according to him, significant enough to derail him from reaching his objective. Additionally, he recounts a sense of cultural insensitivity and dismissiveness from the host country. As the UK does not seem to care about his background, this puts Stallion in a much more severe sense of exclusion. This feeling has accompanied Stallion for the entirety of his voyage. The latter only extenuates and exacerbates the international doctoral students' case. Finally, Stallion admits to a feeling of nostalgia to his home country and what it encompasses such as culture and society, highlighting a sense of homesickness toward his home

country. Such discrepancy might also be indicative of the differences in individualistic-collectivist culture where the UK leans more towards a less collectivistic culture and Algeria into a less individualistic one. The latter is displayed in how Stallion feels secluded and alienated in comparison to when he is in Algeria.

What Stallion describes perfectly accords with sociological literature on alienation (Marx, 1990; Jaeggi, 2014, Royce, 2015). The dislocation between the international doctoral students' culture and values with the host's creates a sense of alienation or feeling like an alien. Indeed, Stallion living in a country where his background (which represents his identity) is not only non-existent but also not considered triggers feelings of seclusion and loneliness. The latter also corroborates with Seeman (1959) on his psychosociological dimensions, namely isolation. In this case, Stallion feels isolated from the host's community as they have no common values nor does the host consider his. This forces Stallion to feel stranger to himself and unable to act normally. The latter is known as self-estrangement which is also another dimension of alienation. Brennan and Auslander (1979, p.16) describe that any individual "*in this mode is theoretically expected to be unable to be genuine self in participation with others*". Similarly, Stallion does not feel genuine in a setting that is totally different from his and thus acts 'mechanically' (Jaeggi, 2014). It is important to highlight that most participants felt isolated during their relocation and hence this interpretation echoes with the rest of the respondents.

Interestingly, Stallion has conducted his MA in disenchantment, making him knowledgeable and aware of such a concept. He highlights that alienation is inevitable during relocation as he states "I think it's very expected to experience alienation when relocating to a new country" (Stallion, line 32-33, page 38). This passage parallels Marx's (1990) foundational work, much like experiencing alienation is inevitable under the capitalist system, relocating to a new country represents also a cogent argument behind such a shift. As there are multiple variables stranger to Algerians, the latter creates a gap that seems to dehumanise and deprive Algerians of their true selves. Thus, alienation for international students moving from one country to another is a natural occurrence.

Moreover, Stallion reinforces his argument by stating "un-belongingness...you feel like an alien, you feel like a stranger, you feel like this is not your natural cultural space, that you are inhabiting a cultural space that is not yours" (Stallion, line 17-20, page 37). Stallion describes poignantly the feelings of alienation as reported by the literature such as Jaeggi (2014) and Marx (1990). Alienated people act the opposite way of what constitutes normality, leading them to feel 'strangers' and 'aliens'. Because the host's country does not represent their 'normal' environment, Stallion, and the rest of the participants, feel detached and separated from it unable to 'inhabit' its cultural norms. The act of

refusing to inhabit the culture of the host coincides with feelings of normlessness (Seeman, 1959) where a breakdown of his norms is observed and is obliged to integrate a new set of norms totally stranger to him. The latter leads to what he calls ‘unbelongingness’ which also aligns with Strayhorn (2012, 2019) and how lack of belongingness and integration is a prelude to alienation. Thus, alienation at an international doctoral level exists and exerts additional pressure on students who are not only undertaking the PhD alone from their home country but also realise the solitary endeavour of social science research in comparison to natural sciences (Mulligan, 2021).

5.1. Academic Alienation: A Manifestation Among International Doctoral Students

Participants' experiences of alienation were categorized into Academic, and Social and Cultural. The categories provide examples of alienation not only as being demotivating but also subtly relating to disenchantment. It is also noteworthy that the most important patterns that surfaced from the data on alienation began predominantly post-relocation to the host country and hence after the commencement of their doctoral studies.

John talks about the price of autonomy and the standards changes when relocating to a new academic setting, such factors triggered academic alienation as he highlights:

...plus they need to get used to all this; to studies, to how things work, to independence because most PhD students don't have classes, I didn't have any class and you've got to learn things, sometimes you may feel as an alien because a lot of students did their undergraduate degree here, their masters. (John, line 22-26, page 67)

John's sense of alienation stems from UK academic standards and overreaching emphasis on autonomy. The latter is observed when noticing that PhD students do not attend classes and have to learn everything by one's self. In other words, he remarks a distinct pedagogical shift from a structured curriculum to a mode of study that is entirely independent. Such a sudden transition resulted in feelings of alienation due to the difficulties of the challenges faced and the adaptability necessary to reach the required level. Finally, John's sense of alienation and estrangement was magnified as he saw other colleagues mitigating the transition better as they had previously achieved their undergraduates or postgraduates within the same institution.

John describes alienation as a sense of being estranged in the academic setting in relation to his context which could be termed as a lack of academic belongingness merged with a potential feeling of inadequacy (Strayhorn, 2012; Bandura, 1985). His adjustment to the new environment ‘to get used to all this’ and the PhD independent study requirement may indicate a sense of unfamiliarity and potential discomfort. Moreover, the absence of classroom contact ‘don't have classes’ might generate feelings of isolation and alienation (Marx, 1990; Seeman, 1975). Classes often serve as a shared space

where students interact and form connections thereby creating a community of practice (Lave and Wenger, 2001) or 'academic family'. The latter corresponds appropriately with John as it is crucial to his motivation and academic flourishing as he appears to be a social person.

Concerning Vegeta, he expresses that his academic alienation stems from his dislocation from the scientific communities and their ideas. The alienation is observed within a few passages such as "I feel like an alien to what is known as the mainstream social scientific community. I do not feel related to their mainstream ideas, nor do I feel represented by them" (Vegeta, line 27-29, page 82). Furthermore, he shares what ideologies he feels disconnected by and how the scientific community only works to substantiate them as he furthers:

All they're doing is substantiate ideologies... postmodernism, feminism, gender ideology, critical race theory, Marxism. It increases my alienation when I see social scientists defending these instead of talking about social phenomena in a scientific, factual manner instead of political discourse. (Vegeta, line 32-40, page 86)

Vegeta offers his critique of how researchers only serve to reinforce the already established ideologies. As Vegeta does not feel represented by them, a sense of normlessness emerges, which is individuals failing to feel recognised or recognise the current norms adopted by society (Seeman, 1959). Therefore, the current result corroborates with feelings of normlessness which further explicates his deviance in the latter stages. Vegeta adds "The works of older authorities, who defined the field, aren't anymore justifiable than any modern claim that can be made using the same method...I felt alienated when I realised that social science is not as empirical as I expected it to be" (Vegeta, 39-43, page 83). He expresses his disillusionment with the perceived departure from traditional empirical methodologies and human social activity. The sense of alienation triggered by the deception resonates with the definition of disenchantment of Max Weber (1948). Vegeta was disillusioned as his fascination towards the social world moved from empirical investigation to adhering purely to what he termed as 'The works of older authorities'. In this case, Vegeta finds himself unable to relate to the 'product' he is crafting, thus engendering feelings of meaninglessness (Seeman, 1959). Consequently, as he feels alienated from the product and the machine where he investigates, a sense of isolation emerges (Seeman, 1959) "I do not feel related to their mainstream ideas, nor do I feel represented by them" (line 28-29, page 82). Thus, Vegeta's alienating experience in this passage, among many others, highlights his alienating experience and displays the dimensions of powerlessness, meaninglessness and isolation presented by Seeman (1959).

Furthermore, Vegeta expresses his disagreement and deception over how social sciences pursue the truth:

I don't value this arbitrary relativistic approach to knowledge production. If there are multiple truths, then I don't see the value of research anymore...I thought the limitations put on the PhD are there to make sure that everybody is pursuing the truth, not make sure that nobody is. (Vegeta, line 7-12, page 85)

A sense of disillusionment emerges over a disagreement on how truth is sought. Vegeta argues that the only path to reality is through scientific measurement and hence rejects the prospects of 'multiple truths'. Consequently, he devalues the current research stream and considers the pursuit of knowledge useless or invalid. Moreover, he portrays the academic environment as a terrain for ideological warfare as he stresses "Because I see the social scientific community now as people who are going to university in order to become a member of an ideology community...it's like joining the Champions League" (Vegeta, 37-3, page 85-86). Vegeta became completely disoriented due to the transformation of the search for truth into an ideology war, and the penetration of political components into science only contributed to his desire to leave and feelings of estrangement.

Vegeta's journey culminates in a crisis of integrity as he furthers: "...It kind of brings questions about your integrity as a researcher... are you using this method, approach or ideology in your research because it's going to get you closer to the truth or because it is trendy or the trending ideology or philosophy" (Vegeta, line 17-20, page 87). Vegeta consequently out of alienation grapples with conflicts of integrity as a researcher. He wonders whether the truth-seeking pursuit is set on tools that approach the individual closer to the truth or rather the tools used are agreed by trend. In this case, Vegeta's reaction to these instances relates to what Seeman (1975) refers to as isolation and self-estrangement. Isolation is a result of failing to connect with the community due to the misalignments of their objectives. The worker in this case Vegeta is estranged from the community he works in leading him to "*assign low reward value to goals or beliefs that are typically highly valued in the given society*" (Seeman, 1959, p. 789). This perfectly fits Vegeta, as he assigns low values to the actual pursuit of truth which is highly valued by the community. Consequently, as the assigned value to the target objective or goal becomes low, the performance and efforts displayed would decrease, leading to a feeling of pure demotivation.

Vegeta's experiences depicted through these intimate reflections emit a wider call for an academic culture that prioritizes empirical truth-seeking, a pursuit that would deflect future researchers from ideologies of myopia. His lifeworld expressed through IPA hermeneutics allows for a deeper investigation of his profound sense of alienation. Fuelled mainly from ideological dominance, methodological disparities, and perceived loss of truth in academic inquiry, Vegeta allows us to enter his phenomenological core of being a stranger in his chosen field of study.

Moving to Leila who brings a distinct perspective on academic alienation. Her main alienating experience resides in the changed methodology which made her question her abilities as a PhD student “I felt alienated because I've found facing an obstacle in my PhD and I thought that I could never overcome it, so I thought this has to do with me being not qualified to be PhD student” (Leila, line 30-32, page 76). Leila reports having second thoughts about her adequacy in regard to undertaking the PhD. Interestingly, she reports that the obstacle was at that point impossible to solve, aligning with what Marguc et al.(2010) define in their obstacle theory as overwhelming and insurmountable. Further examples were provided such as “I had to make a major change to my methodology, and I couldn't really see the way through” (Leila, line 34-35, page 76).

This struggle led her to profoundly question her competence and place within the academic community: “I couldn't really see what's supposed to be done, what needs to be done, what's the way out, I was stuck, I thought that maybe I got it wrong from the very beginning, maybe I'm just not good at it, this is not where I belong”(Leila, line 35-2, page 76-77). Leila’s lifeworld provides a window into how academic alienation fosters feelings of reduced confidence, imposter syndrome and disconnection from the academic community. Despite being an Algerian laureate, this instance of academic alienation triggered a sense of questioning and doubt that shook her pre-established identity as a researcher (Hall, 2018) and led her to feel that she did not belong (Strayhorn, 2012; 2018). These elements serve as a sharp sword that severs the rope of motivation that is necessary to progress and succeed at this stage.

Concerning Liza, she emphasises once again the student-supervisor relationship. She expresses a disconnection between herself and her supervisor that made her feel academically alienated as she stresses: “...whenever I have a meeting with my supervisor...I feel that we are two people from two different worlds that we do not get each other” (Liza, line 3-7, page 84). The sense of alienation seems to be rooted in a perceived lack of understanding and empathy from her supervisor ultimately making her feel like an 'alien' “I feel like I'm an alien for her because sometimes I believe she doesn't understand what I mean, or even what I am saying...so I feel like I am weird to her” (Liza, line 7-11, page 84). Despite her ability to communicate effectively with other English teachers and students, her interactions with her supervisor make her question her adequacy as a PhD student. She reflects, “Whenever this happens, I feel like I'm not a good fit for the current position I'm in. I feel that I'm not a good fit for being a PhD student” (Liza, line 17-19, page 84). It appears that whenever Liza has a supervisory meeting, the latter shakes her confidence and ability towards completing the goal she sets. These results corroborate the seminal work of Chambers (1993) on how demotivated students display a lack of self-confidence. However, the notable difference is the ability of Liza to

clearly articulate her predicament and how she feels during the experience ranging from doubt, and questioning to pure existential crisis.

Interestingly, Liza's alienating experiences are only present when conversing with her supervisor. Indeed, she expresses that whenever she communicates with her academic surroundings, she feels a sense of belonging, "I feel I belong to this group of people however, when I talked to her, I feel that I do not belong" (Liza, line 33-35, page 84). The passage highlights that her alienation only resurfaces when talking to her supervisor which could indicate a major alternating factor for her success and wellbeing as supervisors are the pillars of postgraduate students' success (Wisker, 2008). Additionally, she highlights that the supervisor does not seem to be aware of her needs "I feel like she doesn't know what I need, what I want, even if I communicate this with her verbally, as if she doesn't get me or as if I'm supposed not to ask these questions or not to suggest suggestions or not even have such conversations with her" (Liza, line 26-29, page 85). Belongingness and integrity are important parts of human thriving and motivation (Maslow, 1954; Strayhorn, 2018). The alienation Liza experiences through her frequent contact with the supervisor seems to deprive her of that sense of belonging exponentially. Thus, deprivation of belongingness and integrity made Liza doubt her competence and abilities leading to the symptoms of disengagement.

In sum, Liza's experience corroborates Seeman's (1959) dimensions of alienation, particularly powerlessness, meaninglessness and isolation. Liza seems to have lost the power to convince her supervisor, despite her aptness to do so with her peers. Meaninglessness emerges as a case of her communication breakdowns and misunderstandings with the supervisor, driving her to lose meaning behind her PhD pursuit. Finally, isolation is a result of failure in establishing working relationships with her supervisor. Consequently, Liza finds herself isolated from her academic community whenever she meets her supervisor "when I talked to her, I feel that I do not belong". The data suggests the need for supervisors to foster a better relationship with the supervisees where they can feel understood and can communicate safely as they have the power to shake students' sense of academic belonging and overall PhD journey. The latter is much more accentuated within the international PhD community who are far away from their home and consider universities and supervisors part of their abroad family (Walsh, 2010).

Finally, Oreo's academic alienation concerns an instance that converges with Liza's theme. However, the cause was not a difficult relationship but rather the sudden departure of this later. When Oreo's primary supervisor was made redundant, it caused a severe sense of dislocation and alienation as she stresses, "I felt estranged to the rest of my supervisory team, I felt alone" (Oreo, line 35-37,

page 40). Oreo describes feelings of estrangement from the rest of the supervisory team, which corroborates with definitions of alienation such as Jaeggi (2014) where Oreo felt a relationlessness towards her team. It is important to highlight that her situation is made worse as her supervisor was knowledgeable, helpful and motivating. The latter drove Oreo to consider abandoning her PhD project. This type of academic alienation serves as a cogent argument for her demotivation and potential attrition thinking. Moreover, what deepened Oreo's predicament is the university management as she stresses "But [what] made it worse is that graduate school did not really care that much about the fact that I had no supervisor, they didn't contact me, they didn't try to assign a new supervisor for me" (Oreo, line 30-32, page 41). Oreo reports being neglected and not being updated or comforted about her situation by the university which made her feel betrayed, discriminated and excluded justifying her academic alienation.

These elements are further magnified due to Oreo's nature as an international student. The graduate school's lack of responsiveness and perceived poor management of Oreo's predicament only heightened her sense of alienation. The importance of university support has already been established, for example (McCray and Joseph-Richards, 2020) found out that such factor is the reason behind students' resilience and PhD timely completion. The university services such as academic and emotional support were reported as one of the core elements leading to their success. Similarly, as these are lacking, they induce feelings of doubt and weakened resolve. In this case, Oreo's experience confirms the previous study's data by showing its significance in its absence and how the latter could either facilitate or worsen worst case scenarios.

This section highlighted the different academic alienation from different perspectives. Although the element triggering the alienation was different, the outcome relates to academic mismatch and disconnection. Examples reported include alienation in relation to research traditions, research methodologies, communication breakdowns, and lack of support. These results call for the creation of a more inclusive academic environment that ensures equitable treatment for all students.

5.2. Social and Cultural Alienation

As its name suggests, social and cultural alienation refers to feelings of being dislocated from the host's country from various areas such as the societal, religious and cultural. Due to relocation, the participants' equilibrium was compromised to the point of altering their goal of completing the PhD. Therefore, social and cultural alienation induces feelings of demotivation towards PhD completion.

To start, John talks about feeling a bit disconnected and out of his comfort zone when relocating to a new setting where his background may seem a bit useless as he states "studying in a new place, the

culture is different, people are different, standards are different, the society is different, everything is different” (John, line 21-22, page 67). He further adds “when I started my PhD, I went to a university where I didn't know anyone, I was the only Algerian at that university that year, so I was out of my comfort zone...the whole world was different from my world” (John, line 2-6, page 68). John's responses emanate all features of social and cultural dislocation. Upon relocating for PhD studies, he notices differences and unfamiliarity across all aspects of his new local such as the culture, people, standards, and society. The emphasis was noticed when using words such as ‘different’ and ‘new’. The latter represents not only alienation (Marx, 1990) but also the psycho-sociological element known as normlessness (Seeman, 1959) where his norms and regulations have disappeared, highlighting a sense of general anomie. Furthermore, being the only representative of his nationality at the host university exacerbated his feelings of isolation ‘I was the only Algerian at that university’, such kind of isolation from other potential UK Algerian postgraduates intensifies the divergence between his familiar world and the new one. This multi-layered experience underlines John's struggle with adaptation and integration into a socio-culturally different milieu leading to feelings of alienation. Moreover, highlighting a flagrant difference in cultures where everything is different might also indicate that what John has found during his relocation is a different country in terms of individualism-collectivism spectrum, leading him to be outside his comfort zone.

Zineb underwent myriads of instances that drove her to feel alienated. She expresses Cultural and Linguistic misalignment as she declares:

...I felt alienation first with policeman when I tried to find my way, he was like “*you go to the roundabout...*” I was like “*can you speak slowly please? It's my first time*” but later on, you discover other things that are culturally different...something that I really felt weird towards is seeing transgender, I was like in a shock. So, it's something that puts you out of your own place, it's like experimenting that notion of being inside an environment that doesn't resemble you in any way. (Zineb, line 34-5, page 69-70)

The quote provides multiple elements related to social and cultural alienation. Zineb expresses the huge difference between her and her host country based on language and culture. She provides a first example of linguistic alienation upon her contact with a police officer who spoke too fast for her to comprehend on the first interaction. Despite the fact that Zineb is an English major who has English proficiency, she could not fully interpret the message and had to ask for repetition and a pace decrease. The latter could be understood as a communication breakdown when Zineb is unable to fully communicate with the policeman only serves to fuel her dislocation with the host country. Another example she provides relates to cultural differences, more specifically ‘transgender’. Zineb who comes from Algeria narrates that such a phenomenon does not exist, and such differences not only accentuate her alienation but put her in a state of shock. These experiences serve as a demonstration

of the additional linguistic and cultural challenges international students face during their transition to a new country and how such differences make them that they do not belong.

Moreover, Zineb shares instances of being disregarded and prejudiced within her academic context. She recounts an example of attending a seminar where she was not listened to with interest as she recalls “...when starting the PhD like proposing ideas that seem a bit complex...people have lack of interest towards what you were saying...people having prejudice against you without knowing you” (Zineb, line 22-31, page 72). Being disregarded in a conversation is not uncommon for international students as they are most of the time stereotyped (Moh et al., 2021). This feeling of being excluded and wrongly judged serves as a powerful alienation amplifier. Zineb by being discounted in the conversation feels demotivated and left out as being uninteresting. The latter not only corroborates with previous studies of international students’ challenges such as Sherry et al. (2010) and Titrek et al. (2016), but also the feelings of being excluded worsens the feelings of lack of belongingness (Strayhorn, 2012).

Lastly, Manel’s experience revolves around alienation induced/caused by religion. Indeed, as a Muslim girl who practices her faith, Manel dresses with the Hijab attire denoting her devotion to Islam. The latter makes her feel different as her clothing style is visibly noticeable. Consequently, Manel reveals a sense of insecurity and fear as she states, “In the UK...being a Muslim girl with not only a headscarf but the whole Islamic hijab...makes you feel alienated...it's something that people can see, that you are different because the way you dress is apparent to others” (Manel, line 16-20, page 79). Therefore, her alienation goes beyond the simple internal fact of adhering to the Islamic religion but also practising it through externally wearing the Hijab. Interestingly her alienation not only corroborates with definitions of the terms such as Marx’s (1990) or Jaeggi’s (2014) but offers an external layer of the phenomenon which people actually can see on the spot. Alienation if only internal will not be easily observed or noted; however, by wearing something observable, Manel finds herself more exposed than her other Algerian female colleagues who do not wear the Hijab.

Due to such alienation, Manel confesses having concerns about personal safety. She expresses the fear that her visible markers of faith (Hijab) could potentially make her a target for Islamophobia: “...it generates feeling of insecurity because you know that Islamophobia is a thing, and you may be targeted because of the way you’re dressed... sometimes you question the looks of people at you...someone can attack you because you're dressing that way” (Manel, line 3-8, page 80). Manel highlights important aspects related to the complex nature of alienation among international students. She pinpoints how her visible religious identity seems to generate feelings of insecurity as Manel feels

'looks' from some people which she fears is related to Islamophobia, thus intensifying feelings of isolation and marginalization within the host country. Subsequently, Manel is 'mortified' (Marx, 1990) as her safety needs are at risk because of her religious designation. Her testament adds new layers and dimensions to the already-established framework of alienation (Seeman, 1975).

Another powerful impact of alienation Manel reports is what could be termed as 'double alienation'. Manel divulges that when she goes back home to her family to recharge, she finds herself treated like a 'guest'. The family represents the nucleus of someone's identity and belonging. By having her appartenance/root dismissed, Manel is left with feelings of resentment and melancholy as she reports "I felt when I came back home, I was always treated like a guest...it's more like a bitter feeling, heartbroken at times...you just feel like you are neither home when you're in the UK and you have all lost that feeling of home in Algeria as well" (Manel, line 9-11, page 80). The passage reflects the powerful changes alienation exerts on international students the experience the notes a sense of dislocation and isolation. Manel yearning for her family represents her nucleus and sense of belongingness. However, alienation makes her feel like a stranger in her own family. The experience provides a compelling insight into the heavy emotional toll that alienation exacts on international students. 'Double alienation' represents thus a transition wherein international students due to their absence from home feel alienated at the end of both spectrums.

This small section outlined the varied differences that trigger social and cultural alienation. During their travel to the UK to undertake their PhDs, participants lived instances of cultural, linguistic, societal and religious dissimilarities, fuelling the sense of alienation. The fact of having to integrate too many differences and focus on finishing the PhD represents a daunting task. As these elements represent an important part of their identities and personalities, incorporating new elements that go against what they used to know appears rather unpleasant and disenchanting.

5.3. Alienation as Demotivating

Alienation was a source of demotivation for the majority of the participants. Manel's case is particular due to her introverted personality. However, she confessed that if the alienation had been a little bit more intense, that would have demotivated her. The table shows how many of the participants related alienation to demotivation:

Table 9: Participants Reporting Alienation as a Source of Demotivation

Participant's Name	Stallion	John	Zineb	Manel	Vegeta	Leila	Liza	Oreo
Study Participants Identifying Alienation's Demotivating Effect	X	X	X		X	X	X	X

Stallion reveals that his initial feelings of alienation lead directly to demotivation “alienation led to a feeling of demotivation” (Stallion, line 29-30, page 39). Thus, creating a bridge between alienation and demotivation. In other words, alienation as a phenomenon represents a sociological dimension contributing to demotivation. Moreover, the feelings not only decrease the mood but also the feeling of belongingness “When you’re feeling alienated, you also feel demotivated, you feel that you do not belong in a particular cultural space” (Stallion, 24-26, page 41). Subsequently, alienation and demotivation share similitudes and impact international students with both a lack of belongingness and a decrease in academic engagement.

John's accounts resonated with similar experiences: “I had no feedback from others and there was no construction of knowledge, I needed to learn everything the hard way...So, alienation didn't have a good effect on my PhD experience” (John, line 11-17, page 73). John elaborated on the feeling of emptiness, lack of interest, and motivation, which in turn led to a decrease in self-confidence and productivity “When you’re not proud of yourself then of course it affects...my motivation, I wasn't motivated, I couldn't study, I couldn't be as productive as I was” (John, line 8-12, page 76).

Zineb acknowledged that the feeling of alienation could decrease motivation but also mentioned developing a sort of resistance to this negative impact over time. “Sometimes at some point, it could decrease your motivation, but with time, you develop resistance for this negative impact”. In this respect, Zineb talks about the ability to develop resilience and coping strategies necessary to combat negative feelings.

Vegeta's account was particularly poignant, highlighting the demotivational impact of alienation on his studies “I had the sense of loss of value...So, it had a demotivational effect” (Vegeta, line 15-22, page 84). Vegeta further talked about the integrational motivation being eroded and how it affected his identity as a researcher and a human being “The demotivational effect that alienation had on my PhD, it removed this integrational motivation...It kind of have a paralysing effect makes you stop and reconsider before you engage” (Vegeta, line 26-27, page 87). The loss of value caused by alienation ultimately decreases his engagement towards his studies, which are typical symptoms of demotivated students (Chambers, 1993), thus denoting a sense of demotivation.

Leila's story echoed similar sentiments "it made me demotivated, I couldn't progress...I doubted my capacities, which meant I doubted my identity as a researcher" (Leila, line 23-25, page 80). The myriads of feelings of doubt, low self-confidence, and low motivation were clearly expressed in her narrative. By having her positive attributes deprived, the lack of confidence and low self-esteem are to be soared which constitute the foundations of a demotivated pupil (Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2021; Kikuchi, 2015; Chambers, 1993; Bandura, 1985).

For Liza, the academic alienation led to demotivation and questioning the very purpose of embarking on a PhD. "What's the purpose? I'm embarking on this PhD just to be academically active, if I'm academically alienated, what's the purpose of all that?" Despite seeing a potential positive outcome, the demotivation and depression were clearly emphasised "So, if it causes demotivation...even if you push yourself further...what's the purpose if you're already alienated" (Liza, line 39-41, page 89).

Finally, Oreo describes how her alienating experiences led to a halt in productivity and feelings of demotivation "That did affect my productivity because I couldn't think clearly" (Oreo, line 10-11, page 42) and "So, if that takes you a month to just bind the thesis how does that not demotivate me to prepare for my viva?" (Oreo, line 12-13, page 44). Therefore, feelings of alienation and its subsequent outcomes result in unproductivity and disengagement, which are components of a demotivated student.

Overall, this section has disseminated how alienation impacts UK Algerian students during their relocation to undertake the PhD. The multiple experiences of alienation were numerous and touched various sectors such as academia, society and culture. Moreover, the dimensions of alienation developed by Seeman (1959) were found within the participant's excerpts. Finally, a direct link between alienation and demotivation was established, bridging the two concepts from two different disciplines. Alienation therefore represents a potent additional factor faced by international students during their relocation. The participants' responses serve as an actual proof of such a claim and despite the fact that they are scattered around the UK, they shared similar concerns around common themes.

3. Disenchantment

The final sociological dimension explored is disenchantment. Alongside alienation, disenchantment helps in deepening the demotivational phenomenon's comprehension. Data reveal that all the participants went through a disenchantment phase that lasted from one month to a permanent duration. The latter leads to a disengagement or demotivation towards their respective theses and ultimately delaying their PhD progress. This coincides with (Shanachilubwa, 2023) on how graduate students experience disenchantment at such a level leading to negative phases such as

attrition thinking. The chapter is outlined according to the chronological order of the interviewed participants. The quotes reported are representative of their disenchanting state. Moreover, the details and uniqueness of each participant are offered to fulfil the fundamental core of idiography (Smith et al, 2022). A table is included for illustration.

Table 10: Participants Reporting Disenchantment as a Source of Demotivation

Participant's Name	Stallion	John	Zineb	Manel	Vegeta	Leila	Liza	Oreo
Participants Identifying Disenchantment's Demotivating Effect	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

The UK Algerian laureates reported that not only they have experienced disenchantment during their relocation to undertake the PhD but also that the experience was strong enough to turn down their motivation to its negative counterpart (Dörnyei, 2001). The present chapter will present personal accounts of disenchantment and how the latter is perceived by the participants.

Stallion approached the PhD with a certitude that he would undertake the endeavour with no issues and roadblocks. However, the reality was different in that it triggered feelings of disenchantment. The latter made him realise harsh truths, unexpected challenges, and the realisation of the potential needed to reach goal completion:

Before I started my PhD, I'd hoped that the journey would be very smooth and seamless, I thought that I'd start working in the PhD and my progress would be consistent and regular, but it wasn't, it was a journey of ups and downs, I've faced many struggles, challenges, I hadn't predicted that I'd face them, I think before the PhD, I was a little bit naive and idealistic, I wasn't realistic, I was overconfident, I thought that I'd face the PhD bravely and intelligently, then I discovered that I needed to learn further skills to finish the PhD. (Stallion, line 15-21, page 55)

The quote depicts a sense of disenchantment stemming from multiple aspects. The following could be considered as *Misalignment of Expectations and Reality*, *Naivety and Overconfidence*, *Unanticipated Challenges and Need for Additional Skills*. Although these elements were consistently echoed among all participants in the study, they were not all included in the final report to maintain brevity and focus.

Misalignment of Expectations and Reality: Stallion anticipated a 'smooth and seamless' journey which already sets him to feel disenchanting as he did not predict any potential hurdle. After starting his PhD, his enchantment was crushed by the reality that was accompanied by many 'ups and downs'. This demonstrates the unpredictability of the PhD which has been described as a roller coaster (Cushieri, 2021).

Naivety and Overconfidence: Stallion realised his naivety and idealism “I was a little bit naive and idealistic”. Furthermore, he expressed his overconfidence in his abilities which might hindered him to

account for potential demotivating factors. His overconfidence was also highlighted in sentences such as “bravely and intelligently”. Stallion despite his familiarity with the phenomenon did not expect to face such challenges and was not expecting that his motivation would be stopped.

Unanticipated Challenges: Stallion was unable to foresee the potential challenges that accompany the PhD “I hadn’t predicted that I would face them”. This demonstrates that the PhD requires more than hard work or motivation. The passage highlights a skill needed to anticipate and devise strategies that come with undertaking a task. The latter is accurate considering how challenging the PhD can be (Gardner and Holley, 2011; Spaulding and Rockinson-Szapkiw, 2012).

Need for Additional Skills: Stallion realises that additional skills were necessary to meet the journey's demands as he states, “I discovered that I needed to learn further skills to finish the PhD”. Stallion realises there is a gap between his skills and the PhD demands were a source for his demotivation. The latter aligns with Marguc et al. (2010) on how an insurmountable obstacle leads to a total action block. Stallion's disenchantment represents a demotivating force that hindered his PhD progress. This resonates with most motivation theories such as perceived competence and self-efficacy. When students recognise gaps in their skills, it can impact their perceived competence and self-efficacy, leading to feelings of inadequacy (Bandura, 1997). Ultimately, such perceived inability to perform can be a powerful demotivating force. Additionally, the concept of “learned helplessness” (Seligman, 1972) corroborates with the experience if students repeatedly encounter obstacles they feel they lack the skills to overcome. This was apparent in Stallion’s recurrent encounters with the ‘downs’ and the realisation that such gap needed filling through a new acquired toolkit in his repertoire of skills.

An interesting comparison made by Stallion to describe his state was relating his PhD’s disenchanting experience to the movie called 'The Matrix'. Such imagery highlights the uniqueness and usefulness of IPA in collecting idiographic and deep experiential features/accounts (Smith et al., 2022). Much like Neo who is trapped in a simulated reality, Stallion was trapped in preconceptions of the PhD that were enchanting and resembling the blissful ignorance of the ‘blue pill’. However, the reality experienced by Stallion mirrors the ‘red pill’ in the movie. After that, Stallion realises that his journey is full of 'ups and downs' and would not be as 'smooth and seamless' as he envisaged it to be. Subsequently, Stallion offers adequate and resourceful imagery that perfectly suits the PhD disenchantment process. It presents and coincides with what Smith (1987) called a harsh or 'rude awakening' after having previously held idealistic and less realistic expectations. Therefore, the imagery offers a deep and nuanced account. It accounts for the parallelism of enchantment and

disenchantment in the PhD journey where the former represents the blue pill whereas the latter represents the red one.

Ultimately, Stallion reported a multitude of negative emotions that hindered his progress and overall motivation:

Disappointed, demotivated, depressed, nervous, anxious, realism is very bitter, disenchantment has a bitter taste, it's very unsavoury because it's an awakening, you suddenly wake up and discover that reality is very bitter, sad, melancholic and miserable. (line 33-6, page 57-58)

Stallion is filled with feelings such as 'disappointment', 'demotivation', 'depression', 'nervousness', 'anxiety', 'bitterness', 'unsavouriness' and 'sadness'. He further adds that reality is very melancholic and miserable, highlighting his extreme disenchantment with reality. The combination of the lived feelings could all be categorised under the umbrella of the dark side, leading to a halt in his thesis progress. Thus, disenchantment as a sociological dimension leads to feelings of demotivation and much more. The newfound reality was negative to the extent that it disrupted Stallions' equilibrium which includes positive feelings and motivation. The elements described by Stallion echoes with Smith's (1987) definition of disenchantment as a 'rude awakening'. In this case, Stallion emerges from his idealistic expectation and finds a reality that is disappointing, depressing and bitter. Moreover, Stallion used the term 'awakening' which perfectly corroborates with the seminal work of Smith (1987) and Weber (1918) on losing all the magic only to find negativities such as those presented above. Subsequently, Stallion's experiences strengthen the previous scientific debate on disenchantment by adding how the phenomenon also spreads among international PhD students.

Other important effects of disenchantment on Stallion are a lack of trust and a radical thinking shift. Disenchantment not only deprived him of his confidence but also of expecting potential positive outcomes. The latter is demonstrated in his apprehension of publishing writers. Stallion highlights that after being disenchanted many times during his multiple trials to get published, he is now expecting rejections as a normal process. This indicates a shift from positivism to an inclination toward negativism after disenchantment. Furthermore, he states a shift from idealism to realism "I've become realistic, I'm no longer idealistic, I'm no longer naïve, I think I understand how the world works now realistically. I think the main effect is this shift from idealism towards realism" (Stallion, line 20-22, page 60). It seems that from the awakening, Stallion lost what Weber (1918) referred to as "losing magical significance" which is "idealism" and that part of "naivety". The transition from idealism to realism often comes after experiences that reveal the complexities, harsh truths, or pragmatic aspects of the world that were previously overlooked or unknown which was what Stallion reported. However, despite the negative perception of the experience, it could also be portrayed as a necessary route

toward growth and development. In other words, the experience was bleak, but also a teachable instance.

Another impact reported by Stallion is his lack of progress. He expresses that his PhD progress was compromised due to the demotivating impact of disenchantment. The evidence was when Stallion himself declared “I’m not making milestones here” (Stallion, line 21-22, page 61), or “I’m not progressing quickly” (Stallion, line 21-22, page 61) highlighting yet another time an expectation of progress shattered by reality and an actual proof of the hindering effect of disenchantment on motivation and progress. Therefore, disenchantment that stemmed from unmet expectations and ‘bitter’ realities of PhD progress act as a psychological barrier. In the context of PhD research, disenchantment is not just a transitory phase, it is also a substantial barrier to progress. It acts as a catalyst for demotivation by distorting the researcher's perception of the work and the world.

Moreover, to support the argument that internal motivation was severely impacted, Stallion stated that disenchantment deprived the PhD from its initial excitement and thrill as he states, “Oh no fun, I don't think it's been fun at all” (Stallion, line 30, page 62). Such a deep quote serves as a testament to how an experience gets unpleasant as a result of disenchantment. This result corroborates Case’s (2007) on how alienation deprives students of the elements of fun with academic pursuits. As alienation and disenchantment are closely related phenomena, one common result they share is the erosion of the initial motivation responsible for taking upon the PhD endeavour. Stallion’s experience represents a factual case of how motivated and enthusiastic individuals get completely overshadowed by disenchantment. Moreover, losing internal motivation is a huge impediment in his journey as previous studies highlighted that internal motivation is the predictor of PhD success and timely completion (Froiland and Worrell, 2016; Lindsay, 2015) The decrease in motivation stresses the importance of recognizing and addressing not only the academic demands but also the emotional challenges faced during a doctoral journey in education.

Concerning John, the flipping force to his disenchantment was the pandemic. John is a fundamentally sociable and outdoor individual and the deprivation of the latter darkened his overall experience as he states “...then there was COVID and I started being isolated, and I spent a lot of time alone at home, and then the nightmare started, and I lost all my motivation” (John, line 18-20, page 92). John reports losing all his motivation due to what Covid caused, which is total isolation and deprivation of the social component. This, according to him, was vital to his motivation and wellbeing. Moreover, the use of the word ‘nightmare’ represents a shift from his initial satisfaction with the previous situation to a new and unwanted situation. John seems to have lost the vital aspect that

contributed to his motivation, which is working in a community of practice (Lave and Wenger, 1991). Therefore, Covid caused an abrupt shift from a collaborative community where John was meeting, exchanging, and learning from his peers to a total form of isolation and seclusion where the only parties involved are his thoughts.

After disenchantment, John reported that the PhD is harder than what he expected:

it's harder than what I was expecting...I thought I'd have been at a more advanced stage at this level, PhD requires a lot of patience, motivation, I didn't know I was going to lose my motivation along the way, I didn't know I was going to be late, I didn't know I was going to have health issues. (line 26-29, page 98)

This excerpt coincides with the thoughts that Stallion shared on how little prepared he was and how numerous skills were needed to achieve the goal of PhD completion. John did not expect to be late in his PhD progression, to develop health issues, intensifying his disenchantment and demotivation. This episode of self-realisation is common among demotivated symptoms, where individuals no longer think that their initial skills and motivation are enough to compete with reality. Similar to Stallion, John felt stress, lack of self-confidence, lack of self-esteem, and instances of questioning himself, the quality of his work, and whether he possessed the right tools to complete the PhD. These factors perfectly describe the symptomatic behaviours of demotivated pupils (Chambers, 1993) leading to visible outcomes such as tiredness, sleeplessness, weight gain, concentration problems, negative self-image, and the development of an auto-immune disease.

Additionally, John reports having unproductive days, unable to achieve small goals due to the fact that disenchantment made him hate his topic:

I'm not motivated, but I have to do it, and when you force yourself, you're not happy because you feel like you used to love something a lot, and then all of a sudden you hate what you're doing, I used to love research, and then all of a sudden I hated my topic, I hated everything related to it. (line 28-31, page 99)

John went through a transitional phase from being motivated and happy about research and his topic to someone demotivated and hating his academic product/topic. Therefore, an apparent link between disenchantment and demotivation is noticed through drastic changes in the behaviour of someone being driven by study and research to a disillusioned individual whose own fascination with academia rendered him unhealthy and demotivated. John seems to have lost the inner force and fascination he once had, which is intrinsic motivation (Deci and Ryan, 1980; 2016) or in this case 'love for the topic'. A parallel is noticed when John moved from 'loving the topic' which signals motivation and enchantment to 'hating the topic' which in this case signals demotivation and disenchantment. This data shows how disenchantment is dangerous to people's intrinsic motivation, which has been related to success in long-term projects, developing autonomy and competence (Deci and Ryan, 2000;

Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2021). Subsequently, further research should be conducted as the phenomenon’s intensity is not only virtually apparent but also has an impact on the external side of PhD students, leading them to undergo severe negative episodes of mental and health issues.

Zineb's experience of disenchantment stems from a personal level. The latter concerns the truth about relocating to another cultural setting. Zineb thought that moving to the UK would allow her to be better understood as she already felt alienated back in Algeria, only to find her expectations shattered/disenchanting:

I had high expectations, I thought “*this is the time for you to be understood somewhere*”. But stumbling with the reality was quite bitter because “*if I'm not understood back in Algeria and I'm not understood here in the UK, where can I be understood? like in Mars for example!!!*” (line 31-35, page 92)

This quote represents a gateway to Zineb’s inner world through the unique intricacies and choice of words. Just as Stallion, Zineb used the word ‘bitter’ denoting her disgust/disappointment when her expectations were not aligned with reality. For better illustration, the main ideas are discussed in a table.

Table 11: Zineb’s Disenchanting Aspects during UK PhD Relocation.

Disenchantment Aspects	Explanation
1. Cultural Displacement and Alienation	Zineb's experience illustrates the emotional challenges of cultural transition. She expresses a profound sense of alienation that was not mitigated/alleviated when relocating which contradicts her initial expectations. Thus, Zineb experiences what could be termed as ‘double alienation’.
2. Expectation vs. Reality	A disparity between Zineb’s expectations of being understood in a new cultural setting and the 'bitter' reality of continued misinterpretation is evident. Apparent in her use of the phrase “High expectations”, it indicates that Zineb had an overly optimistic apprehension of her experience. The latter sets the stage for disappointment.
3. Individualized Experience	Zineb's account underscores the idiographic focus of IPA. In this case, the feeling of being an outsider regardless of geographical context. Whether it is Algeria or the UK, Zineb feels like an alien which intensifies her sense of disenchantment.

<p>4. Irony and Humour</p>	<p>Zineb’s use of humour “like in Mars for example!!!” may serve as a coping mechanism to deal with her disenchantment, suggesting resilience despite ongoing struggles with belonging and identity. It also may convey that her alienation makes her question her whole existence as to whether she truly fits somewhere. Interestingly, the use of the word ‘Mars’ indicates an extreme feeling of alienation, to a degree where no place on earth understood her. The latter adds a dramatic element to her disenchantment; emphasizing that her experience is not only challenging but also isolating to an extraordinary degree of a mere alienated person.</p>
<p>5. Existential Reflection</p>	<p>Zineb’s passage also tackles topics such as deeper existential questions regarding belonging and understanding. Reflecting on the universal human experience of searching for one's place in the world. Upon her disenchantment, Zineb seems to not find a sense of belongingness neither in her home country nor in the host one.</p>

Zineb's narrative provides a rich and nuanced understanding of how personal disillusionments are intertwined and how the latter affect the research participants' experiences profoundly. These results also offer implications for support systems. This narrative can prompt academic institutions to consider the broader social and emotional needs of international students that go beyond the academic support systems usually provided. Therefore, the study appears to support the argument that international students are facing bigger hurdles than domestic students echoing with Sherry et al. (2010), Desa et al. (2012) and Titrek et al. (2016) on how international students are indeed more vulnerable. Thus, the latter deserve more attention and a more welcoming environment socially and academically.

Manel experienced recurrent episodes of disenchantment that had a significant impact on her self-image, productivity, and motivation. From her responses, not only did Manel go through a period of extreme disenchantment, but she is still battling its effect:

...I had a very high expectations...I thought that the PhD would be full of adventures, nice things, conferences, seminars, it won't be boring, I would be writing interesting stuff, articles. However...it wasn't a nice experience, it was just trying to write stuff every month, receiving comments, correcting that version, submitting it back, receiving new comments, writing a new version, submitting it at the end, it's just that cycle that's repeating itself. (line 27-36, page 104)

From this testimony, Manel was not expecting the PhD journey to a monotonous circle of reading, writing, and recycling which she describes as ‘boring’ denoting her sense of disappointment and deception. It seems that she set her expectations to be beyond the writing component, as she expected more ‘adventures’, ‘nice things’, ‘conferences’, and ‘seminars’. Since the latter were not experienced, she went through a period of disenchantment and boredom. Consequently, Manel lost enthusiasm

once her apprehension was shattered, thus corroborating with the demotivation phenomena as the deprivation of enthusiasm and reality crash turns motivation to its dark side (Deci and Ryan, 2016; Dörnyei, 2000). As the enchantment stemming from expected adventure and other positive attributes were not found, Manel's intrinsic motivation got disfigured and changed, living a disenchanting version of her wanted reality (Deci and Ryan 2016; Weber 1918) which she concluded as being not 'nice'. Finally, Manel's state worsens as the whole experience feels like an endless loop that is 'repeating itself' denoting that the disenchanting experience is not a one-time occurrence but a perpetual negative one that weakens her resolve. Subsequently, the discrepancy between expectation and reality in PhD apprehension leads to disenchantment and demotivation.

The lifeworld of disenchantment deprived the very essence of Manel's motivation. She declares that her PhD experience was bleak and dark as pinpointed: "[it] turns you off, [it] turns off your excitement, your enthusiasm, the way you were seeing this PhD, it wasn't that great apparently, it's not as shiny as it seems to be from a distance, it doesn't shine and it's not that tempting after you're involved" (Line 13-16, page 107). Manel reports the loss of many positive attributes necessary for a motivating journey. The deprivations concern 'the self' 'excitement', 'enthusiasm', 'perception', 'greatness', 'shininess' and 'temptation'; altogether denotes a state of demotivation (Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2021). By dispossessing the PhD from its intrinsic motivation, the engagement and drive towards quality production and on-time completion gets heavily disturbed (Deci and Ryan, 2016). That being said, disenchantment from a PhD not only leads to demotivation but also deprives the self of its essence and identity, almost to the point of existential crisis. The experienced loss of excitement and enthusiasm lived by Manel can be understood as demotivation. Defined by Dörnyei as the "reduction or absence of motivation or enthusiasm, resulting in a decrease or cessation of goal-oriented behaviour" (Dörnyei, 2001, p. 5). Manel's experience of disenchantment aligns with this definition, as she has lost the motivation and enthusiasm that initially drove her to pursue the PhD due to shattered and unmet expectations "...was not that great apparently".

Manel reported a plethora of negative emotions decreasing her self-image. Upon probing, Manel expresses feelings of self-doubt, self-criticism, being harsh on herself, self-guilt and self-dissatisfaction. These emotions are common when expectations are not met and because of that, people begin to feel disillusioned and disappointed (Dörnyei, 2005, 2009; Weber, 1948).

These feelings associated with disenchantment and resulting boredom ultimately impacted the quality of the work. Manel expresses:

it's not like I enjoy them, but I did them anyways because I didn't have the choice.
When you don't enjoy what you're doing, you might not produce the same quality as

when you enjoy it. When I'm enjoying writing, I feel the quality is better... the final result is better than when I do things out of obligation or to meet a deadline. (Line 14–23, page 112)

Manel elicits a perfect example of working under motivation or obligation. She stresses that the element of joy is omitted and what remains is obligations and deadlines. Such results align with Marx's (1844) alienation, and Deci and Ryan's (2016) SDT theory. Because of the loss of enthusiasm, Manel feels that what she is doing is just out of obligation which is similar to Marx's theory on labour and how workers are the product of their own creation. Concerning SDT, intrinsic motivation has always been the precursor of success, engagement, and productivity (Deci and Ryan, 1980; 2016) and the lack thereof is a clear indicator of demotivational attitudes and behaviours towards the task at hand. Therefore, from the reported data and discussion, a clear motivational shift is observed within Manel, from an initially intrinsic tendency based on excitement and enthusiasm to finishing and meeting deadlines, leading to decreased quality work.

Consequently, Manel finds herself feeling like a robot and that everything feels mechanical: "...turns mechanical but in that aspect that I'm disenchanted where you're just like a robot doing something because you have to do it, not because you love it or because you feel eager to do it" (Manel, line 20-22, page 119). After her motivational transition; Manel has undergone a performance shift wherein her production does not feel human and compares it to a 'robot' or the process of production as 'mechanical'. Both theories of alienation and disenchantment corroborate within this context. Manel seems to be completely detached and isolated from her product, feeling like a robot or a 'cog in a machine' (Marx, 1844; Weber, 1918). Similarly, a demotivated person often displays reduced enthusiasm and commitment to the task at hand that resembles a 'chore' at that stage such as Manel. Demotivation renders activities at hand mechanical in the sense that the person goes through the process without much passion, creativity, or genuine interest. The behaviour here is to perform in a routine manner, with the sole goal of completing the task with the least amount of effort necessary rather than investing fully.

Other important results reside in her inner change and perception. Manel displays negative self-image tendencies "I see myself as less excited person, as less fun-loving person, as boring person, negative person" (Manel, line 16-17, page 119). As reported, a clear shift in her self-image when experiencing disenchantment is noticed. The negative attributes are evident through the use of descriptors such as 'boring', 'less fun-loving', and 'less excited', which indicates the impact of disenchantment on her inner image. Moreover, the sense of emotional change from a cheerful person towards a 'negative' one denotes how alienated from her old self she became also known as self-estrangement (Seeman, 1959), where she no longer recognises herself.

These elements triggered by disenchantment rendered Manel to feel ‘trapped’. Manel admits to feelings of imprisonment “you’re trapped in this PhD, and you cannot have the key to get outside of this experience unless you have that degree” (Manel, line 8-9, page 120). She reveals the sensation of being ‘trapped’ within the context of her PhD journey. Instead of a positive and joyous journey to pure discovery (Wisker, 2008), Manel describes the PhD as being a confining predicament that ‘traps’ its victims with no perceived escape unless reaching the finishing line. The entrapment designates a sense of emotional and psychological confinement in which degree completion represents the only ‘key’. The negative experience aligns with Hughes’s (2011) on how the doctoral journey is filled with negative instances leading to loneliness and anxiety about the future. Moreover, the experience described corroborates with Weber’s (1918) ‘iron cage’. Manel, due to her disenchantment, is trapped inside a cage with no chance to escape unless getting the PhD. Nevertheless, a slight difference is the fact that Manel’s case designates a situation that goes beyond a mere psychological blockage. The latter could be termed as ‘the Iron cage of PhD’ where doctoral students have to endure the harsh truths and tumultuous waves of the journey with no escape until reaching graduation. Interestingly, Manel’s description offers reinforcement and collaboration to Stallion and John. While the former used ‘The Matrix’ movie and the latter used ‘nightmare’ to describe their situation, all of them denote a sense of being trapped (Stallion trapped inside a simulated reality and John trapped inside a waking terror). Thus, this demonstrates how the uniqueness of experiences can lead to convergences in lifeworld (Smith et al., 2022).

Finally, just as Stallion, Manel provides an imagery of the disenchantment journey, where the experience resembles driving without joy:

When disenchanted, you're just driving, stopping for get gas, don't look to admire anything on your way, don't listen to music, you just stop for food because you don't want to faint from hunger, you're driving just to get somewhere because you've a parcel to deliver and come back, because you've an engagement to do, not because you're excited about getting there. (line 23-30, page 120)

This imagery effectively captures the essence of disenchantment. It denotes a sense of navigating only to reach the intended destination ‘you're just driving’, disregarding any joy ‘don't listen to music’ during or stops to discover new places ‘don't look to admire anything’, except for utilities such as ‘food’ and ‘gas’. The driving to fulfil an obligation or for the sole purpose of completing the task without deriving any joy or thrill captures the mechanical and purpose-driven nature of actions during disenchantment, as well as the purely extrinsic/mechanical motivation (Deci and Ryan, 2016; Marx, 1848). The nature of her PhD seems to have fully transformed into the role of a chore ‘parcel’ that needs ‘delivering’ instead of the joys of discovery (Petre and Rugg, 2010). Subsequently, as Manel

lost the thrill from her previous conception of the PhD journey, her image of the PhD is ‘collapsed’ and hence drives her to a sense of disenchantment and demotivation (Smith, 1987; Dörnyei, 2001b).

Next is Vegeta who experienced disenchantment through academia, particularly from the PhD and the social sciences. Consequently, he finds himself questioning his pursuit’s value and displays demotivated behaviour as a logical reaction:

My expectations of a PhD abroad were that of joining a community interested in empirical science to describe, criticise social phenomena, and articulate improvements to social reality. The reality: it’s a rite of passage, a process of knowledge production to the standards of your new institution, for the purpose of showing alignment with the community’s practices rather than the pursuit of truth. It’s more procedural than objective; more emphasis on process than on truth. (line 29-38, page 97)

From this passage, Vegeta seems to begin his pre-academic journey with an idealisation of the academic/scientific community. He starts his PhD with a perception that the scientific community is rooted in empirical science. His expectation was grounded in a view that science and research are means to investigate, criticise, and improve social realities. Unfortunately, he found a blatant contrast of his preconceived/enchanted reality; thus, putting him in a state of disenchantment or ‘rude awakening’ (Smith, 1987). Vegeta reports finding the PhD to be more of ‘a rite de passage’, that the experience is more on how adherent to procedure and institutional norms individuals are rather than the genuine pursuit of objective truths and substantive scientific exploration.

Subsequently, Vegeta was forced to incorporate the hard truth he faced and unlearn his enchanted version. The latter could be demotivating and even traumatic as Smith points “*Disenchantment appears to be a particularly traumatic instance of unlearning*” (1987, p. 39). The old information Vegeta possesses has been unwillingly crashed and replaced leading him to lose his sense of value to the task at hand and ultimately demotivating him. However, what is unique about Vegeta’s experience is that his disenchantment core opposes Weber’s fundamental of disenchantment, where he longs for a world of rationalisation and pure intellectualism rather than magical/enchanted attributes. The latter contrasts with the conventional understanding of disenchantment as described by Weber where things lose their mystical or magical qualities due to the rise of rationalisation and scientific enquiry (Weber 1918; Royce, 2015). Therefore, through IPA, Vegeta’s idiographic experience allows us to provide a novel interpretation of the phenomenon.

Vegeta, just like Stallion, admits his naivete. However, he holds himself accountable for being primarily enchanted or fooled:

I feel like a fool for being enchanted in the first place. I feel like I was a victim of unrealistic marketing, and it was raised in a way where being pulled by anyone is on you, it's not on the person who fooled you, it's your fault if you were fooled by

someone, a magician, a university, anybody, if you were able to be fooled, then it's on you, you are stupid enough to be fooled. (line 4-8, page 99)

Vegeta battles with feelings of self-blame and accountability as to why he got lured by such unrealistic academic marketing. He does not seem to hold anyone accountable for his state apart from himself which denotes a certain responsibility and accountability. Nevertheless, the severe questioning and self-blame serve as a gateway to his emotional and cognitive state when disenchantment invades the experience. Vegeta falsely based his image and hence his motivation on a shaky foundation which eventually disenchanted his previous beliefs and impacted his motivation. Therefore, the quote offers unique insight not only on disenchantment but also on how unique reactions are observed across people (Dweck, 1999; Smith et al., 2022).

Moreover, Vegeta reports feelings of 'self-loathing', 'self-pessimism', 'self-degradation', 'self-hate' and feeling like an idiot. All of these elements are consistent with demotivated behaviours reported by Chambers (1993). However, the nature of this study offered a plethora of feelings that go beyond mere lack of self-confidence and self-esteem and provided the symptoms of adult learners at an international doctoral level in contrast to 9-year-olds. This is a novel way of looking at disenchantment and demotivation symptomology that has been rarely reported in the previous literature.

Consequently, much like Stallion, Vegeta transitioned from optimism to realism. However, Vegeta's difference from Stallion is he first went through a period of pessimism to regulate to realism "I was optimistic, then I became pessimistic, and now I'm going back to realism" (Vegeta, line 22, page 99). As an imminent consequence of disenchantment, Vegeta reported having lost his inherent curiosity and sense of value to the postgraduate endeavour "I was motivated by my sense of value. So when I value something, I'm motivated to do it, and disenchantment has devalued the PhD for me enough for me to hate going through the motions" (Vegeta, line 40-2, page 102-103). As his motivation is attached to his sense of value, having the latter omitted would only result in the motivation being restrained leading to a state of demotivation.

These traits are prevalent in the existing literature, thus aligning with, and supporting the findings in question (Dörnyei, 2001b; Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2021; Deci and Ryan, 2016). Losing interest entails a lack of internal motivation which highly suggests a state of demotivation and disinterest (Chambers, 1993; Dörnyei, 2001b). The latter corroborates with Vegeta's disenchantment in many instances such as "I think the PhD was over-sensationalized, it's just an over-glorified task" (line 11, page 98). Moreover, the disenchanting experience resulted in him feeling like an idiot and fooled and demotivated corresponds with what Kikuchi (2015) terms as pulling the learner down. Vegeta was pulled down from optimism to pessimism to feeling like a fool due to his disenchanting experience

leading to a devaluation of the task at hand and hence demotivation towards completing the goal. Therefore, a cogent argument stemming from both evidenced data and literature is the fact that disenchantment has a demotivational effect on people's motivation at an international doctoral level.

Leila's experience highlights yet again her uniqueness compared to other respondents. She seems to have made more sense of her disenchantment than other participants highlighting "expectations are always far from reality" (Leila, line 32, page 89) and "because we cannot expect everything" (Leila, line 3, page 90). Thus, a background understanding of the phenomena is apparent as she seems to have already undertaken her own thought processes on the subject matter. The latter corroborates with the IPA principle known as hermeneutics; where individuals make sense out of their experience (Smith et al., 2009; 2022).

Leila's experience of disenchantment stems from anticipating many positive enchanting experiences from diverse sectors as she stresses: "I was expecting more social integration, more academic integration, more support, more value to the PhD, meeting more people, getting more job opportunities, more development academically, all of that didn't happen" (Leila, line 10-13, page 89). Before embarking on her UK doctoral journey, Leila expected to be stimulated from various domains such as social, professional and academic. However, these were not met once she relocated and started her PhD. The latter leads to a sense of disenchantment as she was under the desirable spell (Smith, 1987) that appears to be the prelude to her disillusionment. Therefore, Leila concluded that "expectations are always far from reality" (Leila, line 30-31, page 40) which reflects a common sentiment many individuals experience and share when their initial anticipations of a given experience do not align with the actual outcomes. Such realisation can have implications for demotivation, especially in terms of academic pursuits. Previous studies have related unmet expectations and demotivation, which appears coherent as motivation is based on a set of expectations and gains from a given objective (Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2021; Deci and Ryan, 2016). If the foundations of motivation are not found, the latter collapses paving the way to demotivation.

Leila seems to have experienced a misalignment between her expectations and reality that stagnated her PhD completion. Her extended timeline regarding her doctorate which contradicts her initial expectation of 3 years likely exacerbated the feeling of demotivation and this example is one of the clear-cut discrepancies between plans and actual reality. The present study's results corroborate with previous ones as Leila and all remaining participants had a reality check that disfigured their motivation leading to a sense of demotivation.

Difficulties in integration and socialisation have also previously been reported (Sherry et al., 2010; Desa et al., 2012; Titrek et al., 2016) stemming from a lack of sense of belongingness or due to the absence of emotionally supportive networks. In this research, Leila's disenchantment emerges from various reasons including isolation as a consequence of the pandemic and disenchanted expectations. As established, the nature of the PhD is already solitary (Cuschieri, 2021) and the addition of forced solitary confinement makes the journey much more difficult to surmount. Moreover, this is particularly hard for internationals who relocated and have left everything behind; described as a 'vulnerable population' (Sherry et al., 2010) this infers that simple obstacles are multiplied for this population. Subsequently, disenchantment is a barrier to students' academic engagement and PhD timely completion.

Leila experienced a heightened emotional response in reaction to disenchantment which included feeling stupid, doubtful, disappointed, and sad. All that can be categorised under internal demotivating symptoms. Moreover, a crucial change in Leila lies within her motivational orientation. She reported that initially, she expected a passionate experience wherein she "fall(s) in love with the topic" (line 25, page 90). Similar to Stallion's declaration, this statement indicates a strong sense of internal commitment/motivation to her topic almost to a level of a human relationship. This internal motivation has been reported as a necessity for achieving long-term goals (Deci and Ryan, 2016; Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2011; 2021). Nevertheless, the nature of motivation changed from loving the topic to "it's all about feasible research, something doable in a short period of time" (30-31, page 90). Thus, disenchantment deviates the motivational core from wanting something deeply because of the derived joy to just being able to achieve on time it without any emotional attachment. Such change was highlighted by John and Manel, pinpointing the influencing power of disenchantment on motivation.

An important emerging data is Leila's declaration "disenchantment will never lead to happiness" (Leila, line 14-16, page 93). It seems that Leila is trapped in a dark iron cage of disenchantment that resembles demotivated thinking tendencies. Happiness is an important factor of intrinsic motivation (Deci and Ryan, 2016) and the loss of the latter would trigger a cascade of negative outcomes. However, instead of being a temporary phase, the state of disenchantment according to Leila may never lead to happiness and therefore motivation may not be regained. In other words, leaving motivation in a perpetual state of depletion. This was previously mentioned in prior literature such as (Saltus, 1985; Furnham and Treglown, 2017) where happiness was lost due to disenchantment either in life in general or work in specific. Nevertheless, there was not an instance of absolute eternal unhappiness due to disenchantment. This new emerging data appears to support the argument for a reevaluation of the current set environment for international students who apparently still remain

vulnerable and exposed to danger zones. It is important that future studies emphasise disenchantment at an international doctoral level for the purpose of aiding and informing policymakers and institutions to make the necessary arrangements for a better and supportive learning environment.

Lastly, Leila reveals that disenchantment deteriorated her perception of the PhD. Initially, she aspired to the PhD out of curiosity, thrill, and excitement; all of which are intrinsic motivators (Deci and Ryan, 2016). However, disenchantment degraded her perception and importance of the goal to a simple chore or “*corvée*” (Leila, line 2-3, page 94) that needs to be finished. These findings are broadly in line with the conventional definition of demotivation and how unmet expectation deceives the individual’s sense of value (Furnham and Treglown, 2017). Individuals, like Leila, who are initially highly motivated intrinsically got disenchanted as their enchanted vision got severely impacted. This corroborates with seminal works of Weber on how the magic was lost due to the unexpected rapid change which perfectly describes Leila’s predicament. This also resonates with the recent work of Shanachilubwa (2023) on how developing academic disenchantment dissuades highly motivated students from completing their PhDs and pursuing a career in academia. Given the risk of losing motivated students in achieving their goals, it is relevant to investigate and address academic disenchantment at the doctoral level.

Nevertheless, the study offers an originality regarding the changed perception of the PhD. The Algerian case presents with a particularity. Their signed contract stipulates that they will get an offer back in Algeria only if they successfully complete the program within their set timeframe. Leila expresses that she is faced with no other choice but to finish the program successfully as any unexpected delays might endanger her 'entire future'. This puts extra pressure on the Algerian laureates to complete their program regardless of what might happen such as mental or health, financial or personal issues. This extra layer of inescapable pressure might have shifted the PhD from an endeavour based on curiosity and discovery (Wisker, 2008) to “a life or death” situation. The described situation entails a somewhat forced imprisonment of both the mind and the body. This result corroborates with feelings of entrapment known as The Iron Cage (Weber, 1848). However, the current study differs in terms of its participants and their idiosyncrasies (fully-funded students) which offers genuine and new insights into the phenomenon.

To conclude, Leila offered a unique imagery of disenchantment, comparing it to feeling drowned and hit by ocean waves: “...on the beach, you expect swimming to be very exciting, enjoyable, fun experience. But when you go into the sea, you like drown, the waves slap you in the face, then you get bites, you really deal with the entire thing, you see the dark side of it” (line, 40-3,

page 90-91). Describing her disenchantment as being drowned in the ocean, she apprehended that the swimming experience would be enchanting full of stimulation, elation and pleasure. However, when starting the experience, Leila was 'slapped' in the face by waves which represents unforeseen challenges in real life. She also reports getting bites from animals lurking inside which also denote unexpected and hurtful life events. The imagery concludes with the act of 'drowning' which describes a dangerous state that no individual wishes to experience. The latter represents her disenchantment in academia and society as she reported. The cumulative impact of disenchantment and disappointment of being constantly hit by waves contribute to the decline of motivation. As hindrances and stressors serve only to weaken motivation (Kikuchi, 2015), it is safe to assume that Leila's constant disenchanting moments will only weaken her resolve and determination, ultimately leading to demotivation. Subsequently, this study contributes to demotivation literature by contributing at the international doctoral level through sociological dimensions, namely disenchantment.

Liza was disillusioned mostly by the supervisor and the university resulting in various repercussions notably demotivation. Liza longed for an opportunity to study in the UK which she described as "once in a lifetime" (Liza, line 7-8, page 102) due to the fact that the country is developed and hence had "pink expectations" (Liza, line 16, page 103). The latter denotes an optimistic apprehension of the PhD route wherein she expected positive relationships and academic development at her highly ranked university. Such projected ideas and scenarios represent her motives behind pursuing the PhD, which align with prior literature (Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2021; Deci and Ryan, 2016). However, the lived reality was different to the extent of triggering disenchantment and demotivation as she states, "as if someone has slapped me to wake [me] up from that expectations that I want to call a dream" (Liza, line 5-6, page 104). Her actual lived experience is different reaching the point of being "slapped" which underlines a rude awakening (Smith, 1987). Liza calling her expectation a 'dream' designates that what she initially anticipated was fictional and unreal like a 'dream', which set her to failure when confronted with reality.

Her main reason behind disenchantment was the supervision and administration. Before embarking at her current university, Liza mentioned having undertaken background research through the university website, media, and YouTube. After starting the journey, Liza reveals that she was deceived by the 'lies' she read as her experience did not match her prior documentation. The supervisor was a landmark in her motivational shift due to the lack of feedback and help which according to Liza was a core agreement between them:

...they promised to take care about any query that I might have, to care about my questions, my opinions, my ideas, that we'll be discussing whenever I want, that they

will be interacting with me as a researcher, not as a student, but this did not happen, nothing, nothing has happened. (line 36-40, page 104)

Liza opted for X university due to the agreed terms which was in her favour. The promised continuous help, care and open discussion constituted Liza’s motivation to undertake her PhD in that establishment. However, she reports that none of the terms was found once started which stripped her motivation and drove her into disillusionment. Interestingly, the absence of these elements concurs with Wisker’s (2008) key supervisor’s elements (see literature review chapter). In this case, ‘being available when needed’ and ‘being friendly open and supportive’ (Wisker, 2008, p.40) are missing which triggers a reality clash and a profound sense of betrayal. As Liza did not find any of the expected agreements which constituted her foundation/motivation, the logical reaction is demotivation.

Consequently, Liza recounted multiple instances of demotivation, decreased value and isolation. To illustrate, a table with key themes and a supporting quote is presented along with a further interpretation and discussion:

Table 12: Liza's Reported Consequences of Disenchantment

Consequences	Quote
Decreased Respect for Supervisors and Credibility of Highly Ranked Universities.	“...I'm only talking about academic needs, what PhD students need from supervisors, only that. So the respect to some supervisors diminishes and the credibility of highly ranked institutions” (Liza, line 29-31, page 108)
Isolation and Alienation	“I'm only talking to my laptop, there's nothing that encourages me to progress, nothing that motivates me to go further with this PhD” (Liza, line 17-18, page 110)
Motivational Change	“if you’re not motivated, how would you progress with your PhD?...as if you’re forced to make progress but you’re not really happy with your learning experiences, if you’re not gaining much, you cannot provide anything new” (Liza, line 39-41, page 109)
PhD Perception Post-Disenchantment	“I thought it would be something that I really wanted to do...I’ll be studying for pleasure but it's not, it's more boring, I feel like I'm supposed to be considered as a tool not as a human being...” (Liza, line 11-13, page 110)
Distorted/Decreased Self-Image	“...I consider myself as a failure. In my normal state, I consider myself as a PhD researcher who's investigating something that would contribute to the health, education and lifestyle of disadvantaged children...But when I am disenchanted, I feel like I'm a failure, I cannot do it and I will not do it, this is how I see it” (Liza, line 4-11, page 111)

Demotivation	“In terms of motivation, I become very demotivated, I start blaming myself for opting for these supervisors and this institution, and it affects from all sides, to be honest” (Liza, line 36-38, page 106)
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From these extracts, a core consequence to Liza’s experience could be under the category of demotivation. First, *decreased respect for supervisors and credibility of highly ranked universities* occurred due to the misalignment of their initial agreement. Liza attached her decision to embark on University X due to their respective agreement which constituted her motivation to study her PhD at that institution and breaking that agreement logically breaks the enthusiasm and motivation attached to it.

Isolation and alienation are a big component of a PhD journey (Janta et al., 2014; Cuschieri, 2021). However, Liza’s case appears much more severe as she lost her academic and institutional support; leading her to a complete separation from both the world in general (away from family and friends) and the academic world in particular. Having no one else to converse with makes her alienated to the point of her only talking to her ‘laptop’; highlighting the severity of her isolation talking to a non-human (machine). Liza also points to the importance of having someone to encourage her which aligns with previous studies such as Templeton (2016) Breitenbach et al (2019); McCray and Joseph-Richards (2020) highlighting the prominence of families and friends to doctoral students’ motivation, resilience, and success. Subsequently, Liza being deprived of such a helping factor decreased her confidence and alienated herself leading her to be demotivated and paralysed in PhD progress.

As for *motivational change*, Dörnyei and Ottó (1998) reported that motivation is not a permanent constant and that it fluctuates over time. Similar to Liza and most participants, her motivation waned and changed in nature and direction after facing disenchantment. Liza reports that she cannot progress due to the absence of her motivation and forcing her would not help. Her statements not only align with previous literature but offer insights into the heavily understudied population of international doctoral students. As her motivation has been disrupted, the unfortunate consequence would be decreased progress and ultimately delayed timely completion (Lindsay, 2015).

PhD perception post-disenchantment for Liza was ‘boring’. She reports that her preconceived image is different from her factual reality as she expected to do good research, impact her academic community, and be encouraged to further her development. Liza, again, highlights the importance of having encouragement to better handle and further her research (McCray and Joseph-Richards, 2020) which is lacking. Moreover, she describes herself as a mere ‘tool’ in the academic context rather than a human being the fact that she is deprived of any pleasure. This data corroborates not only with demotivation instances but also greatly the established work of Kark Marx on alienation by situating

workers as merely cogs in a bigger machine and that working mechanically deprives them of feeling joy as they have no control over the product they realise (Marx, 1990). Hence, Liza is confronted with an alienating, disenchanting and demotivating reality that metamorphoses her PhD from pleasure and excitement to pure boredom.

Another consequence is *distorted/decreased self-image*. Liza upon her disenchanting reality and inimical relationships with university and supervisors declined her image considerably from a valedictorian student to a ‘failure’. Such change of inner perception corroborates with works of Chambers on demotivation (1993) and the socio-psychological dimensions of Seeman (1959) known as self-estrangement. Liza appears to have lost her confidence, motivation, power, and engagement towards what was initially a very prestigious and noble pursuit. Subsequently, she found herself in an estranged identity that she barely recognised, highlighting the danger or pitfalls of disenchantment to individual motivation and well-being.

Finally, Liza reports directly that one of the consequences of her disenchantment is *demotivation*. In her responses, she repeatedly reported that due to her shocking reality, she lost her motivation and fell into the danger zones of motivation (Dörnyei, 2001). Subsequently, Liza’s testimony serves as a poignant and direct link to how disenchantment leads to numerous motivational pitfalls among which is demotivation. These reported answers paved the way for a new understanding of demotivation through sociological dimensions at the international doctoral level that remained until now unveiled.

Lastly, Oreó’s disenchantment stems mainly from academia and institutions. Similar to Liza, the initial letdown has had a domino effect on her overall experience:

Expectations were high... they picture this university as having the best teams, the best support, the perfect place for you. When I first saw my supervisor, I said, ‘That’s the one I want,’ and I got to work with him. But the university was like a Wonderland painted as wonderful, like Willy Wonka’s Chocolate Factory. In reality, I didn’t get what the advert mentioned. It got worse when they made my supervisor redundant without updating me. That’s when I experienced disenchantment. I still believe it was a big mistake to choose this university, especially when I see my colleagues at other universities. (Oreó, line 17–34, page 61)

Oreó's account delves deep into the contrast between initial expectations and subsequent experiences during her PhD journey abroad particularly the gap between advertised university experiences and the clashed reality. However, a slight difference is that Oreó lived in the ‘wonderland’ for a short period until the supervisor’s departure, which was her demotivating factor (as mentioned in Chapter VI).

Oreó’s disenchantment stems from the university’s promotional techniques “they picture this university as being the best...”. She reports that the adverts highlighted that the university would provide all the requirements needed for students to thrive academically, socially and professionally.

The image pictured by the university made Oreo think that the place is a 'Wonderland', which describes a place that includes only wonderful things. Oreo was already motivated and enchanted by what the university has to offer. Her desire to embark on the university was exponentially increasing when she found a suitable supervisor with a record and specialism that suited her needs. These factors constitute her reasons fuelling her motivation and enchantment toward x university.

However, Oreo quickly realises how her reality differs from her expectations "I didn't get really what the advert mentioned". She reports that none of the advertised positive attributes were met hence puts her in a state of shock. The latter resembles what Smith (1987) referred to as a 'rude awakening' where Oreo discovers the truth behind the wonderland and how such reality collapses. Moreover, she pinpoints that her state worsened when they made her supervisor redundant without even informing her. This experience perfectly aligns with the conventional definition of Weber (1978, p.506). where things "*lose their magical significance*". Subsequently, Oreo's experience moves from a state of wonderland and enchantment to a demotivating and disenchanting one where the magic has ceased its effect leading to seeing things in their truest form.

Consequently, Oreo's disenchantment leads her to question and regret her academic choices "I still do believe it was a big mistake to choose this university". Oreo's previously held reality that was based on pure optimism was dispelled upon experiencing and extracting her truth. This perfectly coincided with Abramowski's (1982) on how rationalisation replaces value judgment. Moreover, Oreo's state worsens as she compares herself with other colleagues who successfully navigated their PhD journey at other universities. Support has already been documented as a factor for students' wellbeing and success (McCray and Joseph-Richards, 2020) which accords with the findings in this section.

A novel theme emerged from the Algerian community in the UK. Oreo stresses at the previous Algerians' lack of sharing experiences and information to avoid disenchantment, which disappointed her "they didn't provide the support as being previous students which had been through experiences which they could share" (Oreo, line 18-20, page 62). This absence of communal empathy and guidance could have eased the academic journey and transition for newer students adding another layer to Oreo's overall disillusionment. In this context, Oreo refers to peers and colleagues who have been reported to be "*important agents of community, learning, and development at this level of graduate work*" (Flores-Scott and Nerad, 2012, p.75). Because previous laureates have gathered experience of what it is to be an Algerian doctoral student in the UK, therefore, any piece of

information or guidance would be invaluable. The latter accords with Oreo's statements as she expected to gain insights from people she deemed more knowledgeable than her.

Oreo's attitude has clearly changed post-disenchantment. Her narratives describe instances of regret, anger, short temper, and impatience; all of which denote a disequilibrium in her motivated attitudes (Atkinson, 1997). Subsequently, the data reported herein demonstrate that the sociological dimension of disenchantment has had a demotivating effect on Oreo's behaviour.

Furthermore, Oreo highlights losing a component of her enchanted self which is productivity. Indeed, Oreo after losing her supervisor reveals "I couldn't really be productive or focus on my PhD" (Oreo, line 22, page 65). Oreo admits not only being unproductive but also not being able to focus on her main task. The lack of productivity due to disenchantment obtained in this study corroborates with previous research (Furnham and Treglown, 2017) where a decrease in productivity deteriorates the health and wellbeing of the individual and generates dissatisfaction. Similarly, Oreo's disenchantment is filled with dissatisfaction and guilt. Additionally, lack of productivity is a trait of people who are demotivated (Chambers, 1993; Dörnyei, 2001). People who display positive and efficient behaviours and tendencies in learning processes are known to be motivated. Conversely, people with little engagement, interest and poor outcomes are known to be demotivated. The latter describes accurately Oreo's state after being disenchanted and how the traumatic event deprived her motivated and positive self, leading to experiencing severe demotivation.

Additionally, Oreo reports losing confidence in her abilities. The feeling reaches the other side of the spectrum:

...when you're disenchanted, it's the opposite, you feel disappointed, you question yourself, your ability, your decision to pursue the PhD in the first place...it's some sort of existential crisis, you basically regret somehow the fact that you have undertaken this journey. (line 16-19, page 69)

Due to the shock of being deceived and disappointed and having to forcefully adapt to the new situation, Oreo's axiomatic reaction is a state of doubt and questioning. Oreo seems to have built solid a foundation when starting her PhD that stemmed mainly from her supervisor. The latter represents her source of motivation and confidence to unlock her potential and proceed with the PhD. This corroborates with previous research demonstrating the importance of academic support to build confidence and succeed in the PhD (McCray and Joseph-Richard, 2020). In this context, Oreo losing her motivational source found herself empty and lost confidence and belief in her abilities. It also accords perfectly with the study of Chambers (1993) on how demotivated students lose their motivated attributes and display a lack of self-confidence and self-esteem. Oreo, reports having constant negative

feelings of lack of self-esteem and unworthiness towards the task at hand “...the most recurrent feeling is lack of self-esteem, I don't believe in my ability at all what I write, I feel that it's not worthy of PhD level” (Oreo, line 24-25, page 69). It is clear that Oreo in this passage displays demotivated tendencies through sociological dimensions of disenchantment. However, Chambers’ research was not extensive in offering deeper answers as the participants were nine. Oreo who is 29 at this stage was much more mature and aware of her feelings and was able to fully convey them through language. Subsequently, the present research not only confirms previous data but adds a layer of complexity and depth that were unobtainable from very young pupils.

It is also worth noting that Oreo highlighted that the feeling was constant which denotes the ever-presence of disenchantment. This was conveyed in the excerpt “disenchantment always been there ever since it occurred, it was all the way until the submission” (Oreo, line 2-3, page 69). Therefore, from the emerging data, we could easily imply that disenchantment is a long-lasting period of negativity that impedes students’ well-being, motivation, and completion. It also indicates a sense of entrapment that lingers until submission. Educationalists and policymakers should come up with better approaches to resolve the issue at hand.

Overall, much like an anomaly in a human body, disenchantment infiltrates expectations and introduces a disconcerting unpredictability. All participants have reported being disenchanted at multiple stages of their respective research and ultimately falling into the danger zones and pitfalls of motivation (Dörnyei, 2001). Similar to demotivation, disenchantment disables motivated students from reaching their goals, depriving them of the joy of research, negatively impacting their mental health, and ultimately hindering their PhD timely completion. The disenchanted participants displayed dissatisfaction, lack of self-confidence and self-esteem, lack of engagement, isolation, alienation, powerlessness, and many more. All these exhibited behaviours helped to understand the phenomenon of demotivation much more deeply and provided future educationalists and researchers with valuable insights from an IPA perspective.

Summary

The chapter delineated extensively the sociological dimensions that contributed to demotivation. From the data discussed, it becomes apparent that all of the sociological dimensions triggered demotivation, from disenchantment being the highest to alienation being second. The PhD in the UK was a once-in-a-lifetime opportunity for Algerians; however, they did not seem well equipped to face these elements that demotivated them immensely, which ultimately impacted their progress and overall PhD experience. The relocation, the time pressure, the supervisor, the institution,

the pandemic, and many more represent the elements that advocate the reality crush. Moreover, these elements could have been coped better if participants were in their homes surrounded by their family and friends. Consequently, as this population was vulnerable due to deprivation, future research should try to study how to make future Algerians feel better, integrate faster, and forge better relationships to avoid isolation-related problems.

Concluding Chapter

Introduction

This chapter concludes the present IPA research. It starts with a brief overview of the research and its possible impact on society and academia. Following that, it summarizes the research findings and major contributions. Afterwards, it identifies and discusses some recommendations for policy and practice to minimise the effect of demotivation. After that, it presents some of the limitations encountered during the process of this research. Drawing from these limitations, the chapter then explores and offers recommendations for future research impact. Lastly, the chapter brings closure with an autobiographical reflection and lesson learned during the PhD.

1. Overview of the Research

This thesis has investigated the phenomenon of demotivation in an international doctoral context. Particularly, the study emphasised three main issues/questions: the PhD demotivating factors that are in the journey of UK Algerian postgraduates, and how they experience the phenomenon through feelings and thought processes. Finally, it enlarges the scope of demotivation by assessing which of the sociological dimensions of alienation or disenchantment contribute to the phenomenon of demotivation. The study employed IPA, a type of methodology permitting a highly detailed examination of people's experiences at a micro-level (Smith et al., 2009, 2022). It is noteworthy that this study focuses solely on the dark side and does not cover the positives of doing the PhD.

The issue of demotivation is of detrimental importance for the understanding of doctoral journey risks, especially attrition and self-harm such as suicide. Previous studies demonstrated high mental and physical health issues doctoral students experience in comparison to other levels (Levecque et al., 2017; Cornwall et al., 2019; Mulligan, 2021). The latter makes them more susceptible to mental breakdowns, depression, attrition and suicide. Despite this, very little attention has been paid to the phenomenon of demotivation as a potential phase preceding the irreversible threshold that is attrition and at times suicide.

In this research, I set out to enlighten the stages that precede these alarming phases by collecting the stories of international doctoral students across UK soil, particularly from a new set of participants, namely Algerian postgraduates. The latter permits to get a fresh perspective of the phenomenon as faced by them first-hand. The goal is to point at the insurmountable challenges that block students' progress and lead to feelings of demotivation responsible for creating a cascade of negative effects.

2. Summary of Research Findings

The findings reveal that UK Algerian postgraduates face demotivation at an alarming rate. They are confronted with many factors that imprison their motivated behaviours such as *the pandemic, isolation, supervisors, institutional factors and personal and emotional factors*. Moreover, the study confirms the earlier work of Chambers (1993) on demotivated students displaying a lack of self-confidence and self-esteem. However, the present study results found that demotivated symptoms include novel findings such as Dissipation of Enthusiasm; lack of socialisation, emptiness, alienation and avoidance; Negative Self-Perception and Imposter Syndrome; Overwhelming Emotions and Mental Health Challenges; Autonomy, Guilt, and Regret and; Fear and Uncertainty. Cognitive patterns include Negative automated thoughts, avoidance, self-deprecation, attrition thinking reaching points of existential crisis, depression and suicidal ideation, highlighting ‘the danger zones’ of demotivation at an international doctoral level. Therefore, taking these elements into account, demotivation appears to be a much more complex and severe phenomenon at the doctoral level. Finally, the research was able to detect and link alienation and disenchantment as sociological dimensions contributing to demotivation and therefore enriching the limited understanding and theory of the latter. For example, powerlessness as an alienating symptom contributed to the comprehension of demotivation as the participants when demotivated exhibited/displayed such a tendency. Lastly, participants’ expectations of the journey did not match the actual reality triggering feelings of disenchantment and demotivation. Subsequently, the study made a significant contribution to the phenomenon of demotivation through its novelistic approach of IPA.

3. Contributions of the Present Research

The present section outlines the multiple contributions to the current social science debate on demotivation and how the current research distinguishes itself from others; offering unique gap-filling niches. These contributions are classified accordingly:

3.1. Demotivation at a PhD Level: An empirical void

To the best of my knowledge, this study is the first attempt to examine demotivation at an international doctoral level. Most studies have focused on demotivation in FLL for all levels and only one on the doctoral level (Cantu, 2016). However, Cantu (2016) focused on domestic doctoral students in STEM subjects and disregarded the study of the phenomenon from an IPA perspective and did not collect the essence of the experience. Despite the fact that PhD students experience more alarming psychological, social, and health-related issues, very little has been undertaken to study such phenomena. This study permitted to push the current borders of demotivation by enlarging its

comprehension of the international doctoral context by decontextualising the phenomenon where it is highly likely to be experienced.

3.2. Symptomology of Demotivation

Demotivation processes in higher education are not sufficiently documented. Therefore, one of the most important contributions generated from this study is the symptoms of the dark side of motivation. Building on the work of Chambers (1993), the present study extends the comprehension of demotivated symptoms by extracting the phenomenological core as faced by students. This study differs from Chambers as it incorporates the voices of participants who are adults and highly educated in contrast to 9-year-old participants who might be unable to fully process and reflect on complex issues such as demotivation.

The present results reflecting the inner world were categorised under feelings and thought processes (the dyadic presentation is extensively discussed in Chapter 7). Feelings attached to demotivation are diminished motivation and energy, social isolation, avoidance, and cultural dislocation, negative self-perception and imposter syndrome, overwhelming emotions and mental health challenges, autonomy, guilt, and regret, and fear of failure and uncertainty. The thought processes of demotivation include critical voice and NATs, work avoidance and detachment, doubt and purpose, suicidal thoughts and ideation, and seeking solutions and reconciliation.

As far as the current literature indicates, there were no bodies of research delineating the phenomenon of demotivation on these specific aspects. Thus, the findings presented herein offer a new contribution to the symptomology of demotivation from an international doctoral perspective, represented by participants who are older and more capable of higher levels of reflective and cognitive motions than 9-year-olds (Chambers, 1993).

3.3. Sociology of Demotivation

The sociological dimensions adopted in this research expanded the current understanding of demotivation. These dimensions offer deeper insights into the complexities of demotivation and provide what Alvesson and Sandberg (2013, p.11) call ‘application spotting’ which moves beyond the already established psychological perspective through the consideration of other disciplines. This research highlights the broader sociological milieu in which demotivation occurs such as societal norms, cultural clash and disillusionment of perception. Thus, expanding the current understanding of demotivation through its corroboration with the pioneering works of Marx (1848) and Weber (1948); creating the sociological dimensions of demotivation.

Specifically, alienation addresses how IDS' disconnection from work, peers and cultural norms leads to feelings of demotivation, powerlessness, meaninglessness, purposelessness and self-estrangement. Disenchantment captures multiple instances where PhD students lost their intrinsic motivation and positive/enchanted perception upon clashing with actual reality. Therefore, the present findings enrich the current understanding of demotivation that remained limited for a considerable amount of time. The sociological dimensions offer opportunities to develop more holistic strategies to address demotivation and permit creating a more demotivation-free environment for international doctoral students.

3.4. Type of Participants

The participants involved in this research represent a unique subset of the population. Derived from a relatively small-studied populace in contrast to Europe, Asia or America (Chambers 1993; Onwuegbuzie et al., 2014; McCray and Joseph-Richards, 2020; Hazel et al., 2021), Algeria represents an uncharted study population offering a fresh and unique contribution to the phenomenon of demotivation. UK Algerian Postgraduates are highly motivated to undertake the PhD as they were carefully selected through a national contest, representing the laureates in their respective universities. Having these students experiencing demotivation demonstrates the severity of the phenomenon and how it derives the most engaged and achieved individuals to a state of total blockage. Moreover, the involvement of Algerian participants allows the current study to contribute to the debate around demotivation in new and original ways due to their particularities. For example, suicide and even lesser forms of self-harm are categorically prohibited (haram) in Islam, which discourages Muslim people from engaging in such actions out of fear of punishment in the hereafter. The Islamic ruling on such actions informs the culture of Muslim societies, contributing to relatively lower rates of suicide in Muslim nations; however as shown in chapter seven, an Algerian Muslim participant described having suicidal thoughts during her PhD experience, which demonstrates how demotivation can make students susceptible to suicidal levels of emotional distress despite religious and cultural safeguards. Although there are no cases of suicide among the participants, considering suicide as a Muslim entails death followed by eternal torment which should completely discourage such thoughts or at the very least reserve them for the most extreme cases of emotional distress. Thus, the originality of this research is underscored by the distinctiveness of its participants and how they perceive the same phenomenon differently.

3.5. Methodological Underpinning

Another potent contribution is the study of demotivation through IPA. Demotivation has been extensively studied in levels other than the PhD for many years, utilising a wide range of

methodological approaches, mainly through surveys (Gorham and Christophel, 1992;1995; Fallout et al., 2009; Sakai and Kikuchi, 2009). However, most of these studies did not consider investigating demotivation from a pure ‘phenomenon’ or ‘experience’ perspective. Despite the fact that demotivation is an experience in essence, this research was not able to locate studies from a phenomenological point of view. IPA is suitable when dealing with a phenomenon that lacks detailing and depth and permits the extraction of first-hand information from a fresh perspective (Smith et al., 2022). The phenomenon was studied extensively and reported to be an occurrence of extreme importance that PhD students undergo during their transition from students to novice researchers. The latter could be termed as a critical life event that shaped the overall PhD experience though its nature varied across participants. Finally, the study reported a multitude of feelings associated with demotivation namely anger, betrayal, disappointment and demotivation towards the culture and organisation (university) which reflects accurately what phenomenological study represents (Hays and Singh, 2011; Patton, 2015; Merriam and Tisdell, 2015). Thus, the present study represents one of the very first attempts at demotivation through IPA and provided not only reinforcement to previous endeavours but also offered substantial contribution and addition to the poorly studied phenomenon.

4. Recommendations for Practice

This research offered different insights for practice which aims to prevent demotivation and hence foster a better environment for future doctoral students. The following subsection particularly focuses on items that are the following: *mental health support services, cultural sensitivity training, mentorship programs, community building activities, regular feedback and communication, recognition and validation, promotion of self-care practices, and long-term support networks.*

Mental health is paramount in navigating important events and transitions in life. Studies from different backgrounds and methodologies have demonstrated how doctoral transition negatively influences mental health wellbeing; this includes the development of stress, depression, anxiety, insomnia and many more (Hyun et al, 2006; Kernan et al, 2011; Onwuegbuzie et al., 2014; Levecque et al., 2017; Cornwall et al., 2019; Pizuńska et al, 2020; Mulligan, 2021). Moreover, the case is exacerbated for international students which was even found in the present study. This study has demonstrated how demotivated students descend into severe mental health issues. For easement purposes to doctoral students in general and international doctoral students in specific, mental health services should establish a support system offered uniquely to these voiceless populations. This could be achieved through including counselling and mental health resources at their disposal. Examples of how this could be done are through pop-in visits to their domiciles. Moreover, mental health practitioners or trained professionals should be allocated to follow demotivated cases and help them

navigate and cope with such phenomena and potential other psychological threats. Finally, these professionals should be more understanding in discussing mental health issues with minorities such as Algerians as mental health issues are not as widespread and accepted in Algeria as they are in the UK. By having their mental health checked and aided regularly, their resilience and motivation would only increase incrementally and therefore deal with the vicissitudes of the doctoral journey more positively and powerfully.

Another important recommendation for practice is *cultural sensitivity training*. Culture represents the nucleus of people's identities, and colliding with a new cultural setting stranger to one of the internationals generates acculturative stress, alienation, estrangement, stereotypes and so on (Sherry et al., 2010; Desa et al., 2012; Titrek et al., 2016). The present study also found the cultural element to be demotivating. For these reasons, providing cultural training to university staff to raise awareness of the different cultures that exist and enter the UK universities. The training also includes how such differentiation might impact motivation and wellbeing. By doing so, the chances of creating a more supportive, understanding and inclusive environment for international students might increase considerably. Therefore, as their belonging needs are fulfilled (Maslow, 1954, Strayhorn, 2012, 2018), they could focus better on higher forms of needs that are intellectual such as the PhD and hence perform at a significantly better degree.

Moreover, international students can better navigate their doctoral journey if offered *mentorship programs*. Indeed, students can gain invaluable insights from mentors through guidance, support, and encouragement; all of which foster a positive mindset and strengthen motivation. In this context, mentors can be regarded as MKO (More Knowledgeable Other) wherein they act as Mediators for students to transition in what Vygotsky termed the Zone of Proximal Development (1978). The latter also resonates with Lave and Wenger's (1991) notion of Communities of practice wherein international doctoral students learn from mentors who are in this case professionals and hence advance their basic knowledge to meet the standards. Therefore, by working collaboratively, mentors can also help students make sense of their transition, navigate academic challenges, adjust to a new cultural environment, and maintain motivation during the doctoral journey.

Furthermore, a highly advised practice to increase inclusion and motivation is *community building activities*. Integration and belongingness are crucial in international students' experiences. For these reasons, universities should organize social events, workshops, and networking opportunities specifically for international doctoral students to foster a sense of community and belonging (Strayhorn, 2018). Moreover, these events would be perfect opportunities for new students

to meet and build connections with peers who share similar experiences. As studies have shown that international students tend to create friendships/bonds with other international students who are either from the same country or culture (Sherry et al., 2010). Thus, sharing stories with freshmen will lead to decreased feelings of isolation and enhance motivation through stories of success.

Additionally, to lighten international doctoral students' thesis writing journey, *Regular feedback and communication* must be upgraded. Most research on doctoral studies has found that supervisors are a key to either success or failure of students in their doctoral thesis completion (Hockey, 1996; Golde and Dore, 2001; Heath, 2002; McApline and Norton, 2006; Ives and; Halse, 2011; Platow, 2012; Devos et al, 2017; Hardman, 2020). Moreover, van Rooij et al. (2019) found that two supervision characteristics lead students to withdraw from their doctoral program namely: lack of academic support and high expectations. The present study also demonstrated how supervisors' lack of academic support leads to demotivation. Therefore, establishing open channels of communication between international students and supervisors is paramount to prevent worse-case scenarios. For instance, encouraging regular feedback sessions to discuss progress, address concerns, and provide encouragement and support. As said earlier, the supervisor is of crucial importance to students' futures. Therefore, supervisors should realise their importance and use that to draw the students' potential by motivating them and avoiding demotivating them which only leads to counterproductive outcomes.

Another implementation advised is motivation through *recognition and validation*. Motivation has been documented as the necessary tool for doctoral progress, timely completion and success (Bair and Haworth, 2004; Lovitts, 2001, 2008; Kyvik and Olsen, 2014; Lindsay, 2015; Litalien and Guay, 2015). Thus, recognition is essential to providing sense to the efforts displayed. For this reason, the achievements, and contributions of international doctoral students within the academic community should be recognised. This should be done through celebrating milestones, such as transfer events, research presentations, publications, and conference participation, to validate their efforts and boost morale. Such initiatives will permit students to actually see the concrete results of the efforts displayed and thus rejuvenate the motivation and give it sense for future endeavours. The act of receiving such accolades is an important part of what is known as rewards in extrinsic motivation (Deci and Ryan, 2016). Thus, allocating some time to students' achievement will serve as a motivating tool which will only benefit students in general and universities in specific.

Equally important is *the promotion of self-care practices*. Because the PhD is a highly demanding task, it becomes a priority and entails having to undertake some sacrifices (Gardner and

Holley, 2011; Spaulding and Rockinson-Szapkiw, 2012; Cuschieri, 2021). Doctoral students often neglect their personal lives and cannot manage to balance between them and their academic demands (Onwegbuzie et al., 2014). The latter leads to demotivation and burnout. For this reason, students should be encouraged to take care of their mental and physical health by promoting self-care practices. They should be reminded to enjoy their lives through exercising, yoga, mindfulness, and relaxation to manage stress and maintain well-being which is a crucial element to succeed in the doctoral journey. Doctoral research is defined as an isolating journey (Cuschieri, 2021) which leads to negative impacts on mental and physical health; all of which hinder academic progress. Therefore, by undertaking such activities, students release negative energy and allow them to break from the isolation bubble.

Lastly, *establishing long-term support networks*. Support and networking are great allies for career prospects and development. For this reason, long-term networking with international students should be established to maintain connections even after graduation. The network should also serve as a mediator for these students to transition from postgraduate careers to beyond. The new Zone of Proximal Development (Vygotsky, 1987) hence moves from being a PhD student to actively searching for career prospects. This will help boost international students' motivation and remain integrated within the host community (Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2021).

By implementing these strategies or some of them, the university is guaranteed to create and foster a more equalitarian and positive environment that is more inclusive and cross-cultural. The universities for internationals represent a second home and feeling a sense of belongingness would negate feelings of alienation and isolation and hence avoid demotivation as demonstrated in this study.

5. Limitations of the Current Research

As no research is absolute, the acknowledgement of the shortcomings represents an important part of academic integrity. First, the present study data are by default non-generalisable. This means that, unlike quantitative measurement, the results cannot be applicable instantly to the whole population. However, for a qualitative study, there is a concept called theoretical transferability (Smith, 2022) where the data found are transferrable or applicable to a population of similar/common attributes; in this case international students. Therefore, the data generated are only generalisable to the students who are engaged in further studies outside their hometown.

Another limitation is the sample size undertaken. The study only collected stories from 8 participants across the UK which would seem as a relatively small number. However, IPA is an intensive study of a small number of participants and the main aim is therefore centred on quality rather than quantity. The pioneers of IPA highlight *“the issue is quality, not quantity, and given the*

complexity of most human phenomena, IPA studies usually benefit from a concentrated focus on a small number of cases". (Smith et al., 2022, p.46). IPA is a study engaged in a detailed examination of people's lifeworld through a microscopic lens or 'microlevel' (Smith and Osburn, 2015, p. 42). Moreover, the quality of the participants was optimised through the sampling technique (convenience). In other words, by choosing respondents who are willing to be engaged in a long-term project and are somewhat experts in the domain, the data richness is thus ensured. Therefore, having quality people making sense of their experiences and providing unique cases of their lives outweighs having a large number of participants who might not share or are willing to take part.

One additional limitation is the nature of the topic and its subsequent effect. Opening up about such a topic can be daunting for several reasons. To begin with, *fear of judgment*: people might be under pressure and fear being judged when admitting to such feelings (Davis, 2011, 2015; Perrin et al., 2014). Academia is a rather competitive environment and there is often a stigma attached to struggling with motivation. Second, *perception of weakness*: admitting to feelings of demotivation can unfortunately be regarded as a sign of weakness or even incompetence (Golde, 2000). In research, success is often associated with factors such as productivity and innovation, and the fact of admitting to such feelings might be or feel counterproductive (Lovitts, 2001). A final point could be *the professional image*: in the world of academia, an image to maintain through is professionalism. Indeed, such identity is of paramount importance, and addressing personal struggles can lead to the destabilisation of the perceived competence or dedication to the work (Hughes, 2011). However, this could be solved through the process of research integrity and rigour. For example, ensuring confidentiality and anonymity by protecting their answers, stories and identifiers from being traced can help the participants to feel less pressured and more comfortable when discussing such topics as they are insured to remain protected and sheltered from being identified.

Furthermore, there were multiple instances where participants felt a discrepancy between their culture back in Algeria and the host's. Participants reported events related to a lack of belongingness, isolation, homesickness, nostalgia and alienation within the UK. This could be the result of the different cultural norms residing in both countries in terms of notions of collectivism and individualism. The family is a core unit of life in Algeria as well as an influencing system over many aspects of an Algerian's autonomy. Such cultural differences were raised during the research but do not represent a key element in the study. The latter constitutes a limitation worth mentioning as culture is an important facet of human identity (Triandis, 1995). Thus, to fully establish this, more research on the area should be conducted.

Finally, as explained in the literature review, this thesis was not a gendered study in that I made no attempt to differentiate gendered experiences in my design or data collection. However, during this study, five participants out of eight were female. Although gender would have an impact on the participants and how they react to different factors and events, it was not considered and therefore represents a limitation worth mentioning. Nevertheless, this study sought to identify how the phenomenon of demotivation is experienced across all genders and most of the obtained data is shared between all participants regardless of their gender. Thus, such an issue would be an important area for future research, as I note below.

6. Recommendations for Future Research

As this research is among the first attempts at international doctoral demotivation through IPA, there is a huge need and room for future research projects. The following are a few suggestions:

Firstly, as I noted above, the wealth of literature on gender differences can lead to an important study on demotivation. Thus, it merits a second investigation. It would be interesting to investigate how different factors are perceived across genders. For example, as raised in the data chapter, females such as Manel wearing Hijab had an additional demotivation as a cause of Islamophobia and fear of being different. As people act differently in identical situations (Dweck, 1999), different genders are unlikely to react in the same way to the same stimuli or situation. Therefore, the identification of gendered differences in relation to demotivation at the doctoral level would constitute a new avenue of research whose review and methodology would be suited to the pursuit of the gendered dimension of experience.

Secondly, longitudinal studies, as the name suggests, have the potential to investigate a phenomenon through a considerable amount of time from short-term to long-term periods (Cohen et al., 2017). This type of study could be utilised to assess the evolution or evolvment of demotivating factors over time; whether they intensify or weaken. Longitudinal research also permits to investigate the dynamic nature of demotivation and its subsequent effects over a long period, especially at the doctoral level that lasts for four years. Finally, the research will also be able to offer a chart of individuals assessing their experiences and how they react and change over time.

Another interesting avenue of research is cross-cultural comparison/studies. Cultural teaching constitutes an important part of someone's identity and differs from one culture to another. If people act differently in identical situations (Dweck, 1999), the same could be considered for people who have different cultural backgrounds and teachings, for example, individualism and collectivism. Thus, future studies should investigate how people from different cultures experience and express the

phenomenon of demotivation; what their background tells them to do and how they perceive such occurrence in their lives. The case is particularly true as this study noticed few cultural disparities. Subsequently, cross-cultural studies will shed light on the extent to which cultural norms, values, and social structures can shape individuals' perceptions of demotivation.

A highly contemporary topic in the current debate is technology and demotivation. This theme emerged principally from Liza's and Vegeta's data. Due to the fact that students were working remotely during Covid, a new concept of remote work has been introduced. The latter leads students to what Liza reported as 'only talking to the computer' thereby introducing another type of isolation. Therefore, a future recommendation would be exploring the role of technology in both exacerbating and alleviating feelings of demotivation. Research could examine how factors such as excessive screen time, social media use, or remote work arrangements impact doctoral students' motivation levels and overall well-being.

Moreover, an interesting topic for enriching demotivation research is through interventions. This type of investigation uses a more practical side by designing and testing strategies aimed at reducing the impact of demotivation for doctoral students. This could entail creating strategies targeting negative aspects such as academic stress, using strategies from therapy such as Cognitive Behavioural Therapy developing constructive tendencies such as SMART goals to clearly define the steps to doctoral completion and fostering a growth mindset in order to build the necessary resilience and motivation. Moreover, students could be introduced to wellbeing techniques such as mindfulness, breathing techniques, identifying and replacing unhelpful ways of thinking such as overdramatising, all-or-nothing thinking and emotional reasoning through cognitive reconstructing and thought record.

A very fascinating psychologically-related topic is demotivation and perceived control. The present study reported that students lose control over their emotions and thought processes during demotivation. Thus, a study on how their perceived control over their circumstances influences their experience would only benefit the advancement of demotivation research. The study could explore factors such as locus of control, self-efficacy beliefs, and autonomy and their subsequent effect on demotivation.

Finally, it is important to note that not all PhD students find the dark side in their way, and many enjoy undertaking their PhD. The current research only highlights the less visible and unseen challenges that only serve to foster a better environment for students who might resemble the research participants, in other words, theoretical transferability (Smith et al., 2022) or mental resonance (Hammersley, 1993).

7. Autobiographical Reflection and Learned Lessons from the PhD Journey

The PhD journey has undoubtedly been an invaluable source of personal and academic growth and development. It has been an enlightening expedition filled with enchantment, truth-seeking, and an internal desire of curiosity that remained till the last stages of the research process. During the experience, I acquired important skills necessary for researchers such as locating the appropriate literature, criticality, academic writing, interview skills and detail orientation. However, the transition also encompasses some harsh truths and hardships that were necessary to my evolution. Being a laureate back in my country, I thought that undertaking the PhD was going to be a journey that would require me to do things that were not too difficult. In other words, it might exceed my expectations but not my imagination. Such a sentence could not be any further from the truth (far from being accurate). In a way, I had to relearn almost everything and recalibrate my thinking and perception. Being an expert on the PhD research itself, I can attest that the process is rarely linear and requires multiple round trips/attempts to achieve some goals. This experience resonates with Simone de Beauvoir's (1958) *Memoirs of a Dutiful Daughter* where she had to confront the gap between her expectations and the reality of academic life. Similarly, I had to recalibrate my assumptions on the PhD journey accordingly. Such disparity between assumptions and reality is also a clear indication of disenchantment.

Second, I believe that the nature of my topic also influenced the research completion time. Dealing mostly with demotivation with minimal training was a daunting task, especially because in Algeria there were no intensive trainings on psychology and mental health. I have acquired some certifications and accreditations during my journey such as mental health awareness, psychotherapy, counselling, and CBT which provided help during my research. Nevertheless, I did not expect the research process to have such a negative toll on my wellbeing. Hearing that my Algerian colleagues suffer from demotivation at an alarming high rate triggered both my affective and cognitive empathy. I felt their pain acutely as I have experienced it firsthand due to our shared background. The research not only contributed to the scholarly debate but also represented a valuable life lesson. I had the chance to present my work in various opportunities such as "Avoiding stress and looking out for each other" held by UWS with Chinese students via Zoom and Lately at UWS Learning and Teaching Conference 2024 in a presentation called "Doctoral Students' Voices" where I explained majorly two elements notably isolation and Mental-health wellbeing. Using IPA was for me the most appropriate choice as it allowed me to enter into the psyche of my participants and extract the essence of their demotivating experiences. The latter aligns with Jung's (1961/2011) *memories, dreams, reflections* highlighting the necessity of understanding the psychological aspect of human experience at a deeper level. Moreover, IPA does not simply collect descriptive stories but also reflects on those stories as lived by its

participants thus achieving their full form/nature. The usage of IPA procured both time and space for participants to not only narrate but also reflect on their own lives which seldom happens. Additionally, most participants felt stimulated by the questions as they only concerned them and their lives. The latter could be seen through multiple responses from participants such as Liza:

...you gave me an opportunity to voice my concerns about being a PhD student in the UK; an Algerian PhD student in the UK, so thank you for allowing this opportunity to voice my concerns, my needs, so probably in the future, they will read your thesis, and they will consider the needs of PhD students in general. (Liza, 22-25, page 112)

Thus, the participants have talked extensively ranging from a minimum of 2 hours to 5 hours in all sessions combined. The collected data suggest that participants felt at ease and shared their demotivating experiences in as much detail as possible. Concerning the professional side, I held different positions such as Associate Lecturer in Sociology teaching the work of C Wright Mills on Sociological Imagination and Aspire Advisor at UWS which consisted of providing guidance and help for freshmen during their transition into higher academia. I was also a tutor at Glasgow International College teaching research methods and how to craft research proposals for foundational and premasters students. These different experiences, among others, helped me sharpen my teaching methods and use my acquired knowledge during the PhD to facilitate the transition of other students at lower levels. Correspondingly, the PhD journey offered me multiple chances for development personally, academically and professionally and provided lessons that I will probably carry for the rest of my life.

Reflection also entails addressing alternative scenarios if I were to start over. Upon reaching the end stage of my research, there are a few things I wish I had done differently. Starting from face-to-face interviews, due to Covid complications, I could not meet the participants and was compelled to undertake the interview sessions remotely which might have impacted rapport building. Second, the addition of research diaries would have added invaluable data to the lifeworld of demotivation. However, most participants would be reluctant as they were absorbed and occupied by their respective research theses (such long-term commitment would be too demanding). Third, time management in the sense of organising every step of the research within a specified timeframe. For example, during the data collection stage, I faced some difficulties in getting second-round and third-round interviews which ultimately delayed my data analysis stage. Finally, more training in mental health and wellbeing would have provided me with more knowledge and confidence to tackle such an endeavour. The research journey I lived was fluctuating and sometimes disenchanting, nevertheless, it was insightful and teachable as most important lessons are learned through hardships. Foucault's (2011) *The Courage of Truth's* 'parrhesia' or truth-telling where a truth seeker speaks his reality regardless of

everything coincides with me presenting my experiences here and defending my work, pinpointing that the PhD is not just an academic achievement but also an ethical one.

Summary

Demotivation is a gate to the other self. The self that only exists in the shadows and resurfaces only once the motivation is imprisoned. The objective of the demotivated self is to oppose everything the motivated self targets such as productivity, positivity, resilience and thirst for knowledge. In other words, it reverses the positive attributes to their negative counterparts. The trigger is something that goes against someone's motivation preventing them from reaching the set goals.

This chapter concluded the present research investigation of Algerian Doctoral Students' Demotivation in the UK using IPA. It outlined an overview of the research, a summary of the findings, the research's contributions, limitations, recommendations for future practices and research and an autobiographical section. The core of this thesis sought to understand the undocumented phenomenon of demotivation at an international doctoral level. Participants in the research have shown how severely demotivated they are and how such a phenomenon could lead to more irreversible situations such as attrition and suicide. It is hoped that this first attempt will pave the way for more future enquiries to mitigate doctoral transition challenges and foster a more supportive and positive environment for future/aspiring doctoral researchers.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: The Methodological Choices, Literature Sources, and Search Strategies

Rationale for the Divisions of Sections

As to the reasons behind such a division of sections, the justifications are as follows. The background chapter was presented for reliability purposes, it accounted for the psychological, physiological, societal and health issues faced by doctoral students in general to understand why these students are more prone to demotivation. This chapter's first section addresses the empirical void of demotivation studies at doctoral level (Cantu, 2016). The second section delves around the unique case of international students as they face additional challenges when settling in a new country (Desa et al., 2012; Titrek et al., 2016). Concerning the third section, another type of gap is utilised called 'application spotting' (Alvesson and Sandberg, 2013, p.11) where an alternative perspective of demotivation is presented through sociology of alienation and disenchantment to further its understanding as the four constructs all relate to a loss of a part that forms our identity due to encountered factors/events.

It is worth reiterating that the aims of this thesis are twofold; first, to identify the demotivating factors of international PhD students. Second, to expand the understanding of demotivation through the sociological works of Marx (1844), Durkheim (1893-1897) and Weber (1946).

Literature Search and Review Methodology

The stylistic approach adopted in this literature review is a narrative one (Baumeister and Leary, 1997; Jalongo and Heider, 2014). Narrative or qualitative reviews are particularly useful as they permit to gather a body of literature supplying one's own storytelling or narrative in order to trigger novelistic thinking of a newly approach using multiple disciplines (Jalongo and Heider, 2014). The motives for doing so are multifaceted: first, narrative reviews allow flexibility in exploring, analysing, and criticizing ideas, issues, and theoretical frameworks with identifying gaps in the literature. Second, it is insightful and original as the materials are not predetermined or selected beforehand which allows a maximum coverage of the literature. Thirdly, by raising inconsistencies and discrepancies within the literature advanced, it permits clarity in thinking and allows refining the research questions as well as developing concepts and theoretical frameworks (Henwood and Pidgeon, 2006; Jesson et al., 2011; Mertens, 2019). Moreover, this approach incorporates new materials as the research advances, that is, the process of inclusion is dynamic and continuous, unlike systematic reviews that compile evidence to answer specific research questions. The fixed variable in this latter is quite useful in some cases but it is not without any limitation; with research questions that remain static all along the investigation

may result in a handicap as one of the research, especially the doctoral research's characteristics is the ability to be flexible and ready to make any necessary changes when needed. Furthermore, the nature and the complexity of educational research influenced the selection of this review type. According to Berliner (2002), educational research is the hardest science of all as it encounters problems and is conducted under conditions that physical sciences would find intolerable. Generalization problems, power of context problems, the ubiquity of interaction and the problem of decades of finding interaction posits some of the challenges the educational sciences face continuously (*ibid*). Therefore, to do a thorough literature that solves such problems is by conducting a narrative review.

The purpose of this narrative review is to describe and synthesize the available PhD experiences on a broader topic to further its understanding. It, therefore, crafts a novelistic landscape of the phenomenon by decontextualizing it from language learning to a new field which is doctoral studies. Moreover, at the end of the review, links between demotivation and sociological concepts of alienation and disenchantment are made to offer an alternate perspective. Narrative reviews are particularly valuable to interconnect a multitude of topics. Therefore, this narrative review represents a 'bridge' that connects three distinctive areas namely: PhD experience, demotivation and alienation-related terms. The following review presents studies of these three distinct and unrelated fields and creates a new map that emphasises the diverse parts to form a single and homogenous structure (Hammersley, 2001). Thus, the study assembles unrelated areas that are very similar in different aspects.

Databases and Keywords

The primary databases for this research include google scholar, JSTOR (Journal Storage), EBSCOhost, ERIC, Francis and Taylor Online, DOAJ (Directory of Open Access Journals), Repository of Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, SSRN (Social Science Research Network), Semantic Scholar, Central and Eastern European Online Library, Springer Link, Scholar Space, MDPI (Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute), Wiley Online Library, and Oxford Academic. Search terms used are 'factors affecting motivation' 'demotivation', 'decrease in motivation', 'reduced motivation' and 'losing the will to study' to extract academic articles related to motivation and demotivation studies. Concerning the international students' part, search terms are 'international experience', 'obstacles faced by international students' and 'international postgraduate students'. Finally, articles collected on sociological areas relative to this work were extracted using keywords of 'alienation', 'disenchantment', 'separateness', 'estrangement', 'isolation' and 'lack of belongingness'. The keywords were carefully chosen as they gather the necessary articles allowing a comprehensive background knowledge on each section. As to the selection dates, an emphasis was

put on recent articles of the last 20 years because, in this period, investigations on both PhD cases and demotivation have soared and a vast number of articles has been collected. However, previous articles and books were not ignored such as Marx (1844), Durkheim (1893) and Weber (1946) as these, among others, are seminal/foundational works. It is noteworthy to state that the paying platforms were accessed through UWS student ID.

Appendix 2: Interview Schedule

Introduction

Thank you for accepting my request to take part in my PhD research study. My name is Juba, an Algerian Ph.D. student based in the School of Education and Social Science, University of the West of Scotland. I am engaged in a research project on the experiences of international doctoral students in the UK. I would like to hear about your own experience as a PhD student. I would be very grateful if you would say as much as you can drawing upon these experiences, personal and academic. I will be asking you deep questions, I am sorry for the inconvenience. I expect our research conversation to last around 60-90 minutes long. Your responses are confidential and anything you say will be anonymised. For data analysis purposes I would, with your permission, wish to record our interview using a recorder. Let me know if you would like a break or wish to stop/end the meeting at anytime. There are no 'right' or 'wrong' answers to my questions. It is about your own views and experiences that I am very interested to explore with you. It is worth mentioning that I might see you more than once.

My area is divided into certain topics which I will present one at a time asking you a series of questions on each topic. Please take time to reflect on my questions. We will proceed at your pace and treatment of my Qs. Section one starts with simple and general questions that serves as an entrée to the main discussion. Section two and three deal with major topics and impressions of the dark side and its effect on the overall doctoral experience. The last section enters the psychological dark side through a new sociological avenue; the major themes/topics to be discussed are on alienation (Marx, 1844; Seeman, 1975), and disenchantment (Weber, 1946).

SECTION I: Autobiographical Questions.

1. Tell me about your life before you began a PhD.

Prompts: Lifestyle, employment, education...

2. Tell me about your education and your experiences in education before you choose to pursue a PhD.

Prompts: Did you enjoy the teaching? Did you mix with the other students? did you achieve your goals?

3. What made you decide to pursue a PhD in the UK?

Prompts: - Who/what encouraged you to pursue your PhD (family, career, funding, general interest, place, topic...)

- Why did you choose the UK? (University)

- What goals do you want to achieve when taking a PhD?

4. How long have you been studying for your PhD?

Prompts: Have you had any interruption? Why? Any impact?

5. What is the topic of your PhD and your discipline? What led you to it?

Prompts: - Explain the stage of the thesis and progress of the overall research.

- Are you happy with your progress so far?

- Have you had any training in your PhD ?

6. Tell me about your background and how it led you into your research area.

Prompts: family background, economic background....

7. What are your expectations from taking on such a journey?

Prompts: Fostering your skills, make new international friends, getting a job in the future.

8. Are you the first member of your family to take a PhD? Are you the first to travel overseas to study in the UK?

Prompt: What can you tell me about that?

SECTION II

In this section we explore the factors that you found to be the more challenging ones in your research journey so far. Please feel free to also expand about your positive experiences.

Interview Questions

1. What does the term 'motivation' mean to you?

2. In an ideal world, describe what you think of as the most positive or best PhD experience?

Prompts: Describe it in your own words. (probe: was that your experience)

3. During your PhD, what has been the most challenging?

Prompts: - What are the elements blocking your progress?

- Which experiences were/are challenging but still manageable?

4. Of those mentioned challenges, which experiences have you been able to cope with?

Prompts: Why have you been able to cope with them?

5. What is your understanding of demotivation? Could you tell me about your demotivating/negative experiences ?

Prompts: - How many times have you experienced it/them ?

- Which demotivating agent(s) come(s) back the most/recurrently? Why?

- What period exactly does that happen? Why?

6. Would you describe other situations during your PhD studies in which you experienced demotivation?

7. As an international student, what are the challenges that you have faced (still face) during your PhD? (Could you name as many as you can?)

Prompts: - What can you tell me about these challenges?

- Which of those are easy to manage? Which ones are difficult to manage and lessened your enthusiasm to study?

- Do you think this/these is/are the main challenge(s) that you faced?

8. Could you elaborate on whether your state of demotivation is reduced or amplified due to your international foreign student status?

Prompts: in what ways it impacted you....probe examples of incidents or episodes that undermined or hurt your experience.

9. What factors/experiential features increase your sense of demotivation?

Reflective Summary: *So, in this section we have explored demotivation in doctoral studies in general and as an international student in particular, is there anything else that you want to say? Have I missed anything that is important? Can you please give me a summary of your perspective explained to me in this section? In summing up, what advice does it lead you to give someone thinking of taking a PhD in the UK?*

SECTION III

In this section we explore the feelings, thought processes and potential outcomes of experiencing demotivation along with the coping styles both male and female participants use.

Interview Questions

1. Can you please describe your state when you are demotivated/ How do you feel when being demotivated ? What does demotivation feel like emotionally?

Prompts:- How did demotivation start ?

- What were the emotional changes during that period ?
- What were the thoughts processes during that period/what were your thoughts at that time?
- What are the key losses, if any?
- Why such change, if any?

2. Could you describe a typical day during which you felt demotivated?

Prompt: How did you cope with that day when you felt demotivated?

3. Do you think demotivation is connected with withdrawing from the PhD?

Prompts: why? how?

4. What are the reasons for wishing to withdraw or to continue your PhD studies? Do you think they are typical of other Algerian students?

Prompts: What encourages students to continue with their PhD?

5. As you will know some students drop out of or leave their studies, why does this happen do you think?

Prompt: Have you ever felt this way?

6. Has your emotional mood ever been impacted by your studies? If so, how? Give me some examples.

7. Has doing the PhD impacted your wider/general life outside of the academic experiences of it?

Prompts: Please provide your lived experiences of these episodes.

8. What were, if any, the low points of your PhD journey?

Prompts: How did they affect you? How did you overcome them? When did they occur? How long did they last? Who supported you?

9. What do you think the consequences of demotivation can be if left unaddressed?

Prompts: consequences (evolvment and adaptation or potential failure and attrition).

10. What are the reasons that drove you to attrition thinking, factors that might (or did) lead you or others to think about withdrawal?

Prompts: Academic factors, psychological factors, familial, peers, environment etc.

11. Does demotivation, by any chance, enhance your skills in a way or in another (for example your cognitive abilities or problem-solving skills)? If so, how? If not, what effects, if any, does demotivation have on your PhD journey evolvment?

12. Can you tell me about your PhD coping strategies? What are they? They may be personal, academic, or social ones.

Prompts: Approach, adjustment, or strategies you use to deal with the situation.

Reflective Summary: *So, in this section we explored demotivation, its impact and how people feel, think and cope with such encounter/lived experience. Can you please summarise your perspective? What advice does your responses lead you to offer others considering a PhD? Did you receive that advice?*

SECTION IV

In this section, we deepen the understanding of demotivation through the exploration of potential sociological phenomenon faced by UK Algerian postgraduates.

Interview Questions:

A. Alienation

What is Alienation?

Alienation is “a relation of relationlessness... [It] is a failure to apprehend, and a halting of, the movement of appropriation” (Jaeggi, 2014, p.1). Alienated people have experiences of powerlessness, purposelessness, isolation, self-estrangement and normlessness tendencies (Seeman, 1959). They simply feel different and live in world that is alien to them.

1. What does the term ‘alienation’ mean to you?

2. Tell me if you have experienced alienation ?

Prompts: If yes, could you elaborate? How do you feel when you are alienated?

3. When, if at all, have you felt alienated?

Prompts:

- Is there any specific moment or event that lead you to experience such a phenomenon?
 - Is it pre-moving to the UK or after? Is it before starting the PhD or after?
 - Why do you feel alienated?
4. When you feel alienated, does it affect your PhD? If yes, how?
 5. What factors increase your sense of alienation?
 6. Given what you told me about episodes of alienation, what have been the main effects of that experience?

Prompts: Has it affected your morale? Mood? Motivation? Identity as a researcher? PhD progress?

7. Do you believe minority students (such as Algerians) on campus are experiencing greater, fewer, or the same obstacles in terms of social and cultural needs?

Prompts: More, less. Why is that?

B. Disenchantment

What is Disenchantment?

Disenchantment is characterised by a shift from a pre-modern view of the world, also known as enchanted, to a modern view of the world that is disenchanted (Royce, 2015). In Weber's terms, things in the world are subject to "*lose their magical significance*" and therefore becomes disenchanted (Weber, 1978, p.506).

1. How were your expectations of PhD abroad versus/in contrast to now/the actual reality? / Have your expectations about taking a PhD in the UK met what you have experienced, or not? What have you expected?

Prompts: - Any difference (reality crash)? If so, what are they?

- Expectations achieved, not met, happy, satisfied or not?
- Were you surprised, why?
- What expectations have not been met? (Disappointment, unsatisfied, blame etc.)
- Were they met/not met? If so why/why not, what do you think?

2. Did you experience any discontent, disappointment, or dissatisfaction since starting the PhD journey? What caused such occurrences?

Prompts: Could you provide some concrete examples from your own experience?

3. Could you tell me about a specific time when you experienced disenchantment?

4. How do you feel when you experience such a phenomenon?

Prompts: are the inside feelings impacting the external side of yourself? How?

5. Are there any changes you have witnessed when you have entered such a state?

Prompts: Internal and external changes

6. What factors increase your sense of disenchantment?

7. What have been the main effects of that experience?

Prompts: worldview/vision of life abroad in general and study commitments in specific.

8. Since the goal of your international experience is to further your education, does the feeling of disenchantment impact in a way or in another the wellbeing of your PhD?

Prompts: Why? How? Could elaborate?

9. How do you perceive your PhD after having a fair amount of experience?

Prompts: Is it fun as you expected to be? Harder? Easier?

10. How do you see yourself when being disenchanted in comparison to your normal state?

Prompts: any relation to your engagement, displayed efforts etc.

Reflective Summary: So, in this section we have explored alienation, and disenchantment, is there anything else that you want to say? Have I missed anything that is important? Can you please give me a summary of your perspective, explained to me in this section?

Appendix 3: Participant Information Sheet

Participant Information Sheet

Study Title: Investigating the Dark Side of doing Postgraduate Research: *An Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis of Algerian Doctoral Students' Demotivation in the UK.*

Researcher: Ameer Zakaria Juba

What is the research about?

Greetings,

My name is Ameer Zakaria Juba, a Ph.D. student from the School of Education and Social Science, the University of The West of Scotland. While attending the UWS, I am engaged in a PhD research project that focuses on the experiences of international doctoral students in the UK. Precisely, the research project is entitled: Investigating the Dark Side of doing Postgraduate Research: An Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis of Algerian Doctoral Students in the UK. My research is centred on important themes under investigated at the international doctoral level such as demotivation, alienation, disenchantment and so on. It aims to unveil and put into light the existence of a potential dark/negative side considering factors such as attrition and distress to provide future Ph.D. students, supervisors, and policymakers with a substantial report to make the journey for future Ph.D. students more enjoyable, supportive and less pressuring. To gather relevant data, I am kindly inviting you to participate in this investigation. The collected data will be only used for the sake of my research. Below is some information about my research. It is important to remind you that the data you share will be confidential and anonymised, hence feel free to share as much as you want.

Why have I been chosen/selected?

This research emphasises on the experiences of Algerian Postgraduate in the UK who acquired at least one year of experience in the program; how they perceive their experiences labelled as the 'dark side'; and the 'dark side' is my emphasis, I know that there are pleasurable aspects, but I am focusing on the difficult or the negative aspects. What are the symptoms of such experience and how does it affect their progress. As a result of you meeting the necessary criteria for this study, you have been selected to participate.

What will happen to me if I take part?

If you are willing to participate in this study, a consent form will be sent (emailed), and hence signed by you in order to confirm your agreement to take part in the research. After that, in consultation with you, I will arrange a convenient time, date, and location for individual interviews (zoom or teams). For the interview, participants' names will be kept anonymous. The interview should last from 60 to 90 minutes (depending on the experience, topics emerged and reflection) and we might meet more than once if you accept that. The researcher at this stage will ensure their data (including audio/video recordings) will be secured and password-protected and only the researcher has access to

Appendix 4: Consent Form

**School of Education
Paisley Campus**

Title of the research project: Investigating the Dark Side of doing Postgraduate Research: *An Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis of Algerian Doctoral Students' Demotivation in the UK.*

Name of the researcher: Ameer Zakaria Juba

Application number: 17598

- 1- I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above project and the researcher has answered any queries to my satisfaction.

- 2- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the project at any time, without having to give a reason and without any consequences.

- 3- I understand that I am going to:
 - a- Complete an interview form.
 - b- Participate in an individual interview(s) (*approx. 1-2 hours*).
 - c- Be audio-recorded during the interview.

- 4- I understand that any information recorded in the research will remain confidential and no information that identifies me will be made publicly available.

- 5- I consent to being a participant in the project

Name of the Participant: _____

Date: _____ Signature: _____

Name of the Researcher: _____

Date: _____ Signature: _____

Appendix 5: Invitation to Participate in a PhD Study

Invitation to participate in a PhD study

Thu 23/06/2022 18:14

I hope this email finds you well,

Ameur Zakaria Juba is a PhD researcher for the School of Education and Social Science studies at the University of West of Scotland. His PhD research project focuses on the experiences of international doctoral students in the UK. His research project is entitled: Investigating the Dark Side of doing Postgraduate Research: An Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis of Algerian Doctoral Students in the UK.

His research centres on important themes such as demotivation, alienation, and disenchantment. It aims to unveil and put into light the existence of a potential dark/negative side considering factors such as attrition and distress to provide future PhD students, supervisors, and policymakers with a substantial report to make the journey for prospective PhD students more enjoyable, supportive and less pressuring.

If you ever felt dark times within your PhD journey that slowed your progress, and you wish to take part in this endeavour where you can voice your experience freely. You can contact him at his personal email at [redacted] or via social media such as Facebook (Ameur Juba).

Please also find attached a copy of the Participant Information Sheet for further details.

With Kind Regards

Ahcn, on behalf of the APS-UK Committee

Appendix 6: Fieldwork Timeline

Fieldwork Timeline			
17/02/2022	18/02/2022	20/04/2022	13/05/2022-19/12/2022
UWS ethical approval was obtained.	<p>The start of the recruitment process.</p> <p>Personally contacting colleagues who expressed interest in the research via social media.</p> <p>Additionally, an email was sent to the Algerian UK representative (APS-UK) on the 22/06/2022 to spread the invitation to all the members of the community and the Algerian embassy in the UK as the latter has a record of every Algerian PhD student.</p>	<p>Sending interview schedules and consent forms.</p>	<p>The data collection stage.</p>

